

10th Symposium on
Resilience Engineering

RESILIENCE ENGINEERING ASSOCIATION

A COLLECTION OF
NEWSLETTERS

Courtesy of the 10th Symposium on
Resilience Engineering

**Resilience at frontiers,
frontiers of resilience**

JUNE 2023

10th Symposium on
Resilience Engineering

A COLLECTION OF NEWSLETTERS

The Resilience Engineering Association connects thousands of thought leaders, practitioners, and academics working with complexity, uncertainty, and change; bringing perspectives including and not limited to Resilience, Safety-I and II, Safety Differently, and Crisis Management worldwide. Through our newsletter, our community is informed on state-of-the-art research, practices, challenges, and potential solutions for safe, secure and resilient operations, proactive processes and practices to increase adaptation, readiness to respond to surprises and learning from what goes well, that span far beyond the individual and delve into team, system, organizational, governmental, and societal issues. Contributing to this work include diverse domains and areas such as nuclear, aviation, maritime, healthcare, software engineering, construction industry, railway, water, electricity, utilities, telecommunications, cyber-resilience, emergent technologies, work across diverse critical infrastructures, work within non-safety critical organizations, design and operation of complex sociotechnical systems and contribution to organizational and societal resilience.

The REA newsletter started as an initiative to rapidly share the latest developments within the community. We thank all contributors to these newsletters for their valuable input. We found out that there are a lot of lessons to be learned and built upon in the individual newsletters. It can also be valuable to connect people interested in the same topics. So, while preparing for the 10th Symposium, as a surprise gift, we would like to share a consolidated version of the newsletter. We dedicate this collection of past REA Newsletters to our devoted readers and members of our Association. We would like to thank all the guest editors and authors who have contributed to the REA newsletter over these past three years. We look forward to many more years of collaboration with fresh and innovative ideas!

Enjoy your Reading!

Lida Z. David, *Newsletter Editor*
Ivonne Herrera, *REA President*
Beth Lay, *Head of Communication Team*

A WORLDWIDE PERSPECTIVE

The collection of newsletters presented in this document includes contributions from over 25 countries in Europe, North and South America, Asia, Australia, and Africa.

Are interested in contributig an article to a future REA newsletter? Contact us at communications@resilience-engineering-association.org

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1.

A collaborative start

October 2019

Editor Beth Lay, USA

Welcome to our Newsletter

by Ivonne Herrera, President Resilience Engineering Association, NTNU Social Research, Norway

In line with the Resilience Engineering Association aim to connect experiences and capabilities involving practitioners and academia across the world, I am very happy to welcome a new “Resilience Engineering Newsletter Initiative”. This is a kind of experiment, and the success of our newsletter depends on the contributions from resilience engineering practitioners and academia, diverse disciplines and industries. We look for people who are passionate about bringing forward science or practice. Therefore, if you would like to share knowledge or experience related to Resilience Engineering, your contribution is more than welcome. Please do not hesitate to contact our communications team at rea-communications-team@googlegroups.com to contribute. We hope you enjoy our newsletter.

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1.1. OOPS! Learning from Surprise

by Lorin Hochstein, Netflix, USA

Some people think it's odd that software engineers at Netflix take inspiration from the work done by the resilience engineering community. After all, Netflix is an entertainment company, it doesn't deal in safety-critical systems. Unlike domains such as transportation, energy, or healthcare, there's little risk of physical harm involved in doing the work of running a video streaming service.

However, like the safety-critical domains, all of the work that Netflix software engineers do happens within the context of a socio-technical system. If you walked the halls, you might even see a scene that wouldn't look out of place in the control room of a power plant: software engineers looking at graphs on an operational dashboard in order to diagnose an operational issue.

In particular, when an incident occurs that results in a service interruption, we can apply the same kinds of accident investigation models as those used in the safety-critical domains to help us understand how the incident occurred.

We strive to use incidents as an opportunity to learn as much as can about how work actually happens at the organization. However, the amount that we might learn from an incident isn't proportional to its severity. In fact, we might be able to learn just much from an operational surprise where there was no customer or business impact at all as we would from an incident with significant customer impact. Any time an engineer is surprised by the operational behavior of the system, there's a mismatch between their mental models and the actual system behavior, and there's an opportunity to learn how that mismatch came to be.

At Netflix, we have a project called OOPS: learning from surprise. When an engineering team encounters an operational surprise, we encourage them to file an "OOPS": a writeup of the surprise. This writeup contains a narrative description of the events that led to surprise, and identifies contributors, mitigators, risks, and challenges in handling.

By sharing these writeups out to the organization, we hope to build shared understanding around how the overall system behaves, demonstrate expertise in action, and encourage discussion around signals of risk that these OOPSies reveal.

1.2. Evolutions of Resilience thinking within Resilience Engineering

by Ivonne Herrera, President Resilience Engineering Association, NTNU Social Research, Norway

Resilience has become hyper-popular, used in diverse disciplines with different meaning. In safety science, resilience is not new, it was introduced by Wildavsky in 1988 in his book “Searching for Safety”. Yet we may be relatively “young” in our design for Resilience Engineering and evolutions in the understanding of resilience.

Resilience Engineering meeting 2004

From the 2004 meeting, resilience is seen as “ability of an organization or system to keep or recover to stable state allowing to continue operations during or after major mishap...”. Erik Hollnagel’s discusses his current view of resilience “A system is resilient if it can adjust its functioning prior to, during, or following events (changes, disturbances, and opportunities), and thereby sustain required operations under both expected and unexpected conditions “. In 2015, David Woods clarified diverse understandings of resilience as 1) rebound – returning to a stable state; 2) robustness – ability to absorb rather than recover (note here he argues that confounding robustness and resilience can be erroneous); 3) graceful extensibility extending the adaptive capacity when facing surprises, how system reorganize and escape constraints to continue operation and 4) sustain adaptability – managing and regulating adaptation in a layered network. Woods argues the scope of RE lies in resilience 3 and resilience 4. There are many recent publications on diverse views and understanding of resilience (e.g. Special issue, Safety Science, High reliability organizations and resilience engineering).

Since resilience has become so popular there are also some traps e.g. those highlighted by Sidney Dekker (2019): 1) reductionist trap on either targeting operations or wider societal systems; 2) moral trap where operators flexibility and adaptation are promoted by regulations having the risk of making accountable operators for safety, 3) normative trap where resilience embraces the idea of something positive and safety is achieved by ensuring local adaptation and strategies, while in some industries like fisheries the argument for resilience is not safety but the acceptance of danger.

Our purpose of the Resilience Engineering Association lies in being open to and building bridges among different views and perspectives rather than dictating a unique view and fixed definition of what resilience is and can be. Only by integrating disciplines, sharing different experiences and perspectives that address increased complexity, emergence and non-linearity will we gain momentum, grow our knowledge and increase our comprehension in how resilience engineering can bring benefit to our society in coping with everyday work as well as surprises in an ever more complex reality.

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Woods, D. D., 2015. Four concepts for resilience and the implications for the future of resilience engineering. RESS, Volume 141, pp. 5-9. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0925753518304065>

Dekker, S. 2019. Foundations of Safety Science – A century of Understanding Accidents and Disasters

1.3. What's happening in research - Work at Safety Science Innovation Lab, Griffith University

by David Provan, Australia

The Safety Science Innovation Lab is led by Sidney Dekker and Drew Rae. Our Lab provides Graduate Certificate and Masters courses in Safety Leadership as well as having an average of approximately 10 Masters and PhD students conducting industry-based research.

The primary research aims of the Lab are to understand:

- 'Safety as done' in organisations
- The current and future role of safety professionals
- How safety differently can be applied in practice

We are currently conducting research across a diverse range of industries including: healthcare, utilities, rail, oil and gas, construction, and education.

Our current research projects include: the identity and daily work of safety inspectors, the effects of 'safety clutter', the phenomenon of 'fantasy planning' in safety, how safety management is compromised by subcontracting arrangements, the application of hazard registers during safety-critical system design work, the professional identity and practice of safety professionals, the influence of accident narratives on safety recommendations, personal risk-taking behaviour among safety professionals, the purpose and function of safety signage, and the nature of safety improvement journeys.

For further information please contact: David Provan david.provan@griffithuni.edu.au or Drew Rae d.rae@griffith.edu.au

1.4. New Course in Resilient Health Care Management,

by Tarcisio A. Saurin, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS), Brazil

Healthcare systems have been a traditional domain of interest for resilience engineering researchers and practitioners. The growing interest in resilient health care has given rise to a unique diploma course on resilient health care management. The course is provided by the School of Health and Welfare at Jönköping University in Sweden in collaboration with the International Society for Quality in Healthcare (ISQua) and supported by Macquarie University, Sydney, Australia.

The course timeline is from October 2019 to December 2020, including residential and online learning.

**INTERNATIONAL DIPLOMA COURSE IN
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ISQua
International Society for Quality in Health Care

MACQUARIE UNIVERSITY
SYDNEY AUSTRALIA

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This unique course is provided by the School of Health and Welfare at Jönköping University, Sweden in collaboration with the International Society for Quality in Healthcare (ISQua) and supported by the Australian Institute of Health Innovation at Macquarie University, Sydney, Australia.

The course is made up of 7 modules, consisting of blended multimodal learning with residential sessions, webinars and self-directed and reflective learning.

All modules require the study of selected relevant literature.

Find out more and register at ju.se/rhcm or contact Axel Ros, axel.ros@ju.se

Module 1:
9 - 13 March 2020 (5 days)
Residential Session in Dublin, Ireland

Modules 2-5:
March - September 2020
Distance learning

Module 6:
21 - 25 September 2020 (5 days)
Residential Session in Jönköping, Sweden

Module 7:
October - November 2020
Dedicated to writing the course thesis based on the student's project and application of the theory

1.5. Bridging the differences – an interview with John Allspaw

by Beth Lay, USA

John Allspaw - Cofounder of <https://www.adaptivecapacitylabs.com/> and <https://www.kitchensoap.com/about-me/>

Imagine a world where the pilot of a Boeing 737 pulls up to the gate and says to his co-pilot “this gage is bugging me; I’m going to make it bigger and move it.” This is exactly what happens in the world of Twitter, Facebook, Amazon, and Google. Web designers are both the pilot and the designer. Scary? Yes, but also liberating. Amazon changes code on average every 11 sec. The frequency and pace of change means that change management practices that exist in traditional companies won’t work for internet-facing businesses. How are things different?

John Allspaw, David Woods, Richard Cook, Asher Balkin, Laura Maguire, and Marisa Grayson have formed a consortium of industry leaders and researchers united in the common cause of understanding and coping with the immense levels of complexity involved in the operation of critical digital services. <https://www.snafucatchers.com/>

“SNAFU is an acronym for “Situation Normal: All F#\$@ed Up”. The term implies that the world is normally broken, that conditions are ordinarily chaotic, disordered, and dysfunctional. Use of the term generally indicates the speaker is worldly wise or even jaded enough that this state is not surprising.”

In this interview with John Allspaw, former CTO of Etsy, we explore the work Snafu Catchers has been doing with internet-facing businesses and how they are changing things up in this domain.

Which paradigm shifts do people experience?

Failure isn’t linear and don’t forget the people. Linear lines of causality are an illusion. It’s easy to illustrate how multiple contributing factors are each necessary but only jointly sufficient to trigger an incident. Software engineers are not deeply rooted in causality (typical level of familiarity is 5-whys) so it’s pretty easy to flip this paradigm but it’s more difficult to shift to what to do differently when considering systemic accident models. Typical post mortems go something like this: at time X, this request went here and the router did this. Written in passive tense, post mortems miss the stories of the people. John asks “Don’t you think what you did is important? What was hard?” He asks “When dealing with an outage, have you ever found yourself completely confused?” Everyone raises their hand. “You are about to take an action, finger poised above the button, thinking to yourself I’m going to do this! Knowing there’s an equal chance it will make it worse. Do you remember that palpable thing, when the hairs on your arm stood up? Show me in this post mortem document where this is! I’ve been there, I’ve felt it...” Per John, we want to learn from failure but the trick is to bring attention to how things normally work. Don’t dismiss what kept it from being as bad as it could have been and what happens in normal work that we can learn from.

The world isn’t deterministic. Software engineers are paid to write and operate code to construct a deterministic i.e. predictable world! They inhabit a world `is` and `os`. What’s on the screen is very real to them. They build remarkably rich mental models with a paucity of information and have a sophisticated understanding of how the system works. Snafu Catchers brings forth that you can’t see code run; what you really have are little keyhole views of the system, snap shots of representations and everyone has a different mental model, based on their own experiences, of the system.

The real work is cognitive. The vast majority of conversations that software engineers have are about what the machine is doing. What is actually happening is software engineers are building and continually recalibrating how the system works; they are anticipating, reframing and prioritizing, using pictures of what's happened in the past to influence designs for the future. As soon as the idea that the real work is cognitive becomes clear, a light bulb goes off. They realize how little of their normal dialog is about cognitive work and this opens the possibility to

A vision of the future.

John has a 13-year-old daughter. He envisions that when she enters the workforce, we'll reflect "Oh, I remember those days! That's when we still saw people as the weak link." the same as we now think about doctors who did advertisements for cigarettes.

1.6. Book corner: Foundations of Safety Science

by Sidney Dekker, Australia

I wrote *Foundations of Safety Science*, my latest book, foremost for safety practitioners and students. I decided, perhaps foolishly or presumptuously, that all could benefit from a more solid grounding in the foundations of the science of safety (such as it is, I hear Erik Hollnagel justifiably say).

My main concern was a lack of fluency, of literacy, in the ideas, concepts and theories that make up our field—the genealogy, the interconnections, the historical roots from which even today’s models stem. Much safety education—if it discusses models at all—stops at Swiss cheese (which is thirty years old). Even more safety education is organized around applicable laws, regulations, policies, best practices, methods and techniques, often driven by peer-to-peer influence—inspirations from what others in other organizations have done—and hand-me-down knowledge.

And actually, not all safety practitioners were educated as safety practitioners. Many have backgrounds in operations, in HR, in engineering or chemistry or a mechanical trade or psychology or something else altogether. To put it crudely, they make up a bunch of happy amateurs, who easily reinvent the wheel, who believe that one model is all there is, who introduce countermeasures, embrace slogans or set targets without understanding the conceptualization of danger and its applicability at all

I’ve chosen an episodic approach to organizing this book. That is, I have divided it up into time slices. Every chapter is founded on the ideas of a particular era—each roughly a decade from the past century and this one. It then explores how these have influenced our thinking in safety in other decades ever since. Of course, the lines and categories of what belongs to which decade, or what inspired what exactly, can always be debated, as they should. They are not in this book to radiate an impression of linear, historical truth. Rather, they are a way for me to organize the ideas, and for a reader to start thinking with them.

How are today’s ‘hearts and minds’ programs, for example, linked to a late-19th century definition of human factors as people’s moral and mental deficits? What do Heinrich’s ‘unsafe acts’ from the 1930’s have in common with the Swiss Cheese Model of the early 1990’s? Why was the reinvention of Human Factors in the 1940’s such an important event in the development of safety thinking? What makes many of our current systems so complex and impervious to Tayloristic safety interventions? I have tried to review the theoretical origins of major schools of safety thinking, and to trace the heritage of, and interlinkages between, the ideas that make up safety science today. Of course, the book concludes with Resilience Engineering as the go-to school of thought today, tracing its roots in the work of Rasmussen, Woods, Hollnagel, Cook and others.

<https://www.crcpress.com/Foundations-of-Safety-Science-A-Century-of-Understanding-Accidents-and/Dekker/p/book/9781138481787>

Contents: The 1900s and Onward: Beginnings. The 1910s and Onward: Taylor and Proceduralization. The 1920s and Onward: Accident-Prone. The 1930s and Onward: Heinrich and Behavior-Based Safety. The 1940s and Onward: Human Factors and Cognitive

Systems Engineering. The 1950s, 1960s and Onward: System Safety. The 1970s and Onward: Man-Made Disasters. The 1980s and Onward: Normal Accidents and High Reliability Organizations. The 1990s and Onward: Swiss Cheese and Safety Management Systems. The 2000s and Onward: Safety Culture. The 2010s and Onward: Resilience Engineering. Postscript.

1.7. Strengths and Weaknesses of Resilience Assessment Grid

by Sheuwen Chuang, Taiwan

Resilience engineering has been advocated as an alternative to the management of safety over the last decade in many domains. However, to facilitate metrics for measuring and helping analyze the resilience performance remains a significant challenge. To facilitate an enhanced understanding of what makes resilience performance of a system possible, Prof. Erik Hollnagel developed the Resilience Assessment Grid (RAG). The RAG is different from a retrospective analysis of organization's resilience after an accident has happened. It is a relatively new open-structured questionnaire-based tool that is used to collect data reflecting the four resilience potentials (respond, monitor, anticipate, and learn) in an organization or system.

The RAG has been tailored and used by a few organizations in practice and researches, such as an offshore oil and gas company, the air traffic management system, rail traffic management, and emergency departments of hospitals. These cases revealed the strengths and weaknesses of RAG as follows.

Strengths

The RAG is composed of four coherent question sets of proxy measurements to each resilience potential for supporting resilience management. Based on the proxy measurement of the four potentials, the applications of RAG indicated that the participants had a better understanding of how resilient performance present, and how the organization supports each of the four potentials to be capable of performing resilient performance. Its visualization charts, i.e. the radar chart for demonstrating each potential and the stat char for presenting the overall system potential, facilitate clear directions to build an organization's resilience.

Weaknesses

The RAG's open-ended structured questionnaire inherently has a questionable quality of survey data, which could be generated by interviewers or interviewees or participants, no matter during face-to-face interviews, focus group discussions or surveys. This method might raise concerns about valid scale in determination of scale level between investigation team members and interviewees. Besides, the use of the open-end questionnaire is a time-consuming process for data collection.

Implementation of RAG

For wider applications, first, it requires the analyst to adjust the RAG's structure to the organization or system being studied. Next, selecting interviewees or participants requires a consistent and reasonable qualification criterion when use it and for multiple investigations. Finally, building a data pool of responding answers to each question for improving scale validity.

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Sheuwen Chuang, Ju-Chi Ou, Hon-Ping Ma, Measurement of resilience potentials in emergency departments – Applications of a tailored resilience assessment grid. *Safety Science*, 2020, 121: 385-393

1.8. Resilience Engineering webinar series – From cheese to STEW: Incorporating a systems' approach to critical incident analysis,

By Sarah Carriere, Canada

Systems Thinking for Everyday Work (STEW) are discussion cards that frame team conversations and support systematic group discussion. After a recent medication patient safety incident, the 6 principles of STEW were applied to better understand, analyse, identify opportunities for improvement and sustain team resilience. Sarah will describe the practitioner and organizational experiences with this framework.

Sarah Carriere is based in Vancouver as a Leader for Health System Improvement for the [BC Patient Safety & Quality Council](#). As a registered nurse, Sarah has worked in surgical and critical care environments, which then morphed into a passion for clinical research, quality improvement, high reliability systems and complexity science. Sarah's passion lies in supporting people to see and do things differently, to challenge the status quo, and learn from what makes things go right and how many times this can be replicated. Sarah's main passion lies in how we hold ourselves accountable for ensuring we support teams to practice in a psychologically safe environment that leads to safer and patient-partnered care. She has also supported and led numerous safety-focused quality improvement initiatives, clinical research studies and large-scale provincial quality improvement initiatives.

Presented by REA & DARWIN Community of Practitioners

REA & DCoP are a global community of practice creating opportunities to collaborate with others who are leading research and developing practical applications in how to create resilience in complex systems. Our events allow participants to learn from other domains seeking to engineer resilience into their systems such as healthcare, critical infrastructure, energy, critical digital services, transportation (aviation, marine, rail), automation (self-driving cars, drones), emergency response, finance, and aerospace.

Our webinar series on resilience engineering topics spans theory, practice, cases, research and more! Watch the [REA website](#) for our calendar of upcoming presentations.

2.

Efforts across domains and linking perspectives

December 2019

A word from this issue's editor

by Lorin Hochstein, USA

Welcome to issue #2 of the REA newsletter, where we'll be adding some resilience to your holiday season. Many thanks to Beth Lay for editing [issue #1](#).

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2.1. Intersection between resilience and innovation management

by Ivonne Herrera, Norway

Innovation management and resilience management are hyper-popular moving targets as contexts and organizational priorities change. I would like to share a study we conducted with Christina Hanssen addressing the question: we innovate, therefore are we resilient?

When comparing the organisational drivers and conditions affecting resilience and innovation management fields the well-known rhetoric question of “what comes first – the chicken or the egg?” comes to our minds. We illustrate our findings in the figure below.

Drivers and organisational conditions between innovation and resilience management

In the middle of the figure, we find organizations exposed to fierce competition, fragmented markets, non-linearities, unexpected changes, increased complexity and uncertainty (red colour). In black, we can see drivers that enable either resilience or innovation, and common to both are (amongst others) adapting to the unexpected, common vision and goals, tolerance, trust, improvisation, flexibility, slack, collaboration across roles, and learning. Furthermore, in the grey box, we find organisational conditions that hinder either resilience and innovation, which are (amongst others) control and strict management, strict boundaries and silo thinking, centralisation and standardisation. Both fields also focus on the importance of monitoring both external and internal activities (e.g. technology watch, user needs) to anticipate changes that affect the organisation’s operation and learning from experience (both failures and successes) to better respond and adapt to changes in the organisations and to establish new knowledge. In the innovation field, this is key to achieving sustained strategic and competitive advantages, whereas from a resilience perspective this is key to sustain required operations in both expected and unexpected events. Furthermore, it could be valuable to explore in practice, how organisational conditions identified solely within resilience engineering or innovation management literature mutually enrich each other.

It is tempting to say that innovative organisations, because of their focus on conditions that stimulate creativity, openness and trust, have a higher potential of being resilient, but one could just as easily turn this around and say that resilient organisations have a higher potential of being innovative due to their focus on flexibility, improvisation and slack. Thus, the question of the what comes first, the chicken or the egg, comes to mind: What comes first – innovation or resilience?

To conclude, Innovation and Resilience are now imperatives for organizations to continue business, support operations and remain relevant to market needs and expectations. Hence, we could further support creating working environments where organisational conditions and drivers facilitating both resilience and innovation highlighted in this note are promoted. The motivation to write this note is to highlight that resilience engineering is not solely relevant for safety or security management.

2.2. Asher Balkin interviews resilience roundup's Thai Wood

by Beth Lay, USA

Silence. We have Thai Wood on the phone. Asher looks at me, puzzled, then mouths “who is interviewing who?” Asher and I were together at a meeting; 45 minutes earlier I’d asked if he wanted to “lead the interview”. Asher resiliently recovered and led the conversation below. Enjoy!

About Thai: Thai Wood writes about resilience engineering every week at ResilienceRoundup.com. As a former Emergency Medical Technician, Thai applies his experience managing emergency situations to the software industry to help teams build more resilient systems and improve their ability to effectively respond to incidents. Thai got his start in the software industry at Zappos.

About Asher: Asher Balkin is a safety researcher at OSU Cognitive Systems Lab with David Woods.

Asher: How did you get started doing Resilience Engineering?

Thai: Many years ago, spent time as an Emergency Medical Technician (EMT), working 911 service in Las Vegas, started to see similar problems in tech. industry but they had different solutions. My thinking crystallized during the Re-deploy Conference <https://re-deploy.io/> where I spoke with John Allspaw and Laura Maguire (OSU).

Asher: What problems, patterns, and similarities did you notice between EMT and software companies?

Thai: Incident response. For software teams, there wasn't a procedure for incident response, there was little opportunity to practice, and incident response was not established as a separate skill set. In EMS and emergency medicine, it's the opposite: they focus on practice and learning from different scenarios. They rehearse.

Asher: How did software companies organize incident responses before? Was it on the fly?

Thai: Has seen a lot. “You have a tangential skill set – emergency response – here’s your pager.” Training may be through shadowing but this overlooks having a core framework of how to respond and how to communicate. Looking over the shoulder of an expert may not reveal why they do what they do. Each responder bears the burden of coping with a lot of uncertainty that they needed to invent for themselves instead of being given a framework to build off of.

Asher: Organizations across domains struggle with how to train people to do incident management, how do you do it?

Thai: Suggestion sounds boring but it is to rehearse and practice. Sometimes we call it “Game Days” or “Operations D&D (dungeons and dragons)” this becomes a precursor to chaos engineering and other things. It doesn't matter at first how you practice, what matters is to create the space for practice, to have some sort of scenario driven training. Doesn't have to be high tech. There can be value in table top scenarios related to your system: you were paged for a database disc that's full, what do you do? Step through role-play to highlight what you don't know. Look at documentation – is it sufficient? Discover only 1 person knows the answer to this question: everyone asks Jane.

Asher: You mentioned “creating space for practice” – this is powerful. A lot of folks struggle with the idea that people need to be doing production work and believe they can’t afford time for training / rehearsal. How have you been able to create and maintain the space for practice?

Thai: It is common across all industry. One point where it’s possible to make change is after a large incident. It becomes evident what the payoff might be to invest in this training. You can’t afford not to. You will see the consequences of not doing so. It may take an incident to open the space.

Asher: Dave Woods calls it “Sweeping up after the parade. All the animals leave droppings then we get called in to into clean-up afterwards.” But when we say “we can help you not have this problem in the beginning for a 10th of the price”, no one is interested.

Thai: Liken it to people who cook, ask “Do you have a fire extinguisher?” They reply “no” or they don’t know but people who’ve been through a fire see the value and say “yes”.

Asher: People who are most committed to investing in resilience are those who have frequent and tangible experiences with surprise. The more often and more startling the surprise, the more you are willing to invest resources.

Asher: Earlier you said “Documentation doesn’t support the work.” We talk about procedures / policies as directing the work, what do you mean when you say documents support the work vs. direct the work?

Thai: In any complex system, work as imagined is very different from work as done. If we could very clearly spec something in a document beyond a few generic responses, we wouldn’t need humans to bridge the gap and be sources of resilience. More useful documents should allow you to learn, maybe provide explanation of how the system works, supporting work versus “type this command”. Understanding what the system touches, what disturbances have been seen before, what mysteries were never solved, what weird things we’ve seen. All these things help us ask and answer questions post-incident.

Asher: Go back to your past life in emergency medical response, what lesson or two are useful to what you do now?

Thai: The number one thing is that the work and focus of responders does not need to be, and should not be, to make sure incident never happens again. It’s not possible. It would be ridiculous to tell responders “make sure this car wreck never happens again”. The first car wreck was in Ohio City, Ohio about 130 years ago. The person who made the car was driving the car and hit a tree. He runs up against this in software: the job of incident responders is to make sure doesn’t the incident doesn’t happen again as opposed to investing in preparation, understanding, and learning.

Asher: Is goal of “never happen again” a legitimate goal?

Thai: It can be aspirational. Of course, we hope bad things never happen but having this be the thing we get grounded in in practice is ineffective. It may be better to dispose of that idea (never happen again) as a whole.

Asher: What’s something learned from time in software systems that rest of world could learn?

Thai: In his experience with medicine, even though we talk about post-mortems, he has seen a lot more post incident analyses, a lot more retrospective, a lot more conversations about failure (in software industry). With the habits and culture in medicine, that didn’t occur very often except in very formalized or disastrous cases. Software is doing a better job of learning from incidents.

Asher: In non-software industries, we hear “I could understand if I just had more data, if could just measure this”. It’s unique to digital systems that it is easier to collect data. How has this affected the ability to learn from events?

Thai: As a whole, wonders if it is harmful. Wouldn’t give it up but it is so easy to collect data – have massive data stores – so easy to make a dashboard w/o really looking at who will use, what are they looking for, how does it work with human part. It can feel like making progress but has hurt a little bit in including humans and making useful things with the data. He spoke with someone recently: they had easy monitoring, so much information about their system, but no way could take this data and form picture of the health of the system.

Asher: In every industry, but especially true in digital networks, how do you teach new people to make sense of what they are seeing?

Thai: The only way is experience. Everything they do is trying to find a proxy for experience. Making space for practice is the most impactful thing and accelerates the cycle of getting experience faster. Consider flight simulators. It’s having things that allow people to get experience more quickly.

Asher: Could you tell us about your newsletter, ResilienceRoundup.com?

Thai: I was doing research, talking to John Allspaw. He told me about the [GitHub site](#). He read the papers, 10 – 40 pages long with abstracts that were only notionally useful to what he would find important at the end. He thought if going to review the papers anyway, how could his time and effort benefit others? Each week, he focuses on one paper and gives his analysis of what technology workers can glean from it. They are always public access papers. He wants people to read the paper, to go further. Resilience Roundup is intended to be a bridge to the field of Resilience Engineering. He offers something to help people get started and keep going.

Asher: Do you have a last thought to share?

Thai: You must practice these skills. Emergency response skills not interchangeable with other skills. We have to have a place to practice.

Follow: [@ThaiWoodHere](#).

2.3. Resilience Engineering in practice: applying TORC to a subscription book club

By Priscila Wachs, Brazil

This year, I was approached by an undergraduate student (Eduardo Schneider) who wanted to develop his senior project under my supervision. We had a first meeting, talked about some options and the idea about developing TORC (Training for Operational Resilience Capabilities) for the company he was working came up. This was a challenge for Eduardo, since it was the first time he was talking and reading about TORC.

Note: if you are interested in knowing more about TORC, check out the REA webinar [Training for Operational Resilience Capabilities, presented by Tor Olav Grøtan](#).

The company Eduardo works for is a subscription book club that has over 50,000 subscribers. Each month, subscribers receive a surprise kit (bookmark, slipcase, book, and magazine about the month's book). In order to develop the training materials, Eduardo conducted interviews to surface what challenging situations the operation managers face that require that they (and their team) possess resilience capabilities. The interviews were done using the Critical Decision Method approach. The critical situations that arose were related to the arrival schedule of the kit components from suppliers. They have a tight schedule to package the kit components and send the kit to the costumers and, since the content of the kit is a surprise, all the costumers need to receive them at the same period of time.

When we first thought about TORC and the theory behind it (namely, Resilience Engineering), we were thinking in terms of a safety management situation. However, since the critical situation presented by the interviewees were different than that, we adapted the use of TORC. And it went pretty well! The gamechangers were related to the delay of the suppliers and also to some product damage. The participants needed to make decisions, develop strategies they were going to adopt and identify resources they were going to use. And still at the and the end of each round they discussed about safety, mental workload and efficiency. We had rich discussions.

It was an exciting experience!

The author can be contacted at wachs.priscila@gmail.com

2.4. REA 2013-2019 Young Talents: Where we have come from over the last six years

by Sudeep Hedge and Riccardo Patriarca (USA, Italy)

At the REA 2019 Symposium, the Young Talents Program (YTP) hosted its 4th edition: a one day workshop for Masters and PhD students in the field of Resilience Engineering (RE). During this workshop, students had the opportunity to present their work and receive mentorship from prominent leaders in the field. The 2019 mentors were Richard Cook, Sidney Dekker, Erik Hollnagel, Gesa Praetorius, David Provan, Mike Rayo, Tarcisio Saurin, Anthony Smoker and David Woods.

Over the years, the YTP has been represented by students from all over the world. The dashboard [here](#) presents data on geographic representation of the participants over the years. It is interesting to note that while the first edition in 2013 had all participants from Europe and Australia, the participation spread quickly to include other continents and regions through later editions. Since 2015, there's been a steady increase in the number of participants from the United States. The last two editions have seen a healthy representation from South America, particularly, Brazil. The relatively few participants from Asia have come from Japan (2015), Singapore (2017) and Taiwan (2019). The dashboard not only provides a visual of our geographic diversity, but also highlights the potential for greater outreach and representation. For instance, Africa, the Middle East, and large parts of Asia and the Americas are yet to be represented. Could this uneven distribution reflect an untapped potential for the larger REA community to explore opportunities for wider outreach and collaboration? Please feel free to explore the dashboard, navigate through the data, and check for any further detail available. It's kinda fun!

The REA Young Talent Committee

- Sudeep Hedge, Chair – Texas A&M University, United States
- Riccardo Patriarca, Co-Chair – Sapienza University of Rome, Italy
- Elizabeth Lawson, Member – Exeter University, The United Kingdom
- Chia-Hsin Cheng, Member – Taipei Medical University, Taiwan
- Vanessa Becker Bertoni, Member – Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil
- Natalia Ransolin, Member – Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul
- Dustin Weiler, Member – University of Wisconsin-Madison, United States
- Morgan Reynolds, Member – Ohio State University, United States

2.5. Book Corner: Working Across Boundaries. Resilient Health Care Volume 5 Reviewed

by Tarcisio Abreu Saurin, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS), Brazil

Edited by Jeffrey Braithwaite, Erik Hollnagel, and Garth S. Hunte, published by CRC Press (2019). The book has 15 chapters written by resilient healthcare experts from several countries. Chapters are divided into five parts: openings, negotiating across boundaries, theorising about boundaries, empiricising boundaries, and closure. Contents make it clear the fluid nature of boundaries in healthcare systems, as well as that there is a wide variety of types of boundaries.

The main theme of the book, collaboration across boundaries, has grown in importance in healthcare research and practice, given the need for multidisciplinary care teams and larger healthcare systems, with multiple participants from different backgrounds. As such, the chapters address many issues such as resolving conflict, collaborative use of slack resources, overcoming barriers to patient-flow management, and building connections through negotiation. They represent a range of approaches, rather than a single way of solving the practical problems and have been written to serve both a scientific and a practical purpose.

2.6. Resilience Engineering should look more closely at cybersecurity

by Matthieu Branlat, SINTEF, Norway

It is everywhere, it is hot, and we have a lot to contribute.

In a 2018 special issue of the Harvard Business Review, provocatively entitled “The end of cybersecurity”, Andy Bochman, expert cybersecurity strategist from the Idaho National Lab, warned: “No amount of spending on defenses will shield you completely from hackers. It’s time for another approach”. To that end, many experts emphasize that it is not possible for large (e.g., industrial) systems to be entirely protected—particularly due to their scale and dynamic nature. In addition to developing and implementing protective measures, it is therefore necessary to assume attacks will sometimes succeed in bypassing defenses, and to build the capacity to manage cyber events.

Regularly, real world events remind us about this point. Less than a month ago, on the evening of Friday Nov. 15th, [a cyber-attack in the university hospital in Rouen](#), France, led to the decision to shut down all networks and assets in the hospital and its subsidiaries, following a protective cyber protocol. The cyber event occurred in spite of the numerous security systems in place, and, for several days, these medical facilities operated on pen and paper while patients with non-urgent conditions were directed to other facilities. The hospital’s management ensured that patient safety was not compromised during this event. Reports indicate the hospital was the target of ransomware, the impact of which was limited thanks to the intervention of the national cybersecurity agency. Drastic measures such as ‘unplugging everything’ might be the only course of action in such an event as too much uncertainty exists around the potential impact and extent of the attack. Identifying, making sense of on-going events, understanding potential impact on critical services, managing trade-offs in response are all highly challenging and primarily human activities. A key question remains how to improve the tools and ways of building expertise for cyber defense.

Human-centered research focused on cyber defense and the management of cyber events is still lacking; most of the research on cybersecurity focuses on protection measures and technical aspects (necessary, but insufficient by themselves). Numerous topics of investigation could benefit from a ‘resilience-inspired’ perspective, including:

- decision-making during the management of events (e.g., ambiguity of events, management of uncertainty, collaborative work),
- cyber defense practices, strategies and tactics (e.g., recognizing cybersecurity as a co-adaptive process between attack and defense),
- approaches to understand the impact, in real-time or hypothetical, of events on network assets and, as a result, on system performance (e.g., on safety in critical settings),
- organizational aspects, e.g., management of production vs. security trade-offs, and development and maintenance of ways of functioning in degraded modes,
- technological means to support decision-making relative to the points above,
- training methods to improve resilience in cyber defense.

With the participation of cybersecurity operational experts and industrial sectors, Resilience Engineering concepts, methods and focus can help develop the necessary body of knowledge and solutions in this multidisciplinary research topic. In the context of ubiquitous digitalization and greater connectivity, such research is needed to avoid or limit the extent of perturbation cyber events may generate for professional and societal systems.

For more information: matthieu.branlat@sintef.no

2.7. Human Factors and Resilience Engineering in oil and gas in Brazil

By Éder Henriqson, Pontifícia Universidade Católica do Rio Grande do Sul (PUCRS), Brazil

Drilling and production of oil and gas in deepwater is a technology and safety-critical challenge. It requires intense technology innovation, specialized labour forces and considerable financial investments. Companies often need to develop new technologies due to the geological conditions they face especially when operating in new fields. Despite the intense engineering for safe technologies and processes, residual uncertainties and associated risks are always part of the business demanding system's capacity to cope with them. Technological and social heterogeneity along with large scale of distributed and integrated offshore operations turn such sites a unique “living laboratory” for applied and interdisciplinary research.

In the pre-salt offshore area of Libra in Brazil, since 2017, PUCRS (Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul) is leading a research project for a consortium of five energy companies that are currently drilling and setting up large-scale productions. This research project aims at developing a human factors program by means of an interdisciplinary effort connecting disciplines such as management, psychology, engineering, economics, sociology, social work and environmental sciences. Applied resilience engineering is an important driver of the project and also an intellectual enterprise, as well as exploring “safety differently” and “safety II” principles. Preliminary results were presented in the Offshore Technology Conference in Rio de Janeiro (2019) and in the REA Symposium, in Kalmar (2019). Dr Eduardo Giugliani (giugliani@puhrs.br) is the Project Manager and REA member Dr. Éder Henriqson (ehenriqson@puhrs.br) is the leader of the Scientific Committee of the project.

LIBRA

2.8. Podcast: The safety of work

The [Safety of Work](#) is a new podcast by Drew Rae and David Provan from the Safety Science Innovation Lab at Griffith University. In this weekly series, the hosts will demystify and devolve safety science research in a practical way so that you can declutter your approach to safety management.

The REA website now has a podcasts page with links to [our favorite podcasts](#) that are related to resilience engineering.

2.9. Resilience Engineering webinar series

Dec. 16, 2019, Professor Erik Hollnagel, All I want for Christmas... is my resilience engineering questions answered!

Jan. 21, 2020, Jenny Colman (WorkSafeBC), Resilience in regulation

Feb. 19, 2020, Dr. Michael Rayo (The Ohio State University), Systemic Contributors Adaptations Diagramming.

2.10. Resilience engineering around the internet

In an essay on the Forbes website titled [In Focusing On What Pilots Do Wrong, We May Be Missing Valuable Lessons From What They Quietly Do Right](#), Kirsty Kiernan discusses resilience engineering research being done at NASA and Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University,

A new website called [Learning from Incidents in Software](#) just launched to help bring resilience engineering concepts to the software engineering community. Check out the introductory post by Nora Jones. (note: this issue's guest editor is a contributor to that site).

3.

Progress around the world

February 2020

A word from this issue's editor

by **Ivonne Herrera, Norway**

Welcome to issue #3 of the REA newsletter, where we'll be adding some resilience to your world. Many thanks to Lorin Hochstein issue #2, all newsletters are available here.

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3.1. Members survey – what to keep and what to improve

by Simon Gill (UK) and Pedro Ferreira (Portugal)

Thanks to REA members for sharing their views on the association and the last Resilience Engineering Symposium. In the analysis of the survey, Simon and Pedro present knowledge that will help us to grow as a community in terms of progress in science and practice. It also provides some markers on issues that we need to consider for next symposium. Let's continue together this journey of discovery, learning and last but not least having fun together. [Click here to read the analysis of the survey.](#)

3.2. Cathay Pacific Airways Readies for Take Off: Applying Resilience Engineering

by Asher Balkin (USA) interviews Adam Johns (China)

Jan 28, 2020 Asher Balkin interviews Adam Johns, Cathay Pacific Airways Safety Risk Manager

Adam Johns, based in Hong Kong, is helping Cathay Pacific Airways move from a traditional risk perspective to including a Safety II and Resilience Engineering view.

Asher Balkin is a Safety Researcher at the Ohio State University Cognitive Systems Lab

Asher: How did you learn about Resilience Engineering?

Adam: It's been very organic, about 5 or 6 years ago I started to look beyond aviation to learn how to innovate in safety management. Aviation often gets held up as a panacea of doing safety very well and, while that's true, aviation tends to look within itself for answers on how to improve. I read blogs and papers, mostly in the occupational health and safety space out of Australia then discovered the [Eurocontrol papers on Safety II and systems thinking](#), it snowballed from there to work by Sidney Dekker, Erik Hollnagel, and David Woods. Essentially trying to think how we could implement these concepts in an airline environment.

Asher: You mentioned aviation looks within itself, this is particularly true of disciplines who do it well. "We are really good at this, why would I look into areas where they're potentially not as good at this?"

Adam: Aviation had to get to level of safety that it has due to a societal expectation: 300 people dying in a single plane crash is huge news for days compared to 300 people dying in 300 surgical events individually. It isn't going to make the news on the same scale. Aviation had to develop safety performance to the level it has now out of necessity. But look at the way aviation is going in terms of growth and experiencing exponential change with new technology. If we keep doing what we've always done, then we're probably going to start falling backwards.

Asher: How has Resilience Engineering thinking impacted aviation?

Adam: We are still at the early stages. I'm only aware of a small number of other airlines who are trying to push into this space. Something needs to be done to take us to next level.

Asher: When organizations start to move to Safety II or Resilience Engineering, there's often a concern that it may be too soft or not standardized enough. Did you experience this?

Adam: No. There was some initial skepticism but once people understood the basics, and they see the simple logic of learning from normal operations, it makes sense. It's taken 2 to 3 years to get to this point of socializing Safety II but there was no resistance. People are now looking for more detail and asking "what do Safety II and Resilience Engineering look like in practice?"

Asher: That is a fair question!

Adam: In a Safety I perspective, safety and productivity are seen as opposing forces but if we apply Safety II ideas, we see safety and productivity as complimentary, so we focus on trying to improve work. Safety and productivity both gain; we focus on trying to improve performance as a whole.

Asher: Has the industry being so heavily regulated confined the space you can explore?

Adam: If you go back 20 years, it would have been more difficult. Now aviation is moving to a risk and performance-based regulatory regime, led by the International Civil Aviation Organization. Taking this regulatory philosophy, as long as we achieve outcomes put forward by regulator, it's up to us to figure how to do that. As long as we meet traditional requirements, there's nothing stopping us from going beyond that.

An example of where Resilience Engineering has existed for quite some time is looking at normal work as part of [Line Operations Safety Audits \(LOSA\)](#): pilots ride in the jump seat and record normal operations against a template.

Within our training and checking environment, we added "clarify" to their process to probe local rational: observe, record, clarify, classify, and evaluate. When training captains observe performance, they use clarify to try to make sense of why a trainee did what they did. We are giving training captains a vocabulary of how to record performance to enable the mining of resilient performance.

Asher: You mentioned a disconnect between performance and risk, how do we discuss the relationship between risk and resilience and adaptation?

Adam: Our focus is currently on flight operations with pilots; we know adaptation has to go on all the time. Workers are masters of blue line; they understand how work has to be done. Now we are asking: what is the adaptation? Is it safe or unsafe? Are we drifting in a good or a bad direction? Using this knowledge to understand the real risks in our organization. Are these adaptations helping us achieve a successful outcome and keep us safe or the opposite?

Asher: How did you come into your current role in safety?

Adam: I completed an aviation degree in the UK which involved getting my private pilot license – always wanted to be a pilot. My thesis was automation on the flight deck so then decided I wanted to get into safety instead. I worked for a company that provides flight data solutions to airlines then moved to work for an airline in the UK, the UK regulator, and now Cathay. I started in safety analysis roles but now focus more on proactive risk management of operational changes.

Asher: What's next for Resilience Engineering in aviation?

Adam: We are focusing on the way we investigate: not just looking at accidents. Airlines have events all the time, most of them with little or no consequence, but they are still events the airline doesn't want to happen. What we know is it's the crew's resilience that prevents that event from leading to a more significant consequence. We are introducing the Learning Review concept (Ivan Pupulidy, see his [TedX talk](#)) focusing on what went right and why it made sense for people to do what they did. This will get us to the next level of performance.

(Operational learning reviews are used in by the US Forest Service).

Asher: One fascinating thing about Resilience Engineering principles is that when deployed, we find that front line folks (sharp end) in a hospital, on a flight deck, or at a worksite are often taking actions that demonstrate much higher

levels of resilience than we'd expect and much higher levels than they would even describe themselves. They say "Of course this is how I get the work done." Is this something you've observed or is there more awareness of resilient behaviors?

Adam: Last year, we delivered a presentation on Safety II and resilience to our training captains, and within that we asked them to write down everything that happened on their last flight that influenced performance – performance shaping factors – things like they were fatigued or dealing with inexperienced crew or had technical issues on the aircraft; they wrote down dozens of things. We asked “how many of those things did you record on your safety report?” No hands go up. That was a window into their world: they are dealing with these challenging aspects that influence performance every single time they go flying. These factors aren't reported because they think, “That's just normal; that's what we deal with every day.” This is the tip of the iceberg in really learning from and understanding normal performance.

Asher: Have you made progress getting front line folks to realize how unique this is and move those kinds of insights up the ladder?

Adam: Yes, quite a few light bulbs went off amongst the roughly 300 pilots in a number of workshops. We are starting to see more reports come in from pilots on events they wouldn't normally report and are getting better quality reports too. Although we haven't provided the language we want to use to describe resilient performance yet, we are getting more detail and people are writing what they learned as a result of being involved in the event.

Asher: Far more has been written on a Safety II approach but not lot written yet on adding Resilience Engineering to a Safety II style program, how do you merge Resilience Engineering principles into Safety II program?

Adam: Start with language. Last year we presented concepts related to Safety II and resilience at each monthly safety meeting such as: complicated / complex systems, work as done / work as imagined, trade-offs, performance variability, local rationality. Using the principle that Words create worlds. We are aligning learning from normal work and how people make sense of what they do. We are implementing resilience by identifying resilient strategies and behaviors that people delivered during each event; with the language of “anticipate, monitor, respond, and learn” being integrated into how we monitor safety performance on the front line.

Asher: The language can be daunting, has this been a difficult barrier to overcome?

Adam: It's not been as hard as expected. After we presented concepts “work as done” and “work as imagined”; the following month people were using the language. As a whole it could be quite daunting but if you break the concepts down into constituent parts around systems thinking and resilience, people can understand what you are trying to do. If you bombard people with all the language, all at once, it's hard. Serve in a bite size way. One month we focussed on tradeoffs and talked about tradeoffs in a really simple way. The language seeps naturally into an organization and everybody starts talking about tradeoffs!

Asher: Early on folks decide that have to make the trade-off to focus less on safety I and more on safety II. Do you have advice for getting started?

Adam: Don't ignore the stuff you currently look at, incidents and near misses. Those still need to be looked at and learned from but you need to learn from them in a different way. Instead of focusing on what went wrong and looking at the human as a problem, focus on what went right as well and so much more learning can be achieved by doing

that. Really understanding why it made sense for people to do what they did. Safety II includes Safety I, it's just a different way of looking at what you already investigate. You don't have to look at everything if your resources are limited. You don't have to go out and observe normal work and look for extraordinary performance. You can just look at what you already look at in a different way.

3.3. Bureaucracy overload calling for audit implosion

by Kristine Vedal Størkersen, NTNU Social Research, Norway

Safety management regulation with functional rules and internal controls offer potential for practical procedures. It makes companies responsible for their own safety by implementing and internally controlling safety management systems, with regulators required only to audit the systems. A movement toward deregulation combined with controls are part of why our audit society has experienced an audit explosion (Power, 2007). Parallel, most research on safety management systems emphasizes that they are experienced as complicated for companies to implement, for operational personnel to use, and for auditors and regulators to control. The International Safety Management (ISM) Code is the maritime industry's safety management regulation with internal control.

The ambiguities displayed by both research and empirical outcomes demonstrate the need for this dissertation, which examines the ISM Code's influence on safety-related decision making in on three levels of Norwegian coastal transport:

- The findings regarding regulators show that internal control regulation severely limits their discretionary space, as they do not control the content of companies' safety management.
- Profit making, accountability, and internal control can cause managers to make decisions as if they had less discretionary space than stated in the ISM Code. Companies purchase easily auditable, standardized systems that are more complex than necessary.
- Seafarers are constrained differently Operational managers translate safety management systems into practice for the operational personnel. The translation provides operational personnel with systematic safety awareness and routines that may decrease personal injuries. It also results in a heavy workload and documentation burden for the operational managers and thus less concentration and limited situational awareness, and can contribute to ship accidents.

Overall, internal controls, documentation, and auditing constrain the safety-related decision making, and thus ironically run counter to the ISM Code's objective of ensuring maritime safety. **The core paragraphs of the ISM Code are beaten by its parts about documentation and verification.** Companies implement easily auditable safety

management systems, which can complicate the procedures. Hence, simple function-based rules like the ISM Code are not transformed into simple safety management in the companies.

These results about core objectives being overshadowed by auditability demands might not be restricted to the ISM Code and coastal transport. It rather can be a symptom of the audit society as a whole, and illustrate how bureaucracy escalates even though policymakers and other actors talk about the necessity to avoid it. Many areas of society might gain by decreased auditability and increased value of un-auditable activities, like some operational seafarers enjoy. To unlock the full potential for safety management with practical procedures, thus, will require an audit implosion. Regulators, companies, and operational personnel would benefit by safety measures less concerned with auditability and more focused on safety itself.

Here is a movie about the study: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s4-MXnA_oQo

3.4. Applying SNAP! to healthcare

by Dr. Rob Robson, MDCM, MSc., FRCP(C), Canada

Healthcare System Safety and Accountability, Inc. www.robobson.ca Let's suppose for a moment that you are an "outdoors" type – into hiking, cycling, orienteering, and generally exploring the world. You decide you would like to travel on the Danube, from its headwaters in the Donaueschingen region to the Black Sea. Before you hop into your kayak, I hope you will at least obtain a map to learn how long your trip might take. And I hope you will gather other information about weather patterns, the kind of river traffic you might encounter, the river currents, any natural or artificial barriers you might encounter – in short a host of important contextual matters that will influence your planning and implementation. And perhaps you will also consult various media sources to learn about socio-political issues – will the conflicts in some areas or the immigration policies in others have a potential impact on the possible success of your endeavour. In short, as a 21st century citizen of the world you will prepare yourself for a dynamic, sometimes unpredictable, constantly evolving adventure, recognizing that this will be far from a straightforward trip from Germany to the Black Sea.

The preparations described above are analogous to what SNAP! (Systemic Nonlinear Analysis Protocol) has been designed to do for patient safety practitioners charged with reviewing and understanding adverse events and critical incidents in healthcare. Why bother, you might ask? In most industrialized societies with relatively "advanced" healthcare systems, the level of unintended harm experienced by patients has been consistently shown to be in the range of 5-15% of all acute care hospitalizations. This represents a major (albeit often unrecognized) public health crisis. For instance, in Canada, where I have been involved in patient safety efforts for more than 20 years, every day, **100 patients will die as a result of a breakdown in the way care is provided.** This is quite simply not acceptable.

For several decades, these events of unintended harm and patient death, when they were reported, were analyzed using linear analysis techniques that had been shown to be effective in many industrial settings. After years of making little or no progress using linear methods, such as RCA (Root Cause Analysis), or modified linear approaches (such as the London Protocol based on the Swiss Cheese model) it became apparent that techniques adapted to the nature of the healthcare system were needed. This required some understanding of the fact that healthcare is a fairly typical complex adaptive system (CAS) which would require techniques or approaches appropriate for such a socio-technical system. These include systems thinking and nonlinear causation as two basic principles.

SNAP! promotes an understanding of nonlinearity, not only with respect to the concept of causation of accidents but also to the way in which the involved parties (patients, families, healthcare providers) are engaged in the analytic process; how the chronology of events is constructed; the way in which recommendations are developed; and even the way in which the course is presented – nonlinear approaches to adult learning are more effective for this kind of workshop. SNAP! is embedded in the broader SPHERE (Shifting the Paradigm in Event Review and Evaluation) workshop which examines the way in which CAS evolve and self-organize and therefore how they can be influenced. SNAP! applies to retrospective analysis of events. The underlying systemic nonlinear principles are equally effective in prospective risk assessment.

Check here to access the [SPHERE Workshop \(Applying Systemic Analysis and Review Frameworks to Better Understand Events and Assess Risks in a Non-linear World\)](#)

3.5. Resilience in action: Outmaneuvering Complexity in Worlds of Surprise

by Dave Alderson & David Woods (USA)

Matched pair of talks from a complexity workshop in August 2019 leading off with Dave Alderson on Organized Complexity followed by David Woods on Graceful Extensibility. Alderson's talk really starts at 4:19 as he provides a short introduction to his institution given the audience.

Alderson: Outmaneuvering Complexity in Worlds of Surprise: Managing Fundamental Tradeoffs:

https://youtu.be/1Xv3_FmYO_4?list=PL7WRGH6pAuSdh1dJsUh2ktl5sJxE6lzyw

Woods: Outmaneuvering Complexity in Worlds of Surprise: How adaptive capacities in human-technology systems are built, extended, sustained, degraded, and collapse.

https://youtu.be/1Xv3_FmYO_4?list=PL7WRGH6pAuSdh1dJsUh2ktl5sJxE6lzyw

3.6. REdeploy "we believe teams can not only survive, but thrive, when faced with failure"

By J. Paul Reed, USA

In this article Paul introduces REdeploy. This initiative was originated by people that are passionate about Resilience Engineering. In this context, teams here deal with developing and operating real-world, large-scale software systems. From their website "REdeploy is a conference exploring the concept of Resilience Engineering and how to deploy it within your organisation". Be inspired and learn how practitioners share knowledge on diverse topics such as resilience and change, chaos engineering, web services operations. There are lots of great presentations ...

[Presentation videos](#) from this year's REdeploy, a Resilience Engineering conference focused on the software development and operations industry, were recently posted. Held in San Francisco in mid-October, 2019 was REdeploy's second year.

Resilience Engineering Association member J. Paul Reed launched the conference with Mary Thengvall to "explore the intersection of resilient technology, teams, and individuals" in 2018. While the software operations space is relatively familiar with reliability and robustness techniques, active resilience practices are fairly nascent in the space.

"We really wanted to create a space where practitioners could come together and explore this concept of resilience, not only from a software development and technological patterns perspective, but also in how teams respond to failure and incidents in the operations side of the software lifecycle," Reed said. "And, because teams are made up of people, personal resilience techniques are important too."

Topics ranged from how [Amazon Web Services operates highly available web services](#), to a [deep-dive exploration of "blamelessness,"](#) so often discussed during incident retrospectives, to [how individuals can build up their own adaptive capacity](#) to deal with an ever-changing (and sometimes wildly so!) world, both in and out of work.

REA members will recognize some of the presenters, including the [opening keynote from Dr. Richard Cook](#) and a [talk by Marisa Grayson](#). Casey Rosenthal also offered a [keynote on Chaos Engineering](#). You can check out the rest of the videos [here](#).

As for whether Reed will sign up for the repeat of REdeploy in 2020? "[Stay tuned...](#)"

3.7. What is happening in research? NPS Researchers Plan Resilient Infrastructure for Next Disaster in the U.S. Virgin Island

by Daniel Eisenberg, USA, Operational Resilience in the US Virgin Islands, Naval Postgraduate School (NPS, Monterey, USA)

Is your community prepared to respond to a Category-5 hurricane? Does your community know how to backup electricity and water systems when power lines and pipes may fail? Does your community know where to store disaster relief supplies when access roads may wash out? Does your community know how to bring communication networks back online when it is unclear who will be unable to access the internet or cellphones? Even if your community has answers to these questions, is your community prepared to handle a second Category-5 hurricane just two weeks after the first? This is exactly the situation that the U.S. Virgin Islands (USVI) faced in September 2017, and a team at the Naval Postgraduate School (NPS) is working with experts across the Territory and Federal government to answer these questions for the USVI.

In September 2017, Hurricane Irma struck the islands of St. Thomas and St. John in the northern part of USVI Territory and Hurricane Maria struck St. Croix just two weeks later in the south. Together, these storms devastated local infrastructure and communities [1].

Since this catastrophic event, the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) has funded a team led by Drs. David Alderson and Daniel Eisenberg of the NPS Operations Research Department and Energy Academic Group to work with colleagues in the USVI Territorial Government, US Department of Energy, US National Labs, University of the Virgin Islands (UVI), and Territorial infrastructure providers to ensure communities are resilient to the next big storm. The project consists of three efforts to improve local infrastructure systems and build local capacity to future disasters:

1. Modeling and analysis of interdependent infrastructure in the USVI to improve operational resilience, including electric power, water, transportation, and telecommunications systems;
2. Support the development of a Territorial Hazard Mitigation and Resilience Plan; and,
3. Develop a capacity building and workforce development program for resilient infrastructure.

Recent developments show the increasing impact of NPS work. The first year of this project focused on reporting the state of USVI electricity, water, roadway, and telecom systems, culminating in a technical report describing systems before and after the storms [2]. Now, NPS researchers have curated enough data, built enough models, and produced enough assessments of USVI infrastructure to inform FEMA disaster recovery and mitigation. This hard work recently culminated with NPS researchers playing a critical role at the second USVI Hazard Mitigation and Resilience Planning (HMRP) Workshop held on the 2nd anniversary of the storms.

The HMRP Workshop was led by Drs. Gregory Guannel and Kim Waddel of UVI and prominently featured work by NPS professors and students on infrastructure resilience. Highlighted was thesis completed by US Navy Lieutenant Commander Jeffery Good and German Army Captain Dominik Wille (students co-advised by Drs. Alderson and Eisenberg) on roadway supply chains [3] and interdependent electric power and water systems [4], respectively. As the outcome of this and future HMRP workshops will be incorporated in the USVI Hazard Mitigation and Resilience Plan, results from NPS experts and students will have a direct impact on future crises response within the Territory.

The recent success working across the US Federal government and local communities now spurs more innovation and research at NPS. Since the HMRP Workshop, the NPS group has grown to include professors in Computer Science and students working on measuring the vulnerability of telecommunications systems to disasters. Future results produced by NPS students on electricity, water, transportation, and telecommunications systems are already planned to be discussion topic in the next HMRP Workshop in Summer 2020.

“This article originally appeared in the Naval Postgraduate School Energy Academic Group (EAG) quarterly newsletter Surge.”

Original article can be accessed [here](#)

References:

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- [2] Alderson DL, Bunn BB, Eisenberg DA, Howard AH, Nussbaum DE, Templeton JC, Interdependent Infrastructure Resilience in the U.S. Virgin Islands: Preliminary Assessment, Technical Report NPS-OR-18-005, NPS, December 2018.
- [3] Good, Jeffrey E. An Operational Model of the Critical Supply Chain for the US Virgin Islands. Master's Thesis., Department of Operations Research, Naval Postgraduate School, 2019.
- [4] Wille, Dominik. Simulation-Optimization for Operational Resilience of Interdependent Water-Power Systems in the US Virgin Islands. Master's Thesis., Department of Operations Research, Naval Postgraduate School, 2019 (expected).

3.8. Concept corner: What do we mean by resilience

by David Slater, UK

There are diverse views and understandings on what resilience is and implications for research and practice. In this newsletter, David presents his contribution to this discussion [Click to read this article](#)

3.9. Concept corner: Don't design for threats, design for surprises

by Daniel Eisenberg, USA

Resilience is a “new” term creeping into many organizations and government directives, but what does it mean and how do we use it to guide decisions? In general, resilience should be differentiated from established notions of risk as the two concepts are fundamentally different. Resilience is more like a verb than a noun, and resilient systems should be designed to handle any possible problem instead of only pre-defined threat scenarios. But how do we start approaching this problem of resilient design when we cannot define specific threats?

In a recent article published in the journal *Risk Analysis*, we answered this question by relying on military theories of surprise [1]. Surprise has always played an important role in military activities by influencing intelligence and operational decisions to generate a surprise attack and overtake an adversary or to avoid being surprised and overtaken. Historical examples of surprise attack on allied forces teach us the kinds of situations we should focus on for resilient design. Reflecting on the Yom Kippur War of 1973, when a combined Syrian and Egyptian attack took Israel by surprise and nearly overwhelmed Israeli forces, Zvi Lanir defined at least two kinds of surprise we should be resilient to [2]: situational and fundamental surprise (see Table 1).

To help make sense of surprise for design, we distinguish surprise from normal events with an example from the lottery. Normal events are when you buy a lottery ticket and lose. Situational surprises are rare events like buying a lottery ticket and winning. Fundamental surprises are the unimaginable events like when you do not buy a lottery ticket and you still win.

Resilience asks us to design our systems to handle all these events, especially the fundamental surprises that lie outside our current understanding. This means resilient design starts with a different question than normal design processes. Rather than asking the question, “what threats do we care about?” before starting to design systems, we should ask, “what plans, processes, and capabilities do we have in place to respond to situational and fundamental surprises?” Importantly, there should be a greater emphasis on learning from historical examples of surprise prior to making any design decisions to improve resilience.

Table 1: Differences between normal events, situational surprise, and fundamental surprise. From [1]

Normal Events	Situational Surprise	Fundamental Surprise
Events occur according to previous beliefs	Events are compatible with previous beliefs	Events refute basic beliefs about “how things work”
System and components operate as planned	Failures and system responses are well-modeled or measurable	One cannot define in advance the issues for which one must model or measure
No contingencies to avert or manage	Surprise can be averted or mitigated with information about the future	Advance information about events causes even greater surprise
Nothing new to learn	Learning seems easy	Learning is challenging
<i>Example</i> Purchase lottery ticket, then <i>lose</i> the lottery	<i>Example</i> Purchase lottery ticket, then <i>win</i> the lottery	<i>Example</i> Do <i>not</i> purchase lottery ticket, then <i>win</i> the lottery

From: Eisenberg et al. (2019)

References:

Eisenberg, Daniel, Thomas Seager, and David L. Alderson. "Rethinking Resilience Analytics." Risk Analysis (2019), click here to access the complete article

Lanir, Zvi. "Fundamental surprise." Eugene, OR: Decision Research (1986).

3.9. Book Corner: Exploring Resilience - A Scientific Journey from Practice to Theory

Editors: Siri Wiig (Norway) and Babette Fahlbruch (Germany)

Series: SpringerBriefs in Safety Management . This book:

- Explores different approaches for operationalization of resilience across scientific disciplines and system levels
- Creates a theoretical foundation for a resilience framework across scientific disciplines and system levels
- Develops suggestions and inspiration for the research community and practitioners in high-risk industries
- Presents chapters from leading international authors representing different research disciplines and practical fields

Resilience has become an important topic on the safety research agenda and in organizational practice. Most empirical work on resilience has been descriptive, identifying characteristics of work and organizing activity which allow organizations to cope with unexpected situations. Fewer studies have developed testable models and theories that can be used to support interventions aiming to increase resilience and improve safety. In addition, the absent integration of different system levels from individuals, teams, organizations, regulatory bodies, and policy level in theory and practice imply that mechanisms through which resilience is linked across complex systems are not yet well understood. Scientific efforts have been made to develop constructs and models that present relationships; however, these cannot be characterized as sufficient for theory building. There is a need for taking a broader look at resilience practices as a foundation for developing a theoretical framework that can help improve safety in complex systems. This book does not advocate for one definition or one field of research when talking about resilience; it does not assume that the use of resilience concepts is necessarily positive for safety. We encourage a broad approach, seeking inspiration across different scientific and practical domains for the purpose of further developing resilience at a theoretical and an operational level of relevance for different high-risk industries.

The aim of the book is twofold:

1. To explore different approaches for operationalization of resilience across scientific disciplines and system levels.
2. To create a theoretical foundation for a resilience framework across scientific disciplines and system levels.

By presenting chapters from leading international authors representing different research disciplines and practical fields we develop suggestions and inspiration for the research community and for practitioners in high-risk industries.

Here is the link to the e-book open access: <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007%2F978-3-030-03189-3>

3.10. Resilience engineering webinar series

February 19, 2020, Mike Rayo Assistant Professor at the Ohio State University, Pragmatic tools to observe invisible adaptations.

March 30, 2020, Professor Eder Henriqson, Pontifícia Universidade Católica do Rio Grande do Sul (PUCRS), Exploring challenges and opportunities of resilience engineering application in the Oil & Gas Industry.

The complete list of upcoming seminars and videos from past seminars can be found on the [seminars page](#) of the REA website.

3.11. Resilience Engineering Association as a partner for the ORCHSE 2020 HOP (Human and Organisational Performance) Summit

Keynote speakers include David Woods and Todd Conklin. Pairing to present on RE theory and application: Ron Gantt & Kevin Furniss (Maersk), Laurin Mooney & Renaldo Blocker (Mayo Clinic), Key and Will Desmukes (aviation), Jake Mazulewicz & Suellen Cook (Argonne Labs), Asher Balkin and Beth Lay (Lewis Tree)

Exciting news! David Woods (Professor, OSU) and Chris Hansen (Head of NASA Spacewalk Operations) will co-present on Columbia: the launch of Resilience Engineering at orchse-strategies.com/hop

3.12. International cooperation between Brazil and Norway

by Tarcisio Saurin, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS), Brazil

Academic and industrial institutions*, three from Brazil and five from Norway have developed a collaborative project on resilience engineering and safety management in complex socio-technical systems. The project has been known as STERNA [1], named after a migratory Scandinavian bird. This initiative, which has counted on funding from both countries, started in 2018 and has recently been granted an extension up to the end of 2021.

The project involves the following activities:

– Distance learning graduate course on resilience engineering, given by international faculty. The first edition of the course happened in 2019 and the next is expected to start in August 2020, involving students from both countries.

– Mobility of Brazilian PhD students to Norway, addressing resilience engineering in the construction industry. One of these has investigated resilience and performance measurement systems, while the other has studied the contribution of unmanned aerial vehicles to resilient performance. Two more PhD students will be in Norway for several months in 2020.

– Mobility of students from Norway to Brazil. PhD students addressing construction industry, cyber security, gig economies. Master students addressing offshore, trade-offs decisions in aquaculture, construction, smart grids

The project also involves joint publications and work visits by faculty members. For more information, you are welcome to contact the project coordinators – Asso. Prof. Ivonne Herrera (Ivonne.A.Herrera@ntnu.no) and Prof. Tarcisio Saurin (saurin@ufrgs.br).

Brazil: Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Federal University of Bahia, Pontifical Catholic University of Rio Grande do Sul. Norway: Norwegian University of Science and Technology, University of Stavanger, NTNU Social Research; Industry: Veidekke; R&D Institute: SINTEF.

[1] Proposed by Stian Antonsen (he won the competition, still waiting for his prize – “The arctic tern (Latin: STERNA paradisaea) is the greatest long-distance migrator of all birds, covering as much as 35,400 km annually. It breeds north of the Arctic Circle yet spends the northern winter at the other end of the world, in the Antarctic. By being able to flexibly adapt to all environments and circumstances on its migration from the Arctic to the Antarctic, the sterna paradisaea is among the most resilient creatures on the planet”). Logo by Ingeborg Andrade Sæternes (Ivonne’s daughter:)

3.13. Podcast: Safety Differently

[Dekker on Rasmussen](#). A lot of people around the world working with safety is influenced by the legacy from Jens Rasmussen (11 May 1926-5 February 2018). Sydney Dekker shared a talk reflecting on Jens Ramussen's work.

3.14. Workshops on learning from accidents

Previous editions of the workshop have been organised with the support of Erik Hollnagel. From Nippin:"The workshop has been running very successfully across the globe with future sessions planned in Vancouver, London, Orlando, Las Vegas, Brisbane, Sydney, Auckland, Wellington, Christchurch and more!" [Click here to learn more about the workshops](#)

4.

Applications, widening across domains and responses to COVID-19

April 2020

A word from this issue's editor

by Sudeep Hegde, USA

Welcome to issue #4 of the REA Newsletter. This issue is underpinned by at least three concurrent themes. Contributors from all over the world have described projects which demonstrate the application of Resilience Engineering (RE) and Safety-II principles in various operational settings across multiple domains. Examples include clinical leaders and fellows applying techniques like FRAM to study variability in their systems; pilot-implementation of a new tool for workers to debrief on the formal and informal aspects of normal work; and safety consultants communicating the importance of studying 'normal' work to their clients and demonstrating its utility. A second theme relates to the widening awareness of RE across various industries, through workshops and webinars. Finally, the preponderance of the COVID-19 pandemic on our current time is reflected in numerous articles that allude to, or discuss this theme in the context of RE. Additionally, there is a summary of the first REA webinar on the pandemic response. The issue also includes more conceptual articles on resilience and its application in unique domains such as city resilience. A detailed update on the benefits of REA membership is provided. Read on for all this and much more!

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4.1. Why become a member of REA?

by **Simon Gill** REA Executive council member, UK

Following the article in the February newsletter with the results of our membership survey, we wanted to update you on the ever-expanding benefits of being a member of REA, as both an individual and as an organisation.

The Resilience Engineering Association added a new role to the Executive Committee at the last Annual General Meeting to focus specifically on the benefits to members. Simon Gill stepped into the role and as a first step asked those of you who attended the 2019 REA Symposium about the event and more generally about your interactions with the Association.

Your most clear request was for REA to facilitate relationships and contacts amongst the REA community members. To that end, we will shortly be adding a membership directory to the REA website and will be asking you for information to populate this. This will enable you to list your areas of interest and contact details to support the development of the REA network. Further to this, we will be seeking volunteers as we hope to feature one member per month to help you raise your profile. Some of you are currently trialling an initiative randomly linking REA members to enable you to find out what others in the network are doing in the resilience sphere. Watch this space – there will be more on this in the next newsletter.

We are also giving you the opportunity to create Special Interest Groups to galvanise efforts around specific topics. In similar networks this has added significant value, bringing together expertise to share learning and best practice.

You also asked for smaller, more focused events in addition to the bi-annual symposium. We have therefore started the webinar series which has been hugely popular. The last discussion, the first in a series on Covid-19 response, was oversubscribed in a matter of minutes so please do sign in promptly if you wish to attend. However, if you cannot make it, members have the ability to access the recorded content via the members-only area of the website.

We are supporting some of you to promote and run events and welcome ideas to develop this concept. We are focused on linking with like-minded organisations, and sharing resilience- focused events in our calendar, ensuring you do not miss any opportunities to learn and share.

As a member you also receive a discount on the symposium and critically you can help shape the future of the Association through your vote at our AGM.

As an organisation, we extend the above membership benefits to a specified number of your team, saving each of them signing up individually. We will also be creating an Organisational Membership directory to promote your association with the “official home of resilience engineering”. Further benefits are available to organisations who wish to become Partners of REA, including a dedicated page on the REA website, an offer to guest-edit a REA newsletter and a specific slot for presentation at the REA symposium.

Other benefits are available, and we are keen to explore other opportunities to add value to members so please do get in touch to discuss further. Please apply here or for further information contact Simon at membership@resilience-engineering-association.org

4.2. REA: COVID-19 Webinar Talk 01 – Monday, 30 March 2020 – Summary

by Dustin Weiller, USA

Talk 01 – 30.03.2020 - Lessons learned from Resilience Engineering (RE) and community resilience. Speakers: Bruria Adini (Israel), David Woods (USA), Ivonne Herrera (Norway).

This is a summary of the first webinar in REA's series on the COVID-19 pandemic. This summary is available in the consolidated document. [Click here to read the summary](#)

Dustin Weiller is a PhD. Candidate in the Department of Industrial and Systems Engineering, University of Wisconsin-Madison.

4.3. Integrating Resilience Engineering into Healthcare Improvement: Early wins from an Australian improvement fellowship program

by Satyan Chari, Michael Tresillian, Linda McCormack, Australia

1. Satyan Chari¹, Senior Faculty, *CEQ Healthcare Improvement Fellowship*
2. Michael Tresillian², Program Director, *CEQ Healthcare Improvement Fellowship*
3. Linda McCormack³, Faculty Director, *CEQx, Clinical Director – Healthcare Improvement Unit*

The fields of resilience engineering, Safety II and the foundational science of complex systems are starting to seed transformative shifts in many industries. For healthcare, the face validity for these ideas seems particularly high. Many clinicians have found deep resonance with the perspectives made available by complexity science and the applied fields of resilience engineering (RE) and its extensions into the safety domain. This emerging paradigm has allowed for the formal recognition of the fluidity inherent in delivering responsive clinical care, the unavoidability of adaptive decision-making, the non-linearities in developing an accurate diagnosis and the seemingly intractable nature of systems we rely on and work within. It is somewhat paradoxical that a paradigm shift towards the acknowledgment of ambiguity and uncertainty in clinical care has reinvigorated the traditional pursuits of clinical safety, quality and improvement to the degree that it has.

Clinical Excellence Queensland in Australia, through its improvement transformation institute (CEQx) has sought to establish a clinician-focused healthcare improvement leadership program but created this on a foundation of complex systems science rather than the more conventional model (derived from the process improvement literature). This program enables deep immersion of our improvement fellows in safety II and resilience engineering theory and methods whilst allowing them opportunities to test these ideas in parallel real-world improvement work. Notably, Professor Jeffrey Braithwaite's seminal papers on creating a resilient healthcare system bookend our program's commencement and culmination to allow fellows to meaningfully gauge their own shifts over an intense and cognitively taxing year. System-level outcomes from this unique investment into a focused group of clinicians will take some time to be fully realised but early indications are encouraging. In this article we share stories from three fellows who recently graduated the program and how the resilient healthcare paradigm has influenced their thinking and shaped their clinical improvement priorities.

Matthew Burstow is an acute surgeon and a graduand of the 2019 iteration of the healthcare improvement fellowship program. Matt recently stepped up to a leadership role as the divisional director of surgical services at Logan Hospital in the south of Brisbane. At the commencement of his fellowship, Matt sought to improve access and utilisation of operating theatres having tried process engineering methods (lean & six sigma) and having achieved mixed results.

Matthew Burstow
Acute Surgeon
2019 Improvement Fellow

Matt narrates the shift he experienced in his perspective

Matt found the fellowship cohort's foray into complex systems science reshaped his perspectives on various issues profoundly. Matt felt complexity science and RE validated deeper suspicions that variation management and waste minimisation goals were incongruent with the unpredictable and reactive reality of acute (unplanned) surgical admissions. Once Matt began to reframe his view of the system as complex, replete with myriad trade-off decisions, sensitive to externalities and subject to competitive pressures (for shared theatre resources across different surgical specialities), he came to view reliable outcomes as more closely tied to resilient performance than merely a function of improved process reliability. Matt gravitated to the functional resonance analysis method (FRAM) to model possible changes within his system. Matt found that the application of FRAM brought some of the complex inter-dependencies in his system into sharper focus, making them more explicit, and therefore more feasible to engage with. Matt noted the ability to model control functions, resource utilisation and preconditions and seeing how they interact to be revelatory. FRAM exposed the multiple appropriate 'paths' through which patients could enter his service and the avoidable problems that a pathway simplification focus might create. Through his application of FRAM, Matt also detected issues that could in fact benefit from optimisation, such as in reducing times spent awaiting diagnostic test results.

Since the fellowship, Matt has been actively engaging with peers to shift the surgical improvement fraternity towards a resilience engineering approach in order to better tackle problems of flow, resource utilisation and safety. As a senior leader in his hospital's response to the COVID-19 pandemic, Matt has found the resilience engineering perspective shaping how he navigates local solutions that have emerged to manage personal protective equipment stocks and anticipatory modifications to care protocols. Matt elaborates: *"The process driven thing to do would be to squash this out and enforce adherence to guidelines." ... "I've been letting some things go, see how they develop and whether they offer some resilience to the system" ... "it was really helpful to have this foundation of knowledge of complexity in a situation like this"*.

Anne Hooper is a senior nurse at Mackay Base Hospital (in regional Queensland) and is an alumna of the 2019 fellowship program. Anne entered the program with a well-defined clinical problem to work on during her fellowship year – specifically, to improve compliance with recommended timeframes for managing emergency patients presenting with a stroke (a serious neurological condition requiring urgent care). Anne described her early months of the fellowship as frustrating on many levels. In terms of her project, Anne found herself having to periodically revisit what the ‘real’ problem was, but in retrospect recognised this as natural progression into a deeper systemic perspective of the issue. Anne recounted how she had a gradual realisation that designing a better ‘pathway’ may have been a solution for the wrong problem. Rather, Anne came to terms with the idea that the time it took to respond to patients (no matter how urgent) was an emergent property of a complex system where simple things (the availability of an open phone line to take an ambulance officer’s call) and very complicated things (access to senior medical officers who might be shared across other teams) all influenced how well orchestrated a system appeared at any point in time. Anne pivoted to a more appreciative examination of the system and how it performed under varying conditions, how clinicians thought about and prioritised tasks and ways in which positive workarounds could be enabled when conditions were less than ideal. Like Matt, Anne also found benefit in guiding her thinking and change efforts by constructing a FRAM model but en route, also discovered a newfound curiosity about how work is (actually) done.

Denise Hobson, a geriatrician and general physician with the Royal Brisbane and Women’s Hospital, joined the fellowship in 2019. Denise led a program seeking to expand an innovative service delivery model for the healthcare of residents from nursing homes across the north side of the greater Brisbane region. Denise’s natural inclination for partnership and collaboration led her to prioritise relationships with general practices in the region, with individual aged care facilities and with receiver services (emergency departments and speciality geriatric services) within the health system. Denise found that learning about complexity and systems resilience lent support for what she felt was intuitively correct, that is taking an adaptive, negotiated and relationships driven approach. Denise sought to build a

sustainable person-centred service model – knitting entities that were traditionally divided and could sometimes be transactional (and even territorial) when managing vulnerable patients across the continuum of care. Denise’s immersion in complexity and resilient healthcare also shaped in subtle ways how the service was structured, the goals the team aligned to and how success was ultimately defined for the project, extending beyond the hard metrics of ‘avoided hospital admissions’.

To learn more about the CEQ Improvement fellowship program, other stories and outputs from our alumni, please get in touch at improvementfellowship@health.qld.gov.au or email the faculty directly.

4.4. Learning from everyday work

by Ron Gantt, USA

This article describes a consultant's experience articulating and demonstrating the importance of learning from everyday work towards improving safety.

This is Gerald. Gerald works for a solid waste collections organization at a large municipality in the middle of the United States. He drives a large truck that picks up carts full of garbage and hauls them off to the local garbage dumps. In the process of doing this work, Gerald and his colleagues occasionally have accidents and incidents. Whether it is injuries, such as strains and sprains, or hitting other vehicles or damaging the property of residents, bad things sometimes happen in the course of picking up garbage.

In an effort to reduce the number of these negative events, we partnered with the organization to figure out what was going on. But how? The traditional approach to these projects, and the one the organization initially favored, was to have an expert come into the organization, tell them the right way to do things (based on understanding how and why things were going wrong), and help them create a process that gets the operators to do this one right way. Then, any accidents would result from not doing things the right way, and those responsible could be held accountable.

But that's not how these things work in real life organizations. Accidents are not a product of something breaking or failing, but rather a product of the normal work system functioning in an abnormal way. This means that creating a system that prevents failure by only looking at how things fail will not work. You cannot understand failure by only looking at failure. You have to understand how the system normally functions, how it normally works, and how that same functioning sometimes fails.

Based on this, we proposed an approach that was based on participant-observation of workers in the real work environment. We would "ride along" with workers to see what the world looked like from their perspective. This way we could see what goal conflicts, constraints, and variability Gerald and his colleagues had to manage, what resources the organization has provided to help Gerald deal with these issues, and what strategies Gerald used to bridge the gap between how the organization imagined work was done and how work had to be done. From there we could identify opportunities to support the work that Gerald and his colleagues are doing, as well as identify adaptations that Gerald and his colleagues are adopting to deal with the complexity of their work.

But for an organization convinced that the traditional approach would be best, an approach based on learning from the things that go well did not make sense at first. In helping organizations understand what we are trying to do, we often find it is important to first break down the idea that we are the experts. In particular, safety professionals often have a nasty habit of telling people how to do tasks that the safety professional has not, in fact, ever done. So, we explained to the organization that all hazards and other "unsafe conditions" exist within the context of work. They are

not there randomly, placed intentionally to hurt people and break stuff. To solve problems, you first have to understand them. If we are going to develop processes and tools that help them deal with the dangers Gerald and his colleagues face, we need to understand the work processes that surround and give rise to those dangers.

But if you're going to get a clear picture of how work is done, you not only need to convince the organization, but you have to convince the workers themselves. They are often not used to people, especially safety people, observing their work. As a result, they often default to showing you how what they think you want to see, not actually what you're looking for. You can alleviate some of this by providing communication to workers in advance, but often that is not enough.

The best way to get across to Gerald what we were trying to do was to spend a good deal of time when we first got into the truck in conversation. We allowed him and his colleagues time to ask us questions and even offered to allow them to read the notes we were writing during the observation. Again, we approached this by being deferential, noting that we wanted to help solve the problems not by looking at Gerald, but by understanding what he and his colleagues have to deal with on a daily basis. To do that we needed to learn from the experts. By acknowledging our ignorance and affirming their expertise it placed us on an even plane with them. Without a significant power differential Gerald and his colleagues were very open with us about the realities they faced every day.

Another important lesson we learned in this process is to avoid taking the lead on anything. Do not do anything unless they do it first. This is especially important when it comes to things that are procedurally required. For example, we would not put on any safety equipment (even if we knew it was required) until they would put it on. We would not put on our seat belt until they did. The reason is that we found that when we led the way on anything, the workers would follow suit. If we put on our hard hat, they would put theirs on. If we didn't, then they would be more likely to do what they normally did. We also wouldn't ask them about it until later. For example, if they weren't wearing a seat belt, we would wait until a few hours into ride, and then ask them about it. Usually, we would ask in a way that allowed us to verify a hypothesis. For example, "I noticed that you have to get in and out of the truck a lot to manually pick up bags. I imagine that would make it hard to wear a seat belt, because you'd have to take it on and off a lot. Is that right?" Then the worker would confirm or deny what we saw.

The amazing thing about all of this was how open Gerald and his colleagues were with us. We got to see how complex their work was, including strategies they use to manage risk in real time and they even told us about the incidents (some of which were not reported to the company) that taught them these strategies. We were then able to use this information in two ways. First, we could present a clearer picture to management about work as done. Showing managers the realities workers face, the struggles and constraints they deal with, helps managers make better decisions, whether that is in terms of allocation of resources, or simply understanding failure better.

Second, we used a cross-functional team that included front-line workers, including Gerald, safety staff, supervisors and managers (we simply called it the Improvement Team) to go over the information and identify opportunities for to improve system resilience. This went beyond identifying and controlling hazards. We focused on ways to improve the flow of information, to reduce physical and cognitive load on drivers, and eliminating bottlenecks in the system. For small changes, employees were able to implement improvements quickly. For larger changes, we developed micro-experiments to test ideas whenever possible. This provides helps managers by managing consequences as much as possible and giving them more information before having to engage in large, potentially politically consequential initiatives. At the end of the process, Gerald and the rest of the improvement team came up with a great list of potential improvements. Perhaps most importantly, the workers all reported being excited by the process. They felt

heard and were hopeful that they may get support dealing with the issues they deal with on a daily basis. The conversations between managers and front-line staff were constructive, which workers realizing that management was interested in listening to them and managers realizing that workers often have great ideas to contribute. And we find that these non-quantifiable relational factors, dialogue and trust, often increase system resilience in ways more profound than even physical changes.

4.5. Engaging the “Uns”

by Laurin Mooney and Beth Lay, USA

Pre-task briefs on managing risks could benefit from going deeper, by engaging the 6 “Uns”. By Laurin Mooney
<https://www.behighlyreliable.com> and Beth Lay

We’ve been trained for decades to do a thorough pre-task brief focused on identifying and managing every risk we can think of. While this is a fine, there’s a major problem when applying this to complex and highly variable work: we lack the certainty that can be found in routine, stable environments.

To probe the “uns”, we start with talking a lot about ambiguity. We train teams to notice when they’re in an uncertain situation and to take actions to learn more about the situation.

For example, while working to restore the electric grid after a storm, crews may encounter deep water from storm surges and rain. Traditional safety might say, “don’t drive through water deeper than the center of the tire.” Guess what, there’s a lot of ambiguity hidden in this simple statement. When people approach water over the road and other uncertain, ambiguous situations, we tend to make assumptions and categorize too soon, leading us into trouble.

Instead, encourage teams to notice the situation and “engage the uns.” Actively probe the:

1. Unknown: How deep is the water?
2. Unclear: Are you in an unfamiliar area? Do you know the roads?
3. Uncontrollable: How much water might be under the road? Can the road cave in?
4. Uncertain: How fast is the water flowing? How strong is the current?
5. Unseen: Is the water muddy? Is it dark/nighttime?
6. Unstable: Was the road fine when you entered? Has the road flooded since?

Here’s a clue: when you think or say, “It’s probably just . . .” your mind is trying to reconcile uncertainty. Pause and enlist your team members to learn more about the situation.

In our example above, what could the crew do? Stop the truck. Get a little closer (within a safe range) to inspect the water. Look for movement in the water. Estimate the depth with a stick.

After actively probing the “uns”, the team will make a more informed decision.

4.6. Practice – Do we really know why things go well? – RPET - sharing experiences

by Stephan Ore (Norway), Erik Hollnagel (Denmark) and Ivonne Herrera (Norway)

The article describes a new tool - RPET - designed to stimulate people to reflect on the practices, formal and informal strategies that makes the health care system work. The authors describe their experiences with the pilot-implementation of the tool.

The Resilience Performance Enhancement Toolkit (RPET) is proposed and used as debriefing tool to explore everyday work. Its purpose is not to seek answers to specific questions but rather to stimulate people to reflect on the practices, formal and informal strategies that makes the health care system works. The tool was introduced in hospitals in Sweden in 2018 ([for more details click here](#)). In 2019, a pilot was conducted in six diverse healthcare units by healthcare personnel in Norway. The units represent diverse context and different needs. Among others, these were a somatic LTC nursing home for the elderly (Oppsalhjemmet, Oslo), a dementia department at a LTC nursing home (Uranienborghjemmet), an oncology department (Arkershus University Hospital), a clinic for substance abuse and mental health (Venstre Viken), and youth welfare institution (Sandefjord). The tool was used to learn from everyday reflection. A template was distributed to all units and it was adapted in diverse ways. After short introduction to resilience engineering and the tool, the healthcare representatives implemented the tool themselves. Academics were at hand for guidance when needed but not involved in the direct implementation.

Images from the presentation delivered in Oslo under the Patient Safety Conference 2019 arranged by the Norwegian Directorate of Health

The three hospital wards included in the pilot-study had just implemented the patient safety tool The Green Cross. The teams swapped the negative focus in the original method (“Have we had a workday free from harm”) to the positive RPET-questions (“Did something go well today? etc) and thereby renaming it The Green Cross V2!

The following are testimonials from the participants participating in the implementation (Patient Safety Conference 2019):

- In the nursing home, “the nurse assistant had an idea on an improvement measure that motivate an elder person to eat breakfast – focusing on “what is important for you today?” – a positive experience“

- In the oncology department, “information was adapted to a cancer patient including his family and children. This highlighted the importance to arrange a meeting that considers important people for the patient and good communication – a reflection to learn“
- A new employee at the clinic for substance abuse found the tool as “really sympathetic, open for organic questions, allow to know what other colleagues stands for, works for debriefing, playful, fun with the colour markers, astonishingly meaningful and want to continue to use it“
- In the dementia department, the tool “change the focus for what did not go so well to include what went well, what went well today, with a small question the mood changes very fast, incredible how little it takes“
- A possibility to share the small things that makes the difference “what went well today? I finally managed to shower one particular resident that never accepts this. What did you do? I play a song! We tried again and it works every time“
- In the child protection institution, there was a person very negative to the therapist. By using RPET the tool “allowed self-reflection, positive toward the positive issues and created a better relationship with the patient“

The above just reflect views on the application of the tool. This note is an invitation for other to try and share experiences on resilience in practice.

4.7. Safety II in practice workshop, with Erik Hollnagel – Brisbane Australia – A compilation by the beneficiaries of the workshop

A first of its kind in Australia, participants and presenters alike were thrilled to participate in the second regional Safety II in Practice Workshop with Erik Hollnagel and our community of practice. Presented and coordinated by Forgeworks, the workshop brought together like-minded professionals looking to share their learnings, questions and successes on how we as an industry are building adaptive capacity. We embraced the messy stories of work as done and we matured our view and approach to the safety of work. Presenters from several countries and a diverse group of companies pitched in. The organization and facilitation provided by the Forgeworks crew was top notch. Andrew Barrett did a fine job of facilitation and the participants did quite a job of keeping the questions and learning flowing!

A short trip report follows, compiled from the takeaways graciously shared by participants. Some highlights:

- Several presenters shared how they were making progress in growing their safety approaches to improve reliability and resilience. From a strategic approach that included branding and messaging a process that showed planned maturity, to a grass roots approach that showed the ‘many small things’ that added up to a successful approach. The key throughout was to make a plan and then exercise courage to learn by doing.
- Event investigation and response was a favorite topic. Presenters leveled the playing field by showing how cause and effect approaches have limits of utility, instead spending time with what is working well as a starting point, and then moving to increase capacity for success and for failing softly.
- Ever wonder how you can tell if you are learning from success? Several presenters provided action verbs illustrating behaviors characteristic of working to achieve the four resilience potentials – anticipate, monitor, respond, and learn.
- A growing conviction was expressed by quite a number of participants and presenters; that what we are pursuing is not ‘Safety I’ or ‘Safety II’ but what we do every day; a combination of learning activities and approaches that focus on integration of insights across the organization, using overall operations as the focus. A gestalt was mentioned.
- Learning provided many opportunities for discussion, insights arose around learning as a non-event, the power of asking how and what rather than why, and the need for due diligence.
- A cadre of presenters and participants alike spoke to the power of collaboration and the recognition that many efforts that looked successful to outside observers were harder to discern from inside the ‘tunnel’. Our collaborators are helping us realize success.

Some other ‘gems’ captured:

- Non-compliance means we don’t understand how things are really done.
- Future events emerge from known variability that is currently considered irrelevant.
- Ask people what they need and resist telling them what to do.
- Foresight doesn’t change the shape of risk. Action changes the shape of risk.
- Accident investigation is a social process. Causes are constructed and socially agreed as being likely, rather than found.
- What you look for is what you find and what you find is what you fix.

- We should seek to understand what's happening when nothing bad is happening.

The new Safety Differently video was highlighted during a surprise visit by Sidney Dekker, who also provided a wonderful summary of how we are progressing!

4.8. Physically distant, socially connected

by Ron Gantt, USA

Like so many others I'm essentially stuck at home right now. In the San Francisco Bay Area, where I live and do most of my work, a shelter in place order has been in effect since March 17th and looks like it will continue at least through April. Furthermore, as a consultant, much of my work has slowed down as non-essential business is shut down for the moment. Conferences are being postponed. Workshops are being cancelled.

Of course, in times such as this you can start to fill

up your time with all those projects you put off. Updating materials. Writing that paper you've wanted to write. But there is a nagging uncertainty that is hard to shake, and it's made even worse by a growing sense of isolation. We need to stay separate from each other right now, and for good reason. But it's a bit jarring to not have regular contact with colleagues, especially at time where the comfort of social connection can be so important.

In times of uncertainty when faced with new constraints people are often forced to rethink old routines and repurpose old tools to develop new ways of relating to each other and their world. It occurred to me that not only was I not the only one feeling the effects of isolation and uncertainty, but that I also had the means to create ways for people to connect and learn together. I just had never used them as a means to create social connection (at least not intentionally). But I decided I could use web-based platforms that I've used countless times for business meetings to create spaces where like-minded people from the Safety-II/Resilience Engineering community could come together to keep learning together in this time.

I called them the Physically Distant, Socially Connected workshop series (thanks to Andrew Barrett for suggesting the title) and I'm hosting them through my company, Reflect Consulting Group. The sessions include presentations on topics such as introductions to Safety-II/Resilience Engineering or learning from work, get togethers where we discuss topics such as metrics or the role of people in safety/resilience, and discussions around more advanced theories or papers, such as graceful extensibility.

If you are interested in joining any of these sessions, you can follow Reflect on LinkedIn or Twitter (@reflectcg). The schedule of sessions for each week can be found there. We are trying to keep the sessions small, with 10 attendees or less, to allow for discussion, so space is limited.

It is important in this time that we do not wait for other people to set up opportunities like this. Yes, there are some things that we need other people to do for us, but there is almost always something we can do to make the situation better for ourselves and others. Reach out, think differently about what you have at your disposal and how you can use your strengths to create the conditions for resilient performance in your world.

4.9. Think of resilience as a verb, not a noun

by Daniel Eisenberg, USA

Across many application contexts, resilience remains a hyper popular, confused, and conflicted term. Part of the reason that resilience is so difficult to apply is that the word itself occupies an awkward position in the English language. Although resilience is used as a noun, the most popular definitions describe it as a capacity to act – which makes resilience an action that systems perform, like a verb, rather than a property that a system has, like a noun. There is a historical precedent to this way of thinking [1], as the word resilience originates from the Latin word *resilio*, “to leap” or “bounce,” and first entered the English language in the 1500s as the verb *resile*, meaning, “to retract”, “to cancel”, or “to return to a former position.” Thinking of resilience as it was originally used – as a verb – has important implications for how we make military installations and operations more resilient.

Comparing different forms of the words risk and resilience illustrate this point [2]. While both risk and resilience work well as abstract nouns, only risk works as a quantifiable noun. This may explain why risk analysis across many organizations involves quantified threats, vulnerabilities, and consequences with little to no ambiguity. This may also explain the difficulty experts have coming up with quantifiable, concrete measures of resilience. Trying to measure resilience may simply be a lost cause, stemming from the linguistic fact that “to leap”, “to cancel”, or “to return” cannot be meaningfully counted.

In contrast, the action verb form of risk is a poor choice, whereas the word *resile*, although obscure, is nonetheless proper and useful. Risk works well as a linking or helping verb, but *resile* does not. This highlights the fact that risk management actions only pertain to a specific threat with known consequences (e.g., flooding). Instead, we should think of resilience not just in the capacity to act, but in the action itself. Resilience flips our perspective from identifying and mitigating known risks towards understanding the systems, processes, and actions taken to manage any risk.

Part of Speech	Risk	Resilience
Abstract Noun	What is risk?	What is resilience?
Concrete / Quantifiable Noun	What is a risk?	What is a resilience?
Action Verb	I risked.	I resiled.
Linking Verb	I risk floods.	I resile floods.
Helping Verb	I risk flooding.	I resile flooding.

Consequentially, the tools and methods for measuring and addressing risks are not appropriate for resilience, as these two related concepts are fundamentally different. An appropriate risk-based question for a real-world system is, “How can we mitigate the damages from the next flood?” Answering this question requires measures of future flooding probability and the likelihood that this flooding will damage military systems and results in recommendations to mitigate these impacts. On the other hand, an appropriate resilience-based question for the same system is, “What do we do when we flood?” Answering this question focuses attention on understanding how floods are sensed, anticipated, responded to, and learned from on base and results in new systems that enhance these actions during disasters.

Note: Green and red colors emphasize grammatically correct and incorrect sentences, respectively.

Editor’s note: Also see David Woods’ 2019 webinar on this topic.

References:

[1] Alexander, David E. "Resilience and disaster risk reduction: an etymological journey." *Natural hazards and earth system sciences* 13, no. 11 (2013): 2707-2716.

[2] Eisenberg, Daniel A. "How to Think About Resilient Infrastructure Systems." PhD diss., Arizona State University, 2018.

4.10. Safety-II vs. HRO in Socio-Technical Systems: An Overview Framed via Resilience

by Rune Storesund and Karlene Roberts, USA

This article provides a high-level overview of Safety-II and High Reliability Organizations (HROs). The two concepts are outlined and a discussion on the similarities and differences between Safety-II and HRO is presented.

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Introduction

This article provides a high-level overview of Safety-II and High Reliability Organizations (HROs). The two concepts are outlined and a discussion on the similarities and differences between Safety-II and HRO is presented. Both frameworks are targeted to more resilient Socio-Technical Systems, where human and organizational factors are acknowledged as important attributes that can enhance and/or degrade operations and outcomes, as well as the ability to proactively and interactively mitigate undesired outcomes before 'failure.' Attributes of a Socio-Technical System are introduced as there are fundamental factors unique to these types systems relative to Resilience and HROs.

Socio-Technical Systems

The concept of a Socio-Technical System originated following WWII[1],[2] and recognizes the inseparable relationship between human and organizational factors and their physical system components. The working hypothesis was that improved operational system performance would be realized by leveraging the knowledge and capabilities of workers to confront technological uncertainty, variation, and adaptation. This perspective is very important when examining the performance of 'systems' that are operated and managed by 'people.' There are key fundamental operational principles, first articulated by A. Cherns[3], associated with the Socio-Technical System framework, which include:

- Principle 1 – Compatibility: The operationalized STS must be compatible with its objectives and intended outcomes. If a system objective includes the capability to self-modify, adapting to change and making the most use of the creative capacities of the individual, then processes must exist to capture and propagate inputs from system agents (i.e. the 'people' of the system). Positive attributes that promote and facilitate system self-modification, adapting to change, and leveraging the creating capacities of the individual include: (a) leadership commitment to safety values and actions; (b) presence of a respectful work environment; (c) an environment for raising concerns; (d) inquiring attitudes; (e) work process/workflow evaluations; and (f) continuous improvement/process improvement.
- Principle 2 – Minimal Critical Specification: This principle has two aspects, negative and positive. The negative simply states that no more should be specified than is absolutely essential; the positive requires that we identify what is essential.

- Principle 3 – The Socio-Technical Criterion: This principle states that variances, if they cannot be eliminated, must be controlled as near to their point of origin as possible. We need here to define variance, a word much used in socio-technical literature. Variance is any unprogrammed event; a key variance is one which critically affects outcome.
- Principle 4 – The Multifunctionality Principle–Organism vs. Mechanism: The traditional form of organization relies very heavily on the redundancy of parts. It requires people to perform highly specialized, fractionated tasks. There is often a rapid turnover of such people, but they are comparatively easily replaced. Each is treated as a replaceable part. Simple mechanisms are constructed on the same principle. Disadvantages arise when a range of responses is required, that is, when a large repertoire of performances is required from the mechanism or the organization. This usually occurs if the environmental demands vary. It then becomes more adaptive and less wasteful for each element to possess more than one function.
- Principle 5 – Boundary Location: In any organization, departmental boundaries have to be drawn somewhere and are usually drawn so as to group people and activities on the basis of one or more of three criteria: technology, territory and time. The principle has certain corollaries. A very important one concerns the management of the boundaries between department and department, between department and the organization as a whole and between the organization and the outside world. The more the control of activities within the department becomes the responsibility of the members, the more the role of the supervisor/foreman/manager is concentrated on the boundary activities.
- Principle 6 – Information Flow: This principle states that information systems should be designed to provide information in the first place to the point where action on the basis of it will be needed. Information systems are not typically so designed. Properly directed, sophisticated information systems can, however, supply a work team with exactly the right type and amount of feedback to enable them to learn to control the variances which occur within the scope of their spheres of responsibility and competence and to anticipate events which are likely to have a bearing on their performance.
- Principle 7 – Support Congruence: This principle states that the systems of social support should be designed so as to reinforce the behaviors that the organization structure is designed to elicit. If, for example, the organization is designed on the basis of group or team operation with team responsibility, a payment system incorporating individual members would be incongruent with these objectives. Not only payment systems, but systems of selection, training, conflict resolution, work measurement, performance assessment, timekeeping, leave allocation, promotion and separation can all reinforce or contradict the behaviors which are desired.
- Principle 8 – Human Values: This principle states that an objective of organizational design should be to provide a high quality of work. We recognize that quality is a subjective phenomenon and that everyone wants to have responsibility, variety, involvement, growth, etc. The objective is to provide these for those who do want them without subjecting those who do not to the tyranny of peer control. In this regard, we are obliged to recognize that all desirable objectives may not be achievable simultaneously.
- Principle 9 – Incompletion: The system is never ‘completed.’ Continuous improvement is required on many of the system elements, including work processes, hazard identification and risk management.

Thus, for a comprehensive approach to Socio-Technical Systems, there is a portfolio of factors that must be addressed in order to positively impact outcomes. Omitting consideration of all factors will result in partial solutions that typically result in overall failure.

Resilience

Resilience, as used in the context of an attribute of Socio-Technical Systems, refers to the ability of a system to “adjust its functioning prior to, during, or following changes and disturbances, and thereby sustain required operations under both expected and unexpected conditions[4].” It should be noted that three important terms are identified in this definition that must be underscored.

Required operations: This term identifies the core functional outcome(s) the system is required to generate. If these outcomes are not generated, system ‘failure’ occurs. We note that it is very common, however, for these core functional outcomes to be implicit rather than explicit, resulting in ambiguity across organizational divisions and personnel. The lack of specificity with respect to the core functional outcomes/required operations results in confusion within a system’s organization and hinders the ability to clearly communicate the core required operations.

Expected conditions: These are the anticipated operational parameters for the system and are typically delineated through a series of explicit and implicit system assumptions generated during the initial configuration of the system.

Unexpected conditions: These are operational parameters that may impact a system that have not been considered or evaluated to date. Unexpected conditions also include parameters that were ‘unimaginable’ as well as remote scenarios that may have been originally considered, but discounted due to a perception of very low likelihood of occurrence.

Woods and Hollnagel[5] describe three time-dependent qualities of resilience within a Socio-Technical System and its exposure to the surrounding environment, which is subject to dynamic developments over time. First, anticipation – knowing what might be expected to occur. Second, attention – knowing what to look for. Third, response – knowing what to do and having the required resources to fully implement the response.

Image result for resilience required qualities Figure1: Resilience qualities as described by Woods and Hollnagel[5].

Safety – II

Notions of Resilience, as manifested through approaches such as Resilience Engineering, Safety Differently, and Safety II, are concepts introduced in the last several decades. These approaches focus on proactive risk management measures and more fully account for human and organizational factors with respect to enhancement and reduction of undesirable system outcomes.

Hollnagel [6] presents the concept of Safety II where emphasis is centered on ‘humans’ as a resource necessary for system flexibility and resilience. The working hypothesis is that Socio-Technical Systems are complex, which results in work situations (workflows, procedures, etc.) being underspecified, thus actual work conditions will differ from what has been specified and/or described. Performance variability (the need for modifications/adjustments) by the workforce is thus not only normal and necessary, but required. Hollnagel states[6]:

Because most socio-technical systems are intractable, work conditions will nearly always differ from what has been specified or prescribed. This means that little, if anything, can be done unless work – tasks and tools – are adjusted so that they correspond to the situation. Performance variability is not only normal and necessary, but also indispensable. The adjustments are made by people individually and collectively, as well as by the organization itself. Everyone, from bottom to top, must adjust what they do to meet existing conditions (resources and requirements).

Because the resources of work (time, information, materials, equipment, the presence and availability of other people) are finite, such adjustments will always be approximate rather than perfect.

Hollnagel presents Safety I as the ‘reactive’ approach to system performance, with focus on ‘root-cause’ analysis and malfunctions from human participation. It negates the positive contributions humans make to eliminating/reducing magnitudes of hazards and consequences (see Table). Hollnagel posits that Safety I and Safety II, collectively, constitute Socio-Technical System resilience (figure). The Safety II approach empowers the human and organizational components of the Socio-Technical Systems to spearhead the “Anticipation,” “Attention,” and “Response,” aspects of the Resilience qualities, as well as the “updating” and “learning” shown in Figure 1.

Table 1: A comparison of Safety I and Safety II

	Safety-I	Safety-II
Definition of safety	As few things as possible go wrong.	As many things as possible go right.
Safety management principle	Reactive, respond when something happens, or is categorised as an unacceptable risk.	Proactive, continuously trying to anticipate developments and events.
Explanations of accidents	Accidents are caused by failures and malfunctions. The purpose of an investigation is to identify causes and contributory factors.	Things basically happen in the same way, regardless of the outcome. The purpose of an investigation is to understand how things usually go right as a basis for explaining how things occasionally go wrong.
Attitude to the human factor	Humans are predominantly seen as a liability or a hazard.	Humans are seen as a resource necessary for system flexibility and resilience.
Role of performance variability	Harmful, should be prevented as far as possible.	Inevitable but also useful. Should be monitored and managed.

Figure 2: Resilience a combination of Safety I and Safety II (Hollnagel, 2014).

High Reliability Organizations (HROs)

Research on high reliability organizations began in the mid-1980s and examined complex organizations that seemed to operate without failure in complex environments [7],[8]. The underlying supposition of this work was that existing organizational theory concepts do not explain the processes at work in such organizations very well. The work initially focused on three organizations considered relatively exotic by critics. They were the U.S. Navy’s nuclear-powered aircraft carriers, the Federal Aviation Administration’s air traffic control system, and a commercial nuclear power plant.

Weick and Sutcliffe [9] identified the major components of high reliability organizations:

- Preoccupation with failure. Attention to close calls and near misses.
- Reluctance to simplify interpretations. Attention to root cause analysis.
- Sensitivity to operations. Situational awareness and carefully designed management practices.
- Commitment to resilience. Constant attention to management practices that might need to be changed.
- Deference to expertise. Listen to experts and follow their advice.

All organizations, HRO and non-HROs, develop beliefs about the world, including susceptibility to hazards resulting in undesired outcomes. Organizations develop approaches to confront these hazards via norms, regulations, procedures, rules, guidelines, job descriptions, and training materials. During the course of operation, organizations accumulate unnoticed events that are at odds with accepted beliefs about the hazards and resulting consequences.

Unlike non-HROs, HROs develop beliefs about the world, hazards, and potential outcomes with fewer simplifications, less finality, and more process-improvement. The definition of what is ‘hazardous’ is continually revisited and updated. HROs tend to accumulate and more rapidly detect unnoticed smaller events that are at odds with what they expect. This gives them the ability to investigate and understand the anomalies and outline proactive responses to more rapidly restore reliable performance.

Comparison of Safety II and HRO

A close examination of Safety II and HRO actually reveals substantial overlap, where the focus is on the ‘every-day opportunities’ for people to anticipate and respond in a proactive fashion to minimize the magnitude (or even eliminate) undesirable outcomes. The ability of people (whether individuals or groups) is recognized as an asset and resource for pro-active risk mitigation.

Extending these concepts to the notion of Resilience by Hollnagel and Woods⁵ (Figure 3), we can map, as a function of time, Proactive as corresponding to the system’s anticipation and attention phases; Interactive measures are taken during the attention and response phases; and lastly, Reactive measures are taken during the response phase. We note that there are frequently post-event actions, based on ‘lessons learned’, that can be imposed on a system based on outcomes of other similar system incidents. These reactive changes can happen years or decades after the original incident.

Mapping Safety I and Safety II on the Resilience Framework shows that Safety II corresponds primarily to the Anticipation and Attention phases. Safety I is almost exclusively focused on the Response phase or, more commonly, on the “After the Fact Imposed Lessons.” Safety II, however, leverages contributions by the people in the system to identify and mitigate the potential occurrence of undesirable system outcomes. Safety II, thus, is an essential part of a system’s ability to be resilient and minimize the occurrence of undesired outcomes.

Lastly, HROs concentrate their resources (people) towards the Anticipation, Attention, and early Response phases as a result of the continual updating processes. HROs do undergo reactive “Learning,” but because the substantial investment in the proactive approaches, rarely experience the magnitude of undesired outcomes as non-HROs and are able to proactively incorporate “After the Fact Imposed Lessons” learned by other systems before having to actually respond to an unfolding event. Figure 3: Scope of attention to System Resilience from a Safety II and HRO standpoint.

Extending Safety II and HRO to the earlier Socio-Technical System attributes, we find that the same techniques are employed through Safety II and HRO; these are summarized in Table 2. Virtually identical approaches can be mapped to Safety II and HRO.

Table 2: Summary of Safety II and HRO approaches to address attributes of Socio-Technical Systems

Attribute - Safety II- HRO

Compatibility - Satisfied by updating and refining objectives and intended outcomes - Satisfied by updating and refining objectives and intended outcomes.

Minimal Critical Specification - Satisfied via process improvement and updating capabilities from workforce by eliminating inefficient processes and augmenting/enhancing where appropriate - Satisfied via process improvement and updating capabilities from workforce by eliminating inefficient processes and augmenting/enhancing where appropriate.

Socio-Technical Criterion - Satisfied by empowering workforce to identify and mitigate variances at origination points - Satisfied by empowering workforce to identify and mitigate variances at origination points.

Multifunctional Principle – Organism vs Mechanism - Satisfied by embracing cross-training and adaptability. - Satisfied by embracing cross-training and adaptability.

Boundary Location - Satisfied by encouraging and promoting variance-tracing across organizational boundaries - Satisfied by encouraging and promoting variance-tracing across organizational boundaries.

Information Flow - Satisfied by promoting information exchange and dialogue across organizational boundaries and hierarchical levels. - Satisfied by promoting information exchange and dialogue across organizational boundaries and hierarchical levels.

Support Congruence - Satisfied by providing compensation schemes that promote and encourage systems-based outcomes rather than individual-focus. - Satisfied by providing compensation schemes that promote and encourage systems-based outcomes rather than individual-focus.

Human Values - Satisfied by allowing some flexibility and individualism in how work is accomplished, but ensuring consistency with intended outcomes. - Satisfied by allowing some flexibility and individualism in how work is accomplished, but ensuring consistency with intended outcomes.

Incompletion - Satisfied via process-improvement programs, training, incident reviews, and mindfulness. - Satisfied via process-improvement programs, training, incident reviews, and mindfulness.

Conclusion

Safety II approach empowers the human and organizational components of the Socio-Technical Systems to spearhead the “Anticipation,” “Attention,” and “Response,” aspects of the Resilience qualities, as well as the “updating” and “learning.” The emphasis is placed on proactive activities that empower risk-reduction activities by system workers, rather than post-incident reactive system changes. Realization of undesirable outcomes is typically the result of potentially flawed procedures rather than

HROs are groups of individuals who monitor deviation in anticipated outcomes with actual outcomes by minimizing inappropriate simplifications, reduced finality, and regular process-improvement. The definition of what is ‘hazardous’ is continually revisited and updated. HROs tend to accumulate and more rapidly detect unnoticed smaller events that are at odds with what they expect. This gives them the ability to investigate and understand the anomalies and outline proactive responses to more rapidly restore reliable performance.

Both frameworks are targeted to more reliable and robust Socio-Technical Systems, where human and organizational factors are acknowledged as factors that can enhance and/or degrade system operations and outcomes, as well as the ability to proactively and interactively mitigate undesired outcomes before 'failure.'

About the Center for Catastrophic Risk Management (CCRM)

The Center for Catastrophic Risk Management (CCRM) is a group of academic researchers and practitioners who recognize the need for interdisciplinary solutions to avoid and mitigate tragic events. This group of internationally recognized experts in the fields of engineering, social science, medicine, public health, public policy, and law was formed following the tragic consequences of Hurricane Katrina to formulate ways for researchers and experts to share their lifesaving knowledge and experience with industry and government. CCRM's international membership provides experience across cultures and industries that demonstrate widespread susceptibility to pervasive threats and the inadequacy of popular, checklist-based remedies that are unlikely to serve in the face of truly challenging problems.

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4.11. Book corner: The Oxford Handbook of Expertise (2020)

Reviewed by Jan Maarten Schraagen, The Netherlands

Edited by Paul Ward, Jan Maarten Schraagen, Julie Gore, and Emilie Roth

The Oxford Handbook of Expertise provides a comprehensive picture of the field of Expertise Studies. It offers both traditional and contemporary perspectives, and importantly, a multidiscipline-multimethod view of the science and engineering research on expertise. The book presents different perspectives, theories, and methods of conducting expertise research. As such, it is organized into five Sections:

- Section One deals with frameworks, theories and models for characterising expertise. Its chapters range from neural mechanisms of expertise, via the classic expertise approach (dominated by the seminal work of Herbert Simon and Bill Chase from Carnegie-Mellon University), to contemporary macro-cognitive models of expertise, as well as situated and distributed approaches to expertise, all the way up to sociological perspectives on expertise.
- Section Two is on methods to study, test, analyze and represent expertise, and covers both familiar ground (Hierarchical Task Analysis, Incident-based methods, Cognitive Work Analysis), as well as qualitative research methods such as ethnography and video reflexivity.
- Section Three delves into the various domains of expertise that have been studied, such as music, sports, healthcare, firefighting, aviation, military, railroad, nuclear, and spaceflight. Interestingly, compared to other Handbooks, this section also covers domains that have only recently been studied, as they have emerged over the past decade or so: the cyber domains and intelligence analysis. Moreover, it also covers ill-structured domains such as law enforcement and business.
- Section Four is on developing, accelerating, and preserving expertise, and is likely the most forward-looking part of the Handbook. It discusses such concepts and theories as ‘team reflection’, ‘cognitive flexibility theory’, the role of mentors and coaches in developing expertise, how to acquire the expertise that will be needed to prosper in the twenty-first century, and how to frame and translate expertise for government. For you as a reader interested in resilience engineering, it also contains a chapter on ‘expertise and resilience’ by Havinga, Bergstrom, Dekker, and Rae.
- Finally, Section Five contains a very readable and timely chapter on the “war” on expertise as waged by five communities that seek to discredit experts and how to respond to these communities. If there is one chapter that everyone in our community should read, it is this one.

Each chapter in this Handbook was thoroughly reviewed by at least two reviewers (as a Section editor, I can attest to this). As a result, at almost 1300 pages this is a true goldmine that both provides state of the art reviews as well as foundations for future research. It also shows how the various views on expertise can be used to address current issues. Compared to other Handbooks, this one is more comprehensive in its scope and more inclusive in its approach. But don't take my word for it: as an Editor of this Handbook, I invite you to make up your own mind!

4.12. How Can We Build Resilient Cities?

by Leire Labaka, Spain

Cities are increasingly complex networks of people, infrastructures and services. The article highlights the importance of focusing on building resilient infrastructures to enable better preparedness of cities to disasters such as the current COVID-19 pandemic.

Nowadays, over half of the world's population lives in cities, and according to United Nations, 66% of the total world's population is expected to live in cities by the year 2050. Furthermore, cities have become more and more complex consisting of an extensive network of people, infrastructures and services that are strongly interconnected. With this rapid urbanization, cities are becoming more exposed and vulnerable to the effects of a wide range of spectrum disasters, ranging from acute shocks such as floods and earthquakes to chronic stresses such as the ones caused by climate change or the current COVID-19 pandemic. Moreover, due to current globalization, the impact of a disaster can extend the city's boundaries affecting regions and nations, even the world as it is occurring with the COVID-19 case.

In light of this situation and in order to ensure the safety and wellbeing of the citizens, cities must develop resilience capacities to mitigate the impact from crisis to be able to respond and adapt to critical situations in order to keep critical services functioning and recover from the crises as soon as possible and in the most efficient way. Resilience is defined as a transversal capacity that allows to cope with all kind of threats, expected and unexpected. It goes beyond the traditional risk management approach, and apart from preparing for already expected threats it is also focused on developing preventive and adaptive capacities to deal with unexpected and unprepared threats.

Building city resilience requires a holistic approach that includes ensuring the safety of the critical services as well as understanding dependencies among them, developing social skills to build resilient society, enhancing cross organizational resilience and collaboration efforts among city stakeholders and having good leadership and governance systems that entails proper policy decision making. Furthermore, economical measures to withstand the damages and the economic impact due to the crises as well as environmental policies to ensure the regeneration of the affected ecological areas are essential to ensure the sustainability of the city.

Although during the last years investments to build city resilience have been made, in some cases these efforts have been made in a fragmented manner without considering the interdependences among the city stakeholders. This leads to an inefficient use of available resources. Therefore, developing public-private-people partnerships mechanisms is essential to ensure an efficient city resilience building process.

Last but not least, there is a key factor that drives and foster the proper implementation of the resilience building policies, which is Awareness and Engagement. It is essential that city stakeholders perceive and understand the need to develop resilient cities, are willing to act and participate in resilience building activities and as a result their

commitment towards resilience building process is improved and the collaboration among the city stakeholders is increased. All this will help us to make our cities resilient.

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4.13. Resilience Engineering in Africa: An Emerging Safety Management Strategy

by Dzifa Ahadzi, Africa

The African continent is witnessing a surge in industrialization in recent times. This has led to a fast-growing workforce across the continent. Industrialization comes with its own problems particularly when it comes to workplace safety. Today, workers and employers are constantly confronted with a barrage of safety challenges that need to be solved. Resilience engineering has been introduced in recent years as a new innovative way of dealing with safety management at the workplace. In Africa, very little is known about resilience engineering. Information on this emerging safety management strategy is almost non-existent, coupled with very limited studies conducted on it in the African region. As a new safety management concept, it is expected that with time it would become developed, accepted and explored as a potent safety management strategy in this part of the world.

The concept of resilience engineering (RE) is about how small and large industrial systems function in a safe manner. RE is also about the people who manage the systems and their ability to implement positive safety measures and encourage employees to put up positive safety attitude. For an organization to be resilient, management and workers must be capable of responding expeditiously to sudden changes while enduring minimal stress. RE involves creating a robust system that can bend but not break and stand the test of time. Investing in RE presents Africa with a great opportunity to tap into the benefits of the concept in improving safety at workplaces across the African continent while increasing productivity. For African organizations to become globally competitive, investing in robust methods and systems like this is key.

One of the biggest problems the concept of RE has faced over the years is that it has no clearly defined theoretical framework. Also lacking is a clearly defined method for measuring RE. These make the concept look more abstract than a reality. It also makes it difficult to explain the concept to the understanding of the ordinary man. Different authors have measured RE differently depending on their perspective and understanding. As an emerging concept, there is the need for the RE community to come up with a clear definition of what constitutes RE and a globally accepted method of measuring RE. This would make it easy for practitioners to explain what the concept is all about to the understanding of the ordinary person. In Africa where RE is barely known, it has become difficult to promote it as a safety management strategy because it is not easy explaining it through a practical demonstration. Currently, RE exists more of a concept than a reality. How RE can be measured needs to be resolved once and for all. Insufficient empirical studies into the area, mostly due to lack of funding remains a major drawback of implementing the RE strategy in Africa. More empirical studies on RE are needed in Africa to promote the concept, make it known and accepted.

The goal of many organizations is to avoid the breakdown of their systems when turbulence occurs. RE remains an important consideration in dealing with this phenomenon especially organizations that engage in high risk operations. With the application of RE, safer working environments are assured, leading to improvement in worker morale and productivity. Promoting RE as a safety management technique in Africa has the potential of reducing occupational accidents, injuries, uncertainty and workload pressure on workers. The potential of operationalizing RE successfully in Africa is huge and needs to be deliberately promoted by the RE community.

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5.

Translating Resilience Engineering into practice and COVID-19

June 2020

A word from this issue's editor

by Tarcisio Saurin, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS), Brazil

Welcome to issue #5 of the REA Newsletter! This issue reports on thoughts and experiences of practitioners and academics translating Resilience Engineering (RE) into practice. It shows how people have gained insight from using RE-informed approaches in higher education, incident investigation, and crisis management. These and other contents of this issue are underpinned by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has posed an unprecedented challenge for the resilience of all sorts of socio-technical systems across the world. I hope you enjoy this issue and get ideas and inspiration to the development of more resilient systems.

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5.1. Resilience Engineering Association: Revisiting the past, minding the present, and rethinking the future

By Ivonne Herrera (Norway), Sudeep Hedge (USA), Simon Gill (UK), Pedro Ferreira (Portugal), Elizabeth Lay (USA), and Gesa Praetorius (Sweden)

Our heritage: The collaboration around the concept of resilience started in early 2000 with a meeting where a Core Group [1] of international experts discussed facets of it. Subsequently, “Resilience Engineering” emerged as a perspective to understand and improve safety in complex systems. As a visible outcome of this first symposium the book “Resilience Engineering: Concepts and Precepts[2]” was published. It marks the starting point for a transdisciplinary cooperation integrating knowledge from diverse lines of work and disciplines [3], addressing safety critical domains such as aviation, health care, railway, maritime, nuclear power, energy, road, industrial process control, telecommunication and financial services. The association was formally founded in 2011 with the intention of generating a “stand alone” structure to manage biennial symposia on resilience engineering. It was not long before wider aspirations started across the community and within a few years, the participative approach that trade-marks the work of the association was rapidly shaping.

Today, the Resilience Engineering Association has become a home for scientists and practitioners that are concerned with understanding the many facets, views and understandings of the term “resilience”. The initial focus was clearly built around safety and this remains a fundamental driver of resilience perspectives. Within resilience engineering [4],[5], the quest is not solely about safety but to support the capability of systems, organisations and societies to perform in such a way that both the overarching purpose and operational goals are successfully pursued, whilst taking into account the inevitable need to cope with rapid change and highly unpredictable conditions. Successful performance emerges, not in spite of adverse or changing conditions, but rather because systems develop and sustain the ability to generate opportunities for success from such changes. Further, the scope of resilience engineering has widened to not only address safety critical domains, but also consider critical services, such as web operations. It can be defined as follows:

” A system is resilient if it can adjust its functioning prior to, during, or following events (changes, disturbances, and opportunities), and thereby sustain required operations under both expected and unexpected conditions. [6]“

The initial collaboration has evolved into the Resilience Engineering Association (REA), a global community of researchers and practitioners. Today, the symposia on resilience engineering are opportunities to learn about as well to contribute to theoretical and practical progress from each other, discuss and evolve the understanding of resilience in the community of practice. The collaboration is now materialized and documented through symposium proceedings, journal articles, books, podcasts, webinars, newsletters, partnerships and friendships.

Our driver – what is different about resilience engineering and the association? The role of the REA is to create and support “inclusive, collaborative, engaging and useful arenas” where individuals and organisations are willing to participate, improve knowledge, thus co-creating processes and solutions manifested in formal and informal partnerships. These partnerships integrate practitioners and academics working together to improve resilient performance. The work involves themes such as understanding of empirical phenomena, patterns of adaptation, potential to anticipate, respond, monitor and learn, translation of knowledge and experience into methods, practices and capabilities relevant to diverse work settings. It includes both sharp-end operations, management and governance

and embraces complexity, emergence, problems and opportunities that are relevant to our society. Resilience Engineering is underscored by a shift away from linear, deterministic, error-reducing approaches, towards recognizing and building upon the emergent adaptive capabilities in a system.

Our future: Our goal is to thrive, support and link resilience initiatives, scientists and practitioners around the world. It includes increasing knowledge through research and education, supporting the life cycle of resilience approaches from idea generation to truly exploitable solutions. A special focus of the association is to nurture and encourage young researchers to become future leaders through our Young Talents Program. So far there have been many developments in theory, and we see the near future focusing on resilience in action, practical applications, and the use of knowledge and methods as a basis for growth.

References:

[1] Core group and symposium participants include: René Amalberti (France), Lars Axelsson (Sweden), Richard Cook (USA), Vinh Dang (USA), Sidney Dekker (Sweden), Arthur Dijkstra (Netherlands), Rhona Flin (UK), Yushi Fujita (Japan), Andrew Hale (UK), Erik Hollnagel (Sweden-Danmark), Nancy Leveson (USA), Nick McDonald (Ireland), Jean Pariès (France), Gunilla Sundström (USA), Ron Westrum (USA), David Woods (USA), John Wreathall (USA)

[2] The English version is translated to other languages such as Japanese and Spanish

[3] Include e.g. safety science, ergonomics, sociology, cognitive ergonomics, organisational and management sciences, system safety, management of safety, emergence response, patient safety, cognitive systems engineering, software engineering, system engineering, aerospace engineering, nuclear engineering, regulation, organisational resilience, resilience engineering, change and innovation.

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5.2. Incorporating Safety-II and resilience in a graduate occupational safety program

by Michael Behm, USA

This report summarizes an occupational safety graduate program's attempts to integrate Safety-II and Resilience Engineering (RE) into student learning outcomes. East Carolina University's Master of Science in Occupational Safety program follows the Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET) criteria which is predominantly Safety-I focused. From 2014 to 2017, Professor David Borys facilitated our Applied Safety Management class; Borys had experience and expertise in Safety-II and RE. This was our turning point.

For the past four years I have facilitated our Systems Safety and Applied Safety Management courses, which are the two primary courses where we integrate Safety-II concepts with traditional safety approaches. The foundation Borys provided us continued and expanded. All courses have three fundamental assessments: an exam; a research project; and a practical project. We feel the practical project is where our students and Program can have the greatest effect on the body of knowledge. It is also where we have struggled the most. A student thesis, Turner (2017), explored tools and methods being used in Safety-II and RE practice. That work was collected in 2016 and found an absence of tools in actual practice among safety professionals familiar with the concepts.

In the System Safety class, the concept of the Functional Resonance Analysis Method (FRAM) has been incorporated as well as has various models and tools from Levenson (2011). FRAM was, and remains, a struggle for me to learn and thus transfer to student learning in a practical project. I hope to attend the FRAMily workshop in the near future, which I believe would be most helpful. Hollnagel's FRAM book (2012) was a required reading, but only a few effective FRAM models emerged in the student projects. One student (Shaki, 2017) completed a thesis using FRAM inspired questions sets, but the FRAM models were not included. In 2018, we removed the FRAM project and book. However, I'm encouraging individual students to take on an Independent Study course to learn FRAM with me in the coming academic year. When System Safety is taught this coming August, I'm planning to re-incorporate an option to study and use FRAM as one possible tool for the applied practice project.

We currently use the Hollnagel books (2014, 2017) as required texts in the Applied Safety Management course, a course we recently finished in early May with thirteen students. The recent Provan et al. (2020) article was added and provides a valuable foundation when discussing practical Safety-II and RE practices. The increased use of the Resilience Assessment Grid (RAG) in peer-reviewed publications has helped shape our thinking. Students in this course take on individual projects that seek to measure resilience, evaluate the gap between work as imagined and work as done, or other forms of practice, such as appreciate inquiry. Lectures and modules for this course have evolved to provide guidance for students to view and practice safety through the lens of exploring everyday work. For example, a module on ethnography applied to safety practice yields thought provoking discussions amongst the students. Four students used a customized RAG in practice to analyze and reflect on resilience. One student sent their RAG to seven regional safety managers for use and comment. A noteworthy comment from that group of seven is that they would rather use this tool than their current assessment tool, which focuses on compliance. Another student developed a qualitative RAG tool and explored its utility through management interviews. One student commented that workers were pleasantly surprised to be asked their view. Four students engaged in mini ethnographies to assess work as imagined vs. work as done. Other students analyzed safety job postings and proposed changes in language to adapt from a Safety-I to a Safety-II perspective; developed a learning module on Levenson's STAMP; and evaluated OSH

Management System standards from a resilience engineering perspective. Students were hampered by COVID-19 but endured with excellent practical learning experiences. The final presentations were most impressive.

Clear and practical tools and methods continue to be a key challenge for students. However, we are making progress. I am encouraging students to take on a longitudinal RAG assessment for their thesis or practicum project. We are constantly seeking guest speakers with experience and expertise around the use of FRAM, RAG, and other tools and scanning journals for examples. Any collaborations would be appreciated as we are continually learning and improving the classes and our approach.

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5.3. Complexity science and resilient healthcare: Report from the Australian Institute of Health Innovation, Macquarie University

by Robyn Clay-Williams (Australia)

Healthcare has been a traditional domain of interest for resilience engineering, which is referred to as resilient healthcare when applied to this sector. The Australian Institute of Health Innovation (AIHI) stands out as a leading research organization in resilient healthcare, maintaining a wide range of collaborations across the globe. The AIHI comprises three centres: the Centre for Healthcare Resilience and Implementation Science (CHRIS); the Centre for Health Informatics (CHI); and the Centre for Health Systems and Safety Research (CHSSR). Although each of the Centres contributes to the Institute's common mission and vision, research on resilience engineering is conducted predominantly within CHRIS.

More about the AIHI research on complexity and resilient healthcare: The Australian Institute of Health Innovation (AIHI) is a research-intensive institute located at Macquarie University, Sydney. Founded by director Professor Jeffrey Braithwaite in 2007, AIHI is part of the rapidly growing Faculty of Medicine, Health and Human Sciences. AIHI conducts world-class translational research relevant to national and international research communities, governments, policymakers, providers of health services, managers, clinicians, patients and the community. The work underpins healthcare reforms and systems improvement and provides new technologies, perspectives and evidence.

The AIHI comprises three centres: the Centre for Healthcare Resilience and Implementation Science (CHRIS); the Centre for Health Informatics (CHI); and the Centre for Health Systems and Safety Research (CHSSR). Each of the Centres contributes to the Institute's common mission and vision, however research on resilience engineering is conducted predominantly within CHRIS.

CHRIS is led by Professor Jeffrey Braithwaite who, along with Professors Erik Hollnagel and Bob Wears and a range of international collaborators, developed the field of Resilience Health Care nearly a decade ago. Within CHRIS, [Dr Robyn Clay-Williams](#) leads a research stream on Human Factors and Resilience in the healthcare setting, adopting evidence and translating this into practice to improve delivery systems and design new models of care for healthcare systems of the future.

AIHI hosts the [Resilient Health Care Network](#) website. The purpose of the Resilient Health Care Net (RHCN) is to facilitate the interaction and collaboration among people who are interested in Resilient Health Care – practitioners and researchers alike. This includes discussions; establishing a web presence; exchange of views, opinions, and ideas; mutual moral and scientific support; collaboration on papers and projects; exchange visits; and the organisation of various events ranging from local informal workshops to international summer schools. RHCN has held annual meetings since 2012 – scientific presentations from past meetings can be found on the website. Professor Jeffrey Braithwaite, [Dr Robyn Clay-Williams](#) and others at AIHI have published a large body of work on Resilient Health Care, including six books, numerous peer-reviewed journal articles, and conference presentations and posters. Links to Jeffrey's work can be found [here](#), and Robyn's work [here](#).

5.4. Incident analysis I: Learning from surprise at Netflix

by Lorin Hochstein, USA

Unexpected events that happen in production are often learning opportunities. At Netflix, we encourage teams to write up operational surprises that they encounter, even when there is no business impact. Watch the talk about learning from surprise at Netflix and check what we hope to learn from these write ups.

[Click here to watch the presentation.](#)

5.5. Incident analysis II: Investigations inspired

by Resilience Engineering, Adaptive Capacity Labs, USA

A blog created by Adaptive Capacity Labs offers interesting reflections and case studies of incident investigation in complex systems of several types.

[Click here to access the blog.](#)

5.6. How resilience management principles could help in addressing the COVID-19 crisis: Hints from a pilot exercise of the DARWIN H2020 project

intro by Ivonne Herrera (Norway), article by Luca & Daniele (Italy)

In this article, Luca and Daniele from the Italian company Deep Blue relate resilience management to the COVID-19 crisis using experiences from the European funded project “DARWIN – Expect the unexpected and know how to respond”. The knowledge shared is based on a pilot exercise addressing a novel disease outbreak during a flight

expected to land at Rome Fiumicino Airport. They describe the translation of resilience management guidelines on the following topics: promoting common ground, noticing brittleness and communication strategies with the public.

The complete article is available [here](#)

5.7. Resilience in action: Learning from COVID-19 in real time, an Aide-mémoire, intro by Ivonne Herrera

by Jeffrey Braithwaite (Australia), Erik Hollnagel (Denmark), and Axel Ros (Sweden)

The handling of the COVID-19 pandemic is a challenge for everyone, in particular for healthcare professionals. Adaptive capacity has been developed on the fly with little or no time for reflection and sharing of lessons learned. As a contribution to coping with these gaps, Jeffrey Braithwaite, Erik Hollnagel, and Axel Ros developed a blog on Learning from COVID-19 in real time: Expressions of resilient performance during the pandemic.

[Click here to learn how you can take part in this initiative](#)

5.8. Managing risk and uncertainty in unprecedented times

by Beth Lay, USA

We had a conversation with Asher Balkin, as he advised leaders from a line clearance company with 4,500 crews distributed across the United States and deemed an essential service in how to respond early in the COVID-19 crisis.

Asher Balkin is a research engineer at the Cognitive Systems Engineering Laboratory at Ohio State University, Columbus, USA. Asher has worked in fields as diverse as public health, international security, surgical research, and human/automation interaction.

Asher Balkin is a Research Engineer at the Cognitive Systems Engineering Laboratory at Ohio State University, Columbus, Ohio. Asher has worked in fields as diverse as public health, international security, surgical research, and human/automation

interaction.

Following are notes from a conversation with Asher as he advised leaders from a line clearance company with 4500 crews distributed across the US and deemed an essential service in how to respond, early in the COVID virus situation.

1. Multiply options for the future: Research shows that when uncertainty is high, it's best to multiply options for the future to avoid making decisions that close off options for things that will change later.

Airline example: When airlines think slow down, they may plan to lay off employees. The decision to layoff is hard to revise and get people back (closes options). They could furlough: don't pay people but can call them back. Furlough comes at a cost to the airline (they risk losing people) and employees. Airlines may choose middle ground: reduced pay, keep paying benefits, with a commitment from employees to be there when called (opens options).

When making decisions under high uncertainty:

- Design strategies and decisions that open options.
 - Pay attention to paths and options that are being closed or lock us into a course of actions.
2. During crisis, priorities and goals change: We need to decide which goals we are willing to prioritize and which goals to sacrifice. Highly loaded people must deal with more work, changes and new goals due to the pandemic such as social distancing. People will need to pick-up extra load to cover for people who are out sick or quarantined.
- Healthcare example: Hospitals have replaced the goal of “providing everybody highest level of care” with “we will try to provide care”.
 - NetJets example: During hurricane Sandy, everybody wanted to leave New York city at same time. NetJets also needed to move all airplanes out of the path of the storm. NetJets was getting overwhelmed with requests for their planes. NetJets could have taken advantage and raised prices or become inflexible on changes but instead they relaxed financial goals (pricing) to prioritize the goal to provide high service and by doing this, they built trust and gained future customers.

Goals, priorities, requirements, policies changes to provide breathing room:

- What goals are we willing to relax? Where do we need slack, breathing room?
 - What requirements or policies can we put on hold or relax to free capacity?
 - General Foremen example: Consider administrative items taking General Foremen's time, what can we postpone, move to another role, temporarily relax constraints on?
3. Minimize exposures and prevent rapid spread: Plan early how we will handle situations that require rapid response.
- Encourage self-reporting and be willing to accept period where we err toward reducing contact with others.
 - Assume that if we see one person getting sick, that other people on the crew have been exposed.
 - Identify “super spreaders”, people who have a contact with large groups and many people.
 - Some companies are using a lock down strategy (Chevron oil platforms, Conoco workers on North Slope) to minimize interactions, disconnect from areas and people from higher exposure risk.

Minimize exposures and prevent rapid spread:

- What areas do we typically frequent that have high exposure?
 - Example, convenience stores and fuel stations: what could we do to minimize exposures? Provide lunches – reduce exposures and add good will.
 - Who are our “super spreaders”? What do they need to change?
 - Example: Safety specialists use technology, Facetime, to connect with General Foremen (still do crew visits but use technology to supplement).
4. In dealing with uncertainty, the more difficult the threat, the more strategies are needed. The more uncertainty, the more the options need to be diverse.

- Frame out what's happening in the world and explore how it could impact our business using scenarios.
 - Example: How are we going to handle if we realize we have an exposed General Foreman and multiple of his crews need to call out sick or be quarantined?
 - Example: What will we do if we can't get trucks in for regular maintenance? Note many businesses are now taking advantage of this downtime. Airline maintenance facilities are slammed as airlines are getting airplanes checked and maintained.
 - When designing actions and strategies to manage risks and uncertainty, break into smaller groups and ask them to come up with 3 strategies for this risk (open options).
 - Identify critical business functions / key individuals / key processes that have single points of failure. Use a strategy used by the military to gather tribal knowledge, ask: what are the 3 things about your job that nobody at our company knows how to do? Write down what they are and how to do them.
 - Example: Only this person knows how to...
 - Example: Need the approval of this one person.
 - Focus on what is urgent and will help us with the current situation.
 - Distribute workload, make problem solving role and domain specific – let people who do the work, solve it. Include frontlines.
 - What do we need to work on right now?
 - Supplies: What do we burn through most quickly? Create static buffer.
5. Increase coordination and communication: When coordination and communication are needed most during times of crisis, they often go down due to people being overloaded and stressed. We share information less when we need to share more. The more people get afraid, the less we share. We want to seem competent; this applies to both people and organizations.
- Example Special forces: A lot of their training is not direct fighting but is about communicating with each other when under increased workload and stress.
 - What is our company doing to update our customer's model of the situation? As a good team player, we could help them update their model. We can see what a variety of utilities are doing. This could help move us from customer – client relationship to partnership.

A customer conversation (or risk assessment) could look like this:

- What are you seeing? Weak signals?
- Here's what we're seeing. Here's what we're doing.
- What are you worried about? What changes are you seeing? What do you think you'll have to do in response to those?
- What uncertainties are you facing? What's important to you? What kinds of information would help you make better decisions? This helps us watch out for things that relate to what you are concerned about.
- What are the sources of risk that we pose to you? What steps can we take to mitigate those risk? (but don't start here!)

5.9. COVID-19 Webinars 2, 3, and 4

Summary By Vanessa Bertoni (Brazil), Shewan Chuang (Taiwan), and Jakob Svensson (Sweden)

The webinars of the REA's series on the COVID-19 pandemic continued in April and May - more is coming in June! These talks offered reflections from various perspectives.

Talk 2 addressed the impacts of the pandemic on the aviation industry, reflected on how ordinary citizens have been engaged in the control of the pandemic, and finished with a complexity theory account of the current crisis.

Talk 3 focused on Taiwan's successful early response to the pandemic, discussing how it accounted for principles of resilience engineering and high reliability organizations.

Talk 4 explored the value of expertise within the pandemic scenario, how to make the most of various sources of expertise, and how people can be "brought up to speed" in the face of rapidly and radically changing circumstances.

Knowledge, strategies, practices to respond to COVID flexibly Ragosta (Italy), Bergstrom (Sweden), Saurin (Brazil), by Vanessa Becker Bertoni (Brazil)

The speakers Martina Ragosta (Italy), Johan Bergström (Sweden), and Tarcisio Saurin (Brazil) shared their perceptions on how the resilience engineering (RE) community can make sense of the COVID-19 pandemic and contribute to the mitigation of its impacts. The presentations had the intention of raising questions and encourage critical thinking from a RE lens.

Dr. Ragosta's talk highlighted the impacts of the pandemic on the aviation industry. According to Dr. Ragosta, the European Commission applied a coordinated temporary 30-day restriction of non-essential travel from third countries into the EU. The restriction has been adopted by all EU Member States (except Ireland) and all Schengen Associated Countries (Iceland, Liechtenstein, Norway, and Switzerland), as an attempt to contain the spread the virus. Then it has been extended to all Member States and non-EU Schengen countries until May 15th. Due to the interconnectedness of the aviation industry, the temporary restrictions have a far-reaching impact, directly affecting the whole Air Traffic Management (ATM) system, including airlines, airports, Air Aviation Service Providers (ANSPs), regulatory entities and agencies. This will result in a drastic reduction of passengers and lost revenues in 2020 for the global aviation industry. From a RE lens, the pandemic makes clear that the industry was not ready to face this situation as an integrated system. Indeed, each country responded to the threat on its own terms by closing their borders, and trial and error approaches for solving problems on the fly. It took a while before stakeholders started sharing lessons working together to adapt their resources and capabilities to face this threat.

Dr. Bergström explored interactions between societal levels as a manifestation of resilient performance. In order to discuss how ordinary citizens have been engaged in the control of the pandemic, he raised the question of whether the measures promoted by governments for coping with the pandemic have been implemented as empowerment or responsabilisation of citizens. Based on Clarke (2005), Dr. Bergström defined empowerment as providing voices and choices, and giving citizens the necessary resources to cope with the pandemic. In turn, the speaker referred to responsabilisation as asking citizens to take the responsibility to manage or avoid the threat without having the necessary resources to do so. At the national level, in many countries, the adaptive measures seem to be more

authoritarian than democratic. However, it is too early to conclude which adaptive strategy, authoritarian or democratic, which seems the most effective in managing the pandemic.

Dr. Bergström also offered the viewpoint that resilience may be interpreted as a neoliberal approach that seeks to share accountability with individuals instead of relying on centralized forms of risk management and protection. He noted that Sweden's response to the pandemic could be seen as an example of a neoliberal resilience approach; it trusts that citizens will do the right thing and take care of themselves and each other without being forced by the State. He also provided practical examples of more meso-level adaptive strategies, such as building new healthcare facilities to those who need treatment, and reallocating supplies to where they are needed. Lastly, the speaker reinforced Dr. Ragosta's feeling that we are all facing the consequences of not being appropriately prepared for the outbreak.

In the last portion of the webinar, Dr. Saurin offered a reflection of how complexity thinking can help us to make sense of the pandemic. He highlighted the fact that many work practices that seemed impossible before the pandemic became a reality overnight. The large scale and widespread adaptations that have occurred across healthcare systems and elsewhere poses a unique opportunity to advance the RE body of knowledge. His talk also stressed the dual role played by complexity in the pandemic: while complexity has contributed to the rise of the pandemic, it has also played a role for coping with the pandemic and will eventually contribute to its end. For example, some features of complex systems, such as trade-offs and dynamic interactions, contributed to the amplification and spread of the pandemic. The management of the trade-off between safety and efficiency (i.e. social distancing vs. reopening businesses) is also at the core of the mitigation of the impacts of the pandemic. All these features have played out across the several scales of complex systems, thus showing the fractal nature of the pandemic. Based on his previous RE research (Bueno et al., 2019), Dr. Saurin presented five guidelines for coping with complexity, and presented examples of how these have been deployed so far. The guidelines are: take advantage of diverse perspectives when making decisions; provide slack; give visibility to processes and outcomes; understand work-as-done; and monitor unintended consequences.

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5.9.1. A story of contrast Taiwan vs USA but also Resilience Engineering vs High Reliability Organizations Theory

Webinar and summary prepared by Sheuwan Chuang (Taiwan), Laurin Mooney (USA), David Provan (Australia), Elizabeth Lay (USA), Ivonne Herrera (Norway)

From talk description: The talk explores insights through HRO and RE lenses, considering impacts of discounting, transparency, anticipating, building flexible systems, dealing with uncertainty, monitoring and responding strongly to weak signals and how these contributed to the capabilities of society to act and respond when dealing with crisis.

Summary of the talk prepared by the speakers and organisers is available [here](#).

5.9.2. Naturalistic Decision Making (NDM) & Resilience Engineering (RE) Insights

Jan Maarten Schraagen (Netherlands), Laura Militello (USA), Gary Klein (USA) Pedro Ferreira (Portugal – hosting) by Jakob Svensson* (Sweden)

This conversation explores perspectives from different countries and industry sectors, relating to the value of expertise within the current pandemic scenario, how to make the most of various sources of expertise, and how people can be “brought up to speed” in the face of rapidly and radically changing circumstances. We combine insights emanating from both NDM and RE, and discuss how these communities can contribute to the capabilities of society to act and respond when dealing with crises.

Speakers for this webinar were: Jan Maarten Schraagen (Netherlands), Laura Militello (USA), Gary Klein (USA) Pedro Ferreira (Portugal – hosting)

Jan Maarten Schraagen led off the webinar by introducing the concepts of NDM and RE, followed by the question of how these perspectives illuminate the understanding of the Covid-19 pandemic? Many governments rely on experts in their decision-making process, but we also need multidisciplinary and even citizen-empowered approaches. The coronavirus presents us with a lot of novelty and an element of surprise. As the Prime Minister of Netherlands expressed it “We need to take 100% of the decisions based on 50% of the knowledge.”

Jan Maarten Schraagen discussed the concept of expertise and related it to intuition. In a metaphorical manner, he compared Covid-19 to an expert chess player, and we must try to recognize the patterns of moves in order to fully counter the attack. However, since we are a novice player against this opponent, we need to consider alternative moves. Experts that give advice on how to counter the pandemic have general knowledge which they can apply in combination with general strategies. These have replaced the specific knowledge in our novice situation, which policymakers base their decisions on. Policymakers can take the advice of experts, but it is hard to measure the effect since many strategies can only be measured in hindsight. The way ahead is instead to implement changes in piecemeal fashion. It is about small changes in course rather than large ones. This means that e.g. schools could be partially opened with only half the number of students, then the strategy is evaluated and before the rest of the students are sent back to school. A piecemeal strategy or “the low-cost probing” has been proven effective in dynamic environments.

Governments need to take into account not only medical, but other areas of expertise as well to form their exit strategy from the pandemic. Experts from railways, shop owners, airline managers and other local experts have crucial information on how to manage social distance in their field. This is the knowledge we need to tap into. Jan Maarten

Schraagen ends his session by underlining that expertise is a social phenomenon, resilience is a network phenomenon, and expertise needs to be distributed and tapped broadly.

Our second speaker was Laura Militello who talked about three challenges for supporting expertise in the Covid-19 crises.

1. Developing just-in-time scenario-based training for healthcare workers.

Healthcare personnel needs to learn new skills and adapting to the situation. It includes, to mention a few: evolving signs and symptoms of Covid-19, evolving treatments, limited exposure. This brings out a lot of new training materials, such as power-point slides or fact sheets on how to use protective equipment. Health systems use high fidelity simulation training but this is not practical in the COVID evolving context, as it requires lots of efforts to implement. A more profound learning experience is shown in those embedded in context scenarios. This means that the new rule or guideline has a deeper impact if they are portrayed in realistic scenarios. Augmented Reality is one way to remotely get the feeling of scenario-based training e.g. shifts in skin tone in a manikin. Virtual patients together with a physical manikin is another example where staff can perform and train on critical interventions.

Laura Militello highlights the assessment action pairing. NDM experience advises to link actions and assessments in training. In that way, to imagine yourself in a situation, what interventions (augmented reality or paper and pen scenarios) and assess it, experience shows that this is more powerful than handing outs lists of interventions to do.

2. Collecting and capturing lessons learned from hotspots

What do we want to do, and what do we want to avoid doing if the virus moves into our region? Laura Militello suggests that we use some of the tools from the NDM-community, in particular the cognitive task analysis strategies and interview techniques. Working with multidisciplinary teams to analyze the data could also be a valuable tool to highlight contradictions and common misconceptions, as well as recommendations. In the same way “knowledge representation” that emphasize boundary conditions and uncertainty would be beneficial. Compelling stories can be used to illustrate findings and their limitations.

3. Supporting people in assessing credibility – “what information can you trust?”

The safety of the individual is dependent on the behavior of all. It’s hard for the individual to navigate when he/she is bombarded with contradictory information about how to act and what to believe. This is all happening at a time in history when there seems to be a lot of skepticism about expertise. So, who do people trust? Research shows three antecedents of trust; benevolence ability and integrity which are well documented. But one recent study shows that people found other people more trustworthy if they were seen as similar to themselves, both physically and cognitively. One important effect of this is that we should think, not just about the content of messaging but also the Messenger, and the credibility of that person in that specific context.

Gary Klein was the last speaker who provided a naturalistic decision-making perspective on the Covid-19 crisis. He highlighted experience and expertise as a concern and reconnected to Jan Maarten Schraagen’s and Laura Militello’s previous talks, but added that there is an additional need to invent expertise. We are learning what the symptoms are, but new symptoms are still being discovered. Therefore, we need to do more than just disseminate expertise. We need to rapidly grow expertise. Gary Klein stressed concern about plausibility and validity. Something that can seem plausible to act on in the Covid-19 crises may not be valid because the mental models we have, and that we use to

appraise plausibility, are incomplete and are being revised as we learn more. This provides challenges for NDM, which relies so heavily on expertise. It also provides challenges to evidence-based medicine, since healthcare workers have to trust plausibility and improvise using social media and anecdotes rather than carefully controlled double-blind experiments.

Gary Klein presented some suggestions on how we can speed-up our growth of expertise on different levels. For instance, we can unpack expertise using cognitive task analysis methods. We can compile expertise using the Pre-mortem Method. The Pre-mortem Method suggests that you imagine your action to be a fiasco, generate the reasons why it failed and then consolidate the list of failures and go from there. Another method is management by discovery (because healthcare managers have to be prepared to revise their goals based on what they learn) or appointing discovery teams (to quickly harvest the expertise within a unit).

To understand the assumptions behind simulation models for the spreading of Covid-19, a cognitive tutorial could be used for individuals or organizations so that they can get a better sense of how the analytical technology works – what are its strengths and its limitations and how to apply it to local conditions.

Gary Klein ended his session by emphasizing the core of NDM is expertise. One strategy for disseminating expertise is a technique called ShadowBox which is a way for trainees to see the world through the eyes of the experts.

*** Jakob Svensson is a PhD Candidate at the Faculty of Engineering, Division for Risk Management and Societal Safety, Lund University, Sweden**

5.10. How do new Information and Communication technologies influence resilient healthcare?

by Tarcisio Saurin, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS), Brazil

Innovative Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), such as remote monitoring of patients' conditions in real time, have been gradually spreading across healthcare systems. However, the full benefits and unintended consequences of these ICTs are largely unknown, including their influence on resilient performance. A group of scholars from Brazil and Australia is developing a research project on the influence of ten selected ICTs on the four abilities of resilient healthcare systems (monitor, anticipate, respond and learn). The project is also investigating the use of those ICTs in the treatment of patients with COVID-19.

A significant part of this research is based on expert-opinion, for which a 10-question survey was developed. The survey is available at <https://pt.surveymonkey.com/r/H7MNX8X>

You are invited to answer the survey and collaborate with this research. The average time demanded to complete the survey is 15 minutes.

5.11. Free courses on complexity science

The Santa Fe Institute (USA) offers a broad range of education programs on complexity science, from undergraduate to professional development.

[Click here to learn more about these courses.](#)

5.12. Book corner: Still Not Safe: Patient Safety and the Middle-Managing of American Medicine (2019)

reviewed by Beth Lay, USA

Kathleen Sutcliffe (John Hopkins and from the HRO community) co-wrote "Still not Safe" with our dear friend and colleague, Bob Wears (1947 - 2017), published posthumously in Nov 2019.

The term "patient safety" rose to popularity in the late nineties, as the medical community -- in particular, physicians working in non-medical and administrative capacities -- sought to raise awareness of the tens of thousands of deaths in the US attributed to medical errors each year. But what was causing these medical errors? And what made these accidents to rise to epidemic levels, seemingly overnight?

Still Not Safe is the story of the rise of the patient-safety movement -- and how an "epidemic" of medical errors was derived from a reality that didn't support such a characterization. Physician Robert Wears and organizational theorist Kathleen Sutcliffe trace the origins of patient safety to the emergence of market trends that challenged the place of doctors in the larger medical ecosystem: the rise in medical litigation and physicians' aversion to risk; institutional changes in the organization and control of healthcare; and a bureaucratic movement to "rationalize" medical practice -- to make a hospital run like a factory.

If these social factors challenged the place of practitioners, then the patient-safety movement provided a means for readjustment. In spite of relatively constant rates of medical errors in the preceding decades, the "epidemic" was announced in 1999 with the publication of the Institute of Medicine report To Err Is Human; the reforms that followed came to be dominated by the very professions it set out to reform.

Weaving together narratives from medicine, psychology, philosophy, and human performance, Still Not Safe offers a counterpoint to the presiding, doctor-centric narrative of contemporary American medicine. It is certain to raise difficult, important questions around the state of our healthcare system -- and provide an opening note for other challenging conversations.

6.

Concepts, RE in practice, COVID-19 organisational and societal impacts

September 2020

A word from this issue's editor

by Matthieu Branlat (Norway)

In this issue, you will first learn about recent work to advance or clarify concepts associated with Resilience Engineering. The concept of improvisation is investigated in the construction industry, and the Young Talent Program presents their efforts to guide readers through the RE literature.

These discussions are followed by practical ones. First, professionals in the aviation industry embark us through their journey in implementing a Safety-II approach in their company. Other discussions revolve a lot around COVID-19, as the pandemics continues to have a tremendous impact on our daily lives and all aspects of societies. Using a perspective grounded in RE, sometimes combined with other disciplines, different pieces propose a look at the impact on work organisations. A post from a practitioner is concerned with societal aspects, offering a larger perspective on the pandemics.

A few new rubriques of the newsletter are proposed. The first one aims to provide regular updates about the new collaboration between the Naturalistic Decision Making and Resilience Engineering communities, in part in preparation for the upcoming jointly organised 2021 symposium. The newsletter will also regularly inform the community of new projects and new graduations in direct relation to Resilience Engineering.

I hope you enjoy this issue and get ideas and inspiration to the development of more resilient systems.

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6.1. Conceptual issues in RE

6.1.1. Improvisation in construction sites

By Farook Hamzeh, Associate Professor, University of Alberta (hamzeh@ualberta.ca), Canada

Managers of organizations always prefer planning and resourcing in a routine and repetitive environment (Weick, 1998). However, according to chaos theory, numerous organizational actions can have unintended or unexpected consequences (Cunha et al., 1999). Woods and Hollnagel (2006) indicated that organizations cannot develop plans and procedures for all possible scenarios. In addition, natural or technological emergencies, whether randomly or intentionally induced, can challenge the planning performance of organizations (Mendonca & Wallace, 2007). Even though there was an approach to eradicate improvisation from business organizations, improvisation continued to exist in many emergent situations (Ciborra, 1999). This led to a new approach that considers improvisation as a complementary part to planning rather than considering it as an undesired fluctuation in plans (Ciborra, 1999).

Ciborra (1999) defined improvisation as the act of producing new combinations of resources, routines and structures in order to cope with the present wicked situations. Furthermore, Moorman and Miner (1998) focused on the time aspect while defining improvisation by considering it as planning and executing simultaneously. They additionally considered improvisation as a spontaneous and deliberate organizational action. Moreover, Cunha et al. (1999) provided a definition for improvisation as the effort performed by an individual or an organization to compose and perform simultaneously at the spur of the moment using the available material, cognitive, affective and social resources.

Hamzeh et al. (2012) have pioneered research addressing improvisation in the construction industry. Conducting interviews with construction specialists, the study evaluated the performance of look-ahead planning and the complementary role of improvisation identifying when, how much, and where it is utilized. Results highlight a difference between white-collar and blue-collar workers when it comes to attitude and freedom to be proactive when the situation requires improvisation. Results indicate that, improvisation may serve to adapt the standard operating procedures or create ones that are more suitable for complex and dynamic environments.

Uncertainties and variations often impact construction planning; what is executed on site may differ from what is planned. Some tasks, not included in the weekly schedule or are included in it but are allocated within the wrong time frame, have to be executed within a given week. These tasks appear at the week of their execution on site and are called 'New Tasks'. Although they might impact a project's progress, the reasons behind their emergence are not known. Exploring planning behaviors and the situations where 'new tasks' emerge can provide more understanding of the planning process and pave the way for improving the planning system. Rohana and Hamzeh 2016 have identified the reasons behind the emergence of 'new tasks' in construction planning as observed on several case study projects, described the planning behaviors responsible for their emergence, and developed a model that explains the emergence process.

To understand improvisation in construction, Hamzeh et al. 2018a have analyzed improvisational practices in construction and investigated factors contributing to successful improvisation. Using data from practitioners on actual constructions projects, the study elucidates antecedents, behaviors and consequences of improvisation in various construction operations. Moreover, Hamzeh et al. 2018b have modelled improvisation as a decision-making process to illustrate how construction personnel can properly improvise and reach their desired actions. The outcomes

of this research are expected to produce a monumental shift in the understanding of decision making in construction while laying a foundation to guide managers and decision makers in the construction industry to identify personal, organizational, and other characteristics that may improve the practice of improvisation for complementing planning processes rather than undermining them

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6.1.2. Towards a Definitive Guide to the Resilience Engineering Literature

by **Natália Ransolin (Brazil)** and **Sudeep Hegde (USA)**

Since the origins of Resilience Engineering (RE) and the publication of the first book in 2006, the field has grown rapidly. The literature is abounded with a plethora of concepts, frameworks and tools developed along the way. Someone new to RE and curious about the field, may be facing several questions, such as: What are the principles of resilience engineering? Where can these be retrieved from? How did the discipline evolve over time? The sheer density of information available in this field presents a challenge in identifying definitive concepts in the literature. This challenge led the REA Young Talent Program (YTP) committee to embark on a project aimed at highlighting some of

the landmark papers, chapters and articles in the literature, and summarizing. The effort also aims to link the various concepts and tools in a coherent manner and identify current directions in which the field continues to grow. The group is comprised of Riccardo Patriarca, Sudeep Hegde, Natália Ransolin, Vanessa Becker, and Elizabeth Lawson.

The initiative will also highlight the uniqueness of RE and the importance of advancing this field. The overarching idea is to demonstrate the relevance and applicability of RE in a wide range of disciplines. Some key insights that might emerge from this collaborative effort could be potentially refined and incorporated in RE to enhance the field itself.

What have we done so far? A summary of activities

As a starting point, a list of seminal and relevant work on RE was created and shared between the participants, in which each one was responsible for systematically analysing a list of papers and chapters. A structured framework was created to list and describe key concepts that emerged from the readings. Key themes relating to resilience from each article were identified, along with illustrative extracts. The articles involving applied concepts were distributed among the participants so as to represent a variety of domains, such as healthcare, aviation, and the built environment.

Next steps

There is a plan to invite researchers across different domains for joining our discussion sessions, in order to reinforce the RE importance across several domains. They could contribute to the project goal by describing similar or conflicting ideas and concepts from their field or theoretical foundations. For instance, concepts of adaptation could be common ground to discuss. We will continue to provide updates on our progress in the coming weeks. Stay tuned!

6.2. RE in practice

6.2.1. American Airlines & Safety-II

by **Bogomir Glavan and Nick Peterson, American Airlines (USA) (Bogomir.Glavan@aa.com) and Nick Peterson (Nicholas.Peterson@aa.com), American Airlines**

American Airlines (AA) started our Safety II journey in 2018 when senior leadership decided to evaluate a path bringing Safety II to AA. AA's safety leadership met with Dr. Erik Hollnagel to chart a path using our robust Safety I systems as a benchmark. It quickly became evident that we had to approach this from a different lens. I was brought on board as part of a grassroots team to figure out how we would bring these concepts into our safety programs and ultimately be able to measure resilient performance in airline crews during everyday line operations. It was a daunting task for the whole group, even those that have been at airlines for a long time, yet exciting to have a blank slate and backing of leadership.

Fast forward two years and we have our own language, a model, 100 observed flights translating into over 2,000 lines of data and a name to hang our hat on, the **AA Learning and Improvement Team, LIT!**

Initial roadblocks

- Refining the language already established to fit the organization and operating style.
- Safety II does not replace Safety I or traditional safety, they complement each other. 15,000 AA pilots who embrace and know a proven Safety I model will have to see what Safety II can bring to the table to hit the "I believe button".

Lessons Learned...so far

- It takes some time to let go of the Safety I security and familiarity and fully embrace Safety II. As an anecdotal reference we found it took about 6 months for us as full-time LIT observers to change our perspective.
- Eventually you need to put a stake in the ground and move forward with your own language and model, what works for your organization may not be verbatim from the text books and academics. That's ok.
- Implementing a learning culture is tough. Getting employees to take time to deliberately "debrief" is difficult, especially when they see that with a negative connotation. However, this is where we can affect exponential positive change.
- Crews love to talk about what they did and how they overcome challenges. These "Shop Talk" sessions are a gold mine of data and insight on how crews think and act.

What's next for AA's LIT

- Begin to incorporate the concepts of resilient performance and observed proficiencies into our captain leadership course and annual pilot training involving human factors.
- Review and analyze the 100 observations we have recorded and begin LIT paper #2!
- Collaborate and share with you!

AA's LIT group would appreciate any and all feedback on our [linked paper](#). Please send us an email (Bogomir.Glavan@aa.com, Nicholas.Peterson@aa.com). We welcome any discussion and send an open invitation to

any organization, aviation or other, to reach out if they want to ask more questions or brainstorm as they embark on their journey.

6.2.2. COVID-19: Combining Resilience Engineering, lean production methods and digital technologies to reduce the impact of COVID-19 in construction

by Carlos T. Formoso (Brazil), Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre (Brazil) – formoso@ufrgs.br

The COVID-19 pandemic represents a major threat to the health of millions of people and to the economic and social development around the world, especially in developing countries. In fact, the need for social distancing and, eventually, social isolation can have a great impact on a number of economic activities, generating unemployment. Although there is uncertainty about the evolution of the pandemic, there are predictions that intermittent social distancing may be necessary until 2022. The construction industry can potentially play an important role in helping economic recovery and generating jobs during and after the COVID-19 pandemic, especially in developing countries. Construction sites are usually large spaces, which can allow the development of activities with an adequate degree of social distancing, as long as they are properly planned and controlled. However, many construction companies have limitations in both production and safety management, often resulting in low productivity, disorganized flows of people and materials, and high incidence of accidents, among other problems. This situation represents an obvious risk for the dissemination of COVID.

By contrast there are opportunities to integrate advanced Lean production management methods and resilience engineering principles, with the support of existing digital technologies. Lean Construction has advanced in many different countries with promising results, and many digital technologies have emerged and can potentially change the way construction has been managed, including Building Information Modelling (BIM), Wireless Transmission Technologies (WTT), mobile computing, among others.

Regarding resilience engineering, the need to cope with complexity has grown as the construction industry has been affected by growing sources of complexity, such as the increasing number of supply chain members, new technological alternatives involving off-site production, rising number of regulations, and innovative procurement approaches. Several studies have provided evidences that resilience engineering principles can be applied in construction projects to devise better planning and control systems that are able to reduce trade-offs between efficiency and safety, improve the way safety performance is measured in construction, and define the necessary slack in production systems.

Considering this context, a network of researchers from four different universities, including the Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, the Federal University of Bahia, The Federal University of Ceará, and Faculdade Meridional, have started a research project which aims to devise a model for the integrated management of safety and production in construction sites that combines resilience engineering, advanced lean production methods, and digital technologies.

Two specific planning and control methods will be explored: (i) the Last Planner System, a collaborative hierarchical planning tool that contributes to the reliability of production systems by protecting construction processes from variability, and (ii) location-based planning, which allows different crews to work in small batches, based on an explicit definition of workflows. Digital technologies will be used to keep the minimum distance between people in construction sites, as well as to provide virtual environments for collaboration and to extend the automation of

production controls. Two main research deliverables are expected in this project: (i) an assessment of a sample of construction sites regarding the implementation of safety protocols to keep social distance and avoid the spread of COVID-19; and (ii) the refinement of a set of integrated planning and control methods, safety management protocols, and digital technologies, with the aim of achieving a high performance both in terms of efficiency and safety. This model will be tested in a small number of construction sites in three different states of Brazil.

Four types of technologies have been pre-selected to be used in this phase, due to their current stage of development and potential contribution to advanced production management methods. These are: (i) wireless transmit technologies, including RFID (Radio Frequency Identification) and Bluetooth; (ii) BIM (Building Information Modelling) for modelling products and processes; (iii) planning and control software that supports location-based planning, advanced lean techniques (e.g. andon, kanban), and positioning systems for tracking work flows; and (iv) mobile computing (tablets, mobile phones) to support social distancing. Differently from traditional research projects, the results of this investigation will be continuously disseminated to the construction industry, starting in the third month of the study. Several virtual means will be used, such as live presentations, webinars, and a project website.

6.2.3. Absent Leaders and Combined Teams - A Conversation with Asher Balkin on Brittleness Encroaching

by Beth Lay

Asher Balkin is a Research Engineer at the Cognitive Systems Engineering Laboratory at Ohio State University, Columbus, Ohio. Asher has worked in fields as diverse as public health, international security, surgical research, and human/automation interaction.

Following are notes from a conversation with Asher as he advised leaders from Lewis Tree Services, a line clearance company with 4500 crews distributed across the US and deemed an essential service in how to respond, early in the COVID virus situation. <https://lewistree.com/about-us/new-view-safety/>

As COVID-19 spreads, there are an increasing number of leaders and team members absent due to illness, precautionary self-quarantine, childcare, etc. To adapt to this situation, teams reconfigure, and leaders fill in, but ultimately there are not enough people to cover the work and our systems become stressed and stretched.

Absent leaders, and teams who do not normally work together, often result in brittle situations.

Combined teams

When you change anyone on a team, you change the entire team. You have a different team. It takes several weeks, at a minimum, to integrate into one team. When combining teams, the first several weeks of working together are high-risk while the team may be out of sync. Communication breaks down. People cannot predict each other's actions, or how they do work, because their routines are different.

Absent leader

A leader being out of sync is more dangerous than combined teams. Every leader has a different style and teams adapt to their leader's style. Fill-in leaders may assign work that is a mismatch with skills. They may not know the customers. With an unfamiliar leader, team members may hesitate to raise concerns.

Bringing teams together and having leaders fill-in for each other ultimately enables us to be more flexible—increasing resilience—if we plan for it and manage differently as teams and leaders adapt. It provides the opportunity to learn from someone new, practice new skills, and build relationships so that people ask for and offer

help. In the military, cross-training is common. For Marines, being basic riflemen is the mission, yet they have regular jobs, too. Cross-training builds bench strength at multiple levels.

A core strategy of Resilience Engineering is having extra help ready to deploy. General, non-specific resources, who can help in a wide range of situations, are needed when uncertainty is high. For example, during the first wave of COVID-19, nurses' associations reached out to retired nurses for help directly in hospitals or to train new nurses. Another version of this strategy is to drop in an expert without a predefined role to co-locate and offer help, where needed.

Following are strategies to plan and manage differently when your system is stressed or stretched

- Build a reserve of individuals who are ready to help (i.e., non-specific, general resources)
 - Bring retired leaders on as contractors.
 - Identify high-potential team leaders who are willing to fill in (as a development opportunity) and have them shadow for a week.
 - Move people in field-support roles to direct field-contact roles. They can act as an extra set of eyes (quality checks), offer general help, and assist leaders to free up capacity.
- Ensure the success of a new or temporary leader.
 - Perform handoffs covering team capabilities and gaps (i.e., team insights)
 - Overcommunicate; include more details than normal when sharing work plans.
 - Make everything as explicit as possible (assumptions get us in trouble)
 - Define decision authority.
 - Ask the team:
 - What do I need to know about you?
 - What would help you to know about me?
 - What problems have you had in the past when a new leader filled in?
- Ensure the success of merged teams.
 - Talk about “why” the team has been brought together.
 - Share the mission, project details and customer objectives.
 - Share skill levels (e.g., this is what I am good at, this is what I am working on, this is what am going to need help with)
 - Ask fellow team members:
 - What do we need to know about you?
 - What would help you to know about me?
 - What problems have you had in the past with newly formed teams?
 - Identify ONE person in charge on each work site.
- Reduce the workload: push off work (e.g., administrative work) that can be done later.
- Postpone critical or difficult work; if necessary to perform, increase peer checks
- Increase leadership engagement and establish routine check-in points.
- Proactively look for signs of stress
 - Failure is asymptotic; things spiral out of control quickly.
 - Cognitive load is limited; once limits are neared, we begin to miss things (Note: This is a team as well as an individual dynamic)
 - Identify which resources are most likely to be over-loaded.
- Notice stack-up of risk (watch out for three or more!)
 - Have extra leadership or safety support.

Risk factors and error-likely situations

Work	Worker	Workplace
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · 1st or 2nd time doing task · Non-routine task · Unusually difficult task · Last-minute change (especially significant scope change or who has the lead) · Emergency work · Rework/call backs · Hard-to-meet deadline 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Leader absents · Combined teams · New to job or team · First day back after more than four days off · Last day before time off. Increased risk: just prior to holiday · End of task · Stepping in at the last minute to help · Distracted, tired, or in a hurry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Weather (e.g., icy, foggy, hot, rainy) · Multiple teams in same area · Irrate or frustrated customer, patients, etc.

6.2.4. COVID-19: Can we give resilience a broader, societal meaning in these pandemic times?, A practitioner's perspective on resilience and our society

by Kees van der Blom, The Netherlands

In these times, where the virus causing COVID-19 seems to have taken a leading role, resilience takes on a very special meaning. Where before February 2020 (global outbreak of coronavirus) resilience was a concept for industry and healthcare, it has now become a concept for society. How resilient is society, are its groups and how resilient is the individual today?

Initially, everyone, from governments to policy makers to individual citizens, was 'taken by surprise' by the speed with which the virus spread and still continues to spread. 'Surprised' as well by the serious consequences this virus apparently can cause. So, panic everywhere, measures galore uncontrollably. In short, a chaos barely manageable was created. Just consider the lack of knowledge about the virus (what we were told), the lack of necessary medical supplies, the intensive care units that were not yet adequately prepared for this outbreak and the apparently enormous global dependency we created ourselves. Suppliers could no longer deliver, huge stock-outs occurred. As it turned out, we were not able to manufacture the simplest of tools ourselves and this only added to the chaos. Gradually, the situation became more manageable and the mere quantity of measures we devised became more structured. Communication about the virus improved, the supply of medical resources got into stride and hospitals got a better grip on the initially chaotic situation.

Finally, resilience started to emerge. After the first 'blows', the bounce of society was back and a new, more stable situation arose. Globally, the charts showed more favorable lines. More and more became known about the virus.

It was and is noteworthy that hospitals and its in-house health care staff had to and could respond rapidly to the first signs that preceded the outbreak. Subsequently, they had to do their utmost to be able to deal with the colossal and visible effects of the outbreak. Procedures and protocols came into play in a different way. Skills and confidence turned out to be crucial. The professionals on the shop floor had to react fast and come up with solutions for new situations. Professional care was provided under great pressure. In short, in hospitals the resilience theories became more visible than ever. The Safety II-philosophy became perceptible in practice. Hats off to all the healthcare workers who fulfilled their healthcare duties in a professional manner and continue to do so ever since. As we speak, the healthcare workers in the Netherlands (and probably worldwide) themselves are recuperating from pushing themselves to their limits, and in this recovery process they are assisted in a professional manner. The impact was, and still is, huge.

In a large part of healthcare in the Netherlands, the phenomena of Resilience, Safety II, 'work as imagined' versus 'work as done' and the FRAM[i]-method are accepted concepts that are increasingly used. FRAM-training courses are offered to healthcare workers (from doctors to nurses). There is increasing attention to what professionals actually do in the workplace. Procedures and protocols are continually analysed and improved in that light. In this way, enhancing resilience is given an important place within healthcare. Apparently, the enhancement of skills in the workplace yields many positive results. During the corona crisis and on the basis of anticipating the changing circumstances, one learned to think and work in other ways. Apparently, it is possible and it works in practice. The question now arises: should we go back to the 'old' again? What can we keep from the 'new way of working'? What about the adaptability and resilience in society?

Initially, after the panic situation, people adopted a 'cooperative attitude'. Publications, communication moments organized by the government and professional advice from experts led us to a situation that offered control. The public and the individual, both at work, in the street and at home, adjusted. Discipline everywhere. Apparently, society can react flexibly and can show its resilience.

Until.... the moment society starts to show the first signs of 'being fed up'. Numbers dropped, everything seemed to be under control, why still the 'lock-down' with all its adverse consequences? Impatience surfaced. People wished and intended to go back to 'normal'. Protests against measures are now being organized. This, incidentally, to the utter dismay of healthcare workers in hospitals. They are still recuperating and are horrified by an anticipated resurgence of the virus.

To what extent is a society really resilient enough to be able and willing to organize a different society, after the first shocking deviations from the 'normal' one? A society with a better inner resilience, able to cope with new global developments. Obviously, people want to go back to 'normal' quickly, whereas it has now been proven that this is absolutely impossible because it no longer works.

In addition to studying the resilience theories for industry and healthcare, it would be interesting to look at society as well. Resilience is not exclusively intended for the industry but should be a quality or character trait of the individual, a group, a society. By now we have seen and experienced that resilience and adaptability are aspects that are becoming increasingly important for our 'survival' in this complex society. How do we raise our children? How do we educate each other?

I believe it to be a challenge to turn resilience theories into a social concept and not just reserve it for the industry exclusively. Of course, in essence we are naturally adaptable and resilient, otherwise we would already be extinct. We are continuously adapting to new developments and changes. We don't even notice it. However, in the context of this coronavirus pandemic, we must also strengthen and enhance societal resilience; in that way are early and better prepared to create a society in which we have to reinvent ourselves at those moments where this is required and inevitable. Tackling this issue will be a challenge for science. Perhaps this is also a topic that can be prominently discussed during the REA^[ii] conference in 2021?

[i] FRAM: Functional Resonance Analysis Method

[ii] REA : Resilience Engineering Association

6.2.5. COVID-19: Everyone needs more RE right now, and they (might even) know it

by Mike Rayo, USA

“And I can't deny the fact that you like me ... right now, you like me!”

– Sally Field, 1985, accepting Academy Award

Life for me since the beginning of the pandemic has been, in a word, crowded. Crowded for space in my house. Crowded for tasks that vie for time and attention. Crowded in the number of extra jobs that I've taken on. I know that each country has had a similar but distinct experience, and I'm assuming that we have all felt this.

I began the pandemic reaching out to everyone in my network, offering help. Many people and organizations took me up on it. I began working with a number of hospitals helping rework their communications so that they could more effectively consume, interpret, and convey the dizzying pace of updated and conflicting COVID-19 guidance that came from the Centers for Disease Control at the federal level, different state public health organizations, local public health organizations, their peer institutions, and their informal network of clinicians at other institutions. Notably, it was the informal network that seemed to be the most effective (hmm ... WAIWAD: Work as Imagined vs. Work as Done, and a covert work system ... need to make a note of that). This was short-lived, as the communications staffs of these hospitals, although past saturation, did not really want any help from those outside the organization (hmm ... saturated and unable or unwilling to ask for or accept help).

After this brief stint of communications help, I worked with a team of data scientists to help my city understand the impacts of closing and opening schools, shutting down businesses, and forcing people to stay in their homes. We were also getting news from around the country of shortages in PPE, staffing and facilities, so my lab started building an Overload Calculator that would help smaller hospitals figure out the time and effort it would take to activate and enable the surge plans they had devised. We have put roughly 150 person-hours into the Overload Calculator, and although it has been a great training exercise for our students, it has not been used by a single hospital yet. Frustrating (another WAIWAD, or some other miss?).

The lack of uptake on the Overload Calculator is perhaps explained by the glut of other COVID projects we started dabbling in. We started working with our city to build a monitoring, communication, and response tool so that

neighbors could speak and listen to each other, and to their city. I wrote a song to help our local and state community understand the confusing information coming at all of us. We helped David Woods launch his COVID-19 blog. We reached out to fellow healthcare system researchers to share effective practices. This last effort didn't go anywhere. We started building the infrastructure for a COVID-19 symptoms and public sentiment tracker that could be connected directly to secure hospital data structures. This, too, has yet to be utilized. In all of these, we were asking different organizations or stakeholders groups to modify something. Borrowing from David Woods's clever word play, we were asking them to "RE" – REvise, REthink, REconsider, REconfigure, or in some other way REdo something. In most of these cases, we were asking an organization (e.g., a local agency) to RE so that a larger community (e.g, the public) would also RE. In most of these situations, the RE that we were hoping for did not come to pass. The ask was too great, or the perceived benefit too small, or both.

However, the lack of uptake on Overload Calculator could also be explained by us REprioritizing all of our efforts, focusing on two larger initiatives in which we are effectively working with organizations, sustaining the necessary RE to effectively reduce the spread of COVID-19. We have been asked by our state and our university, separately, to set up a monitoring capability (Wait ... monitoring! A potential of resilient performance! Yes!) in which we analyze both structured and unstructured data sources to assess relative threats and anomalies and recommend mitigation strategies (another potential, Responding ... right?). The results of these are then analyzed in future cycles of analysis to determine what to do next and how to change our current capabilities (you guessed it ... Learning!). Although we are still fighting to enable capabilities to be more Anticipatory at the state level, the university is moving at full speed in that direction, as a paucity of anticipatory power for us will likely lead to having to REconsider our strategy, either REDucing in-person classes or REMoving students from campus until we can RESume safe operations. We firmly realize that investment in anticipation will be far less costly than the expenditures that those latter RE's would entail. This is a big deal that should be celebrated – the amount of RE to get to this anticipatory footing has been incredibly painful. Everyone doing COVID related activities in both of these teams have been pulled from other functions, often still having to perform both their old duties and the new COVID-related tasks. Individuals and teams are all being asked to do things that we have never done, or are dusting off capabilities that have not practiced in quite some time. Those that are participating are doing so outside of their expertise envelope. But, right now, it looks like we are going to be able to preserve our most important goals (e.g., education and commerce) if we can continue to convince our larger communities to deprioritize some of their personal goals (e.g., Congregating and large-scale socializing) and convince them to keep RE-ing (e.g., wearing masks).

What we are experiencing right now is what our frontline practitioners have known a long time, and try desperately to convey to us as Resilience Engineering professionals: RE-ing is crowded. And messy. The pieces are not all going to fit together again. It takes a lot of effort, and will not always seem worth it. In fact, we will often not know definitively if it is worth it until the RE-ing is over. The difference I've seen in the last 6 months is that, now that there are definitive signals that change is necessary, people are seeing that change, adaptation, and improvisation, are all necessary. They are not to be feared or denigrated, but encouraged. If we can jump into the fray, new folks will realize that they really do like our REA community, and that we are valuable. We can help and are helping. We are uniquely suited to read the signs and signals to propose the right kind of RE that will facilitate and sustain resilient performance. Which is what RE-ing is all about, right?

6.3. Updates on NDM / REA collaboration

6.3.1. How do Naturalistic Decision Making and Resilience Engineering complement each other?

by Beth Lay (USA) and Matthieu Branlat (Norway)

Naturalistic Decision Making (NDM) and Resilience Engineering (RE) researchers and practitioners are beginning to explore synergies with a goal of co-creating new thinking, tools, and practices that will help us in these unprecedented times. This post is written from the viewpoint of Resilience Engineering practitioners and researchers, more novice at applying NDM tools.

Resilience Engineers speak about surprise as an inescapable component in complex, adaptive work. To be resilient is to be prepared for surprise, to “expect the unexpected”. This may seem like an oxymoron but it can be translated into practical strategies and actions. This is an area where Naturalistic Decision Making also provides concepts, tools and insights. We’ll explore this marriage, so to speak, of the two domains through taking a brief look at views, practices, and tools related to decision making under uncertainty.

NDM offers methods to identify critical, domain specific, complex decisions and tools to aid improving sensemaking and decision making. NDM experts use Cognitive Task Analysis (cognitive interviews) to identify common critical decisions and mine cues noticed by experts. They work with organization leaders and experts to define best courses of action and decisions that align with the organization’s risk tolerance. NDM practitioners craft scenarios that include ambiguity and decision points branching to play out in different ways. Novices learn to recognize cues that indicate increasing uncertainty, heightening risk, and signs trouble might be coming. Their decisions and handling of the situation is then compared with what an expert would notice and do. NDM researchers would also try to discover why decision makers were confused or mistaken.

Resilience Engineers claim that we need to monitor ambiguity as a signal to move into a different mode of managing work and that waiting until you are certain is too late. Resilience Engineering specify the need to practice decision making under uncertainty with scenarios where the path forward not clear (the more ambiguity, the better) with a goal of preparing to handle uncertainty and surprise – in general, not necessarily related to specific decisions. Resilience Engineers may craft scenarios based on situations where ambiguity was handled well and query which actions and interactions led to good outcomes then teach and train others to replicate these successful actions and interactions.

From the points above, we see that the management of uncertainty, in particular the notion of ambiguity, is a major topic for both NDM and RE. Ambiguous situations, a frequent characteristic of challenging real-world situations (i.e., “naturalistic” or related to “work-as-done”), provide insight into how individuals, teams or organizations manage uncertainty. For both fields, ambiguity can be a desired characteristic of a scenario used for knowledge elicitation or training. In the context of NDM, the macrocognitive model [1] provides a basis to explain, at an individual level, how the understanding of a situation evolves in time, as cues steer the observer one way or another. For RE, there may be less focus on the role or nature of expertise per se and more focus on how organizations, team dynamics and practices enable its expression.

Here’s a brief comparison of RE and NDM specific questions about managing uncertainty:

- RE: actively probe the “Un’s” [2] to understand unknown, unclear, uncertain, unseen, uncontrollable, and unstable situations through questions such as “How could we be surprised?” “What’s making me uneasy?” “What can I see, and more importantly what can I NOT see?” “What do I know and NOT know?” “What’s different?” “What else could this be?” “What do I need to pay close attention to?” “Who else can help?” The aim is to broaden and deepen the perspective that not all is knowable, however, there are questions and actions that can help move things from the unknown to known.
- NDM (example from nuclear power plant crisis management team) to increase team situation awareness / reduce common ground breakdowns through questions such as: “What is the immediate goal of your team?” “What are you doing to support that goal?” “What is our biggest worry?” “What is the current threat’s location, size, and intention?” “What do you think this situation will look like in 20 minutes? Why?” The aim is to improve sensemaking.

From this brief example, you may notice that both NDM and RE practices to improve decision making under uncertainty are similar, in some cases the questions are almost a mirror-image, while others are complementary.

Interestingly, RE and NDM share a “positivist” view about the investigation of work situations. In both fields, investigating why things go well in spite of challenges such as ambiguity is a central method to reveal the nature and the demands of work as well as expert behaviour. What seems to differentiate the two fields is the system of interest, more focused on individual(s) in NDM, more focused on the environment in which they perform in RE.

Klein, G., Moon, B., & Hoffman, R. R. (2006). Making Sense of Sensemaking 2: A Macrocognitive Model. *Intelligent Systems, IEEE*, 21(5), 88–92.

Laurin Mooney <https://www.behighlyreliable.com/read-more>

6.3.2. Progress on REA/NDM Symposium organization

by Pedro Ferreira (Portugal), Simon Gill (UK), Laura Militello (USA)

Profound changes are being experienced around the world and, as we look back to the days before COVID-19, the only certainty seems to be that the world as we knew it then, will never come to exist again. The joint initiative of the REA and NDM communities looks at the ongoing changes as emerging opportunities for bouncing forward.

Following the traditions of previous NDM and REA Symposia we are keen to offer the opportunity to meet in person, to take advantage of personal contact in discussing these concepts together. However, we also acknowledge that we will all need to practice what we preach and make decisions under uncertainty, in particular relating to the commitment to a physical participation in international events. We are preparing a survey to explore your thoughts in order to create a Symposium that best meets the needs of our communities.

Alongside, a dedicated webpage is being developed to host all information relating to the diversity of initiatives that are being planned from now until June next year. Initial webinars are already underway but, as we move forward, we aim to increase the focus on specific areas of scientific knowledge and/or industry, and prepare the grounds for an innovative type of event that will hopefully, culminate in a combination of face-to-face and broadcasting initiatives from the city of Toulouse, France. The opening of the registrations and other dates to keep in mind will come soon, but please keep an eye on your inbox (or visit REA’s and NDM’s webs) and do share your thoughts.

6.4. News in the RE World

6.4.1. New project: ENGAGE (Horizon2020)

On July 1st 2020 the ENGAGE Project, funded by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 program, was kicked off on a virtual meeting.

ENGAGE aims at linking the informal resilience naturally inherent in citizens with the formal work of authorities to prevent, prepare for, respond to, and recover from disasters. It brings together 14 partners from 8 countries aiming to show how individuals and local practices can interrelate effectively with planned preparedness and response, practitioners, and technology. The 3-year project will provide solutions to support the engagement of citizens, communities and authorities in a "whole-of-society" approach and capitalise on the knowledge, capabilities and social capital existing at all levels of society.

The ENGAGE team combines knowledge and exploits the results of research on resilience, social capital and risk communication. The consortium will work together with a Knowledge and Innovation Community of Practice initially composed by 37 organisations magnifying the ability to create new knowledge and exploit novel solutions.

The project was submitted in August 2019 under the leadership of Ivonne Herrera at SINTEF. Many of its topics of investigation appear relevant to the current COVID-19 situation. Efforts are currently underway to replan some of its tasks in order to better investigate aspects of societal resilience during the pandemics as well as positive formal and informal responses, adaptations and practices that emerged over the last months.

For further information:

Project Coordinator: Dr. Matthieu Branlat, SINTEF (matthieu.branlat@sintef.no)

Dissemination and Exploitation Manager: Alexis Gizikis, EENA (ag@eena.org)

Partners:

- SINTEF AS (Coordinator, Norway)
- Deep Blue Srl (Italy)
- TECNUN University of Navarra (Spain)
- Tel Aviv University (Israel)
- Trondheim Red Cross Local volunteers (Norway)
- European Emergency Number Association (Belgium)
- Ministry of Internal Affairs Department of Emergency Situations (Romania)
- Everbridge (Norway)
- Ecole Normale Supérieure (France)
- Gobierno Vasco – Departamento de Seguridad – Ertzaintza (Spain)

- Cittadinanzattiva Onlus (Italy)
- Local Health Authority- ASL ROMA 1 (Italy)
- Region Östergötland - Centre for Teaching & Research in Disaster Medicine and Traumatology (Sweden)
- NTNU Social Research (Norway)

6.4.2. Book corner: Safety Science Research: Evolution, Challenges and New Directions (2020)

by Jean-Christophe Le Coze (France)

Safety Science Research. Evolution, Challenges and New Directions is a book combining the insights of two generations of writers who are for the first time put together. From a research point of view, our understanding of safety depends on the way research traditions developed in the 1980s and 1990s.

These traditions are rooted in networks of researchers and their backgrounds among which feature prominently, but not only, psychology, cognitive psychology, social-psychology, management, sociology and political science. Concepts such as safety culture, high-reliability organisation, resilience engineering or safety regulation are some of the most visible products of these research traditions' developments.

The book, which follows a workshop held in 2017, wishes to explore ideas within, across and beyond such research traditions to offer a broad view of current issues and developments which translate some contemporary empirical, conceptual, practical and critical research in the field at the end of the 2010s. Thus, a diversity of topics are addressed by the authors of the chapters which can be articulated in a narrative that I borrow from the introduction of the book.

6.5. Special online series COVID-19 and resilience engineering

by Lorin Hochstein, USA

A page was created to consolidate the talks' recording files and summaries, it was regularly updated as new material became available.

In the wake of the pandemic, REA shifted the emphasis of its online seminar series to focus on talks related to the intersection of COVID-19 and resilience engineering.

PhD students helpfully generated summaries of these talks, to increase interaction knowledge sharing. A [handout consolidating the talks](#) was prepared as basis for talk 07: As the pandemic continues, still betting against the odds diverse patterns of adapting to global challenges.

Topics of the summarized talks are:

Talk 01 – 30.03.2020 – Lessons learned from **Resilience Engineering (RE) and community resilience**. Speakers: Bruria Adini (Israel), David Woods (USA), Ivonne Herrera (Norway). Summary from PhD candidate Dustrin Weiller (USA).

Talk 02 – 20.04.2020 Lessons learned from **Resilience Engineering (RE) and societal resilience**, Speakers: Johan Bergström (Sweden), Martina Ragosta (Italy), Saurin (Brazil). Summary from PhD candidate Vanessa Becker Bertoni (Brazil)

Talk 03 – 27.04.2020 Lessons learned from **Resilience Engineering (RE) and High Reliability Organisations (HRO), contrasting Taiwan and USA**. Speakers: Sheuwen Chuang (Taiwan), Laurin Mooney (USA), David Provan (Australia). Summary prepared by organisers and speakers.

Talk 04 – 11.05.2020 **Naturalistic Decision Making (NDM) and Resilience Engineering Perspectives on COVID-19**. Speakers: Jan Maarten Schraagen (Netherlands), Lura Militello (USA), Gery Klein (USA) and host Pedro Ferreira (Portugal). Summary by PhD candidate Jakob Svensson (Sweden)

Talk 05 – 25.05.2020 Resilience Engineering and COVID-19 relevant knowledge, initiatives and practices. Speakers: Marcos Borges (Spain), Simon Gill (UK), Eric Rigaud (France). Summary by PhD candidate Marta Iturriza Mendia (Spain)

Talk 06 – 08.06.2020 Rescheduled to 29 June. **Software engineering responses to COVID-19. Resilience Engineering in action**. Speakers John Allspaw, Richard Cook, Nora Jones and Laura Maguire (USA). Summary will be prepared by Per Håkon Meland (Norway)

Talk 07-23.06.2020 Synthesis - As the pandemic continues, still betting against the odds diverse patterns of adapting to global challenges. Results so far from contributions provided to the special series Sudeep Hedge (USA), David Woods (USA), Elizabeth Lay (USA) and Ivonne Herrera (Norway).

7.

Resilience Engineering in Asia, education, tools and collaborations around the world

October 2020

A word from this issue's editor

By Sheuwen Chuang (Taipei Medical University, Taiwan)

Welcome to issue #7 of the REA Newsletter!

In these times of uncertainty and concern, I am grateful to be part of promoting resilience engineering and resilience to secure global health and safety. We are still facing tough times ahead. No doubt we will all be changed by this pandemic. In this issue, let's learn some Asian countries' recent work that aims to promote or clarify concepts associated with resilience and Resilience Engineering. The last part is a summary of REA activities relevant to resilience engineering in the coming months.

The two Japanese contributors coincidentally emphasize business contingency planning (BCP) as the core vehicle to implement resilience. One elaborates on how Japanese companies or institutions propagated their BCPs from individual to area-wide BCPs to enlarge BCP's scope for economic resilience. The other recommends using human resilience in disaster response, business continuity, and disaster recovery through the design of emergency response systems and BCPs. Contributions from Taiwan explain the status of RE development, development of community and society resilience by governance power, and research are undertaking toward the sophisticated use of data incorporating system design to support human decision-making and to scale up resilience potential.

Finally, thank you for your interest in or being part of the resilience engineering field. Let's applaud our strength and resilience in the face of the global-scale health and economic crisis we have seen in our times. Please stay safe and well.

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7.1. Resilience Engineering in Asia

7.1.1. Propagation and Enlargement of Scope of Business Continuity Planning for Economic Resilience

by Satoru NISHIKAWA, Professor, Disaster Mitigation Research Center, Nagoya University

How can we save our livelihoods? How can we minimize economic damage by disasters? We need to involve the business sector in disaster reduction activities! This was the point I raised, back in 1991, as the main author of the annual Japanese government white paper on disaster countermeasures. In early 1990s, geophysical scientists have warned us on the possibility of a major earthquake to hit Tokyo in the near future. If that is to happen, the earthquake will not only destroy houses and kill people but will also damage offices & factories and disrupt supply chains. Even without physical damage, disruption of supply chains will itself bring economic damage. In 1991, this proposal was supported by only a limited number of major companies in Japan. However, with the experience of the 1995 Kobe earthquake, 1999 Chi-Chi earthquake which disrupted the global semi-conductor supply chain, and the 2001 WTC attack where major financial institutions demonstrated their business continuity immediately after the event, the necessity of business continuity planning against sudden disasters gained support among the Japanese business community. In 2004... [Click to read the full story](#)

7.1.2. Resource-Centric Business Continuity Plans for Human-Centered Disaster Resilience

by: Taro KANNO (The University of Tokyo, Japan)

Business continuity and recovery are major issues in disaster resilience engineering. Since I first participated in the REA symposium 2006 to present our work on agent-based simulation for the assessment of resilience in the emergency response system (Kanno et al. 2006), I have been working on issues related to both human factors- and disaster-related resilience. The key principle in our work is “human-centered disaster resilience,” that is, the idea that various human capabilities, including not only the four resilience potentials but also cooperation, collective intelligence, and other abilities, are the driving force and last line of defense for disaster response and recovery. Therefore,...[Click to read the full story.](#)

7.1.3. Inspirations of Resilience Practice from COVID-19 Control in Taiwan

by Yu-Hsing HUANG (National Pintung University of Science and Technology, Taiwan)

You may not have noticed the inherent resilience capability we have as a natural gift for survival. In recent public health measures against COVID-19 in Taiwan, the author has observed amazing resilience practice and realized the resilience is actually part of the human nature.

Living with the unexpected natural disasters and threats, such as earthquake, typhoon, extremely torrential rain, and epidemic diseases, Taiwanese people have been practicing resilience for survival. While looking back in Taiwan from the very beginning of noticing COVID-19 threat until now, the author observed the whole process of keeping the public healthy matches resilience engineering perfectly. All measures that the central government has been taken reflect a high level of resilience ability perfectly matches that proposed by Prof. Hollnagel^[1]; i.e., respond, learn, monitor, and anticipate. This encourages us as researchers to better find out the resilience ability and the process with which our COVID-19 measures come out.

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a much smaller impact in Taiwan than those in most other industrialized countries, with a total of 535 confirmed cases and 7 deaths as of 16 October 2020. Timely border control might be the most important and effective preventive measure for combating COVID-19 in Taiwan according to the information officially documented. As earlier on 31 December 2019, Taiwan responded with border control and onboard inspections for direct flights from Wuhan. On 26 January 2020, Taiwan suspended almost all air travel to and from China except five airports, and put in place quarantine measures for passengers who flew from China. Later, the same policy is applied to all commercial flights from and to those countries with confirmed COVID-19 cases. Timely border control provides Taiwan precious time for preparing counter measures and reserves limited medical resources for confirmed cases. The resilience demonstrated in combating COVID-19 can trace back to the decades of experiences learned from fighting against SARS, bird flu, and epidemic flu in the past in Taiwan.

The combating with COVID-19 not only demonstrates Taiwan's ability in epidemic prevention but also call for the awareness of the resilience in the human nature. Prof. Hollnagel, Prof. Richard Cook, and Prof. Woods were invited to Taiwan in recent years and introduced resilience engineering to local researchers. Their speeches prompted the resilience engineering research in Taiwan. The definition and Chinese translation of the term "resilience" was discussed for ease of its understanding and promotion^[2]. The resilience of emergency medicine support in the Formosa Fun Coast Dust Exploration event in northern Taiwan⁴^[4] and the resilience of ward nursing practices at a local hospital in southern Taiwan⁵ were studied and reported. A Resilience Assessment Grid (RAG) questionnaire tailored for emergency department was developed^[6], and the hospital COVID-19 resilience potentials were studied^[7]. The Resilience Engineering related studies in Taiwan is growing and would be acknowledged by the world.

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7.1.4. Sophisticated use of data incorporating system design to scale up resilience potential

By Sheuwen Chuang, Taipei Medical University (Taiwan)

Resilience Engineering (RE) has been recognized widely and grown rapidly worldwide. The initiatives that highlight how resilience is unique and essential to safety management have advanced the RE theory and methodology. The four cornerstones of resilience, including the ability to monitor, respond, anticipate, and learn, are well-known to sustain operations or ensure system and individual safety. Various studies developed novel instruments, comprehensive frameworks, and analysis tools to assist in measuring, implementing, and improving resilience potentials.

In contrast to reinforcing human adaptations to deal with contextual difficulties, system design, especially incorporating sophisticated data use, provides algorithmic information that can support humans making adequate decisions to cope with situation challenges. The algorithmic or aggregated data can profile or characterize an entity, such as a process (e.g., nursing care), a kind of resource (e.g., critical care beds), or an inpatient to reveal a certain condition that the entity may possess. The profiling information can be used to derive, infer, predict, or evaluate a situation that the entity would face and should be monitored or anticipated to keep the system or individual (patient) safe.

Our team has collaborated with the researchers and practitioners in various disciplines to initiate two projects by fully utilizing big data such as expert interview data, nursing notes (text), regular quantitative data from hospital operations. One study is to redesign the hospital acquired infection control system in a regional hospital to increase

monitoring and anticipatory ability toward proactive infection control. The other is to build a smart mass casualties distribution system to enhance effectiveness of distribution response. The two studies are to improve system resilience through in-time understanding the profiling information of critical entities involved in the care delivery or emergency medical care system.

Data is power; however, data is the most challenging part of collecting and computing in the studies. For example, how to define the ability of a hospital's mobilization and how to define a patient's risk level in the nursing care processes by data. These difficulties are associated with embedding resilience potential, i.e., the ability to monitor into the system. Nevertheless, we have not achieved our goals. However, the studies have brought rich learning to the team. We welcome researchers who are conducting similar projects to share or discuss with us.

7.2. News in REA

7.2.1. REA and NDM Symposium: Join Initiative - Call for Contribution

15th conference on Naturalistic Decision Making and 9th symposium on Resilience Engineering
June 2021, France (21-24th peak)

Bouncing forward from global crises and challenges Rethinking and guiding adaptations based on Resilience Engineering and Naturalistic Decision Making

Context

The pandemic & other events around the world are shocks that stress human systems at scale. These events produce disruptions that spread over time and space inhibiting usual responses. Critically, there is uncertainty about when and how the event may be resolved, and, especially, uncertainty about what resolution will look like. Whether we are scientists, engineers, or managers, how does our work help stakeholders, look ahead to reconfigure systems and relationships? How do we guide adaptations, changes, and opportunities for renewal, while reducing natural tendencies for retreat and retrenchment?

The Call - Part 1: What do you want the program to address?

The Call - Part 2 What new results do you want to share?

[Click to read the full symposium details.](#)

NDM, REA, FONCSI, ICSI

7.2.2. International Course Open to the Resilience Engineering Community

By Tarcisio Saurin (Brazil) and Tor Olav Grøtan (Norway)

As a result of a higher education collaboration between three Brazilian and two Norwegian Universities (STERNA project), a graduate-level course on Resilience Engineering and Safety Management in Complex Socio-Technical Systems started in August 2020.

While the core audience is formed by masters and Ph.D. students, other academics and practitioner's attendance is more than welcome as occasional participants.

Please feel free to contact the course coordinators should you have any questions. Prof. Tarcisio A. Saurin (UFRGS, e-mail) Associate. Prof. Tor Olav Grøtan (NTNU/SINTEF, e-mail)

[Click to read course details.](#)

7.2.3. Webinar - Tools of Practice: Points of Convergence and Divergence*

Speakers: Gary Klein and Sudeep Hegde (USA)

<https://www.resilience-engineering-association.org/seminars/>

This webinar will focus on comparing the tools for research and practice between the Naturalistic Decision Making and Resilience Engineering communities.

7.2.4. Webinar - What can the REA community learn from ATM in dealing with COVID-19? Speakers: Marc Baumgartner (IFATCA), Rowan Powel (EASA), Tom Laursen (DATCA), Tony Licu (EUROCONTROL). Moderators: Milena Studic (skeyes) & Anthony Smoker (Lund University)

<https://www.resilience-engineering-association.org/seminars/>

By now, you are surely overwhelmed by the notion of 'COVID-19'. But this is not the only buzzword that has been relentlessly circulated in the media in the past six months. More often than not, the word 'COVID-19' was accompanied by yet another word 'resilience', or, 'resilience' somehow connected with words such as 'surprise', 'uncertainty', 'complexity', 'adaptive capacity', 'flexibility', 'scalability', 'interdependence' and 'sustainability', to name a few.

While intuitively all of these words and their relationships make sense, the question is how they have all played out during the COVID-19 crisis?

In this webinar, we have invited leading Air Traffic Management (ATM) figures to discuss the good, the bad, and the ugly of ATM resilience management (within a wider aviation context) in light of COVID-19. The panellists will reflect on the ATM industry good practices and lessons learned related to the implementation of theoretical foundations of

Resilience Engineering (RE). In addition, the panellists will shed light on practical research questions that, in their view, may help in bridging the gap between RE theory and practice.

7.2.5. Resilience Engineering – Open Café - Facilitators: Elizabeth Lay (REA Comm Team), Ivonne Herrera (REA EC team) and Vanessa Bertoni (Young Talent Program)

Resilience Engineering Association - get together - our online Christmas Celebration. The idea is to have an informal dialogue. You can register [HERE](#) to join the event. We will have activities that facilitate dialogue, enjoyable interactions and most important opportunity to meet friends and probably to get to know new people.

7.2.6. A New REA Website!

Exploring technology to deliver value to the community and our members in particular

Almost one year ago, the REA Executive Committee conducted a survey to explore how we are meeting the needs of the membership and asked you about the services that you might like to see developed in the future. Your views were clear and we have embarked on the most significant change to the organisation since its inception, focusing on those wishes.

We have re-developed the REA website, creating a number of new features available only to REA members:

- Membership Directory
- Special Interest Groups
- Webinars
- Organisational Member Directory

[Click here to read more about these awesome features.](#)

7.2.7. The book corner: Synesis - The Unification of Productivity, Quality, Safety and Reliability, Erik Hollnagel

Synesis represents the mutually dependent set of priorities, perspectives, and practices that an organisation needs to carry out its activities as intended. It shows how to overcome the fragmentation in foci, scope, and time that characterises the dominant change management paradigms. This book is consequently not about productivity or quality or safety or reliability but about all of these together. It is about why it is necessary to think of them as a whole. And it is about how this can be done in practice. More information about this book and the author [here](#). If you have had the chance of getting acquainted with this new book, we would also like to hear your thoughts on it.

8.

Enablers, tools, collaborations and resilience related activities to respond to COVID-19

June 2021

A word from this issue's editor

by **Riccardo Patriarca, Sapienza University of Rome, Italy**

Engineering resilience in these turbulent times is crucial to ensure a sustainable future for our systems and our societies.

This newsletter gathers stories of teams who promotes resilience engineering in their everyday work: from anaesthesia wards and emergency surgeries, towards aviation operations, crisis management and digital infrastructures. We will then combine practices with a theoretical discussion on the notion of slack resources

With the 9th REA symposium approaching (jointly held with the 15th Naturalistic Decision Making conference), we will finally propose a summary of RE-related events, and news in the RE world. Among them, a couple of recent PhD theses, defended by two former Young Talents.

The future ahead is challenging, but nowadays more than ever, we believe on the urgency of resilient responses in our everyday activities.

Let's embark on this journey with REA!

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8.1. Slack: a key enabler of resilient performance

By Tarcisio Abreu Saurin, Industrial Engineering Post-Graduation Program, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Porto Alegre, Brazil

The provision of slack is a common approach for coping with variability, as it reduces interdependencies and slows down the propagation of variability (Safayeni and Purdy, 1991). In fact, slack is not only useful to address the undesired aspects of variability, but also to exploit opportunities arising from it – e.g., a surge in demand that offers new market opportunities. Furthermore, slack is an asset for innovation, as it allows a forgiving environment for trial and error through experimentation (Beum-Nyum, 2017). Indeed, slack is also valuable for the resilience of socio-technical systems, since it supports performance adjustment and the maintenance of the system’s core functions, during both expected and unexpected situations (Saurin and Werle, 2017).

Common slack strategies involve the use of redundant components (Clarke, 2005), work-in-progress, margins of manoeuvre (Stephens et al., 2011), repurposing, and reallocation of existing resources. These strategies are accomplished through slack resources, which may take the form of people, time, materials, money, space, equipment, among others.

In loosely-coupled socio-technical systems, there is a chance that expedient, spur-of-the-moment slack resources can be found, even though they were not planned ahead of time (Perrow, 1984). These slack resources are deployed opportunistically, as they play a role as slack even though that was not their original purpose. By contrast, built-in slack resources aim at the control of one or more predefined classes of variability sources.

Examples of the aforementioned taxonomy [1] of slack can be easily found out in a number of everyday systems. An example of the strategy “redundancy”, involving the built-in resource “people”, refers to professionals on standby in emergency departments (EDs). In fact, EDs as a whole are exemplars of the slack strategy “work-in-progress”, as they shield other hospital’s units, such as in-patient wards and ICUs, from variations in demand from the external environment.

The COVID-19 pandemic has made the need for slack resources in healthcare services dramatically visible (Saurin, 2021). From the perspective of built-in slack resources, the need for extra ICU capacity and extra supplies stands out. In turn,

examples of opportunistic slack resources abound in the pandemic, such as the adaptation of factories to the production of hand sanitizer and respiratory ventilators, the use of hotel rooms for quarantining international travellers, and the repurposing of drugs. Opportunistic slack resources also resulted from the mixed effects of the pandemic in the occupation of healthcare facilities, as demand for some services plummeted – e.g., suspended elective surgeries freed up operating rooms. Thus, space and staff were reallocated to meet demands from COVID-19 patients. The pandemic also made clear that slack resources are finite and that their provision must go hand-in-hand with the control of variability propagation – this lies at the heart of the widely discussed need for flattening the curve of infections and hospitalizations (Saurin, 2021).

However, slack resources have drawbacks. First, some types of slack resources add elements and therefore complexity to systems. Second, there is a possibility that slack resources grow disorderly over time, to the point of being randomly distributed across the system, and thus not matching the sources of variability (Saurin and Werle, 2017). Third, slack resources imply a cost, thus creating the problem of balancing costs against benefits (Saurin and Ferreira, 2021). Too much slack can equate to waste, which corresponds to the use of more resources than what would be reasonably accepted to produce a desired outcome (Shingo, 1981). Too little slack can make the system vulnerable even to everyday variability. Therefore, a major problem for designers of resilient socio-technical systems involves the definition of the right amount of the right types of slack resources.

The concept map below summarizes the main points of this technical note, in addition to bringing some additional insights. Starting from the centre of the map, it is possible to obtain insight into the taxonomy of slack resources (in green), their purpose (in orange), and possible drawbacks (in purple).

For more info, please e-mail: saurin@ufrgs.br

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8.2. Providing evidence for Resilience Engineering interventions: the RESPOND study

By Mark Sujan, Laura Pickup and Peter McCulloch on behalf of the RESPOND project team Nuffield Department of Surgical Sciences, University of Oxford

Resilience Engineering and its healthcare-specific incarnation Resilient Health Care are coming of age, with the first Resilience Engineering book published almost 15 years ago and the Resilient Health Care counterpart 8 years ago. During this period, the focus has been on the development of concepts and methods, aimed at making visible mechanisms of resilience or describing resilience characteristics based on qualitative studies using observations, interviews and focus groups. It is no surprise, therefore, that in healthcare the majority of Resilience Engineering research tried to contribute to and extend our understanding of everyday clinical work and the many adaptations that clinicians have to make in order to deliver safe care in complex clinical environments.

However, it is important that these insights are now complemented by a body of research that provides evidence about how interventions based on Resilience Engineering principles can make a difference in practice. This is particularly true for healthcare, where there is a strong tradition of evidence-based medicine, but it applies equally across different sectors.

The RESPOND study is a 5-year research project funded by the National Institute for Health Research in the UK, which aims to provide rigorous evidence of a set of Resilience Engineering interventions through a clinical trial. The topic of the research is the management of patients who deteriorate following emergency surgery. Prior research demonstrated that the rate of complications following surgery is roughly comparable across different organisations (around 1 in 4 patients), but that the rate of patient death following complications can be much lower (about half) in successful hospitals compared with lower-performing hospitals. This means that some hospitals are better at recognising when a patient deteriorates and at escalating their care accordingly.

The rate of mortality following a complication is an important quality indicator, and has been given a specific name – *failure to rescue*. Accordingly, much of the research has been occupied with identifying factors that contribute to failure to rescue, i.e. factors that lead to negative outcomes. Of course, another way of looking at this issue, and one familiar to those within the Resilience Engineering community, is to study how the management of deterioration usually succeeds.

In the RESPOND project we are using FRAM to analyse the management of the deteriorating patient from a Resilience Engineering perspective. We will identify a set of interventions that are aimed primarily at strengthening the resilience of the clinical system. After an initial pilot in a small number of organisations, the set of interventions will be evaluated in a cluster-randomised stepped-wedge trial involving up to 24 hospitals.

A stepped-wedge trial is a rigorous evaluation approach suitable for testing complex interventions. In the step wedge design, there is no (randomised) control group. Instead, all study sites (clusters) receive the intervention, but they are randomly allocated to one of a series of “steps”, which start the intervention at different times during the trial. The change caused by the intervention is measured by comparing outcome data from before and after intervention begins. The evaluation of Resilience Engineering interventions using accepted trial designs can help construct a more persuasive case for the benefit of Resilient Health Care, and can also be a model for other industries.

Further

detail: <https://fundingawards.nihr.ac.uk/award/NIHR200868>

Funding acknowledgement: This project is funded by the National Institute for Health Research (NIHR) [PGfAR NIHR200868]. The views expressed are those of the authors and not necessarily those of the NIHR or the Department of Health and Social Care.

8.3. How to engineer resilience in anaesthesia: stories from the ward

By Federico Bilotta, Alessio Tramontana, Francesco Pugliese (Department of Anaesthesiology, “Umberto I” Policlinic-Hospital, “Sapienza” University of Rome, Italy)

We embraced Resilience engineering (RE) in our Department of Anaesthesiology as a multidisciplinary approach to improve care delivery and patients’ safety and to optimize resources allocation in daily activities and in critical conditions.¹ Following recent applications and case studies of RE in a large variety of domains to improve safety and delivered quality of health care, the specific setting of anaesthesia represents a core environment for RE application.²⁻

4

At the “Sapienza” University of Rome, the cooperation between the Departments of Anaesthesiology and Industrial Engineering has yielded several projects over the last 5 years. Some of them already documented in recent literature, while some others are still ongoing:

1.- The design of an analytic framework based on resilience analysis grid (RAG), intended

to assess perioperative organizational resilience according to an analytic hierarchy weighting process (AHP). This framework aims to help in defining the potential of resilience, and to indicate areas of possible improvement;⁵

2.- The practical application of this RAG-based analysis was verified by an international survey, consisting of 57 items questionnaire completed by 172 anaesthesiologists from 16 countries. Overall, the questionnaire was proven reliable: respondents provided positive feedback and confirmed the significance of each question in assessing resilience potential.⁶

3.- An expert review of medical devices that highlighted the way RE can contribute to optimize the relationship between artificial intelligence and human intelligence in medical practice. The proposed approach relies on “simplicity-oriented principle”: the fusion of the required thinking-complexity with maximal action-simplicity. This approach can generate a decision-making process which meets ongoing practices in other high-risk environments,

such as aviation and nuclear power plants, where most relevant safety and quality standards rely on organizational adaptation rather than individual contributions.⁷

4.- A risk analysis developed through the Functional Resonance Analysis Method (FRAM) to understand adaptive capacities in the management of patients throughout the peri-operative pathways. The analysis led to the identification of variability in normal operations and the prioritization of organizational measures to take advantage of it proactively⁸.

Among the ongoing projects, two are worth mentioning: the analysis of the predicting value of multiple risk factors interactions for post-operative delirium occurrence⁹, and the evaluation of “remote control and delivery” of medical assistance in intensive care units according to the technology readiness level.

All the mentioned projects are undergoing a strict cooperation between industrial engineers and anaesthetists to capture as many details as possible about real work practices and enrich respective risk management strategies. The continuing effort in improving safety and quality in medicine can find in RE principles a valuable support for standardized analyses, immediate decision making and diffusion of best practices. The interdisciplinary cooperation between separate competences necessitate a thoughtful and continuous partnership and confrontation that is the background for a common and shared language which can help in defining the needs and possible solutions that each professional can bring into daily practice.

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8.4. COVID 19, resilience and empowerment of frontline staff

By Francois Jaulin and Frédéric Martin (co founders Patient Safety Database and SafeTeam Academy)

In 2016, authors reported that medical errors were the third leading cause of death in the United States and among the top ten causes of death in the World.

Most medical errors could have been prevented by an appropriate teamwork and culture of safety. This situation awareness wasn't shared among the caregivers community. So, we decided to create a reporting system dedicated to healthcare workers.

The first issue was focused on hazardous events and incidents in the operating theatre. The main goals were to analyse and share experiences to enhance the safe culture.

We've [published](#) approximately 150 reports with seventeen quarterly issues. We asked for successes and great achievements but the major flow was driven by incidents, mistakes and the huge amount of contributing factors. This process was interesting but many colleagues were still reluctant to report their own mistakes and at-risk behaviours. The journey was going to be long and difficult!

Then the health crisis caused by the COVID 19 pandemic reared up. It currently mobilizes all players in the health system and beyond. It has led many care workers to work outside their "comfort zone", often in reconstituted teams and in unusual environments. This pandemic has undoubtedly strengthened exchanges between care workers and administrative staff, gathered around a common objective: to treat a massive and prolonged flow of critical patients

despite a suboptimal environment and above all to treat. To address the complexity of these new activities, many players have made innovative proposals and multiple solutions have emerged in a short space of time. The healthcare community at large has demonstrated a resilience and creativity that is unprecedented in material, technological but also organizational terms. Although the mission is complex, this situation forces us to keep it simple and seek pragmatic solutions.

This organisational adaptation has led to a rethink of certain procedures and identify what is necessary and sufficient – no more no less – which has inevitably led to a salutary review: what is the objective and what is the general philosophy of our health system?

Time has come to underline the essence of sharing experience

which is keeping track and creating a link between the various activities of health institutions, managers and front line staff in particular.

For more info visit: <http://www.patientsafetydatabase.com/>

8.5. Resilience in emergency management at an operational level: A joint research project with OFFB

By Riana Steen, BI Norwegian Business School (Norway)

“Flexibility is the operative principle in the art of war. [...] Those who are victorious plan effectively and change decisively. They are like a great river that maintains its course but adjusts its flow.” Sun Tzu (c. 500 b.c)

In ancient China, a high-ranking military strategist and philosopher, Sun Tzu, in his book “The Art of War” acknowledged the importance of capability building and the role of flexibility and adaptive behaviour as the key to success in warfare. The context of Sun Tzu’s arguments was a war against a nation’s enemies. Yet, it is highly relevant for dealing with real work practices’ complexity during an emergency response (ER) operation. The handling of Covid-19 pandemic, in many respects, shows how uncertainty, time pressures and escalating consequences reinforce the need for new approaches in emergency management systems. It calls for a series of research initiatives to provide a deeper understanding of how ER operations may succeed or fail under varying conditions.

As an ethnographer in ER context, I spent my sabbatical year to conduct field research on resilience in emergency management. From January 2020, in a joint research project with the Operator’s Association for Emergency Response, known as OFFB, we have explored how principles and methods from RE field can be applied to improve the adaptive capacity in emergency management systems. As a second line ER organisation for Oil and Gas operators in the Norwegian continental shelf, OFFB operation engages various multidimensional processes in responding to incidents that may impact the people, environment, and material assets. OFFB is also responsible for training and exercises involving its personnel and those employed by the operating companies and associate third parties.

Our observation through a systematic description of the ER events and team behaviours, when joining in different ER exercises, provided us with a unique opportunity to understand the working environment, to translate our empirical findings through the lens of an ER- operational context. The outcomes of our project, up to the present time, are several contributions addressing the following research questions:

- How to design a performance management system to enhance organisational resilience under turbulent changes, in the context of an emergency management organisation?
- How to sustain an emergency response system’s adaptability?
- To what extent does the application of time-dependent FRAM analysis enhance response organisations’ ability to understand and analyse resilience potentials in emergency response operations, hence its adaptive capacity?

We have also explored a Covid-19 outbreak at West Phoenix floating oilrig at the North Sea from a resilience perspective and studied how the outbreak’s characteristics affected the emergency response. More specifically, we investigated

how interaction and coordination between different response actors bring new knowledge into the ER field, improving learning potential, thus resilience in ER operations.

While we continue our research in this promising area, we will focus on combining ideas from “naturalistic decision making” and RE. In particular, we will research how enhancing an intuitive “pattern-matching” at an individual level (ER team) and improving adaptive capacity at an organisational level leads to building the capabilities needed to extend ER operations’ boundaries gracefully.

8.6. 2020 Challenges & Future Collaborations at Qantas

By Mark Peters, Qantas Engineering, Australia

This year, we've faced our toughest challenge in the form of the global pandemic and the widespread associated effect on the airline industry.

From a personal perspective, my organisation (Qantas Engineering) had been working hard over the course of 2018 and 2019 to pursue a strategy of becoming a High Reliability Organisation. We had been collaborating with multiple external organisations and looking at 'new' methods to manage safety. For example check out [this paper](#).

Figure 1. Main phase of the receipt and dispatch process.

Unfortunately, many of the initiatives we were working on were put on hold in 2020 due to restrictions on financial and human resources. We have another difficult year ahead as we continue to overcome the challenges this pandemic has thrown at us. As we emerge from 2020, innovation and collaboration will be a key part of the recovery, as resourcing will continue to be a challenge as the industry focuses on reducing costs.

It is encouraging to see the work other organisations such as [American Airlines](#) are doing to innovate and investigate how to implement Safety II principles in their operation.

Not only is a Safety II approach the right path to take, but many airlines and safety bodies would have also seen a reduction in the number of incident reports submitted during 2020 due to lower activity levels, leading to smaller volumes of data being available for 'traditional' safety analysis. As such this is also a good time to reflect on some of the current accepted safety management practices, and how they might be strengthened.

So, are there any opportunities here to collaborate within the industry for mutual benefit?

Shared Models

One idea for collaboration is to develop a series of models of functional areas that are of interest to sector participants (Airlines, Air Navigation Service Providers (ANSPs), Airports and Aviation Safety bodies). FRAM is a tool that has successfully been used in many studies in aviation and across many countries ([Patriarca et al 2020](#); [Tian & Caponecchia, 2020](#)).

The concept would be similar in principle to the UK CAA Significant 7 (Sig 7) series of Bow Ties developed for priority risks in aviation, in that a library of FRAM model templates of key airline operational functions is developed. Models can then be adapted by organisations to their needs. Researchers could assist with creation of the templates and associated semi-quantitative tools/dashboards (good potential projects for students)!

A further extension of the shared model concept would be where input data could be obtained across multiple organisations (e.g. airline, airport authority and ANSP) and fed into a model to reflect the potential for variability in the system of operation at a particular location under different scenarios. This would be of benefit to airlines and ANSPs operating across multiple sites/environments, and for airport authorities to consider potential variability associated with different operating modes.

8.7. Air Traffic Management (ATM) resilient response during COVID19

By Antonio Licu, EUROCONTROL, Belgium

*“Bad companies are destroyed by crisis, good companies survive them, great companies are improved by them”
(Andy Grove)*

The business continuity measures taken by the European Air Navigation Service Providers (ANSPs) in response to the COVID-19 pandemic led to a significant reduction in the scope of current and planned activities related to the provision of ATM/ANS. Most, if not all Air Traffic Control (ATC) units operated in very limited configuration (a few ATC sectors only) due to the significant decrease of traffic demand. The duty hours of the operational and engineering staff have been reduced respectively. Staff training and equipment maintenance plans might not have been followed due to the social and physical distancing rules introduced. Some facilities could have been put in ‘sleep’ mode due to absence of operational need and/or of staff to use them

Providers have taken several measures to ensure the wellbeing of their staff. The measures were with dual aim – to protect the health and safety of the workforce in the same time with business continuity assurance. In summary a matching a demand supply with safety and health first using the following principles: *minimize the number of people on the premises, minimize the interactions between people, minimize the technical interventions, maximize cleaning*. Here are just a handful of concrete examples:

- 1-1.5 m distancing (if possible 2m). If this requirement can't be maintained, there's a requirement to wear masks (e.g. for handover/takeover in smaller tower units);
- Cleaning intervals have increased with more disinfecting, etc.

- ‘Buddy of the Day’ policy, where an air traffic controller has to stick to one partner throughout the duration of their duty. This ensures that if either of the controllers tests positive, only two people will be taken off duty (rather than the entire team that was rostered);
- Rostering has been adapted to allow lean team work, resp. create isolated teams in smaller units. Rosters with a 10-15% margin above predicted traffic levels (two weeks lead time). Longer shifts of staff that do not meet to ensure one warm, one cold stand by and one live shift;
- Close contact with health authorities to coordinate actions in case of infections;
- Access to premises for externals highly restricted – resp. prohibited in OPS rooms except for urgent maintenance activities.
- Pandemic Task Forces meeting at regular intervals and is tracking operational and health issues. Apart from all MIL/CIV OPS Units, it usually comprises also the companies doctors, health and safety unit etc.
- Plexiglas separation walls where appropriate etc.

As part of the collaborative effort to ensure a safe, smooth and coordinated recovery of the European ATM network operations from the lockdown caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, the operational Safety unit of the Eurocontrol Network Management Directorate developed in cooperation with the members of the EUROCONTROL Safety Team and SAFOPS group a safety argument and a list of potential hazards/safety issues to assist ANSPs in planning and executing a safe and resilient return to normal operations. The purpose of the Safety Argument is to serve as support and assist ANSPs by providing a comprehensive reference to the elements of the ANSP’s functional system that might have been affected during the COVID-19 lockdown period and need to be properly accounted of and managed when planning and executing the transition to normal operations.

The identified potential hazards/safety issues may occur during the extended period of transition to normal operations due to various factors related to the COVID-19 lockdown. The list contains the issue description, the list of COVID-19 lockdown related causal and contributory factors and disruptors, and potential measures (not an exhaustive list) to mitigate their probability of occurrence or their safety effects. When used, the list of hazards and potential mitigation measures should be reviewed and updated according to the local operational environment and the specific impact of the lockdown on the ANSP’s functional system.

Safety argument [1] and review to return to normal operations must be considered in the context of the overall system, not isolated individuals, parts, events or outcomes. Most problems and most possibilities belong to the system. Hence through Safety argument we need to look at ATM system holistically, and consider interactions between elements of the system and not review each safety argument in isolation like as a merely checklist.

The scope of the argument covers the three main elements of the functional system – operational and engineering staff, procedures and equipment, and identifies the elements’ properties that have been or could have been affected by the reduced scope of operations. Such properties include – inter alia – operational and engineering staff competence, training and medical fitness; equipment configuration and certificates for use; changes to procedures introduced during the crisis period, etc.

The safety argument puts an emphasis on the need to set up a robust transition planning, monitoring and management process. Key elements of this process are: collaborative traffic demand forecasting, monitoring and planning of ATC sector configurations and pre-tactical ATFCM measure scenarios; flexible ATCO rostering in accordance with forecasted and actual demand; coordination and collaboration with all transition stakeholders (NM, ANSPs, AOs, airport operators, CAs); targeted safety monitoring and timely identification and resolution of transition issues.

To support the risk assessment part of the Safety Argument a generic hazard/safety issues identification of the ATM/ANS provision during the recovery period has been carried out. The output has been captured in a non exhaustive list of generic behaviours that may occur during the extended period of transition to normal operations due to various factors related to the COVID-19 lockdown. The list is not restricted at one particular level or boundary of the ATM system. The transition hazards are potential safety issues that are not necessarily independent of each other. Some of the items in the list can also be considered as disruptors that could affect higher level operational hazards.

Air Navigation Service providers possessed resilient operators’ characteristics and behaved accordingly during the pandemics:

- They faced down the hashed reality immediately and reacted as described above
- They found meaning for surviving and focused not only on short term survivability but on long term as well (e.g. European Operational Excellence programme that starts in 2021)
- They had the capability to improvise safe solutions with what resources were left by the Pandemics

Finally in my view ATM European industry is resilient because it has a large cognitive diversity – one should never estimate how much cooperation, collaboration and sharing of knowledge and practices is taking place through European organisation facilitation such as Eurocontrol, European Aviation Crisis Coordination Cell, EASA and EC.

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8.8. Action Item: Ban All Vacations

by J. Paul Reed, Netflix, USA

“I just got pager alert! Our service is reporting 100% CPU utilization; any ideas?”

“Not sure, but let’s start by reverting the last code deployment and seeing if that helps.”

“Ok... uhh... how do I do that?”

“Not sure; Sue knows all about our release pipeline, but... she’s... on vacation...”

Sound familiar?

As a Senior Applied Resilience Engineer on Netflix’s Critical Operations & Reliability Engineering (CORE) team, one of my jobs is to dig deep into the operational incidents we experience, mining for weak signals warning of high-impact risk, searching for areas for organizational development and learning, and discovering systemic themes about our ever-changing socio-technical ecosystem.

As we’ve invested more in these investigations, we’ve run into many cases where “vacation” turns out to be a contributory factor to how an incident unfolds. But, surprisingly, we’ve seen this play out in ways that aren’t the simple exchange above, where an engineer isn’t available in the moment of a specific incident.

In one case, a new code deployment was causing an issue for a small subset of users. The team involved elected to “fix-forward,” and release a new version of the code. The fix didn’t end up fixing the issue, and the decision was made to rollback not to the previous version, but to the *version before the previous version*. Code deploys were automated, but code rollbacks were not. And the engineer who normally does these sorts of tasks was out on vacation. When another engineer valiantly attempted the rollback, they succeeded... but unfortunately they didn’t fully complete all the required rollback steps, resulting in a impactful incident.

In another case, a service deployed a new version of their code and within about two hours, it started impacting customers. System monitoring detected the issue, and it was remediated relatively quickly. But in the post-incident investigation, it was discovered that a member of the team owning the service had been on vacation. That engineer normally did the weekly deployments after the Monday team sync meeting. But, because they weren’t there, they did the deployment on Tuesday, when they returned. *However*, another team member had added some code *thinking they would have a full-week to run that code in the test environment*, because... “our team always deploys on Mondays!” (Except for the week their release captain took a three-day weekend!)

This “vacation” risk often presents itself as a more specific case of a broader risk my colleagues and I have dubbed “Something somebody doesn’t know.” These can appear as mental model gaps, operational expertise gaps, observability gaps, or the omnipresent “missing important context.” Because we take extra time to examine our incidents, we find that vacations can uncover context missing or highlight areas of operational expertise to improve... but in the cases above, because the vacation was a minor triggering event, not an explicit utterance during the incident

response effort, we might have never fully understand the impact of vacations and leaves if we'd hadn't taken the time to more fully understand the incident.

So what's the solution? Well obviously, everyone's expertise should be available at all times, so we need to ban all vacations immediately! (Just kidding.)

But, these types of investigations *do* highlight the importance of organizational learning efforts that support the *emergent exchange* of information—what we'd call "[context](#)" at Netflix—and that we action the signal they raise that there may be an opportunity for upping a team's on-boarding processes, so team members don't find themselves on-call, responding to an incident, and lacking the details on how to execute important operational tasks. (Or, perhaps, code rollbacks need to be added to the pending feature list, to be automated just like deployments, and the rollbacks should be [chaos tested!](#))

Whatever the path toward remediation is, learning that yes, even vacations and leaves can trigger and contribute to operational incidents in ways we would have never expected is a discovery we would never have made without looking more closely. And that gained insight reveals far more areas we can all work on to increase our resilience prowess.

9.

RE in new places: Societal-scale Resilience

June 2021

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9.1. A word from this issue's editor

By Mike Rayo, The Ohio State University, USA

Welcome to issue #9 of the REA Newsletter! REA made the mistake of giving my the (login) keys to the newsletter this month. The following is what resulted ...

If it wasn't clear before 2021, it is now: we live in a complex, uncertain world in which we cannot predict in advance what will be necessary to remain viable. Instead, we need to invest in the ability of our communities to anticipate, absorb, extend through, and recover from shocks. Keeping pace with the current tempo of change will require input and engagement from all stakeholders in the society, using multiple points of view to synthesize learnings into interventions that preserve structures, functions, and goals while simultaneously preserving future adaptive capacity. Our new world is quickly understanding the necessity of extensibility as a requirement for viability. This sounds like Resilience Engineering, right?

However this new world is already quite full of researchers, practitioners, and decision-makers committed to solving these societal-scale problems. The vast majority of them are not conversant in the language of resilience engineering (don't believe me? Ask them to list the four resilience potentials, or to differentiate between the concepts of rebound, robustness and graceful extensibility!!). They have their own language and models, some of which are in direct contradiction to ours.

If we are serious about wading into this new scale of system, we will need new collaborators and n-way communication of ideas and practices. We need to quickly and effectively disseminate our findings, and be ready to listen about the vastly different dynamics and pitfalls of societal-scale systems. We will once again be outsiders, but there will once again be fellow travelers who have been making these (societal-scale) systems go.

This edition of the newsletter is focused on engineering resilience at a societal-scale. Some groups are thinking about the barriers and facilitators. Many have already started to put resilience engineering into practice in a variety of settings. We have brought together a set of voices both within and outside of our resilience engineering community. We hope that this spurs conversation and builds connections to accelerate our ability to make a difference in this critically important space.

It is clear to me that the dynamics that are identified, encountered and worked through below are prescient of what will be faced for all future societal issues. These include global climate change, widespread poverty, substance abuse, structural racism and many others. Creating sustained adaptability in government and societies will require rethinking of the interactions between people and their governments. The future will echo the lessons that these groups are already learning.

Interested in learning more? In addition to the articles below, we will be diving deeper into these topics during the REA-NDM-FONSCI symposium next week!

9.2. The hard work is paying off! See you next week!

By Pedro Ferreira, REA organizing committee, Portugal

The organisation of meetings and events often prove to be hard work, especially when you aim to create highly customised programmes and generate close proximity between participants. This has been the tradition of the RE Symposium and, despite the additional challenges of the worldwide pandemic, we wanted to ensure that this year's edition adheres to it. With that in mind, we have practiced what we preach, and in the face of new challenges, we sought to innovate and adapt by bouncing forward. This has led to the introduction of the following two major new features:

- The joint efforts between REA, NDM and ISCI-FONCSI towards fostering diversity of thought and integration of new ideas.
- The design of a programme structure that combines online and in-person activities, and maintains the worldwide interactions that we have become accustomed at REA symposia.

This year's edition of the RE symposium is therefore quite different from previous ones but we are confident that it will bring the usual collaborative reflections and discussions to a whole new level. The following regional nodes are have been confirmed:

- Toulouse, France - ENAC (Ecole Nationale de l'Aviation Civil)
- Norway and Scandinavia
- Porto Alegre, Brasil
- Columbus, Ohio, USA – Ohio State University
- Sidney, Australia

I know that time is growing short, but please let us know if you would like more information about any of these sites!

We are very excited to present the programme of the REA-NDM-ICSI-FONCSI 2021 Joint Initiative as the result of a collaborative thought process and work that started some 2 years ago.

We invite you to visit our programme page here: <https://easychair.org/smart-program/REA-NDM-FONCSI2021/>

If you would like to join us in this new experience and have not registered yet, you may still do so within the next few days. Registration details are also available at the programme page.

I look forward to meet you in Toulouse, one of our other nodes, or online!

9.3. Interaction between citizens and emergency organisations: a key to improving societal resilience

By Rose Michael, European Emergency Number Association (EENA), Belgium

When a disaster occurs, the first people on the scene are often members of the general public. In those first moments, the actions of citizens have the potential to mitigate the impacts of the crisis until professional help arrives. Despite citizens serving as an important link in the emergency chain, disaster management policies currently tend to focus primarily on the response of formal organisations. Improving disaster response therefore requires placing more emphasis on resilience as a whole-of-society endeavour.

Exploring the interaction between the population and emergency organisations is the basis of ENGAGE's work on societal resilience. An EU-funded project, ENGAGE works on the principle that citizens have an important role to play in preventing and managing disasters, both before, during and afterwards. However, for their potential to significantly contribute to resilient societies, citizens' capabilities need to be better integrated into the response of first responder organisations and public authorities.

Resilience involves an inclusive strategy to build a culture of risk. ENGAGE is building on our understanding of the many factors that contribute to societal resilience, all of which may impact the way that formal organisations interact with the public and vice versa. The importance of enhancing knowledge about disaster risk and all its components has been identified in the UN's Sendai Framework (Priority Action 1). ENGAGE is therefore asking: What does an effective response from the population look like? And how can we better ensure that this happens?

So, what kind of factors should we consider? ENGAGE is identifying target aspects, such as levels of risk awareness and methods of sharing information, that can be enhanced through policies and concrete actions. Solutions to address the target aspects and help bridge the gap between practitioners and citizens come in many different forms. They include practical resources, such as technological tools, guidelines, training, and other formal and informal practices. The solutions will be analysed and categorised in a

catalogue of solutions that will aim to enhance the knowledge of decision-makers and strengthen disaster risk governance (Sendai Framework Priority Action 2).

However, solutions should be chosen not only according to the target aspects they aim to improve, but based on what ENGAGE describes as contextual aspects. These are embedded in the culture of the society itself and change requires a more complex and long-term strategy. Contextual aspects, such as levels of trust in different institutions, may significantly impact the success of the various solutions.

Creating a community of collaboration through the research is therefore key, reflecting the broader, people-centred approach highlighted in the Sendai Framework. By working with a variety of actors in a Knowledge and Innovation Community of Practice, including NGOs, practitioners and citizens, ENGAGE will develop a deep understanding of the natural place of resilience in local communities. As case studies are analysed, we're exploring how lessons learnt from countries

across the world, such as Japan, can be built on and implemented in the European context.

Understanding how interaction with citizens fits into disaster

response will help to enhance policy that can ultimately save lives and ensure that societies bounce back quicker and more effectively from a crisis. Once we start considering resilience as an intrinsic ability of a whole society – to be able to adjust itself and

continue functioning before, during and after crises – we see that local communities are valuable resources that can be drawn upon during a disaster.

9.4. Dealing with disasters: What should society do?

By Sahar Elkady, TECNUN, School of Engineering of the University of Navarra, Spain

If we can learn something from 2020 and 2021, is that disaster is around the corner. We cannot survive unless we collaborate. This “we” includes us as civilians and unorganized individuals on one hand and emergency responders and authorities on the other hand. To make this collaboration effective and to react to and recover from crises efficiently, we need to identify what authorities and emergency responders need from civilians to better face a crisis, and what capacities the community has to complement the authorities’ expectations. In this article, we are concerned about the first part, the authorities’ and emergency responders’ needs and expectations. And this is one of the main themes that project ENGAGE covers.

In order to identify these needs, we used two data sources. The first one is an online survey that covered participants from six European countries that have different characteristics (France, Italy, Norway, Romania, Spain, and Sweden) and Israel. We got 5817 responses across the seven countries. The responders came from diverse backgrounds, police officers, firefighters, members of health services, members of authorities, and many more. To complement the results from the

survey, we used a second data source, semi-structured interviews. The interviews also covered members of emergency organizations and authorities from the seven countries. The interviews opened us up to different kinds of information than the ones provided by the survey results, as they gave the interviewee that chance to talk more freely and reflect on their experiences. We conducted around 30 interviews in the seven countries.

The survey results closely match the findings of the interviews. However, the interviews provide us with the “why” part; why authorities and emergency responders need this or that. For example, during a crisis, emergency responders believe that civilians need to follow their instructions. On one hand, this saves the lives of civilians who are not trained to face such situations, and on the other, it eliminates the chaos that could result from ill-advised interventions from untrained citizens, amplifying the number of tasks that emergency responders must manage and making the situation more challenging for them. Having this in mind, it does not negate the necessity for volunteer assistance during a crisis, and

especially during the recovery and coping phases. Authorities and emergency responders appreciate the help of volunteers in the “during” phase but through organized groups, such as NGOs and the Red Cross; as they already have proper training and follow a well-established approach to coordinate with emergency organizations. In the “recovery” phase, citizens’ contribution is looked at from a different perspective. It is more about helping each other, showing social solidarity, and supporting each other emotionally. It is also helping in relief work, since authorities and emergency organizations do not have enough personnel and resources. Moreover, emergency responders expect people to be well prepared to face a crisis through two main things, information and physical resources. They need the public to be risk aware to know how to obtain all the information that helps them better handle a crisis and to have the physical resources; some food, water, and medical supplies.

Authorities, emergency responders, and community members all have responsibility for properly addressing a crisis. In short, it takes two to tango!

9.5. Multi-directional communication between authorities, first responders and the public during adversities – do they have similar needs and perceptions?

By Stoloro Nathan, Bodas Moran, Peleg Kobi, Adini Bruria, Tel Aviv University, Israel

Imagine the not-so-hypothetical-anymore situation: there is a worldwide pandemic, and many countries are in lockdown. People are at home, confused, worried, and some even suffer from a medical condition that they are not sure if it is related to the pandemic. A true crisis is ongoing. One crucial aspect of managing such a crisis is the communication process between authorities and first responders and the public and vice-versa.

Project ENGAGE is an EU-funded consortium aiming to engage societies in risk awareness to enhance their societal resilience. As part of this project, we examined the communication needs and expectations of the public before, during and after emergencies and disasters and how authorities and first responders communicate with the public and vice-versa.

One of the essential communication questions arising in all phases of emergencies and disasters is what does the public need the most? Information? Knowledge on how to cope with the situation (e.g., what to do during an earthquake)? In order to answer this question, we surveyed respondents in France, Israel, Italy, Norway, Japan, Romania, Spain and Sweden. In

addition, we analysed user comments to posts in social media of authorities and first responders in those countries (excluding Japan).

We found that needs related to information and knowledge (cognitive) are perceived to be the most important by the respondents across all countries, followed by the need to receive fast and accurate information. However, both the survey and the analysis of the user content in social media highlighted that the communication needs of the public before, during and after emergencies and disasters are multiplex. They seek information and content that will make them feel better, part of society, and even escapism from reality. Authorities and first responders were, in many cases, in their eyes, the address for fulfilling these needs. In other words, they found authorities and first responders responsible not just for helping them in what to do and what should they know, but on how to feel and even disengage, if needed. This was the first study out of two already conducted examining the communication process.

If the first study focused on the public's point of view, the second study examined the

communication strategy, channels and guidelines of authorities and first responders. In other words, we examined, using document analysis and semi-structured interviews, how do emergency organisations communicate with the public and vice-versa.

Here, we found that authorities and first responders across the countries we examined (seven, again, excluding Japan) use a variety of communication channels, from traditional and mass media channels, through social media, to more innovative communication channels, such as AI-enabled chatbots (very little, but it still exists). The collection of communication channels allowed us to generate a list of possible channels. A list that can serve other organisations in looking for new communication methods to communicate with the public. However, we found that authorities and first responders had minimal guidelines regarding communicating with the public. We also identified several gaps in how authorities and first responders perceive the communication process with the public and how the public perceives it. For example, authorities and first responders were very concentrated on

disseminating information, while the public, as mentioned above, desired the fulfilment of other needs.

To conclude, the communication process of authorities/first

responders-the public and vice-versa is complex. Addressing this complexity is one of the keys to enhancing societal resilience.

Achieving this could be done by building communication guidelines grounded in research

and professional recommendation, and not less important – addressing the gaps between authorities and first responders and the public.

9.6. Coping strategies of citizens during disaster

By Jan Verlin, Chair in Geopolitics of Risk, Ecole Normale Supérieure, France

What makes people self-organize to give first aid to victims of an active shooter? Why do people share their houses with others who lost their homes in an earthquake? Who volunteers for searching bodies after a flood? And how can first responders and authorities encourage this spontaneous solidarity between citizens rather than limiting it. ENGAGE wants to understand the potential of spontaneous self-organization of society during a crisis.

ENGAGE is a European funded research project for identifying solutions to improve societal resilience. Our part in this endeavour is to provide and analyse data on what citizens actually did to cope with a crisis to enhance societal resilience by examining closely eight different historical case studies: The Aquila earthquake of 2009, the Utøya terror attack, the Swedish wildfires of 2018, the Tōhoku Tsunami of 2011, the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear accident of 2011, the Negev flash floods of 2018, the Thalys train attack of 2015 and the Covid-19 pandemic. These case studies were chosen to highlight a variety of crisis situations ranging from terrorist attacks to industrial accidents to “natural” disasters like earthquakes, wildfires or flash floods including both large scale events and localized tragedies. We study official reports, scientific articles and conduct

interviews and focus groups to understand the actions of citizens, but also the specific social context in which they take place. The goal of this survey of grassroots experiences is to take seriously what people say made them act.

To do so we first mapped social actors who engaged in “coping actions” before, during and after these historical crises. By “coping actions” we understand “resilience” not as a passive, latent ability of a group to “bounce back” after a disruption, but as a set of actions actively transforming a disaster situation by influencing individuals, social groups or a given society as a whole. Individuals or groups undertake such actions because they believe they contribute to overcome and cope with the crisis at hand.

In a second step, we understood “coping actions” as situated. In other words, we showed that these “coping actions” are rooted in society in the sense that they are enabled not only by material conditions, but also by discourses and representations of the event itself and of the social roles citizens identify with during a crisis. What people do during a crisis to overcome its effects is situated both in a larger social context and in the specific setting the crisis disrupts. Individuals and organizations act because they are attached to

certain communities and involved in specific social groups. They identify themselves with certain values or beliefs in certain ideologies.

Our preliminary findings show that specific professional skills as well as membership in certain social groups make it more likely that people self-organize. Medical professions and politically active citizens are among those who enhance the resilience of their communities. Community norms around gender roles (e.g., “caregivers” and “heroes”) are another contextual aspect that is particularly relevant for successfully dealing with a disaster as well as specific cultural belief systems. Whereas a lot of studies insist for example on trust in authorities as determining factor for successfully building resilience, we can also show how constructive mistrust in authorities is more efficient in some contexts.

To conclude, these contextual aspects help us to identify “target aspects” that should be integrated in solutions that want to enhance societal resilience. For this reason, we develop a comprehensive model that help authorities and first responders to be context sensitive by understanding how citizen’s actions during a crisis are localized in specific social bonds

and values. We placed the contextual aspects from each of our cases on a continuum ranging from those that can and should not be targeted for enhancing societal resilience to target aspects that can be influenced by the type of solutions ENGAGE wants to propose. We also situated aspects on a second continuum measuring the level of

generalizability. This enables us to distinguish between aspects that are rooted in the structure of society from those that are enacted in a given crisis situation. Whereas specific roles may be assigned by gender to citizens in a crisis, the way these roles are enacted in a specific situation may differ considerably. Also, awareness of certain risks does not necessarily

translate into situational awareness.

The position of each aspect depends on the specific case that is modeled. Thus, this model enables us to assess the conditions of societal resilience and compare the different case studies without losing the specific characteristics of each case.

9.7. Acts of resilience? Spontaneous volunteering during the Utøya terror attack 22.07.2011 – preliminary findings

By Asbjørn Lein Aalberg & Rolf Johan Bye, SINTEF Digital, Norway

During the terrorist attacks in Norway 22th of July 2011, 77 people were killed and many more injured. The attacks led to massive, multifaceted efforts of civil society, especially concerning the attacks at Utøya. The officially appointed investigation commission acknowledged that more lives would have been lost if civilians had not taken spontaneous action and helped rescue victims from the island during the attack, providing crucial information to the official emergency responders and assisting in transporting the SWAT team to the island.

The spontaneous volunteering during and after the Utøya attack could be further be seen as a kind of societal or community resilience, in which the citizens demonstrated the ability to self-organize and adapt, when faced by major disasters.

Less is known, however, about what the civil society actually did during the attack, which leads to multiple important questions:

1. How we can understand the mechanisms of such spontaneous volunteering?
2. Once we understand these mechanisms, how should or could we integrate such efforts in more formal, traditional crisis management?
3. Is it possible or advisable to integrate these mechanisms into formal crisis management practice?

First, we wanted to check the characteristics of the academic articles on the Utøya attack. Were there any scientific efforts directed towards volunteer efforts during and immediately after the attack? We conducted a literature search in various sources and found 154 peer-reviewed items. In short, the answer is that we found only one relevant article. Second, we wanted to map the actions taken by volunteers and their perceptions of the events using various document sources, including a free-text-questionnaire issued by the official investigation commission, autobiographical books, newspapers and various reports.

Third, based on the mapping of the actions and perceptions of the volunteers, we tried to identify factors that appears to have contributed to their actions and influenced the efficiency of their rescue operations.

In the next paragraphs, we briefly summarize some of our findings so far.

Spontaneous volunteering during and in immediate aftermath of Utøya terror attacks

Spontaneous and voluntary rescue operations emerged at the landside of Utøya during the attack. Actions taken during the attack included: 1) evacuating victims from the island by boat, 2) distributing life jackets and rescuing victims by boats in the water during gun fire, 3) providing physical and psychosocial first aid, 4) organizing ad hoc emergency care centres and transporting victims to hospitals and an initially ad hoc emergency centre at a nearby hotel. These actions emerged spontaneously and informally, before any formal emergency organizations arrived at the disaster area. With the arrival of the different emergency services volunteers did offer and provide their assistance. This included 1) intelligence based on local knowledge, 2) transportation by boat, 3) first aid and psychosocial support, 4) transportation of victims to the positions of ambulances, emergency centres and hospitals. In the immediate aftermath of the attack (after the perpetrator has been captured) both convergent non-affiliated and affiliated volunteers showed up at official emergency centres offering services like psychosocial support and administrating the registering of victims.

Based on information from the island (sounds and observation), telephone calls and messages, social media and official media coverage, several civilians in the proximity of the island (local residents, campers, drivers passing by etc)

initiated – quite independently from each other – different types of rescue operations. The efforts in the first phase of the attack were conducted by both individuals operating by themselves and individuals that informally organised responses together with fellow non-affiliated volunteers. When the formal emergency organizations arrived at the site, some spontaneous volunteers provided their assistance. Some volunteers received orders from the police and ambulance to terminate their operations and evacuate from the area but chose not to comply with these orders.

Contextual factors that influenced the volunteers' rescue operations

There seems to have been an alertness among the volunteers due to information about the first attack in Oslo. This might explain both the outcome of the volunteers sensemaking when they heard about and/or observed unusual activity on the island, and their willingness to act on this knowledge. Community alertness and unsolicited initiative taken by individuals inclined to act seem to have been a prerequisite for the fast response among the volunteers. The same applies to the spatial proximity to the attack. The spatial proximity had probably an impact on the outcome of the volunteers sensemaking and their choice of adequate actions. Access to resources and the ability to utilize resources relevant in the specific situation (such as boats, life jackets, showers, buildings, clothing, cars were essential) was decisive for the type of tasks that could be performed by the volunteers, as well as providing necessarily resources for the police (e.g., boats). Local knowledge among the volunteers regarding accessible resources (equipment and personnel) contributed to the efficiency of the operations. Intelligence based on local knowledge about the local geography was also crucial for giving the Police ability to efficiently localize and navigate to the island. Established social bonds between individuals was important for both recruiting more personnel and to establish efficient ad hoc emergency organizations. Several independent ad hoc organizations of volunteers with limited coordination contributed to focus on handling tasks based on the volunteer's situational awareness in the area they were operating. This contributed to fast tactical adaptations to the perceived needs in the area they were operating. Further, the redundancy in both organizations and task performance did ensure the efficient continuation of certain tasks in cases when volunteer resources were reallocated to new tasks (due to their own choice or due to commands from formal organizations). The disregarding of orders from the police to evacuate from the area meant that rescue operations continued, and that several lives among the escaping victims were saved.

Dilemmas of spontaneous volunteering

In the Utøya case, the spontaneous volunteers have been highlighted as “heroes who saved the day”, when the efforts of some of the formal organizations failed in several areas. The volunteers have received praise from the official investigation commission, and some have been given medals of honor.

Hypothetically – although the volunteers' definitely showed ability to self-organize and adapt – several of volunteers could have been killed or wounded by the perpetrator when performing their tasks, and/or performed tasks that would harm the victims, or even hampered and delayed the formal operations. For example, volunteers rescuing victims with boats were shot at, and volunteers operating at the shore-side were within the shooting range of the perpetrator. Further, non-professional volunteerism may also represent a dilemma in terms of exposing civilians to situations that may provoke post-traumatic reactions. If the outcome of the action taken by several volunteers had led not successful in terms of rescuing the victims, several of the contextual factors contributing to the volunteers' actions could also be considered as problematic in an emergency. Factors such as lack of coordination and reluctance to submit to the command of the formal organizations could hypothetically be used to explained negative outcomes of an emergency situation.

Conclusions so far

We may briefly conclude our preliminary results and notions

1. There was a massive mobilizing of volunteers a Utøya, including individuals and groups, and their operation was largely autonomous and detached from the formal response.

2. Despite the impactful participation by citizen, there has been little effort on volunteerism in the literature on the Utøya attack, particularly from a scholarly perspective, where we identified that only one of the 164 academic articles was related to spontaneous volunteers. Thus, one can hypothesize that societal and community perspectives on resilience related to such events is somewhat lacking.
3. Contextual factors like spatial proximity, local knowledge, social bonds and reluctance to submit to the command of the formal organizations seems to have influenced the volunteer efforts.
4. Volunteering represents dilemmas with regards to relation with formal crisis management, and their own physical and mental health. First, whereas formal first responders operate within a safe zone, spontaneous volunteers could often find themselves in proximity of real danger, both during the event as well the experience of traumatic events have potential psychosocial and mental effects. Second, whereas integration and coordination of spontaneous volunteers into formal crisis management could increase control and overview of a particular situation, our findings show that in this case, the autonomous and parallel performance contributed to “successful” outcomes of rescue missions – thus balancing between autonomy, coordination and control is an interesting aspect. Finally, acknowledging hindsight bias and counterfactual thinking, the coping actions that “went well” could hypothetically had led to catastrophic outcomes in slightly different circumstances. In sum, these dilemmas are important to acknowledge and further investigate in relation to how we can understand volunteerism within the theoretical notions of resilience.

We propose to further investigate how the identified contextual factors, as well as the dynamic and multifaceted nature of volunteerism during crisis, implicate the design and operation of crisis management models – to leverage the potential of civilian efforts to societal resilience.

10.

On the 9th Symposium on Resilience Engineering

November 2021

A word from this issue's editors

By Vanessa Bertoni & Natalia Ransolin, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul, Brazil

Even though we all are still facing Covid-19, the Resilience Engineering Association (REA) continued its legacy bringing a joint initiative Bouncing forward on global crises and challenges based on Resilience Engineering (RE) and Naturalistic Decision Making (NDM) communities. The “15th Conference on Naturalistic Decision Making” and “9th Symposium on Resilience Engineering” ran from June 21 to June 24, 2021, in Toulouse. This event was partially presential and transmitted online for those who could not attend in person for the first time. This event was attended by 372 participants from 31 different countries.

Senior and new investigators in the RE and NDM areas showed the potential of their research in panels, presentations, and immersion. From the total, 20 participants attended the Emerging Talents, which is an opportunity for young researchers from those fields to get in touch with renowned researchers who could give feedback and insights in their thesis dissertation. A total of 76 submissions from 19 different origins, of which 75% were integrated into the program. Figure 2 shows the distribution of submission by country in percentage. For additional information, please visit the dashboard with symposium data.

In the end, four days of immersion proved to be too little for the amount of research and learning work and exchange of experience. This newsletter is composed of main topics discussed during the event, in articles covered by keynotes of respective areas.

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10.1. Diversity of perspective: Resilient healthcare and NDM

By Tarcisio Saurin, Brazil

As usual in the REA Symposiums, resilient healthcare was the topic of several contributions last June. The investigation of how health services have coped with COVID-19 and the corresponding lessons learned was addressed by three papers. These papers categorize and discuss COVID coping practices adopted in Brazil, Japan, and the USA. Practices included role reassignment, workers training, communication of change, inter-departmental cooperation, knowing where to find resources, adaptations in the built environment, and suspension of elective procedures. The pandemic also gave visibility to the human cost of resilient performance, which according to another paper can arguably be measured using workload as a proxy measure. Of course, a question mark remains on whether the pandemic lessons have actually been learned by health services and whether at least some of the newly demonstrated resilience capabilities can be maintained after the pandemic subsides. Depending on the answer to these questions, the pandemic can reveal a distinctive pattern of resilience curves in healthcare, characterized by performance

bouncing forward to a new improved state, rather than simply bouncing back to the previous state.

Work unrelated to COVID also stood out. Resilience experts from Taiwan presented a novel hospital selection algorithm composed of driving time from the disaster site to hospital, care adequacy, and mobilization ability to determine the best hospital choice for mass casualty distribution. Contributions from the naturalistic decision-making community also showed their value to resilient healthcare. For example, one of the papers discussed how frontline child welfare practitioners make decisions that affect the safety and well-being of children under conditions in which facts are incomplete and information is frequently unreliable. Another similar study emphasized that many organizations, such as child protective services, need experienced practitioners but face real challenges in staff retention. Cognitive training approaches promoted by NDM researchers might play a role in the development of resilient health services.

10.2. COVID-19 as a stress test for NDM and RE

By Jan Maarten Schraagen, Netherlands

What has COVID-19 taught us about the usefulness of both Naturalistic Decision Making (NDM) and Resilience Engineering (RE) to explain the unprecedented and large-scale events that happened over the past 1.5 years?

The pandemic and our response to it showed many characteristics of resilient systems. However, it may be too early to say whether countries or organizations or groups responded appropriately to the disturbances imposed by the pandemic. Countries differed largely in their approach. Many showed flexibility and continued to adapt to changing environments, for instance by modifying their policies as the situation demanded. Others rigidly continued with their pre-set approaches. Resources are finite and surprise is inevitable. There were many surprises, for instance about the rate of infections, the multiple waves of infection, and the variants of the virus. There were also positive surprises, such as the speed with which vaccines were developed. And although resources are finite, some of the richer countries could draw on their reserves to develop support programs for the groups hit hardest by the economic crisis. Therefore, resilience is not just about managing trade-offs, it is

also about developing support structures for those affected by the management of trade-offs.

Resilience showed itself in two ways: first, as the management of trade-offs as a professional craft, in the form of contingency planning, coordinating efforts; second, as the development of support structures as a political craft, developing a social distribution of risk and harm across groups and interests, and pushing for or blocking systemic reforms and navigating blame games.

What is missing from current resilience theories is an account of the political craft involved in dealing with a crisis such as COVID-19: how to turn faster-better-cheaper pressures around and how to deal with the consequences of those pressures in a politically charged and contested environment. It is one thing to talk in a neutral, scientifically detached way about trade-offs, as if one trade-off is just as desirable as another, but when we are talking about the health of at-risk groups versus the prosperity and well-being of society at large, difficult choices have to be made that will inevitably harm people. This pandemic has magnified the importance of the consequences of various trade-offs.

Therefore, ‘coping with complexity or ‘adapting to complexity has limited traction in a crisis of this scale. We don’t want to adapt to or cope with it; instead, we want to ‘transform’ or ‘go beyond’. The most effective way to do that is to network and invest in protocols for connecting. If there is anything we should learn from this pandemic, it is that expertise is a social phenomenon and that if knowledge is lacking, we need mechanisms and strategies for connecting the various bits of scattered and incomplete pieces of knowledge that we have. There are strong tendencies for acting in our own short-term interests, but these tendencies need to be counteracted in an all-encompassing crisis such as this pandemic and the climate crisis. As Adam Tooze recently wrote in *The New York Times* (Sept. 3, 2021): “The challenge for a progressive globalism fit for the next decades is both to multiply those crisis-fighting networks — into the fields of medical research and vaccine development, renewable energy, and so on — and to make them more democratic, transparent and egalitarian.”

NDM and RE theorizing would do well to heed this challenge.

10.3. Implementing resilience engineering and safety II

thinking into organisations: Reflections from two different approaches to the need to learn from every-day work

By Pedro Ferreira (Novellus Solutions)

The main focus of this session was to explore the challenges experienced in implementing RE and Safety II thinking from the perspectives of two different approaches. These two approaches adopted a similar starting point by pursuing the enhancement of the ability to learn from every-day operations (WAD). The disparities resulted mostly from the way the two approaches were structured, built around their different contexts of application, and how they coped with different constraints, limitations and business expectations.

The first approach presented was the experience of the Learning and Improvement Team (LIT) at American Airlines. The main challenges and achievements of some two years of work on this project were presented by the LIT. The second approach was the one developed under project Confidus. The concept and its current state of development were presented.

The American Airlines project is essentially built around uncovering WAD through either debriefing interviews with pilots, or direct flight observations. This provided a precise time and space on which to focus data collection. Project Confidus

contrasted this by aiming to develop a more generic approach that could facilitate the discovery of every-day work, regardless of the industry and the time and place of the work context. Both projects faced the same fundamental challenge of building a workable structure and process for data interpretation. This alludes to the ever-difficult question of how to describe a “non-event”. In fact the problem is much more complex than that, as this is more about building an understanding as rich as possible of the context around that “non-event”. For both projects, the focus is on the work itself and not its outcome.

Keeping with the premise that the aim is to learn from WAD, but rather in the scope of more conventional safety thinking, the focus on “events” brings a unique opportunity to narrow-down the work context that needs to be investigated, and the event itself makes it possible to define a clear purpose for that investigation (i.e. to find out why, how, who...). When dealing with “non-events” (or every-day work), alternative means of establishing realistic boundaries for data collection must be found. But perhaps the real challenge emerges from the lack

of a clear purpose to drive the analysis and sense-making of that data. In the face of an “event”, the purpose (almost) naturally becomes to explain how that came to happen. When and how does a “non-event” become an “event”, in the sense that an organisational or business-wise purpose emerges and enables sense-making from that “non-event”? The answer to this ought to be quite straightforward as the purpose of any element in every-day work would be to fulfil a known operational need. However, it often seems difficult to understand why people do what they do, and this is perhaps the most outcry evidence of the gaps that have come to exist between WAD and WAI.

LIT has met the challenge of structuring and interpreting data by systematically categorising information according to a set of different “potentials and “proficiencies”. These were the outcome of an extensive development and revision work, which was mainly guided by empirical knowledge and pilot expertise. In this sense, the fact of having pilots developing a learning system for pilots was put to very good use and has proven to be successful. In just over two years’ time, the project

has facilitated the interrogation of every-day work to inform various levels of decision-making. LIT's work has been embraced by the organisation and the team has recently nearly doubled its size.

Project Confidus follows a different path by considering data gathering as an open and continuous process, as opposed to a discrete moment, during which a given flight operation is revisited. The LIT approach has the advantage of generating a time and place for reflection, which can be considered a fundamental condition for any learning to take place. Ensuring that such opportunities for reflection take place constitutes one of the key challenges for Confidus, as data tends to be gathered under a great variety of conditions, ranging from ideas and comments raised during a worker's time-off, to observations that can be made during and at work.

The openness of Confidus data collection also renders its processing and analysis an even greater challenge. Developing a pre-defined structure such as the one developed by the LIT, to support a systematic analysis also becomes increasingly harder. This challenge is being addressed through the use of a communication platform that enables the development of customised topics and categories of information, depending on the industry and work context at stake. As the project further develops and the volume of data

increases, this is expected to be combined with the use of Artificial Intelligence solutions, thus enabling scalability and the exploring of further analytical possibilities.

Confidus is at much earlier stages of development than the LIT project, and there is yet no evidence of an effective impact in terms of learning experiences. However, shifts in organisational mindsets and practices, in particular relating to communication, have been registered. This was described as a shift from the "one-way" communications that most reporting systems tend to foster, towards a multi-way and more conversation driven kind of communication. In practice, Confidus has introduced the perception that any information communicated has the potential to generate responses and reactions, both from the hierarchy as well as from peers. This has created a sense of accountability on how and what is communicated, which in return encourages a reflection process that may resemble that which is made possible through the LIT approach.

Focusing on WAD implies looking at "what is there", as opposed to "what may not be there". In the latter case, existing standards and a wide range of metrics may tell us whether or not something is missing (or that it is non-compliant). One of the initial challenges for those who venture off in learning from every-day work is the lack of these

normative references, against which data gathered can be assessed and interpreted. In addition to that, there is naturally much more to look into and to look for, then when singly looking for what is wrong or missing. The challenges of gathering, processing and making sense of data are therefore far greater. However, the two approaches briefly discussed here, illustrate the potential to be explored, once such initial challenges are overcome. Learning opportunities can be fuelled by an incredibly wider diversity of possibilities, and such that build on a much more precise and complete understanding of real operations, as opposed to singly relying on their formal description and representation (WAI). Perhaps more interestingly, this is a potential that may grow exponentially as data accumulates and one that may also continuously evolve and keep pace with the dynamics of real operations.

This reflection does not aim to report on the discussions that took place during the REA-NDM-ICSI-FONCSI Symposium in June. It is rather an additional contribution from someone who has had the privilege to follow the growth of the LIT project with some proximity and has been involved with the Confidus project since its birth. Additional information and references can be found in the following table, along with the names of those who contributed to this session during the Symposium, and to

whom I would thank for inspiring
this humble reflection.

10.4. Societal resilience today and the steps needed to move forward

By Amanda Hellström, Sweden

Under the theme Societal resilience, preparedness and reconfiguration, various examples were presented of how society can relate, adapt and prepare for disaster scenarios or pandemic situations. Common to all presentations were health care issues. Everything from organizing care from prehospital stage to providing adequate hospital care, how a pandemic situation can be managed at nursing homes or how the public can be invited to discussions about the measures taken at community level in connection with the COVID-19 pandemic, through so-called Citizen Audit for Resilience and Preparedness (CARP) - with the aim of anchoring the measures, creating transparency, responsibility, and clarity.

However, society's interests in resilience should not be limited to health and medical care issues. A growing problem, not least in view of the recent IPCC

report from the UN Climate Panel, is the various climate changes that can have a direct impact on all infrastructure in society and on our health. The working methods that have been developed so far to deal with various forms of problems, and which we experienced through our presenters Sheuwen Chuang (Taiwan), Taro Kanno (Japan) and Simon Gill (United Kingdom), will need to be implemented and scaled up - possibly also adapted to other societal stakeholders and domains, so that we can achieve a flexible but safe structure for our societies. Not only considering health issues, but also transportation, water, and power supply as well as communication. The ability to innovate among researchers within resilience engineering is good, the important task now is to implement this in our societal structures so that an application also takes place.

10.5. Facets of Curiosity

By Gary Klein, United States

Unfortunately, there are many different practices that can interfere with curiosity. They include overconfidence, different kinds of pressures such as guilt, fear, anxiety, and threats. Instructors often discourage curiosity by asking closed questions, focusing on procedures, emphasizing memorization, discouraging questions and class discussion, and using ridicule. On the positive side, instructors can elicit curiosity by posing questions, by creating suspense (e.g., who will win an election), showing trainees that the gap in their knowledge is manageable. Most importantly, instructors can alter their mindset — instead of criticizing students who make a mistake, instructors can themselves become curious about why the mistake happened.

Loewenstein identifies several features of curiosity. It is superficial and transient and intense and impulsive. It is transient in that it reflects attention, and when

attention is captured by something else, curiosity disappears. It can be intense in that people will work to satisfy their curiosity despite being hungry or thirsty. And it is impulsive — something can evoke curiosity and stop us in our tracks.

Most contemporary approaches view curiosity as a motivation to fill a gap. It could be thought of as an information gap, a sensemaking gap (trying to find order, to see patterns), a mental model gap, a plausibility gap in a sketchy explanation. We needn't worry about which of these types of gaps is operating because they overlap so much. What matters is that we are dealing with a motivation to fill a gap.

Curiosity is an intellectual force — a motive and an emotion — that drives many of the macrocognitive processes, especially sensemaking, problem detection, attention management, uncertainty management, discovery of insights.

10.6. The Emerging Talents workshop 2021

By Elleke Ketelaars, Switzerland, and Sahinya Susindar, United States

It is 2021 and the world is trying to reimagine life as the COVID-19 pandemic continues to disrupt the old “normal”. The NDM and REA communities also re-imagined elements of their symposiums and the “Emerging Talents Program (ETP)” was one of them. While a portion of the community met in-person at Toulouse, France for the REA/NDM/FONCSI symposium, the ETP was held as a virtual event for the first time in 2021 and was a combination of NDM’s doctoral colloquium and REA’s Young Talents program. This year, the ETP was a one-day workshop for select Masters and PhD students within the field of Resilience Engineering (REA) and Natural Decision Making (NDM) that took place during the REA/NDM/FONCSI symposium. Twenty students from Australia, Belgium, Brazil, Canada, France, Greece, Israel, Malta, the Netherlands, Norway, Sweden, Switzerland, the United Kingdom, and the United States met under the auspices of renowned experts (mentors) in the domains of Resilience Engineering (RE) and Natural Decision Making (NDM). During this one-day workshop, the students were given the opportunity to present their work to prominent researchers in the field and solicit feedback from experts and peers. This year’s ETP was well attended with 18 mentors and 20 students.

The mentors for the NDM 2021 workshop were Gary Klein, Rhona Flin, William Wong, Jan Maarten Schraagen, Wendy Jephson, Neelam Naikar, Julie Gore, Cindy Dominguez, Emilie Roth, and Laura Militello. The mentors for the RE 2021 workshop were Erik Hollnagel, Sidney Dekker, David Woods, Sudeep Hegde, Jane O’Hara, Gesa Praetorius, Anthony Smoker, and Mike Rayo.

In adapting to a virtual format, it was determined that splitting the workshop into two segments, pre-workshop and workshop will enable maximum opportunities for participation from students and panelists across the world.

The pre-workshop was designed as a 3-minute thesis (3MT) format wherein students were asked to prepare a three-minute presentation of their dissertation/thesis to present to the ETP organizers who would then provide individual feedback for the students to use as they prepare for the final workshop. The 3MT format involved a three-minute presentation accompanied by just one slide on display (see figure 1 for an example). Students were asked to use these three minutes to provide an overview of their research work leading up to their thesis/dissertation. These presentations took place in groups of 6-7 people. The pre-workshops were guided by the ETP organizers and REA/NDM

experts, Sudeep Hegde, Olivia Brown, Riccardo Patriarca and Joel Suss, who shared their valuable experience as mentors supervisors, providing each student with constructive feedback and preparing them for questions they could expect from the experts.

The final workshop was held on the 21st of June. Students were asked to pre-record a ten-minute video to present their work to the panel of experts. The videos were played live during the workshop and each student presentation was followed by feedback and questions from the experts. The 2021 group of students was not only diverse in terms of geographical representation, but also covered a wide range of research domains including healthcare, artificial intelligence, Human-AI collaboration, oil & gas, ports, maritime, emergency incidents and response, law enforcement, teamwork, and surface transportation.

Through their research presentations and during the discussions, participants in the RE group widely acknowledged the need for understanding systems before changing them. The majority of contributions in the RE workshop showed the ambition to inform design through better system understanding in their research. One of the major cautions provided by the experts

concerned this giving prominence to primarily analytical contributions. The mentors confronted the group with the need of thinking one step ahead, and trying to already think about the system's adaptive capacities for the future. A burning question remained how to evaluate the consequences of interventions.

During the final day of the REA/NMD/FONCSI symposium,

the emerging talents, for the year 2021, were invited to briefly share their experience with the other participants of the conference. The ETs focused on the feedback they received from the experts and how they envisioned addressing it in their future research. One of the participants: "Based on the discussion with my mentors during the workshop, I realised that I also need to consider the context or external factors that may be causing performance variations

at the front end. Therefore, I plan to extend my current framework to consider these aspects."

The RE/NMD workshop was never intended to be the end of this journey, but the start of new connections, interactions, and collaboration. Some ETs have gone on to join the organising committee for the next Emerging Talents workshop to keep this pursuit successful.

Understanding everyday work in petrochemical facilities

Traditional safety uses a small portion of the total experience base

Unwanted outcomes

Planned Outcome

Positive Surprises

Measures:

- Violations
- Near misses
- Slips
- Trips

Measures:

- How?

What about the 99.999% of the time in which things go right?

Do we understand why success is the rule and not the exception?

The way to make the red part (unwanted outcomes) on the left smaller is not by making it impossible for things to go wrong (as we've done almost everything in that regard already). We make the red part smaller by making the white part bigger: focusing on why things go right and enhancing the capacities that make it so. Figure by Kelvin Gerns.

Means-ends Hierarchy of a procedural system

Overall System Goal
 Operational Goal
 Task Goal
 Step Goal

Replacing a level control valve

Task Goal

Isolating upstream flow Isolating downstream flow Removing an LCV and putting a new one

Step Goal Step Goal Step Goal

Functional Requirements (PASTA)

Pre-condition	Actor	Space	Temporal	Apparatus
M101-10 is open (flow)	A single operator	At M101-10	Not too slow	With bare hands or tools

PASTA Framework

Key takeaways from the workshop:

1. Explore factors other than procedure interaction that can describe performance variation
2. Expand the current PASTA framework beyond the step/task goals

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Figure 1. Example of a single PowerPoint slide used during the pre-workshop by Atif Ashraf.

11.

Compounding disasters

February 2022

A word from this issue's editor

by Lida Z. David, Greece, the Netherlands & Changwon Son, USA

The Resilience Engineering Association started off on a simple mission: Connect the experiences and know-how of practitioners and academia to promote and incorporate resilient operations. Now more than ever, our community is called to investigate and understand complex challenges, as well as design and implement RE and Safety solutions to major problems of interest.

This newsletter issue sets out to explore the concept of compounding disasters: concurrent events or cascading strenuous incidents that call for prolonged resilience; all of which are becoming increasingly prevalent in our social, business, and political systems. Through a series of short articles, we aim to provoke discussions and debates on the challenges brought about by these compounding events, and foster conversation on the solutions that can stem from a Resilience Engineering perspective, by introspecting on what happened, while anticipating what the future will bring.

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11.1. Unique challenges of recent compounding disasters and the role of Resilience Engineering

By guest editor Changwon Son, Ph.D., CSP, Assistant Professor, Department of Industrial, Manufacturing, and Systems Engineering, Texas Tech University, Lubbock, Texas, USA

Communities in the world have experienced or witnessed increasing risks of disasters. Since 1980, the US has sustained over 300 climate-related disasters that caused overall economic losses of \$1 billion or larger (inflation-adjusted, US NOAA, 2022). Not only that, but the frequency of disasters has

Katrina in 2005, the combined costs seldom exceeded \$100 billion. Since 2005, the economic consequences of disasters have been increasing rapidly. One of the worst records in US history was marked in 2017 when Hurricanes Harvey, Irma, and Maria hit the US and Puerto Rico, resulting in a total loss of \$346

earthquake and tsunami in Fukushima, Japan (2011), or the disastrous hurricanes that hit the US (2017).

In addition to the increasing frequency and impact of disasters, recent years have seen a new challenge: compounding disasters. A compounding

also increased. In 1980, only an average of 2.9 large-scale disasters (with over \$1 billion losses) had occurred annually. In the last three years (2019-2021), the average number of disasters has reached an average of 18.7 disasters per year. Economic losses incurred by weather-related disasters have also skyrocketed. Before Hurricane

billion. A similar tendency has been reported with respect to the whole world. According to a report published by the United Nations Office for Disaster Risk Reduction (UNDRR, 2018), the global economic losses incurred by disasters have steadily increased. Some major catastrophes are the earthquake in Sichuan, China (2008), the

disaster initially meant cascading events—one incident leading to another incident. For example, the earthquake and resulting tsunami struck a nuclear power plant (NPP) in Fukushima, Japan. Consequently, the NPP lost the core cooling capacity of the reactors and eventually radioactive materials were released into the environment

(Hasegawa et al., 2016). These days, compounding disasters represent multiple, concurrent incidents where one event makes it more difficult to respond to another, and vice versa (Potutan & Arakida, 2021). One common example of compounding disasters is the concurrence of the public pandemic (i.e., COVID-19) and other types of disasters such as wildfires, winter storms, droughts, hurricanes, volcano eruptions, and chemical explosion (e.g., ammonium nitrate explosion in Beirut, Lebanon in 2020). Such compounding events bring in unique challenges that were not seen often in the past. First, compounding events make it even more difficult to allocate resources that are already limited and oftentimes insufficient. Emergency medical service (EMS) providers, for instance, have to deal with patients from everyday incidents (e.g., a car crash) and those with COVID-19. Second, a response protocol for one disaster may not be compatible with another concurrent disaster. Wildfires that occurred in California, US caused thousands of evacuees who needed to be put in shelters. However, collocating the evacuees also raised concerns about increased risks of virus transmission. For another example, urban search and rescue (USAR) specialists were deployed to the city of Beirut in the aftermath of the massive chemical explosion.

However, the USAR specialists had to follow a quarantine policy that prevented them from conducting immediate search and rescue operations. Third, compounding disasters make it more challenging to manage the information being fed by multiple sources and coordinate multiple agencies and organizations. Emergency managers have to process a constant influx of new information, including misinformation and rumors, from different sources and integrate them into meaningful intelligence. As multiple agencies operate concurrently, it may be challenging to prioritize response goals and objectives to be accomplished. For example, providing shelter to hurricane evacuees would be a priority to Red Cross; however, a public health department would prioritize individual evacuees' risks of getting COVID-19 infection.

Experts anticipate that the current pandemic will not be over (Phillips, 2021). Moreover, there is no guarantee that a similar global pandemic will not occur in the future. This means responding to compounding disasters would be a new norm for many communities, if not all, in the world. Addressing compounding disasters is a multidisciplinary effort and there must be a role for resilience engineers to play in such an

effort. As resilience engineering scholars claim (Hollnagel et al., 2011), lessons must be learned from the past and current responses to compounding events. Specifically, the focus of learning needs to be on adaptations that take place at different parts of an organization (e.g., sharp ends) and sources of success and failure in the responses. Lessons on adapted decisions, improvised actions, rebounds, and workarounds against the unique challenges from compounding disasters will fade away if they are not adequately observed, documented, and analyzed. Such lessons, if learned well, will help us better anticipate future compounding disasters—imagine a COVID-25 pandemic and other simultaneous events—and prepare for expected threats and even unexpected hazards. Then, the knowledge of our future threats and their impacts will let us monitor current preparedness (e.g., resources, plans, communication, decision-making policy) and identify gaps to be filled out.

Resilience engineering since its inception has contributed to addressing various socio-technical system problems such as healthcare resilience (Hollnagel et al., 2018). In the face of increasing disaster risks and unique compounding disasters, disaster resilience has become another goal of communities in

the world, including us—resilience engineers.

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11.2. Nurses' utilization and extension of adaptive capacity in sustaining hospital care during the Covid-19 pandemic

By Dana Womack, Ph.D., RN, FAMIA, and Christine Jefferies, MSN, RN, USA

The Covid-19 pandemic was a shock to hospital work systems around the globe. Over a short period, hospitals experienced a dramatic shift in the type and volume of services required by the populations they serve. All but the most urgent of outpatient services stopped while the most severely ill Covid-19 patients were admitted to receive acute or intensive care services.

In addition to collaborating with many professionals in establishing patient plans of care, Registered Nurses (RNs) are responsible for around-the-clock care delivery. Therefore, nurses' continued presence is critical to sustained hospital operations during the Covid-19 pandemic. Nurses utilize professional judgment to anticipate, monitor, and respond to ever-changing patient needs, and they are recognized as ardent patient advocates. For the 20th year in a row, nursing has been named America's most trusted profession (Gallup, 2022). In this article, we explore the utilization of RN adaptive capacity, specifically initiative and reciprocity, in sustaining patient access to hospital care during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Shocks and surprises

RNs are accustomed to high work tempo and variable patient demand as baseline characteristics of the hospital work environment. Nursing theorist Patricia Benner describes nurses' ability to concurrently absorb, respond, and react to dynamic situations as thinking-in-action (Benner, 2009). Thinking-in-action involves clinical foresight and the skilled know-how of managing a crisis, which enables nurses to adapt to a wide variety of clinical, technical, and logistical challenges in everyday clinical care. Nurses' baseline ability to think-in-action contributed to graceful extensibility during the early days of the pandemic. As time went on, repeated shocks to the system created situations in which hospital organizations and individual nurses needed to make adaptations that were beyond the routine adaptations that nurses make in everyday clinical care. Although Woods' (2015) term sustained adaptability conventionally implies a longer timescale, the phenomenon of a work system changing how it adapts in the face of recurring surprises and adaptive shortfalls seems to apply here as well.

The global Covid-19 pandemic has presented hospital-based nursing work systems with multiple challenges, including a sudden increase in demand for patient care services, beds, ventilators, and personal protective equipment (PPE). Staffing patterns were highly disrupted as elective surgeries were canceled in anticipation of caring for an influx of patients with a highly contagious virus. Physical spaces were converted into new, makeshift patient rooms. Ancillary departments experiencing staffing challenges reduced service hours while shifting additional tasks to nurses. RN availability decreased as staff quarantined after exposure or called in sick after contracting the Covid-19 virus. RN availability further decreased as they left to become traveling nurses, retired early, or left the profession altogether. Vaccine hesitancy was an unexpected surprise that in some cases led to resignations or layoffs.

As the pandemic continues, nurses continue to draw from their own adaptive capacity in response to personal, patient care unit, and organizational pandemic-related pressures.

Concurrently, hospitals are experiencing high staff turnover and weakening of the clinical “bench” as experienced staff leaves the bedside. In turn, hospitals must compensate for this growing experience gap by securing agency staff, hiring new nurses, and providing extra support to new graduate nurses whose in-person training rotations may have been abbreviated due to the pandemic.

Nurse initiative and reciprocity

Amidst this crisis, RNs have displayed considerable initiative (Woods 2019) in recognizing that organizations’ typical plans, and even their contingency plans, did not fit the demands of a global pandemic. Although nurses’ willingness to adapt without explicit authorization is not novel behavior, new instances of authority decentralization facilitated the extension of this effort. Examples of RN initiative in dynamic replanning include willingness to re-use personal protective equipment in the first wave of the pandemic, volunteering to redeploy from procedural areas to medical-surgical and intensive care units, and offering extra support to patients whose family members could not be at the bedside due pandemic-related hospital visitor restrictions.

During the Covid-19 pandemic, RNs also demonstrated

remarkable reciprocity, committing to mutual assistance and being willing to expend their limited resources to sustain delivery of high-quality patient care, with the implicit understanding that other agents (e.g., peers, nursing management, hospital leadership, the public) would do the same (Woods 2019). Examples of pandemic-related reciprocity include nurses’ acceptance of the risk of caring for patients with a novel and highly contagious virus, working extra hours to support colleagues and sustain high-quality care, and taking on additional time-sensitive tasks such as respiratory therapy treatments and blood draws when ancillary departments needed to reduce service hours due to lack of staff. RNs skipped meals to keep up with the pace of work and risked bringing the virus home to children, elderly parents, and immunocompromised family and friends.

Consistent with their reputation as the most highly trusted profession, nurses’ willingness to exercise initiative and reciprocity has been assumed, and some would say taken for granted, during the pandemic. However, nearly two years on, RNs, alongside all humans, may be realizing a finite capacity to exercise reciprocity. RNs who extended themselves during the pandemic expected their

organization to mutually support them by providing the staff and physical resources needed for high-quality inpatient care, and allowing them to take overdue vacation time. When staff and physical resources were scarce, reciprocity was extended as nurses continued to work in short-staffed units, worked extra hours, and helped onboard temporary float and agency staff. As RNs continue to experience understaffing and high work intensity, and as organizations telegraph the necessity of care delivery model changes to reduce labor costs in the future, nurses may begin to perceive a lack of organizational reciprocity. Indeed, despite high demand and high public trust, a reported 22% of nurses are considering leaving the profession, citing insufficient staffing, intensity of workload, emotional toll of the job, and lack of perceived support at work as driving factors (Berlin, 2021). Frontline workers in at least one state find themselves needing to engage with their state legislature to advocate for nurse-informed safe staffing levels during the current and future protracted public health emergencies (State of Oregon, 2022).

Such proposed regulations and career decisions of individuals hold potential for additional shocks to hospital work systems and new shocks for local communities. If hospitals are

unable to secure adequate numbers of nurses to satisfy organizational or regulatory requirements, hospital beds may need to be temporarily or permanently closed, thus reducing patient access to care. Notable unknowns remain, including the success of hospital-at-home pilots and whether sufficient numbers of college students will continue to choose nursing as a profession. We anticipate that both nurses and healthcare organizations will continue to adapt how they routinely adapt to changing situations for some time to come.

Concluding thoughts

In this short commentary, we explored concepts from the field of Resilience Engineering (RE) to contextualize the experience of RNs during the Covid-19 pandemic. Nurses' superlative expressions of initiative and reciprocity contributed to graceful extensibility in the hospital setting, but the number of nurses considering leaving the profession suggests that their adaptive capacity may be nearing exhaustion. To better understand the nature of eroding workforce adaptive capacity in the setting of protracted strain, we perceive the potential for fruitful collaboration among members of the RE and organizational psychology communities, particularly to increase our understanding of how repeated

shocks may change individuals' willingness to exercise initiative and reciprocity as time progresses under both nominal and extraordinary circumstances.

In our next article, we will discuss the applicability to this situation of an organizational psychology theoretical framework that has recently been used to explain employee burnout in meaningful work professions such as nursing. You may wish to brush up on your Woods & Wreathall (2008) because the framework proposes a familiar-looking stress-strain curve!

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11.3. Resilience Engineering research activities in South Korea

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Two new safety issues-Safety-II and resilience engineering (RE) have been attracting much attention in South Korea. Here, I would like to introduce the following briefly: (1) how Korean safety engineers and researchers currently look at the concepts of Safety-II and RE, (2) what activities have been done in relation to Safety-II and resilience engineering so far in South Korea, and (3) what plans are being made to advance the state of the art of Safety-II and RE in South Korea.

As is known, Safety-II has emerged as a new safety concept in response to the motivation of overcoming the limitations of traditional safety concept called Safety-I, which include overreliance on deterministic causal models and root causes, find-and-fix approach, bi-modality assumption of safety, and so on. Safety-I defines safety as a condition where failures are minimal or absent. However, Safety-II defines safety as a condition in which successful outcomes continue or a condition where such successful outcomes are maximized. Although both of them can result in the same result, which is the minimization of wrong outcomes, they have fundamentally different concepts

and approaches to enhancing system safety. While Safety-I focuses on how to minimize failed situations, Safety-II aims to guarantee successful situations continuously on the basis of understanding how successful outcomes are obtained. For this, Safety-II emphasizes that safety professionals should monitor a working system and its surroundings vigilantly and proactively respond to various changes in the system and the environment, while always concerning about system safety. RE is a new practical discipline to ensure system resilience, which is the ability of a system that achieve its functional purposes, adapting to unexpected conditions as well as expected ones. RE aims to develop the principles and methods that are needed to enable a system to function resiliently. Associating RE with two different safety concepts, we can say that RE aims to proactively manage system safety through a synergistic integration of Safety-I and Safety-II.

Steven Shorrock wrote a short article titled 'What Safety-II isn't'. This article summarizes several myths or misconceptions that safety professionals can have. From my experience of working

with Korean safety professionals, I can say that a lot of them had those myths and misconceptions as well when they first met Safety-II and RE. First of all, they had an idea that Safety-II aims to replace all the things of Safety-I. As you know, this is never the truth; Safety-II is a new concept that emerged to supplement the shortcomings of Safety-I. Thus both of them should be used appropriately depending on safety concerns and contexts. Most Korean safety professionals had had opinions that Safety-I has critical limitations and cannot be effectively applied to several work domains, and thus a new alternative should be developed. Accordingly, they might first think that Safety-II aims to discard all the things of Safety-I. The second common misunderstanding that they could not dismiss easily was that Safety-II looks only at successful outcomes. I think that they had a misunderstanding because Safety-II emphasizes the examination of successful outcomes. As Safety-I is not concerned with a large number of everyday successful outcomes, Safety-II claims that they should be understood thoroughly to understand how they can be obtained. Nonetheless, Safety-II does not focus only on successful outcomes; they are concerned

with all of the possible outcomes. Another typical misconception among Korean safety professionals was that Safety-II is only useful in a complex socio-technical system such as air traffic control systems. Although Safety-II can have many advantages when they are applied to a complex system, its concepts and methods can be reasonably used for any type of work domain. However, many Korean safety professionals have had a more accurate understanding of Safety-II and Resilience through several conferences, workshops, and tutorials during the last decade. Currently, one of the most critical safety issues in South Korea is the adoption of 'The Serious Accidents Punishment Act (the SAPA)' law passed by the national assembly on January 8, 2021. After the introduction of this law, all of the companies in South Korea are concerned with how their safety management systems should be established and operated to satisfy the requirements stipulated in the law. Regarding this, a lot of Korean safety professionals currently agree that Safety-II and RE can be viable means to deal with this issue.

There were several academic societies related to safety, including The Korean Society of Safety, Korean Society of Disaster & Security, Korea Institute of Construction Safety, and so on.

However, there was a strong need for establishing a new academic society in order to promote the academic research activities and practical applications of Safety-II and RE and to disseminate the usefulness of applying systems approaches to safety issues, including Safety-II and RE, in South Korea. On the other hand, a new academic society was also needed to offer a place where safety professionals working in different work domains, such as nuclear power plants, healthcare systems, manufacturing systems, and rail systems, can meet and discuss their domain-specific or domain-independent safety issues, based on system thinking and approaches. Under these academic and industrial needs, a new society 'Korean Society of System Safety (<http://systemsafetykorea.org>)' was established on June 2, 2019. This society aims to enhance the resilience level of all of the companies and organizations in South Korea by the effective use of system safety engineering concepts, models, and methods, including Safety-II and RE. So far, this society had led several RE research and consulting activities in South Korea. Some examples include: (1) establishing a systemic strategy to introduce innovative safety concepts and methods, (2) development of practical methods of using Functional Resonance Analysis Method for accident

investigation and risk assessment, (3) development of processes and methods for assessing the resilience level of an organization based on Resilience Assessment Grid (RAG), (4) improving the system for evaluating safety activity level of public institutions in Korea, and (5) Assessment of resilience and safety culture of a power generation company and suggestion of practical ways of improving its resilience and safety culture. In addition, this society has held several tutorials and workshops to make Korean safety professionals acquainted with Safety-II, RE, FRAM, RAG, and so on. This society has much contributed to the community of Korean safety professionals so that they can have a right understanding of Safety-II and RE, and can think about several ways of applying them to their safety problems.

I expect that The Korean Society of System Safety will serve as a key hub for promoting academic research activities and industrial projects in the fields of Safety-II and RE in South Korea. I can list some plans to be implemented by this society. They include: (1) developing a FRAM model of two healthcare work systems, which are intensive care unit and emergency department, (2) applying FRAM to the identification and organization of decision requirements needed for coping with severe accident

situations in nuclear power plants, (3) instructing industrial safety professionals in the third generation accident analysis methods such as FRAM and AcciMap, (4) Investigation of industrial accidents by using FRAM, AcciMap, and STAMP, and (5) developing industry-specific

key assessment questions for the four abilities (monitoring, responding, learning, and anticipating) of a resilient system.

I hope that Korean safety professionals will establish an active collaboration network

with anyone in the world who is interested in Safety-II and RE. I would also like to request REA members to have continuous interest in the academic and industrial activities to be conducted in South Korea.

11.4. Want to better understand resilience? Study homeostasis!

By Gil Regev, Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne | gil.regev@epfl.ch, Switzerland

Hollnagel (2006, pp. 17-18) defines the challenge for resilience engineering as the necessity to “understand when a system may lose its dynamic stability and become unstable.” Resilience is therefore the maintenance of dynamic stability. This is all very well, but dynamic stability is also known by another name, homeostasis. Walter B. Cannon coined the term homeostasis in the 1920s, describing it as (Cannon 1929):

“The highly developed living being is an open system [...]. Changes in the surroundings excite reactions in this system, or affect it directly, so that internal disturbances of the system are produced. Such disturbances are normally kept within narrow limits, because automatic adjustments within the system are brought into action, and thereby wide oscillations are prevented and the internal conditions are held fairly constant.

Compare Cannon’s description with Hollnagel’s (2006, p. 16) :

Complex systems must, however, be dynamically stable, or constrained, in the sense that the adjustments do not get out of hand but at all times remain

under control. Technically this can be expressed by the concept of damping, which denotes the progressive reduction or suppression of deviations or oscillation in a device or system (over time). A system must obviously be able to respond to changes and challenges, but the responses must not lead the system to lose control.

These descriptions are obviously very close, if not identical. The main aspect of a resilient system, as much as that of a homeostatic system is its ability to keep disturbances within narrow limits, in Cannon’s terms, or to dampen them, in Hollnagel’s terms. Cannon himself used the term resilience to explain homeostasis (Cannon 1939, p. 244):

The possibility of obtaining further insight into the organization which makes for resilience and endurance in spite of the fell blows of circumstance lies in an examination of the ways in which stability is achieved.

Referring to research done by his predecessors, Cannon explains the dynamic nature of this stability. It is therefore surprising that resilience engineers rarely

mention homeostasis. One of the reasons may be that homeostasis is understood as the maintenance of a rigid state whereas resilience is seen as bouncing back and dynamic. But this rigidity is not what Cannon had in mind at all. Here is how he explained the choice of the term Homeostasis (Cannon 1929):

Objection might be offered to the use of the term stasis, as implying something set and immobile, a stagnation. Stasis means, however, not only that, but also a condition; it is in this sense that the term is employed. Homeo, the abbreviated form of homoio, is prefixed instead of homo, because the former indicates “like” or “similar” and admits some variation, whereas the latter, meaning the “same,” indicates a fixed and rigid constancy. As in the branch of mechanics called “statics,” the ‘Central concept is that of a steady state produced by the action of forces; homeostatics might therefore be regarded as preferable to homeostasis. The factors which operate in the body to maintain uniformity are often, so peculiarly physiological that any hint of immediate explanation in terms of relatively simple mechanics seems

misleading. For these various reasons the term homeostasis was selected.

Notice the painstaking care he takes in choosing a term that does not imply “rigid constancy” or “simple mechanics” to maintain it. Cannon (1929) defined “six tentative propositions” that form the basis of homeostasis. The first proposition is not only important for resilience engineering, it even addresses the subject of this newsletter, i.e. compound problems, or compounded instability (Cannon 1929):

In an open system such as our bodies represent, compounded of unstable material and subjected continually to disturbing conditions, constancy is in itself evidence that agencies are acting, or ready to act, to maintain this constancy.

It is these agencies, acting or ready to act, that are the source of constancy and therefore of dynamic stability and resilience. It is through this constancy of their internal conditions, requiring slight instability (Cannon 1929), that systems maintain their resilience. A simple and obvious example is to examine what is our resilience when our internal conditions are not maintained constant. Our body temperature varies slightly and constantly. But if it drops below or rises above very strict limits (e.g., lower than 34 or higher than 40) we lose most of our resilience.

Homeostasis describes how systems remain more or less the same by limiting the effects of perturbations that can appear in their internal or external environments while needing

these perturbations in order to limit them. It provides a precise explanation of what it means to bounce back. Bounce back to what? To the limits that make the system remain more or less the same.

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11.5. Resilience Engineering now has a Technical Committee at the International Ergonomics Association (IEA)

By Tarcisio Saurin, Associate Professor, Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul | saurin@ufrgs.br

As of January 2022, the International Ergonomics Association (IEA) has a new Technical Committee (TC) dedicated to Resilience Engineering (RE). In line with core human factors and ergonomics values, RE is systems-oriented and regards variability as an inevitable portion of everyday work, which is responsible for both desired and undesired outcomes. Therefore, the new TC acknowledges RE as a mainstream approach, which can benefit from and contribute to the broader human factors and ergonomics community. The main objectives of the TC are as follows:

- Contribute to IEA conferences and other relevant conferences with special sessions, workshops, papers, and group meetings on resilience engineering;
- Collect and share educational materials (e.g., lectures, videos, serious games) on resilience engineering;
- Foster the dialogue of resilience engineering practitioners and

academics with the broader human factors and ergonomics community; and

- Support international collaboration on resilience engineering.

Main planned activities for 2022 – 2024:

- Annual course(s) on RE with lectures given by leading international scholars. The course(s) will be run in the distance learning format;
- Webinars, occasionally in collaboration with other scientific associations; and
- Special session/workshop at the 2024 IEA Triennial Conference in South Korea.

Examples of topics of interest

- Resilience engineering (RE) and safety management
- Safety-II
- Measurement of resilient performance
- RE, climate change, natural and man-made disasters

- Modelling of complex socio-technical systems
- Contribution of digital technologies and industry 4.0 to resilient performance
- Cyber-resilience
- RE and sustainability
- RE and naturalistic decision-making
- Design for resilient performance
- Design and management of resilient procedures, policies, and rules
- Regulations and resilient performance
- Leadership for resilient performance
- Management of trade-offs in socio-technical systems
- Cross-learning opportunities from RE in multiple sectors – e.g., healthcare, aviation, maritime, manufacturing, construction

Contact Tarcisio Saurin for more information or to join this Technical Committee

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11.6. Resilience Engineering in numbers: Data from the 2021 symposium

By Francesco Simone and Antonio J. Nakhal A., Sapienza University of Rome, Italy
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REA is glad to present analytics on the last 15th Conference on Naturalistic Decision Making & 9th Symposium on Resilience Engineering held in hybrid mode in Toulouse, France; Columbus, USA and online from 21 to 24 June 2021. This report contains data about participants, speakers, and contributions (manuscripts or posters) presented during the symposium. The report includes three main pages.

The first one contains general summary about the event and data by country and type of submissions.

The second one illustrates the keywords of the event as proposed by authors in their manuscripts.

The third one presents detailed description of each manuscript data, including abstract, complete authors list, keywords, etc.

Every dashboard has been designed and tested to ease usability. It allows users to interact with data dynamically: to apply filters or highlight one or more fields; to drill-through for in-depth investigations. In other words, you can filter each graph or table according to your needs!

Whether you are an experienced Resilience Engineering scholar and attended the symposium, or unluckily you missed this one, or whether you are new and just approaching the field...we trust you will find the content handfual and informative!

11.7. Final balance on REA-NDM-ICSI-FONCSI 2021

By **Pedro Ferreira, Ph.D., Secretary of REA**

Last year's symposium was a challenge in many ways. In our best tradition, we worked to explore new possibilities in the face of radical uncertainty and entirely novel conditions. The outcome was considered by many attendees a success, but important problems and shortfalls should be reflected upon. One of such shortfalls was the failure to deliver the recordings from sessions. Foremost, we would like to sincerely apologize to our community for not delivering on this, and provide a more clear explanation.

As we approached the dates of our event and during the event itself, it became clear to us that their VCS (Virtual Conference System) was at least in part, yet lacking the robustness to undertake the impact with a full scale, worldwide, and diverse event such as the one we were bringing together. However, EasyChair demonstrated outstanding support throughout the whole process and, despite many problems experienced in the day before and throughout the first day of the event in particular (i.e. people not being able to access their accounts, sessions...), the continuous presence of EasyChair support was greatly appreciated and valued by us and all attendees in general.

Overall, our impressions were positive. Problems will always emerge no matter what, and there's nothing better than having a capable technical team to rely upon.

The one single problem which has radically changed these rather positive impressions emerged long after the conclusion of the event:

EasyChair staff assured us on various occasions, that VCS sessions would be recorded and that these recordings would be made available to attendees. This was after all, vital for an event that engaged participants across all time zones. Many of our participants were in fact relying on these recordings to follow parts of the program that were taking place within time zones too far apart from their own.

We enquired with EasyChair staff on how and when recordings would become available, not only during the days of the symposium but on numerous occasions between then and now. We were systematically reassured that they would be ready soon, or even "within the week" of that given contact. To our great disappointment, months went by and nothing ever came through. The utmost unacceptable was the fact that eventually, EasyChair staff no longer bothered to reply to our emails. For months now, we have experienced a total silence that has no reasonable explanation and does not live up to any of the standards EasyChair advertises on its website.

We have tried on many occasions to obtain from EasyChair a justification as to why recordings were never delivered, but mostly why such unacceptable customer care. We have come to accept their silence as an indicator that any further attempt to resolve this in a positive way is a waste of time and that it is time to move forward with the firm belief that we've exhausted all means within our reach.

Work on the 10th Symposium on Resilience Engineering has begun and information will be coming very soon!

11.8. A recap on 10 REA Newsletters: Looking back and moving forward

By Lida David, University of Twente, The Netherlands | L.david@utwente.nl

REA is officially celebrating the release of 10 REA newsletter issues, so delve with us into a journey looking back on the topics we've explored so far, before moving forward to so many more interesting newsletter issues to come! Our newsletters aim to keep nurturing connections and collaborations all over the world, and as always, continue to promote and distribute state-of-the-art research, activities, perspectives, and plans for the development and incorporation of Resilience Engineering in practice.

In our very first issue, released in October 2019, our newsletter set out to promote the notion that maintaining, adapting, and improving system operations is not anymore considered only a challenge for safety-critical

domains such as healthcare or transportation. Resilience Engineering is embodied in any complex, interconnected socio-technical system found in business, academia, or industry that needs to function safely, effectively, and efficiently in the face of change and adversity. And the topics explored in each newsletter emphasized that.

In every newsletter, we explore the world of Resilience Engineering starting from questions as simple as what is Resilience Engineering [1] and how it can be implemented in organizations [2], all the way into exploring how to build resilient cities [3], utilize data to promote resilient potential [4] or improve disaster response by investing on the interaction of citizens with emergency organizations [5]. REA also

explores topics regarding how RE and Safety-II apply in the fields of cybersecurity [6], oil and gas industries [7], aviation [8, 9], healthcare [10, 11], construction [12, 13], environmental disasters [14] emergency management operations [15] or even entertainment companies like Netflix [16].

REA newsletters incorporate 'concept corners', aiming to stimulate debate over controversial issues such as diverse views and understandings of resilience, connections between resilience and risk, or the need for slack resources (see newsletter [archive](#)). The REA community further arranges RE webinars with thought leaders in the field, which can be found on the [REA website](#). Be on the

lookout for future webinar promotions on the REA website!

We are honored to have you as members of this community, and we look forward to more talks,

events, and collaborations! It is our mission to further expand and collaborate with practitioners or academics from all around the world who are interested in sharing or debating

over current RE issues. Interested readers can always reach out to us for collaboration in future newsletters. Contact us at: rea-communications-team@googlegroups.com.

11.9. Book Corner | A Book Mistitled: A Review of Ten Patterns That Explain The Universe by Brian Clegg

Review by E. Asher Balkin & Dane Morey, USA

In his newest book, *Ten Patterns That Explain The Universe* (MIT press, 2021), a well-known science author presents an implicit argument for the driving forces behind the development and operation of the physical and biological world. Of note, he does not explore the cognitive or social spheres in any way, nor does he suggest what, if any implications, the patterns he does explore might have for thinking systems.

Cycling through his ten patterns: cosmic, background radiation, Minkowski Diagrams, particle patterns, Feynman Diagrams, the periodic table of the elements, weather patterns, number lines, (evolutionary) cladograms, the double-helical structure of DNA, and finally, symmetries, the author introduces his readers to a wide range of physical and basic bio-scientific research offering a brief introduction to the major scientist and thinkers as he does.

Critically, Clegg fails to distinguish between the underlying patterns themselves and the ways in which we typically visualize or represent them. Two of the most stunning examples of this phenomenon deal with Clegg's treatment of

the periodic table of elements and his exploration of cladograms. Rather than exploring the deeper sub-unit interactions, which we now know drive the larger, more emergent patterns we observe, Clegg becomes rightfully fascinated with depictions of those patterns.

Reaffirming his interest in visualizations, in his second chapter—Minkowski Diagrams, Clegg notes that the same principles which permit physicists to plot distortions in three-dimensional space onto two-dimensional plots also allow for the generation of maps that require the translation of three-dimensional objects onto two-dimensional surfaces. Interesting though this fact is, the author misses a critical opportunity to explain the deformities generated and inaccuracies introduced by such methods; even more critically Clegg fails to note to his readers that trans-dimensional plotting is only possible due to a far more foundational mathematical pattern—that of the regularity of integration between the units of the systems under study.

At several points in the text, Clegg seems to graze the deeper

question of what it means to be a pattern, how and why patterns form, and the relationship between patterns and the observer, but quickly retreats from addressing the issue. Admittedly the book is meant as an introduction to the topic, not a masterwork or graduate school discussion piece. Clegg attempts to walk a fine line, offering enough foundational information for the novice while providing a deeper insight to those with a deeper background. In the end, the text seems far better suited to the former. More knowledgeable readers will quickly bore of the isolated context of each chapter and the little attention paid to making connections among the patterns he does explore or seeking to recognize even the simplest of meta-patterns (patterns of patterns). In final assessment: an

interesting read, but not to be looked to for insight or thoughtfulness.

Clegg, B. (2021). *Ten patterns that explain the universe*. The MIT Press.

12.

The role and support of Resilience Engineering to organisations and frontline teams

September 2022

A note on this issue's editor

Guest editor David Provan, Australia

This issue discusses the role and support that **Resilience Engineering can offer to organisations and frontline teams**. Guest editor David Provan argues on the key milestones toward resilient organisations, and contributions from other pioneers in the field of RE explore processes to increase adoption of RE in healthcare, means to support frontline workers, and the hallmarks of practising High Reliability Organising.

The newsletter features a dedication manuscript to the life and accomplishments of Richard Cook, as the beginning of REA's initiative to honour Richard's work and legacy at the 10th Symposium on Resilience Engineering.

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12.1. Lessons from Assessing Organisational Resilience

By guest editor David Provan, Australia

In most organisations, the dominance of compliance-focused safety management approaches requires a concerted effort to deploy the insights from a holistic view of both traditional and contemporary theories to build the foundations for growing resilient capacities.

The inaccessibility of the scientific literature (indeed it is not written with the practitioner in mind) led to the creation of the [Forge Works Map®](#), which unpacks the last 100 years of organisational theory and safety science into the key milestones of the journey towards resilience. The key principles derived from this meta-research revealed that resilient organisations:

- Develop leaders with a safety motivation who care for every person
- Understand their own organisational logics and how they drive local action
- Set workers up for success in all operational objectives
- Understand the variation and complexity of work performance
- Closely monitor operations and reflect deeply on insights garnered
- Anticipate future operational scenarios and update their model of work

- Establish a priority for learning and support it with diverse practices
- Make continuous adjustments to goals, structures and resources

Over the past two years, Forge Works has worked with 18 organisations from a variety of industries not typically fitting the description of High Reliability Organization theory (i.e. mining, manufacturing, automotive, energy, transportation, construction and technology) to conduct assessments of, and identify opportunities to grow, their organisational capacities for resilient performance. The assessments, performed using the model established in the [Forge Works Map®](#), revealed both unique insights for each organisation and, despite the differing nature and complexity of these organizations, a clear trend of common challenges, including:

The persistence of safety work with no measurable impact on the safety of work

Focus on human error, the need to assign blame and punitive outcomes

Covert goal conflicts and the unintended prioritisation of production over safety goals

Insufficient allocation of resources for risk reduction

Under-specified critical risk management processes

Underinvestment in developing frontline workers' non-technical skills

A lack of capacity and capability within the safety organisation to support adaptive practice

Due to a general lack of understanding or guidance, past efforts to resolve these challenges typically focused on minimizing variability through robust systems of work and enforcement of compliance to those systems, with the benefits of contemporary safety management practices going unrecognised.

Collectively, the contemporary 'new view' theory describes that:

Error is normal, so **anticipate** performance variability as a normal part of executing work in complex settings, by ensuring free flow of information and ideation of future operating scenarios;

Context drives behaviour, so **monitor** normal work and what goes well, by exploring everyday work;

Blame fixes nothing and learning is vital, so **learn** about the gap between Work-As-Imaged and Work-As-Done, by facilitating learning from surprises and normal work; and

Management response matters, so **respond** to variability/local adaptations in a way to ensure work goes well, by supporting local practices, balancing frontline demand and reducing goal conflict through sacrifice judgements.

By viewing the new view theories collectively in this way, a way forward is revealed: organizations must learn to

accept the truths/realities described by Human & Organizational Performance and establish the objectives described by Safety II, before they can start to grow the capacities described by Resilience Engineering to achieve the objectives. However, there remains a need to educate industry that the traditional management approaches must first be implemented and working. Indeed, scientific management led to documentation of operating practices and safety culture focussed attention on the importance of organisational

learning from incidents. These, among other factors that are described in the [Forge Works Map®](#), are essential prerequisites on which to build complementary or evolutionary resilient approaches, e.g. critical steps and learning from normal work, respectively.

Organizations operating in complex and dynamic contexts can only be better supported on their journeys towards resilience when the destination is agreed upon, milestones are set and, of course, a map is used to guide the way.

12.2. Increasing the adoption of resilience engineering in healthcare – overcoming practical and systems challenges

By Professor Janet Anderson¹ & Dr Satyan Chari^{2,3}

¹Professor of Human Factors, Department of Anaesthesiology and Perioperative Medicine, Monash University

²Adjunct fellow, Centre for Human Factors and Sociotechnical Systems

³Program Director – CEO Bridge Labs, Clinical Excellence Queensland

The field of resilience engineering (RE) offers novel conceptual and practice tools to tackle long-standing quality, safety and performance issues in healthcare. However, healthcare improvement teams are often comprised of nurses and other healthcare professionals. Typically, they have an intimate understanding of the challenges facing frontline staff, but they often do not have training in safety science or human factors methods. They instead rely on targeted training programmes and accepted practices driven by policy makers and regulators. Compounding this, policy makers and regulators often require them to use methods such as root cause analysis in ways that do not foster deep understanding or effective improvement. For example, the requirement to complete recommendations within short timeframes and use restrictive report templates can mean it is not possible to analyse the problem deeply or frame effective solutions that require in-depth planning or approval for more resources, both of which

take time (Anderson & Watt, 2020).

In my conversations with quality improvement teams, they often express frustration with these processes and their limitations, and are aware that there is a need for a different approach. Similarly, healthcare practitioners are usually positive about adopting Resilience Engineering (RE) because it speaks to their experiences of clinical work and acknowledges the challenges inherent in navigating a poorly designed complex system. It also provides a language to articulate why flexible adaptation is a core part of clinical work, to discuss decision-making and trade-offs in the context of system complexity, and to change the focus from individual behaviour to system design. Positive reactions to RE is not, however, sufficient to galvanise adoption into practice.

There are two main challenges in translating RE into healthcare improvement practice. First, it requires an understanding of system thinking and the ability

to move beyond focusing on individual patients to think about the system as a whole. These ideas are difficult to grasp, especially as the theory and evidence are still evolving and there are multiple ideas which can be confusing and time-consuming to untangle. Second, there are few practical, easily understood methods for implementing RHC into healthcare practice (Anderson et al, 2016). The philosophical underpinnings of RE developed, as is the case in many fields, without considering translation into practice. Research in this area has focused on analysing the dynamics and interactions of complex systems such as emergency departments or hospitals. This has greatly increased our understanding of complexity but harnessing these insights for improvement is now essential, but not straightforward. The idea of understanding work-as-done is attractive, but how can that understanding be captured and used as a basis for improvement? Similarly, learning from what goes right sounds much more

positive than focusing on errors and adverse events, but when most things go right how is it possible to learn from everything? In the vignette below, Dr Satyan Chari, a healthcare improvement expert and experienced RE practitioner shares some of his strategies for navigating potentially difficult conversations when introducing RE to clinical colleagues.

The challenge of the solitary RE practitioner in healthcare settings – Satyan Chari

I periodically find myself in conversation with clinical colleagues on the threshold of undertaking improvement work. I am often that lone voice suggesting a different approach. This used to be a daunting exercise but as I have refined my approach, it has also become much easier. I find some strategies work better than others when it comes to creating the openness necessary to introduce RE into improvement work, even when speaking with teams without any knowledge of the field. Here are **my three top tips** ([link to YouTube video](#)) for getting a foot in the door more often and being more effective in translating your advocacy into meaningful forward movement.

Translational tools are needed which have been designed for healthcare users specifically and which address their unique problems and challenges. Tools

need to speak the language of healthcare quality improvement and be designed to fit with how quality improvement works in practice. Alongside such tools the key principles underpinning RE need to be articulated so that practitioners understand the foundations of the approach and have access to a summary of the state of the science. This is important for ensuring that RE does not share the fate of other tools and methods that have become simplified and distorted in practice. Methods often become corrupted in practice as they are adapted to fit common misunderstandings and shortened to yield quick results. RCA is an example of a method that does not support effective learning because of the way it has been implemented (Peerally et al, 2017).

The CARE-QI Handbook (Anderson & Ross, 2020) was written to fill this gap. Based on the work of the Centre for Applied Resilience in Healthcare (CARE), it describes how to apply RE to quality improvement, and is based on the empirical work of the Centre in emergency and older peoples' care. The introductory section begins with an overview of the need for RE and articulates the core principles of the approach. The CARE model is then described which proposes that the need for adaptation is driven by misalignments between demand

and capacity (Anderson et al, 2016). Five resilience activities that underpin system adaptive capacity are then explained – anticipating, responding, monitoring, coordinating and learning. These underpinning principles of misalignments, adaptations, and the five resilience activities, are crucial for implementing the method, so it is important that they are articulated clearly and using healthcare language. For example, what we have termed resilience activities have previously been called resilience potentials or systemic potentials (Hollnagel, 2017) which is arguably confusing and not the language usually used when describing a work. Clarity is essential for effective implementation.

The Handbook outlines a four-step method for quality improvement based on RE principles. The first step, project setup involves determining the suitability of the project for the approach. We recommend CARE-QI is particularly helpful for difficult and complex problems which cross system boundaries, and/or which may have been resistant to previous improvement efforts. The aims, scope and system boundaries, and project team are then considered. The second step is to capture work-as-done in the system of interest using a combination of methods such as

observations of clinical work, document analysis, interviews with a range of staff and quantitative analysis of relevant data. These are then analysed in a third step to identify the resilience or adaptive capacity in the system, including common misalignments between demand and capacity, which adaptations are used in response and how effective they are, and how

each step. The worksheets structure the problems faced at each step and provide a way to think about effective and defensible approaches.

This method provides guidance for designing interventions based on a deep understanding of the work system which must be completed before deciding on interventions. This is different to

provides a strong evidence base for predicting how interventions will work in practice, and for sustaining interventions over time. Implementation and evaluation can follow established methods. The recommendation to evaluate both patient outcomes and resilience outcomes is also important. If the intervention is designed to target, for example, the activities

effectively the five resilience activities are carried out. This analytic step should reveal opportunities to improve quality through either reducing misalignments, improving adaptations or increasing the effectiveness of the resilience activities, or a combination of these. The final step is to co-design interventions to address the problems and challenges identified and to decide on outcome measures. For each step, there is guidance, tips for success and worksheets for documenting the outcomes of

most QI methods that start with the intervention design. Analysing the work system from a resilience perspective provides a strong basis for understanding the challenges and adaptations that occur, and for tailoring interventions to the context to support workers as they try to make the system work. Interventions will focus on improving system design by reducing misalignments and reducing the need for adaptations, or by increasing adaptive capacity through the five resilience activities. This

of co-ordinating and responding, outcome measures should include measures of those activities because theory suggests that strengthening these activities will boost resilience and lead to better patient outcomes. Resilience outcome measures will typically be a mix of qualitative and quantitative indicators. For example, responding could be assessed using response time measures, patient and staff experience, adverse reactions due to delayed response, or a mixture of these.

The Handbook is freely available online and the hope is that it will be used by improvement teams and iterated on the basis of feedback from users. We are interested in supporting and coaching teams to use it so that we can gauge how it works in practice and how it can be expanded and improved.

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12.3. Supporting frontline worker resilience during storm response

by Beth Lay, Director of Safety & Human Performance, Lewis Tree Service

Think about the many times when your organization has been under stress. In the utility vegetation management industry, we don't have to look far. Over the past two years, we have faced a global pandemic, back-to-back active storm seasons, labor shortages, and supply chain interruptions to name a few stressors. When stretched, the goal for all of us is to recover quickly and emerge stronger. One key to success is proactively monitoring and acting on early warning signals that we are approaching an overload situation or safety boundaries and have a plan to adapt.

Lewis Teams are first responders after major storms. Convoys of bucket trucks move into storm ravaged areas to remove trees from downed power lines. In this article, I'll share strategies to increase resilience during storm response.

What is pinging?

We use the term "pinging", which borrows from the echo location of a submarine, to refer to actively sending out our sonar and probing for signals of organizational stress.

A few years ago, when I first joined Lewis, I went out on storm with a seasoned division manager. We were at a large

fairgrounds parking lot where Lewis trucks were staged awaiting tickets to perform work. What was immediately noticeable was that the Lewis teams, deployed from different regions nationwide, were not talking to one another. Fast forward: we now create structure and practices to build teamwork, collaboration, and engagement when on storm. We are one team with one mission.

During Hurricane Ida, our operations leadership formed a new, cohesive team and assigned field leadership from the diverse teams who mobilized to lead the new team together. This allowed our boots on the ground, some of whom were deployed for weeks, to maintain stronger coordination and a high level of consistency during a situation of extreme variability.

Our mission was to "de-stress the frontline". To accomplish this, we proactively looked for signs of stress. For example, leaders actively "pinged" for signs of fatigue: Quieter. Chatter goes down. | Mood changes. Upset easily, grumpy. | Tradeoffs to get more sleep: skip breakfast, eat quick lunch to take a nap | Drink energy drinks, increasing caffeine intake. | Begin making mistakes, taking shortcuts. | Lose focus. General forgetfulness increases. | Delayed reaction time. | Nod off

(micro-sleep). | Muscle cramps. | Pace is slower.

We implemented teammate-to-teammate peer checks. Leaders asked, "how did you sleep?" (a better question than "are you tired?") We did everything within our power to support our teams with a clean place to sleep in situations where lodging was scarce. We set the pace for our safety.

Signals of increased stress

We analyzed the After Action Reviews that the teams working storm submitted daily for trends and risks. This enabled us to figure out where and what type of help was needed in real-time. We were able to increase attention across the team and act to manage areas of high risk (e.g., large piles of debris stacked beside roads, long commutes, roads that were ok yesterday are not ok today, etc.)

We pinged frontline leaders and crews, asking "what are you most concerned about right now?" "How are teams being pressured?" "How are moods?" "How are things at home?" We listened for weak signals. Are people who have never worked storm too quiet?

As risk increased (as we got closer to safety boundaries), we lowered our risk tolerance, lowering our number to 2 on our

“uncertainty gauge” for raising stuff up (uncertainty = 1 means 100% certain and controllable, a 10 means we are highly uncertain and we have little control). We increased leadership touch points. We brought in extra safety and logistics support with goals of unloading the frontlines and bringing a fresh set of eyes.

Building reciprocity

Reciprocity is when a team is willing to sacrifice their individual goals to help a larger group achieve theirs. We see this clearly with utilities who are willing to provide mutual aid to others facing widescale outages and infrastructure devastation. We also witness it closer to home.

Years ago on storm calls, we would hear stories of trucks rolling into a hotel parking lot only to discover the rooms had been given away or already heavily loaded operations leaders trying to find rooms on the way to storm. Sometimes teams would sleep in their trucks. At our corporate office, we embraced our mission during storm is to destress the frontline. Fast forward: People from our corporate office now actively take on new support roles including travel planning, providing meals, and sourcing hotels during storm response, putting some normal job duties on hold. We added flexibility and adaptability to reduce the pressure where we can—knowing that a good night’s sleep is critical to keeping our

craftworkers safe. And we never say, “not my job.”

Build it and they will come

Reciprocity is present when teams anticipate another’s needs and offer help without being asked. We are now beginning to experiment more deliberately with corporate and operations spending a “day in the life” together to build knowledge of codependent roles. What’s it like for our general forepersons to work out of their trucks all day long? Conversely, what’s it like to respond to a multitude of varying IT requests all day long? These days are designed to give each team a better idea of what the other does and their challenges so they can codesign better solutions and offer each other help.

Four Strategies for Managing Overload

Overload is the relationship between demand and a system’s inability to meet that demand. Since systems differ among organizations, there may be things that larger companies handle easily but overwhelm smaller companies. Storm work provides many concrete examples. When managing one storm, an organization may be okay; however, two or three simultaneously may lead to overload. As an industry, we need to build flexibility to respond effectively.

Add more resources

During storm, utilities are willing to make significant financial investments outside of

established budgets to restore power as quickly as possible. Mutual aid kicks in to rapidly deploy line and tree trimming crews from other areas. Craftworkers work 80-hour weeks to meet demand. We send in extra leaders and logistic support.

Shift load

When deployed on storm, managing expense receipts by traveling crews is difficult; however, the urgency remains. We shift the resource load to another team who can reprioritize their work and assist. Loads can be shifted in time, too. If a storm is coming, schedule preventative maintenance sooner to ensure vehicles are road worthy.

Create slack

When all hands are on deck, loosen policies or extend due dates to give team members more leeway. Proactively raise credit card limits to avoid inconveniencing traveling crews. In the office, instead of auditing every report, spot-check for accuracy.

Shed load

When capacity is strained, review your list of priorities, and decide what can be skipped or postponed. As corporate teams shift to new roles during storm response, take something off their plates.

In closing

Most organizations have unofficial early warning signals of a system under strain but few well-defined strategies for

noticing and managing these effectively. The key is to define your organizational pings and

have strategies and capacities in place before they are needed.

12.4. High Reliability Organizing is about how you handle possibilities

by Laurin Mooney, USA

Do your eyes glaze over when somebody says “High Reliability Organizing” or “HRO?” Do you find your body tensing, preparing for a recital of the “5 Hallmarks” that again leave you unclear on what “practising” HRO means?

Well, I am on a mission to counteract that experience because I believe the thinking and actions of HRO are 100% critical for success and safety in our increasingly complex and uncertain world. If you have been curious but not clear about HRO, my wish is this article leaves you more confident and convinced.

I have included quotes from *Managing the Unexpected* 2001, (first edition, yellow) by Karl Weick and Kathleen Sutcliffe because I can't say it better, and I try to get everyone to read the book, it's just that good.

1. Believing more is possible than we can plan for or imagine.

(If you are a Resilience Engineer reading this, please excuse this first paragraph I know I am preaching to the choir).

HRO flows from a humble but optimistic assessment of the realities of performing high-risk work in complex systems nested in a VUCA world. I sum up the HRO mindset like this:

- *We don't know everything, so, we can't plan for everything.*
- *Because of that, our systems are imperfect.*
- *We are imperfect humans, so despite our best intentions, sometimes we will fail.*
- *We can't imagine all the ways humans and the system can fail.*

Sounds depressing, and negative I know, hence the “Preoccupation with failure” hallmark. However, the mindset shift from probabilities to possibilities allows us to recognize that something not very probable but totally possible is happening (think Twin Towers or Los Vegas shooting, the list goes on). It is believing something is possible that allows us to see it.

“The trouble deepens even further when I kid myself that seeing is believing. That's wrong. It's the other way around. Believing is seeing.” p46

Embracing the humbling, scary conclusion of vast possibilities is exactly what propels the attitudes and actions for success. Best of all, it forces the idea that instead of being the problem, people are the solution! Let's look at what people

practising HRO do to be the solution.

HRO means asking “what could possibly be happening?”

2. Seeing as much as possible

Accepting that more is possible than what we can plan for or imagine means we know unexpected and unclear situations will arise. The strategy here is this:

“HRO's take deliberate steps to create more complete and nuanced pictures. They simplify less and see more. Knowing that the world they face is complex, unstable, unknowable, and unpredictable, they position themselves to see as much as possible.” p11

What are some deliberate steps to seeing as much as possible?

First, cultivating a culture where everybody knows it's always safe to share a question, concern, or idea. High Reliability means “all voices on deck.” Silence stops HRO in its tracks. I call employee silence the elephant on the road on your high reliability journey. Why?

“People who refuse to speak up out of fear enact a system that knows less than it needs to know to remain effective.” p13

(Uh, oh...I think we have some work to do here...)

Second, is understanding, and improving individual and collective sensemaking, the process by which we come up with a plausible understanding of the information we are literally “sensing” around us. We are trying to figure out what something *means*. This process *precedes* decision-making and if it is not accurate, then there is a much greater risk of the decisions being ineffective or worse.

“Reluctance to simplify interpretations” means a mindful approach to news. In. People practising HRO are extremely careful to welcome new information. They don’t dismiss it by saying what I call the HRO no-no phrase, “it’s probably just...”

Instead, they stay open to many possibilities of what it might mean, invite diverse perspectives, and are willing to update their understanding when presented with new information. (There are many individual and group dynamics

that get in the way of accurate sensemaking, but that’s for another day). Suffice it to say, they respect the process and are deliberate about removing the obstacles to it.

They ask “what could this possibly be...”

3. Acting as early as possible

How many times do we look back at a failure only to see people did act, but it was too late...? A third way HRO addresses possibilities is the speediness and vigor of their response to weak signals of possible trouble.

“The key difference between HROs and other organizations in managing the unexpected often occurs in the earliest stages, when the unexpected may give off only weak signals of trouble. The overwhelming tendency is to respond to weak signals with a weak response. Mindfulness preserves the capability to see the significant meaning of weak signals and to give strong responses.”

Engaging ambiguity or “acting to learn” by probing a situation immediately allows early learning

so people can improvise solutions when the problem is small and can still be contained. Our natural dislike for uncertainty often leads to a weak response or delay in responding to weak signals. Training, cultural, and system support is needed to help people adopt curious and action-oriented behaviors. Improvisation and engaging front-line expertise wherever it is found is the norm.

They ask “what can we possibly do right now to learn more?”

In summary

Believing more is possible than we can plan for or imagine by embracing the challenges of complexity, positioning yourself to see as much as possible by creating psychological safety and improving sensemaking, and acting as early and strongly as possible in response to weak signals can all be embedded in our mindset and work practices.

For a free download of an infographic with questions to get you started [Click here](#)

12.5. The Career, Accomplishments and Impact of Richard I. Cook: A Life in Many Acts

The following manuscript has been prepared by Richard's friends and approved by his family, sharing the way he has impacted our lives: [Richard Cook: A life in many acts](#).

On behalf of the Resilience Engineering Association, an initiative is underway to honour Richards' work and legacy. The primary purpose will be to support members of the community interested in Resilience Engineering. This includes a dedicated session during the Resilience Engineering Symposium to acknowledge Richard's contribution to the field. More information will be available on our website.

12.6. Book corner | Resilience in a Digital Age

Editors: Florinda Matos, Paulo Mauricio Selig, Eder Henriqson, Brazil

In recent years, resilience has become a buzzword as it is cited regarding climate emergency, disaster management, impacts of digital transformation, and, more recently, the COVID-19 global economic crisis.

But what is resilience? How can we benefit from integrating digital transformation into this framework? And in what areas might it be most relevant? Some of the world's leading experts in resilience were invited to participate in this book and discuss possible answers to these questions

12.7. 10th symposium on Resilience Engineering

26-30 June 2023, Sophia Antipolis, France | Resilience at frontiers, frontiers of resilience

The Resilience Engineering Symposium is coming back to its place of birth in the sunny south of France. And what better time to go back than to celebrate the 10th edition of the symposium. There is much to revisit and reflect upon, and diverse future possibilities to explore. The theme for the 10th RE Symposium – Resilience at frontiers, frontiers of resilience – aims to focus on precisely that.

Using concepts of frontiers, borders, or boundaries in Resilience Engineering involves a paradox. On the one hand, they are omnipresent; on the other hand, the nature of boundaries and their neighbourhood are rarely elaborated. Boundaries can be broadly defined as categories of difference that create distinctions between systems. They are a line between order relationships that creates a fuzzy zone-like phenomenon of inclusive disjunction identified as “neither/nor” or “both/and.” The goal of the symposium is to deepen the description of relationships between resilience capacities and boundaries:

- What is the nature of boundaries to be considered in Resilience Engineering studies?
- How do their nature and dynamic affect adaptive capacities?

- How do other boundaries (organisational, national, or geographical) affect systems’ adaptive capacities?

Guidance for the submission of academic and industrial contributions will be available at the symposium website: <http://www.resilience-engineering10.org>

Important dates

- Symposium dates: 26-30 June 2023 (including two days of workshops)
- Paper submission deadline: 30 October 2022
- Acceptance: 15 December 2022
- Final revised paper deadline: 30 January 2023
- Industrial testimony and visual representation studies deadline: 15 January 2023

What else will be happening at the RE 10th Symposium

Honouring Richard Cook’s work and legacy

We would like to bring your attention to a very special initiative that is to be launched at the RE 10th Symposium. In line with the wishes of Richard Cook’s family and friends, *REA will be honouring Richard’s work and legacy through a dedicated session and other initiatives that will focus on supporting and funding work on RE-*

related topics. More information will be available as detailed planning progress but in the meantime, we would be very happy to hear any suggestions or thoughts on Richard’s work that you may want to share. Please [email](#) us what’s on your mind.

Young Talents Workshop

The symposium will also host a Young Talents Workshop! During this one-day workshop, Masters’ and PhD students within the fields of Resilience Engineering will have the opportunity to present their work to prominent researchers in the field. Find more details [here](#).

Executive Committee Elections

The pandemic has imposed unprecedented challenges and for the REA Executive Committee (EC), this has meant ensuring that the livelihood of our community would persevere. Throughout this very demanding period, the 9th edition of the symposium took place under a unique format and conditions, our website has seen a growing volume of activity from our members and from the wider public, a number of online initiatives were launched, and we also registered a steady growth of memberships.

Current members of the EC will (to some extent) remain involved in REA’s activities but it is time to give way to new ideas and views.

The 10th RE Symposium will be an opportunity to bring back our face-to-face General Assembly, during which elections for new EC members will be held. We would love to hear your thoughts on the future of REA and how you would see yourself

contributing. *We also strongly encourage all of our members to step forward as a candidate for one of our 6 EC functions* (President, Secretary, Treasurer, Young Talents, Communications or Membership Officer). For more details or

information please contact us via [email](#).

Come and join us at Mines Paris for yet another unique opportunity for open discussions and reflections!

13.

A collection of memories and research in memory of Richard Cook

December 2022

A word from this issue's editors

by Lida Z. David (The Netherlands) & Emily S. Patterson (USA)

This newsletter issue is a special tribute to the life and work of Richard I. Cook, as part of an initiative within the Resilience Engineering Association to honour Richard and the invaluable role he played in the foundation and progression of the field of Resilience Engineering. The issue includes a collection of memories and research from colleagues and friends of Richard's. A special thank you to everyone who contributed to creating this tribute issue, and who shared with us and the REA community precious stories and memories.

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13.1. Always be helpful, cooperate, and never do SWAG

By Emily S. Patterson, Ph.D.

My time as a Research Scientist at the Veteran's Health Administration Midwest Getting at Patient Safety Center was never supposed to happen. I had purposely avoided healthcare my entire career (as well as avoided marrying a physician on the advice of my mother). I was supposed to continue with my dissertation research on addressing text data overload in intelligence analysis. But...my verbal offer from Battelle disappeared due to a Reduction in Force over the weekend, and when I walked into my PhD advisor's office to seek guidance, there was Dr. Marta Render visiting David Woods to collaborate with him and Richard Cook on a grant to address patient safety.

Little did I realize how fortunate I was at the time. Richard was a truly exceptional mentor in every sense of the word, and he spent countless hours with me patiently teaching me the many gaps in my knowledge, clinical as well as about the fundamentals of resilience. I will share just three of the lessons that he taught me, all of which I try to follow many years later.

First, early on, Richard, David, and Marta all warned me that I needed to be prepared to feel

despondent once I learned how truly difficult it was to advance patient safety in the hospital environment. Analogies were made to the first stage of grief in learning that there were no silver bullets. At 50 years old, I feel like I now understand this deep in my bones, and sometimes I'm surprised that I still keep at it. Yet one of Richard's first lessons for me was: "Always be helpful." This statement was often combined with "Never be unhelpful or quiet." It sometimes went along with the idea that speaking truth to power is not only expected, but the only choice, and that choosing to be silent only meant that you could not be invited back. This advice was specifically given as I was entrusted at a young age with serving as a scientific advisor to The Joint Commission, in part based on his recommendation, and I have strived in every occasion to make at least one or two insightful comments at a time when they are needed – which usually means paying more attention to what others are saying than I might have otherwise.

Second, I attended a workshop organized by Richard with human factors representatives from all the major manufacturers of IV pumps to discuss patient safety.

Some of the initial comments from the representatives mirrored some of the defensive stances that were based in market competition and protection of the company from lawsuits or reputational damage. Richard took a deep breath, which usually indicated that something brilliant was forthcoming, and quietly reminded everyone in the room that it was highly likely that most of the people there would be hired by the person next to them when some companies bought out other companies. There was a noticeable shift in tone towards cooperation and technical expertise in human factors. Soon after that, Richard created a platform for me to share insights from military command and control, NASA Johnson space shuttle mission control, and 911 call centers and how I thought those might relate to IV pump design, implementation, and post-marketing surveillance in hospitals. At one point, I asked him if I should halt there as I had been dominating, and he said: "Keep going. This is great!"

Finally, one of Richard's most impressive skills was to identify my weak areas and perform an 'intervention' in a classy, kind, compassionate, but direct way.

As my early career opportunities expanded to more opportunities to provide insights as a scientific advisor that were beyond my years of experience, I had the tendency to indulge in giving advice that was beyond my base of knowledge. Richard told me in no uncertain terms: NEVER do SWAG (Scientific Wild-Ass Guessing). Basically, he was telling me that I should remain silent or say “I am not sure what would happen” if there were no human factors (or resilience) principles, evidence, or experience on a particular topic. As with so many things, once

Richard gave me the conceptual looking glasses to see SWAG, I unfortunately saw many examples of it being done, with great detriment to the design of policy of various types.

In this newsletter, we are fortunate to have remembrances from so many facets and epochs in Richard’s career. He touched so many and he is greatly missed, both professionally and personally. His two tribes are represented – physicians and human factors/resilience engineers. He had a truly international reputation, as

attested by his Israeli colleagues as well as his academic appointments in Europe. We were blessed at The Ohio State University to host his last chapter as both a physician and resilience expert, when he benefitted all of the students in the Cognitive Systems Engineering Laboratory as well as students in my own Leverage Point Engineering Laboratory, itself a legacy of Richard’s influence as it is in the College of Medicine.

13.2. Richard Cook's love for Taiwan

By Sheuwen Chuang, Taipei Medical University Hospital, Taipei, Taiwan

I was fortunate to have known Dr. Richard Cook, when I first participated in the Resilience Health Care Net (RHCN) meeting in Demark 2012. After Richard passed away on August 31, 2022, whenever I think of Richard's care and help for me, there is always an urge in my heart to write down his love and contributions to the world, specifically to Taiwan.

Richard visited Taipei Medical University in January 2016 after the Formosa Fun Coast Dust Explosion (FFCDE) occurred on June 27, 2015, in New Taipei City, Taiwan. A flammable cornstarch explosion caused injuries to 499 people. The 499 burn victims were transported to 36 hospitals. Despite the extreme patient surge and limited resources, the mortality rate was 3% (15 out of 499). Richard was very concerned about this event. When he visited the initial receiving hospitals for delivering talks, he always liked to ask the hospital's staff how they responded to the event after giving a resilience talk to the hospital.

Because of his encouragement and advice, we initiated an investigation proposal to study how the initial receiving hospitals responded to the mass

burn casualties beyond their surge capacity. It is the first research to explore disaster resilience from the resilience engineering perspective in Taiwan. He explained what questions should be asked in the incident investigation questionnaire, what I should conclude after the investigation, etc. He drew his ideas on the table paper during lunch, wrote a key measure as a safety index on a napkin after a talk, and listed the critical investigation questions to support my future interviews during a meeting (see figure 1, Richard Cook's handwriting). I felt that he wanted to give away all the relevant knowledge about incident investigation and resilience to me during such a limited visiting stay and let me know more about how to do well in an incident investigation.

Figure 1. Richard Cook's handwriting on table paper and napkins (left), and a piece of his meeting draft on right

He introduced me to Prof. David Woods to expand the research scale after he returned. With Prof. Woods' advice and support, the FFCDE's resilience studies acquired incredible advancement and accomplishments. As a result, Taiwan collected and analyzed the hospitals' staff and organizations' detailed adaptations to varied situations aftermath. The findings contribute to the potential improvements of Taiwan's emergency medical services system for large-scale mass casualties. Other disasters in Taiwan are greatly missed in this part.

Besides his support for the FFCDE project, Richard had a secret donation to support the recovery from the southern Taiwan earthquake, which caused widespread damage and 116 deaths in February 2016, just a few days after he left Taiwan. Because of Richard Cook's generosity and justice, he made the world a more human and brighter place. In honor of Dr. Richard Cook, the Taipei Medical University resilience research team wrote this letter to express our appreciation for his love and contribution to Taiwan.

13.3. The Radical

By Christopher Nemeth

Richard Irwin Cook was a software engineer, anaesthesiologist, researcher, and thinker. None of those terms captures his character as fully as “radical.” Richard Cook was a radical in the truest sense of the word: going to the root of what concerned him. This led to a constructive discontent. He was impatient with quick fixes that were conceived and implemented without any understanding of the underlying problem. He disdained those who acted without understanding and those who acted to create the appearance of doing something responsive.

Faced with so many instances of this, he saw how absurd it was to funnel time, energy, and money into fruitless pursuits. The physical evidence of this was his lab door that was festooned with cartoons by Gary Larson. They included a particularly appropriate one in which the Devil is saying “C’mon, c’mon— It’s either one or the other,” while holding a pitchfork to the

back of a sad soul considering two doors marked “Damned if you do” and “Damned if you don’t.”

Richard Cook could have chosen a more comfortable path and accepted an honorific title and adulation. Instead, he took the path of honesty, answering only to the toughest critic: himself. That required courage to stay the course, call out absurdity, and pursue what he knew was right.

He saw what others didn’t, even though the evidence was right in front of them. How information technology (IT) is a mismatch for clinical care, including simple infusion device interfaces that hide hundreds of states that no clinician could fathom. How patients who are less sick are bumped from an ICU bed for a sicker patient. How artefacts such as the resident sign-out sheet and Master Schedule for anaesthesia staff assignments could serve as a “way in” to gain a grounded understanding of that complex, emergent domain.

How medical organizations perform as a system, and deal with adverse outcomes that insightful investigation can improve. How all sharp-end operator decisions are made under uncertainty and in effect are bets about the future that are based on their understanding of the current situation. How “technical work” influences the provision of care, even though it is widely dismissed as simply “the way we do things here.”

Richard was able to publish in some venues and those works endure. What we can take from his example is more of a challenge than it appears to be. Following his example requires his intellect, courage to call out absurdity, and to forsake the need for recognition.

In the seven years I was a member of his lab, every day was an adventure; quirky, revelatory, and never dull. His vision enabled me to sharpen my own and seek the root of what matters.

13.4. Avoiding human error in the hospital: Mission possible?!

By Yoel Donchin

I met Professor Daniel Gopher just before the Passover Seder, which took place at my brother's home in Urbana, Illinois. I asked him: "What are you doing in life?" His response was: "I investigate why workers fall from a height, why carpenters lose their fingers." I had no idea what kind of scientist he was. As an anaesthesiologist, I did not perceive psychology as evidence-based or scientific (even though my brother was chair of the psychology department at the university). I told Danny that I had a problem. At my ICU at the hospital, we encountered on an almost daily basis that teams make mistakes and errors, sometimes by nurses and sometimes by physicians. Back in Israel, I invited the Technion team from the "Center for Human Factors and Safety at Work", where Danny was the head of the centre, to visit our operating room and intensive care unit. The team arrived one day, looked around, made notes and photos and interviewed staff. At the end of this tour, they stated: "We have visited factories and power plants and assembly lines, but chaos like that, we have never seen!" This was the start of my understanding that we need the help of "human factors engineers."

We applied and received a substantial grant, and we conducted the first study in 1986. Human factors students observed the ICU 24 hours a day and recorded their notes (on paper!) They were determining what an "accident" was. Simultaneously, a special form was designed for medical personnel to report and describe events that they have diagnosed as a failure or a near-miss incident. We submitted an abstract to the Human Factors society in Colorado (1989, Fig 1) and it was accepted, but the organizer did not know what section to place it in. The organizer created a "POTPOURRI" section, as healthcare was not one of the domains studied at that time. I was the only physician at that annual meeting of Human Factors. The paper topic was "The nature and causes of human error in the ICU" A year and a half later, I received an invitation to speak before a group at The Ohio State University on a letter co-signed by Richard Cook and David Woods. I kept showing the invitation to the university, with a date correction. (Fig 2) After the lecture, Richard and David took me to the Barnes & Noble campus bookstore and for an honorarium gifted me with the book titled "Human Error". In this

book, James Reason introduced the Swiss cheese model of accidents. Richard signed the book. (Fig 3)

Then my life changed.

The story of the paper after the conference is interesting enough as we decided to send it to the New England Journal of Medicine, where it was rejected because the journal "was not interested in medical error" and only accepted scientific work. (Fig 4) The rejection included twelve pages of recommended revisions and was recommended to send it to the Journal of Critical Care Medicine. We did this immediately **without making a single change**. A week later, I got a message (fig 5) asking "Why you did not make the changes recommended by the NEJM editor?" Finally, it was published and got me the ticket to Annenberg 1. I would not be surprised if Richard arranged the invitation to attend, as I think that I was the only anaesthesiologist who attended among a small number of other physicians, including Lucian Leape.

During my visits to learn from and consult with Richard, he took me to his apartment, which consisted of two rooms in a basement. There I stayed and ate

food he prepared for me while lecturing and shaping my thinking.

I was so naïve that, with hutzpah, I informed the director general of Hadassah Hospital that I would like to start a safety unit. It took him a few minutes before he agreed. So, for the first time in Israel, a conference with the logo “Avoiding human error in the hospital: mission possible?!” was planned. Richard agreed to come and give the keynote presentation to this group that is beginning to care about this unknown idea of “safety.” At the end of his unforgettable presentation, he took out his camera and took a picture of the audience from the podium. He said: “You are the safety group in Israel, as you all understand the issue.” (Fig 6) He was right!

Every visit to Richard’s Cognitive Technologies Laboratory at the University of Chicago after his transfer from engineering to anaesthesiology gave me the energy and new ideas to pursue implementation in Israel. I find that conferences are very expensive, and some are a waste of time, but being with Richard for a few days was truly inspirational. Of course, it was also wonderful to tour the campus, the library, and their

unbelievable bookstore. We established a regular video conference between our paediatric intensive care unit and Richard’s laboratory. He inspired me to study human factors and I joined Danny’s department as a graduate student. I left the operating room and started a full-time job at my hospital as a safety “expert.”

Richard and his wife, Karen, visited us in Israel, preparing his talks in our home (fig. 7 and 8) and later touring the holy places, including the Dead sea and of course the old city of Jerusalem (fig 9).

On one of his visits, when Richard stayed in our home, there was a mass casualty event at our hospital. I asked whether he wanted to come to observe with me as the mass casualty victims were on their way to the Emergency Room. His response was: “Sure!” His impressions and reflections on differences in approaches between our hospital and the United States were published in a 2006 book chapter in the book: *Resilience Engineering Concepts and Precepts*. The chapter starts with “A senior Israeli physician (DY) heard the detonation of the bomb at 07:10 and he drove with one of the authors (RC) to the

Hadasah Elin Karem hospital.” (page 210). It is a must-read. While I was at work, Richard didn’t say anything. He met my wife that came later to work at the information centre rather than in her room at the public health department, and he spoke with parents that accompanied their daughter to receive a CT scan. When I read the chapter it was the first time I realized what he had seen. Like the hero of Moliere, who didn’t know he was speaking prose, I didn’t know that the hospital had great resilience. The door was now opened for me to think differently.

I went with Richard and his family to a restaurant in Chicago. I joined him as he went to see his granddaughter at school (Fig 10, 11). I feel like I’ve lost a relative. A loved one. It has been my honour to be a part of his professional life.

A few months before he passed, I read a Hebrew poem that I felt I needed to share with Richard. Mike O’Connor read it to him when he was having challenges reading small print. I sent it after his death to Karen.

Do the songs soothe the pain?

13.5. Cognitive artefacts as a window into “ordinary” work

By Yuval Bitan, Ph.D.

The Cognitive Technology Laboratory (Ctl) was a unique research lab. Richard Cook assembled a multidisciplinary team of clinicians and human factors researchers that worked together on challenges clinicians face when working in healthcare systems. Richard, Michael O'Connor, Mark Nunnally, Chris Nemeth, and Allan Klock were the permanent members of the lab, which was housed in the Research Pavilion building at the University of Chicago. Visiting researchers such as Yoel Donchin, Sara Albolino, John Wreathall, Geva Greenfield (nee Vashitz) and myself joined for varied periods of times. For me, as a young researcher that had just finished his PhD, this was an opportunity not only to work with very experienced researchers but also to have direct access to the “field” – the operating rooms and the intensive care units of the University of Chicago hospitals.

One of the many challenges we studied was medication reconciliation. Medication reconciliation plays an important role in patient safety as it is a window into healthcare that highlights conflicting priorities and inconsistencies in patient care. One of the first things we learned was that medications were reconciled with respect to a

patient’s ongoing needs, not their prior or current medication list. When we started to study medication reconciliation, we used a cognitive artefact to represent the thinking process clinicians apply when performing this task. The idea was to use cards that represent medications and patient conditions from a real patient record, and to capture how clinicians arrange these cards on a table. In the first study conducted by Geva Greenfield we used a camera that was mounted above the table and captured the cards’ movements. In the following study we further developed our card sorting task (CaST) method and used software running on an Android tablet computer as a mobile platform to collect data from clinicians in the intensive care units. This allowed us to recruit 153 on-duty clinicians and improved our ability to analyze the cards’ positions. The findings from these studies were presented in three papers that Richard led. We concluded that clinicians apply various cognitive strategies while reconciling medications and medical conditions, and that clinical information systems should support multiple cognitive strategies, allowing flexibility in organizing information. Richard elaborated on this concept in his

2017 chapter “Medication reconciliation is a window into “ordinary” work” in the book “Cognitive Systems Engineering: The Future for a Changing World” that was edited by Smith and Hoffman. He referred to medication reconciliation as a seemingly simple task that must be carefully weaved into the processes and tools of the healthcare system. A system that did this well would generate good outcomes for its patients and resilience with respect to other vulnerabilities; a system that did this poorly could cause failures and degrade its resilience.

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Newsletter14

RESILIENCE ENGINEERING ASSOCIATION

LEARNING SYSTEMS

in aviation and beyond

March 2023

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FRESH DESIGN FOR **RESILIENT IDEAS**

The Resilience Engineering Association connects thousands of thought leaders, practitioners, and academics within the fields of Safety-I and II, Resilience and Crisis Management worldwide. Through our newsletter, our community is informed on state-of-the-art research, practices, challenges, and potential solutions for safe and resilient operations that span far beyond the individual, and delve into team, system, organisational, governmental, and societal issues.

Welcoming our redesigned newsletter, we celebrate its launch with a special issue dedicated to aviation, with guest editor James Norman.

And do not forget...

Registrations for the

10th symposium on Resilience Engineering are now open!

Follow instructions on our [website](#)

For other interesting upcoming events on resilience and safety [click here](#)

Enjoy your Reading!

Lida Z. David

REA Newsletter Editor,
on behalf of the REA team

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A WORD FROM THE EDITOR

James Norman, Ph.D

Welcome to Issue 14 of the REA Newsletter. Focusing on aviation, this edition sets out to explore two related constructs: learning systems for resiliency across domains, and using learning systems to capture Safety-II and resilience. Fourteen thought leaders from the resilience engineering and Safety-II community contributed to this edition, ranging from pilots, air traffic controllers, training experts, academics, and applied practitioners. They offer a depth and breadth of wisdom in their writing that I trust you will find valuable.

Aviation is both a fascinating and frustrating subject for resilience engineering.

On one hand, aviation folks have robust debates regarding high reliability (HRO) versus normal accident theory (NAT), Safety I versus Safety II, and so on. On the other hand, we have a near absence of accidents—a denominator of zero. Theorists like Cooper have vociferously raised the issue of a lack of empirical evidence to support the efficacy of theories such as Safety II. However, with such a lack of accidents, we barely have Safety I data to begin with. We are therefore left with a Gordian knot of trying to identify weak signals in Safety I incident data, or try to explore the variability in everyday work with robust Safety II data. Unfortunately, compounding the problem is that airlines operate at such thin financial margins that the resource allocation for Safety II is nearly absent, because it is not a regulatory requirement.

During the time our authors composed their pieces, a quartet of remarkable events took place in US aviation, pushing “resilience” into the headlines and discourse. Two of these events exposed organizational brittleness and collapse. Conversely, two revealed sharp-end performance success. Viewed as a composite, these events offer a timely background to the theme of organizational learning for this issue. Significantly, resilience (or the lack of it) was brought up numerous times in broadcast and print media, entering the public consciousness as it related to the aviation domain.

First, a Christmastime polar vortex delivered cold and misery to much of the US. Understandably, many airlines were affected.

However, Southwest Airlines was unable to recover their operation for more than a week, stranding millions of passengers and prompting a congressional investigation. The reason? A network system that held insufficient slack for disruption, and a manual (yes, manual) system of rostering crewmembers. Southwest CEO Bob Jordan apologized to customers and employees, saying the company had “swiftly taken steps to bolster our operational resilience and was undergoing a detailed review of the events” (MSN, 2023).

Two weeks later, the antiquated NOTAM system imploded. Still based on 1920s teletype technology, the NOTAM system is used to notify pilots of the safety of flight information. It apparently collapsed due to a contractor deleting a single file in a database. This led to a temporary ground stop of all flights and cascading delays of more than 32,000 flights. The US federal government took notice, stating “the F.A.A. made the necessary repairs to the system and has taken steps to make the NOTAM system more resilient” (FAA, 2023). The chairwoman of the Senate Commerce Committee added, “the public needs a resilient air transportation system” (US Government, 2023).

Two days after the NOTAM outage, a Delta 737 was departing runway 4L at New York’s John F. Kennedy Airport (JFK), and conducted a high-speed abort after an American Airlines 777 incurred across the runway. According to the NTSB, the Delta 737 came within 500 feet of the crossing runway (NTSB, 2023). An automated alerting system called ASDE-X alerted the tower controllers of the conflict, which resulted in a call to abort the takeoff. While commercial aviation communication is still handled over analogue VHF radio signals, there was sufficient capacity at that moment for the tower to transmit the dire warning. The Delta 737 pilots had enough alertness, and the aircraft had enough engineering capability to stop immediately.

Finally, as a bookend, Southwest was again in the news. During low visibility operations at the Austin-Bergstrom International Airport (AUS), a FedEx 767 performed a missed approach at low altitude, overflying a Southwest 737 by less than 100 feet, accord-

ing to ADS-B data. While this proximity has yet to be validated and the NTSB has not issued a preliminary report, this incident is profoundly concerning. The successful outcome of this event may have been due to technologies aboard the aircraft, including an Enhanced Flight Vision System (EFVS) and Mode-C transponder displays. It could also be attributed to something as simple as well-rested pilots who were at their best that day.

The preceding events may be bifurcated in this way:

The former two were blunt-end organizational failures that had been metastasizing for decades. When the system reached its limit, it was unable to provide adaptive capacity, and cascading failures followed. The boundaries for both the Southwest Christmastime fiasco and the FAA's NOTAM systems were in hindsight closer than previously imagined, due to lack of redundancies and reliance on manual systems.

The latter two events were sharp-end human performance successes, likely a result of decades of technological enhancements, training, and a bit of luck. When the human operators reached their limits, sufficient capacity was available to overcome the dire situations, even if such capacity was of mere seconds. Resilience was both a system property and an individual property in these latter cases.

The location of resilience was raised by Bergström et al. (2015) in a literature review of the topic, concluding that although resilience is usually conceptualized at the system-level, it has been better seen as an individual characteristic when empirically measured. It is therefore ironic that in the four aviation examples cited, (lack of) resilience was attributed to system-level failures, yet there was an absence of dialogue about resilience when it came to individual crew performance in JFK and AUS.

For this edition, we asked our contributors to explore how learning systems may be able to capture instances of resilience and learn in a double-loop fashion. Are our reporting systems designed to

capture resilient behavior? Aviation is heavily prescriptive...think regulations, training, and compliance. Given the stellar safety record previously discussed, we may fall a victim to our own success in a self-perpetuating affirmation that "if it ain't broke, don't fix it." However, a credible safety management system demands we seek continuous improvement. And the healthiest safety cultures are generative, able to challenge assumptions and the status quo.

Our 14 contributors to the 14th edition have diverse and varied expertise, ranging from the theoretical to the applied. It is my hope that the remarkable effort our authors made will help to move the needle in the aviation industry, and beyond. It was encouraging to see the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) recently infuse its updated guidance with over 30 references to resilience. The altruistic effort of the Resilience Engineering Association's (REA) newsletter and annual symposia will bolster these efforts as well.

James Norman is a B-767 pilot and holds a PhD in Aerospace Science from the University of North Dakota, where he is a faculty member. His dissertation focused on voluntary reporting (ASAP) and the factors that promote and discourage reporting, comparing pilots, dispatchers, maintenance and air traffic controllers. In addition to line pilot duties, he works on behalf of the Air Line Pilots Association (ALPA), teaching risk management, safety management systems, and safety leadership in aviation.

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Can We Continue to Climb the Mountain in Ballerina Shoes?

Understanding Normalization of Adaptation in Aviation

By Gitte Furdal Damm

When I started flying some 25 years ago in Scandinavia, aviation seemed more simple. Getting a job in an airline usually meant that the career path could be secured for the next 30-40 years, and the industry was known for its beneficial terms and conditions. Working conditions were characterised by a sense of stability and predictability – permanent bases, fixed roster, familiarised route-net, fewer procedures and less automation. Training was associated with classroom sessions, social interactions over dinners and an occasional beer with the chief pilot, which paved the way for relationships across the system, to be built and nurtured over time. Although this might seem like a slightly romanticised and simplified version of the past, we find ourselves in another aviation reality today.

Aviation has grown in complexity and is today characterised by multiple uncertainties emerging from a constantly changing working environment that contains dealing with mergers, multiple Aircraft, Crew, Maintenance and Insurance (ACMI) wet leasing operations, adjusting to multiple national and organisational cultures, and a more distant management, where the chief pilot is known only by name rather than through personal appearance in the everyday operations. The level of social interactions associated with the past is more frequently replaced by online settings, computer-based training (CBT) and check-in happens at the gate of the aircraft rather than the crew room. What used to be a pre-

dictable job for 30-40 years is now replaced by contract employment and job expectancies of 2 to 3 years, before employees find themselves in a 'new' aviation reality.

The Normalisation of Adaptation

The world is constantly changing. More than ever, people employed within aviation (at all levels of an organisation) find themselves immersed in constant adaptations in order to keep up with the pace of change. They create the capacity to get the job done in a constant fight for survival. Going the extra mile and stretching a bit more, while dealing with the many uncertainties that emerge in the working environment seems to have created a normalisation of adaptation.

This goes unaddressed in training sessions, which are dominated by compliance and achieving standards often based on arbitrary measures. This normalisation

of adaptation is invisibly patching up the system and making it work. It contains both the contributions that people make, as well as the trade-offs people have to make that seem to go unnoticed in

the way airline training and opportunities for learning are designed.

It seems that both the understanding of work and training design in many airlines is based on obsolete thinking (e.g., Safety-1), where the human is seen as a liability and system "improvements" happen by fixing the people at the sharp end, and not the system. This approach lacks the robustness to deal with and learn from the ongoing changes and growing complexity that influence the system's performance and system learning. We may find the people working in the aviation industry equipped with ballerina shoes, as they climb the mountain of aviation complexity, afraid to cause disruption. The underlying assumptions on which aviation training is based have become saturated and are in need of an update.

“...training...is dominated by compliance and achieving standards often based on arbitrary measures...normalisation of adaptation is invisibly patching up the system and making it work.”

However, new regulatory winds are blowing on the mountain. They may demand a steadier foothold, which in turn requires more solid footwear. In early 2023, the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) published updated guidance on its aviation safety plan for the next three years. They state:

“As the aviation system changes, it is imperative that we ensure that human factors and the impact on human performance continue to be taken into account, both at service provider and regulatory levels. Resilience and a Safety-2 approach, where the number of intended and acceptable outcomes is as high as possible, shall be introduced alongside the Safety-1 approach.” (EASA EPAS, 2023, Vol. 1, p.43).

The Organisational Proficiency Check

People are part of the system, and not isolated from it. This, in my opinion, means that for learning to occur it requires a more holistic approach. Every six months European pilots are in the simulator for an Operators Proficiency Check (OPC) to check, train and improve their qualifications. Maybe it's time to explore the possibility of an Organisational Proficiency Check as a recurring theme in an airline, not for the sake of an audit, but for the sake of constant organisational learning and improvement.

Features of this Organisational Proficiency Check could involve an update of the

existing platforms available in an airline (e.g., CRM, SMS, OPC, Line checks, reporting system etc), where employees at all levels of an organisation would play an active role in redesigning these platforms. For example, this could involve setting up 'learning teams' that participate in the daily operation to feel the pulse of the airline, in the effort to constantly create and adjust the capacity and adapt the existing platforms to match the needs.

Perhaps most important to this process is challenging the underlying perspective that's been dominating the aviation world (e.g., Safety-1), and improving upon this with a curiosity to create opportunities for learning by understanding the contributions and challenges from work-as-done, and by tapping into the practical wisdom present in an airline. These learning teams are thereby not experts or managers, but colleagues that work as collaborative links in an airline for the purpose of constant organisational learning.

Learning teams could for example ask questions like:

- How do we redesign the training platform to include learning opportunities, that tell us about how people adapt and make it work in everyday operations?
- What needs to be in place for people to proactively address concerns and potential signals of risks without the fear of retribution?
- How do we establish and nurture relationships across the system that benefit the organisation as a whole?
- What sort of human adaptive contributions are present in our system?

Incorporating learning teams in everyday operation could assist in a continuous effort of organisational learning and resil-

ience. In the aviation world of compliance, it may be worth noticing that the regulatory winds seem to be changing here as well, encouraging more holistic approaches.

EASA elaborates further that:

“Organisational resilience is a key factor in successfully managing safe operation, but there is scant regulatory guidance on how to apply the concept. Resilience comprises both a system's ability to withstand disturbances, challenges and change, and to recover and sustain operations thereafter. The positive contribution to safety of each and every staff member is a key component in an organisation's resilience” (EASA EPAS, 2023, Vol. 3, p.53).

I welcome these times of regulatory change that suggest broadening our perspective to include the system, and not just looking at the individual. We may find ourselves in need of new shoes which may hurt a little at first, and may even be a bit of a struggle to put on, but over time may provide the necessary comfort and support to climb the mountain.

Gitte Furdal Damm is a former pilot and has for the last 8 years been providing CRM and HF training as a consultant through her own company About Human Factors. She completed the MSc program at Lund University in Human Factors and System Safety in 2021, writing a thesis about resilient performance within aviation.

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Are Black Swan Events Trainable?

By Endre Berntzen

I once was told that aviation safety is like making moonshine: everyone knows when you are doing it bad.

In aviation, we find the types of professionals you would expect, the ones dressed in uniform making decisions on everything regarding your life for the next couple of hours. You expect the best service as well as the safest duty of care.

If I told you the opposite—that everyone involved is doing their best to make this unsafe—you would select a different airline or not travel at all.

Flying is a profession; it is a specialized task requiring certain skills and training. It also requires specific competencies to precisely navigate a steel tube through the air at high speed, surrounded by flammable liquid.

Our expectation is therefore a high level, or perhaps the highest level of safety. We take it for granted. Like moonshine – we expect the recipe to work. It is so safe that when something happens everyone jumps to quick conclusions - this must be an error (pilot error). In theory, high reliable organizations (HROs) have complex systems

that work in symbiosis, procedures that are well-tuned and effective. Aviation is well-regulated and already has well-working concepts in place. Using the theory of resilience may then be seen as an add-on or something extra.

“ To enter the world of the Black Swan, we need to understand two elements: hidden interdependencies and brittleness. ”

Pilots on an airplane shall never perform a task that they are not trained for – it's where we build our competence and establish our culture. Culture is a buzzword and can be defined as “what you do when no one is looking.” When you operate there will be risks – how you deal with them can be different. Surprise in training, or Black Swans if you will, can be difficult to both facilitate and solve and need identification of when the resources required to solve the task is higher than the resources available. It can be achieved when the workload is high and there are added requirements in place – a situation that could approach negative training.

Applying a resilience perspective in training means adding knowledge of what type of resources you have available and how they can be applied. The most significant change we made when introducing this concept is the language. Instead of asking the 5 why's - we simply ask “how come” or “what was it...” The idea is that pilots always have their attention on something. And when you understand what they need you will probably increase the resources available. The problem for many HRO

companies is that there are weak leading indicators or lack of meaningful markers; what you are looking for are thin margins and small indicators.

To enter the world of the Black Swan, we need to understand two elements: hidden interdependencies and brittleness. You should look at job requirements in a specific order - starting with the rules, then going to technology, and ending up with training. The hidden facts of your work will then potentially expose brittleness. This is the point where performance starts to decay and higher risks in your operation begin to appear. We found the most effective way of studying this is by doing a work-as-imagined vs work-as-done gap analysis. You will not see the Black Swan if you do not know what to look for (e.g., hidden interdependencies and brittleness). New training concepts introduced worldwide seek to find these answers and introduce new rules and training concepts. The problem I find from a resilience perspective is that the introduction of these rules may introduce new complex clustering and the possibility of weak links. Since mapping your dependencies can be complex, you run a risk of missing important datapoints relevant to performance. In other words, you risk a higher degree of brittleness that increases your risk level because of very small indicators.

We find examples of this in everyday airplane operations. After an accident we often find investigators using “loss of situational awareness” in their reports. We can argue that this is not true, people always have their attention on something – we just need to figure out what, learn

and then train. In Black Swan events, we could find that the crew has been (or not) exposed to a certain situation and the response to the threat is either too quick or too slow, and most likely a cascade effect putting strain on time management.

A specific example is the altimeter procedure setting in an airplane. Airlines have rules on how this should be set and if the airplane (technology) is either old or extremely modern the training is increased. If you are AQP, ATQP or EBT approved, you monitor pilot performance to check the effectiveness of the procedure. In your observational data, you may find that 3,8% of pilots are performing the procedure incorrectly and conclude that the deviation is statistically within your margins. However, looking from a two-person crew perspective, the deviations then double to 7,6% which is way above your expectations. From a normal perspective you would probably call the pilots for tea and biscuits and give them a reason to be proud (and perhaps walk out the door with Penny Benjamin – for all the Top Gun aficionados). Or you could flip the line of thinking – if your procedure is 100% effective you might

have a bad culture, or if your procedure is a 100% ineffective you have a good culture. Why? The observation during LOQE or LOSA would focus on how the procedure is corrected and which pilot played the active role when corrected. At this point you are capable of, and knowledgeable enough, to know what to train.

Aviation is inherently complex and based on many unknown factors, yet still resilient enough to operate with the highest degree of safety. Working within the margins of safety, we should always question what our acceptable levels of risk are. Risk tolerance and training to reduce exposure to risks is complex.

Training for Black Swans is a marathon and not a sprint. Are you up for the task?

Endre Berntzen has been flying since he was 15 years old and has experience from the oldest four-engine Lockheeds from the 1950s to the newest technology of today's jets. Through his airline, he has led a number of research programs and has been involved in almost everything that has to do with the training of aircrew. He has extensive experience with ATQP and has assisted OEMs and CAAs in certification requirements of new and old aircraft. The most interesting study he has been involved in relates to the effects of somatogravic illusions and pilot training. In his spare time, he enjoys driving a 11.5 ton snowmobile and making ski tracks for cross-country skiers.

Are We Learning All We Need for Resilient Performance?

By Laura Maguire

Competency in performing a task is a minimum requirement that is assumed for workers in high-risk/high-consequence environments. Organizations utilize a variety of mechanisms to assess proficiency such as competency matrices, ride-alongs, peer review and coaching, refresher training, regular re-certification cycles, and performance reviews to assess technical skills. Many simulation-based assessments also include assessments of explicit skills in coordinating and collaborating for team dynamics.

While the knowledge and skills demonstrable in these processes are important, they are insufficient to account for resilient, adaptive performance. What is missing is the significant amount of knowledge learned outside traditional channels and expressed most noticeably during adaptive performances. In the literature, the concepts of shared mental models (Converse, Cannon-Bowers & Salas, 1993), common or mutual knowledge (Clark & Marshall, 1981; Krauss and Fussell, 1990) and common ground (Clark and Brennan, 1991; Klein, Feltoovich, Bradshaw, & Woods, 2005) are well established, and were a central component of my own doctoral research. This article expands on this important component of workplace learning to suggest ways to enhance existing organizational learning systems.

The importance of the implicit

In modern work environments, practitioners face trade-off decisions, goal conflicts, and requirements to continually

revise, replan, and reprioritize in the face of changing conditions (Woods, Dekker, Cook, Johannesen & Sarter, 2017). But the knowledge of these aspects of work, which is crucial for carrying out tasks and coordination across inter- and intra-organizational boundaries, is typically not made explicit in traditional training systems. Instead, it is left to individuals to uncover these requirements and put this knowledge into practice alongside the technical demands of their role.

In my doctoral research, studying software engineers resolving complex large-scale system outages, I discovered many different classes of knowledge that were used in responding to incidents (Maguire, 2020). The knowledge that aided not only timely and effective incident response, but also how to enhance current knowledge of system behaviour included crucial information about:

- the kind of organizational demands (including shifting priorities, new management, pressures & constraints for action);
- organizational and team priorities and how they tend to shift relative to different kinds of pressures as well as how quickly/slowly these shifts take place;
- goal conflicts and how those are typically dealt with;
- formal decision processes;
- informal decision processes or role-specific decision-making authority;

- when to use formal vs informal decision processes and the implications of each;
- who makes decisions in emergent situations and at what speed; and
- in complex, large-scale, interactive failures, who were the dependent units, and what were their role & function (espoused and actual).

In looking at formal job descriptions, training programs, and competency assessments there was little to no evidence that this contextual knowledge was recognized and valued for the central role it played in minimizing the impact and duration of the incident. And conversely - when it was absent- of the role it played in amplifying impact and extending the duration of the incident.

Contextual Learning

Practitioners often acquired this knowledge in an emergent, ad hoc fashion often initiated on their own volition. To many organizations, this process of establishing and maintaining common ground looks like slack in the system - inefficiencies to be eradicated. It is the casual but protracted conversation two residents have in the cafeteria after bumping into one another getting coffee. It is the equipment operators lagging behind after the morning meeting to talk about the difficulties faced on the jobsite the day prior. It is the investment made by an engineer to spend her lunch hour at another team's weekly meeting to listen in for any disruptions in their work that may impede her own

team's efforts.

"To many organizations, this process of establishing and maintaining common ground looks like slack in the system"

This learning becomes knowledge about how the system functions under different conditions and, to the practitioner, it enables resilient performance much in the same way expertise enables knowledge to be flexibly applied to novel problems (Feltovich, Spiro & Coulson, 1997).

Pre-emptively, the practitioner uses this knowledge to anticipate problems that interfere with their ability to carry out their work, proactively adapt their actions or gather more information to keep their options open, to recruit needed resources or secure access they may need in future. For example, a forest supervisor might know one of their tree faller's children is sick and may need to leave the jobsite quickly that day. They use this knowledge to assign them a location close to the road that allows for a quick and safe exit from the cut block that doesn't impede or endanger other nearby workers.

In the midst of a crisis situation, this knowledge is applied dynamically with the practitioner calling forth contextual information that enables them to trace the loss or gain of additional capacity relative to changing events. For example, a software engineer without access to a critical database knows a member of the database team from their shared work in the employee resource group, and is able to text them asking for help during the incident response.

Retrospectively, this knowledge is used to help reconstruct contributing factors and make sense of seemingly discrepant system behaviours. When a lack of common ground or common knowledge contributes to difficulties in working effectively together, this can be taken as a signal that great cross-functional and multi-level interactions would provide a benefit. For example, a helicopter pilot experiences a near miss when transporting passengers from a staging area and invites the marketing and operations staff of the holiday operator to attend the debriefing, so they may identify potentially hidden barriers to understanding and ways to communicate hazards early and often to passengers.

Encouraging a continuous learning function

Organizations looking to develop learning systems to support this form of learning need to recognize its implicit value and enable mechanisms for it. While formal structures (weekly update meetings, townhall events, newsletters) may serve to capture some of this form of learning, the tendency towards repeated, managed, and structured information delivery is likely to be insufficient for developing relevant and ongoing common ground. In highly variable operating systems - like those of continuously changing distributed software systems - these mechanisms will lack the variability of information and the inability for practitioners to probe for information that is more immediately pertinent for their goals, purposes, and concerns.

Instead, more ad hoc and emergent interactions should be encouraged across internal and external organizational boundaries to encourage diversity of information flows. Workers should be provided training that highlights the importance of this form of learning and enables them to practice establishing and maintaining common ground both within their teams

and across different levels and roles in the organizations.

Cross-functional game days, simulations, or incident reviews consisting of complex, contextually-driven problems coupled with skilled debriefing that can reinforce technical and knowledge factors can assist organizations in learning for resilient performance.

Laura Maguire leads the research program at Jeli.io, where she studies software engineers as they cope with the cognitive complexities of keeping distributed, continuous deployment systems reliably functioning and helps to translate those findings into a product that is advancing

the state of the art of incident management in the software industry. Her research interests lie in resilience engineering, coordination design, resilient systems control, and building tooling to enable adaptive capacity across distributed work teams. She was a researcher with the Cognitive Systems Engineering lab SNAFU Catchers Consortium from 2017–2020, working closely with large and medium-sized digital service companies to identify and support resilient performance within their engineering teams. Laura has a Master's degree in Human Factors & Systems Safety, a Ph.D. in Integrated Systems Engineering from the Ohio State University, and extensive experience working in industrial safety & risk management.

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Two Views on Procedures

By Tom Laursen

There are two very distinct and rather contrasting views on procedures and how the aviation system creates safety.

One view is that the aviation system would be safe if only humans, especially the operators, followed the rules. This belief is governed by the idea that following procedures equals safety. In this article, this view is called **'the adherence view.'**

A different view is that procedures are one recourse, amongst others, for human operators to respond to the inherent variation and uncertainty of the aviation system. In this article, this view is called **'the adaptive view.'**

"The adherence view' is the language of compliance and non-compliance; 'The adaptive view' language is characterised by description, understanding and explanation."

In this short article, I will highlight how operators respond to everyday uncertainty and variation within the aviation system. I argue that the use of phrases like rule-breaking and non-adherence to procedures can be substituted with other labels that are less pejorative and more useful if we are trying to improve the overall performance of the system through our available tools.

Adaptations

There is inherent variation and uncertainty within the aviation system, which aviation stakeholders are good at predicting. They spend considerable resources on predicting what can happen, but we will never

be able to fully predict and anticipate all scenarios. Therefore, the aviation system has been designed to respond and adapt performance to these changes. The place where the largest number of adaptations are taking place is at the operator level.

Operators can respond in real-time and make short necessary adaptations to the planned operation.

An example I have used in the past to describe the everyday necessary adaptations is the number of phone calls that Air Traffic Controllers (ATCOs) execute daily. The main purpose of phone calls between ATCOs is to coordinate smaller or larger changes to the planned operation. During an hour of work, an ATCO will make 10-30 phone calls to coordinate changes to the planned operation. There are, of course,

procedures in place when ATCOs need to make phone calls. The procedure says that phone coordination needs to be performed when there is a revision to the planned operation. Coordinating what is beyond planned operation requires the operator to be sensitive to many subtle variations (requests

for direct tracks, aircraft that can't reach an agreed flight level because of performance, all kinds of revisions, etc.) in the situation. These variations often require real-time interventions from the operators.

Sidney Dekker says that 'applying procedures successfully is a substantive, skillful cognitive act'. If operators followed rigid procedures, according to how they were designed, the aviation system would come to a halt very quickly. There is simply no way that the 10-30 phone calls per hour can be described in detail within the procedures. Despite that, there is a continued belief that rule-following equals safety. The aviation system is safe because it has been designed to be able to respond to the variation and uncertainty in everyday

operations as well as contingencies.

The need for change

'The adherence view' governs many of the processes that have been implemented as tools for managing today's aviation system. Taxonomies, incident reporting, risk assessment, proficiency checks, KPIs, and many more are tools that are based on the idea that any identified non-conformity (a social process where the people with the right to define the paradigm have the power) to the written word can be tabulated and counted to serve the process for safety improvements. This approach aligns well with excel sheets, quantifiable risks and checklists, and managing your organisation with reported numbers through a distant view of work. This method often generates misguided countermeasures.

In contrast to this approach, 'the adaptive view' is based on understanding context and the messy world of conflicting goals. This world is difficult to tabulate and understand without understanding the work context and cognitive processes that lead to performance. It's a world where organisational performance results from organisational preparation (staff numbers, equipment, airspace design, selection, training, etc.) and how human operators respond and adapt to everyday variations.

If we want to move towards an aviation system that is governed by 'the adaptive view', there is a need for change. We do not need to abandon 'the adherence view', but the balance between the two must change.

The language

Another difference between the two views is the language that is used. 'The adherence view' is the language of compliance and non-compliance. Most situations become digital and, therefore, can be judged

to be either right or wrong. This judgment is done after something has happened. Our language to describe failure is very rich compared to our language to describe complexity and the positive system attributions of humans.

'The adaptive view' language is characterised by description, understanding and explanation. This is a language that allows us to understand the situations we describe. Through a language of understanding, it's easier to recognise the complexity involved in real work, which again provides us with improved possibilities to introduce useful countermeasures.

Some suggestions

Our suggestions to change the balance between the two views to improve the tools we use for organisational and industry decision-making are:

- Stop or be more careful with tabulation - use a qualitative approach to manage your organisation. Tabulation often leads to more procedures that lead to more tabulation of non-compliance.
- Managing organisations safely is about collecting multiple perspectives, and interactions between system elements. Not one truth.
- Learn to support the human capacity to adapt. It is a finite resource that must be monitored in the live environment to ensure sufficiency.
- Compliance is never a substitute for engagement.
- Learn to find the adherence/adaption sweet spot and adjust with system contextual changes to minimise the load on the human operators.
- When adding new procedures, trial them first to ensure they are stable enough to be helpful, especially in

messy situations.

- View adaption as a chance to learn about what is going on.
- Learn from adaption to improve procedures.
- There is no such thing as a Root Cause.

Achieving improved performance and doing it safely is about supporting practitioners and other staff when they attempt to solve the variability of the aviation system both in everyday operations and contingencies.

Tom Laursen is an experienced safety expert and an Air Traffic Controller (ATCO). He has worked with three different Air Navigation Service Providers in Denmark, Bahrain, and Switzerland. His work in the area of safety includes head of occurrence investigation and deputy safety manager at Skyguide, Switzerland, as well as serving 5 years on the ICAO safety management panel as a representative for IFATCA. Tom Laursen has a master's degree in human factors and systems safety in Aviation from the University of Linköping, Sweden.

A Multi-Domain View of System Management

By James Burnell and Joji Waites

This article is written not just from an understanding of theory but with one foot in live operations across the aviation industry. To validate our thinking, we have drawn on what works and doesn't in live operations from the frontline operators' viewpoint. This has then been used to find and validate alternative coherent approaches that target areas where the current systems fail to support the operation. Exploring some potential learning improvements that come from conceptualising the system differently, we will open the door to using different types of data. The framework we introduce here draws upon the benefits of moving on from uncontextualised data only approaches, to adding varieties of contextualised data such as contextualised data at scale, or context rich narrative to improve our understanding.

We discuss some of the pitfalls of a single-domain view and, more importantly, the benefits of a multi-domain one. How does a multi-domain view allow us to create new ways to understand the management of uncertainty created by our modern complex adaptive systems? This includes the opportunity offered to balance worker adherence to rules with adaption to unlock the inherent resilience in our systems.

Background

As background for those unfamiliar with the aviation industry, the approach to learning and risk management is realised through a Safety Management System (SMS). Various types of reports or data are

synthesised into largely uncontextualised data that is used to create objective truths for system improvements or corrections through linear risk management structures. An example of uncontextualised data could be the distribution of unstable approaches by location as detected by a Flight Data Monitoring (FDM) programme.

A Multi-Domain View

The alternative approaches we suggest here need to be intellectually scaffolded by one core concept: a shift in our perception of the system. This is a change in systemic conceptualisation from a single-domain system view to a multi-domain view. By domain, we mean a part of the system distinct enough to warrant its own paradigm of understanding, learning and operation.

The phrase coined by the statistician George Box, 'All models are wrong, but some are useful.', is helpful here to highlight why value is generated by a multi-domain approach. Value is found in one view over the other only because one model is likely to be more useful than another under a given context. To make the concept accessible, we have restricted this article to the two main domains organisations expect to manage in daily operations.

The Ordered Domain

The prevailing single-domain view to which we refer is that of the 'Ordered Domain' or Cartesian, 'system as a machine' view that has dogged western-world thinking for several centuries now, and we believe is stopping us all from moving beyond the

asymptote of safety improvement. The ordered domain is where cause and effect are obviously and irreparably linked. We can learn and manage as if building or fixing a piece of machinery. Some refer to this as a "Taylorist" approach, where safety management can be deconstructed into constituent parts in a reductive manner.

The Complex Domain

The second domain, which is undeniably part of every system we operate beyond the merely mechanical, is the 'Complex Domain'. This is an easy concept to grasp, as it is how we experience our own lives outside the working environment. We would not intrinsically organise our lives through systems engineering, KPIs or standard operating procedures.

These complex parts of our system are dispositional (only disposed to repeat the same outcomes but in no way guaranteed to do so) and, therefore, subject to radical uncertainty, emergence, sensitivity to small changes, tipping points and other properties that we don't see in ordered domains. We do not propose to define and elaborate on these concepts here, however we consider it well worth the reader's time to get to grips with the concepts of radical uncertainty and emergence in complex adaptive systems.

“Complexity is, like gravity, a foundational property of the world and ignoring both generate similar results. – Professor Dave Snowden”

To cement this idea, it might be valuable to highlight the other name for complex systems, which is **nonequilibrium steady state systems** which is much more intuitively descriptive of the challenges held within. It is also useful to understand that complexity is not a nebulous concept. It is a foundational property of our world, a world that would not exist without it. In essence, it means that the system's constituent parts adapt and change to one another, creating a higher-order output that is only discernible when the system is operating in its entirety, not by looking at the parts in isolation and extrapolating forwards.

Some Problems Created by the Single System View

We all agree that we must find a way to learn about what is happening in our operations in order to manage them appropriately. This is where ordered domain-only approaches create problems.

Learning and Data

The first problem. If you believe that the system is merely a machine to be fixed and perfected, any unwanted outcomes appear to be failures of that system or the operators of it. Therefore, any outcomes not amplified by unwanted consequences, say an accident or a serious incident, must be a system working well. This would make anyone question why we would learn from normal work.

This is manifestly not the case in complex systems, as highlighted above. They are dispositional, not causal. Hence, outcomes are always subject to variation at any time, so we must learn what the potentials might be. Most importantly, because it is a nonequilibrium system that does not necessarily regress back to the mean, we need to know where the adaptive capacities that

stabilise the equilibrium are in order to ensure they are supported.

The mechanistic view leads us to suppose that our belief in stable cause and effect can successfully support the use of uncontextualised data as the sole source of learning. Uncontextualised data is data stripped of context and is then used to learn in context-rich environments, causing some of the potential operational failures we have seen in frontline operations. In the earlier example of FDM-derived unstable approaches, the data might show that some airports attract higher unstable approach rates than others but without the contextual information to explain why.

There are sound mathematical reasons for not using uncontextualised data solutions in context-rich environments, such as the curves used to describe distributions of events. When we stop using linear mathematics, such as Gaussian Distributions or bell curves, to describe the complex world and switch to far more domain-appropriate nonlinear Pareto distributions, we see a far higher likelihood of serious events, e.g. a 1-in-100 event becomes a 1-in-10 event. The next reasonable next question would be, 'If risks are more and potentially larger than we believe, why do we not see many more serious incidents and accidents?'. We believe this is because humans—a largely undervalued and overlooked form of resilience within our operations—adapt to a considerable amount more variation than is generally acknowledged.

A further problem with using uncontextualised data points is the enormous amount of possible linkages, which in classic fault tree analysis are used to build a picture of what is going on. The maths of using this uncontextualised data approach is that with 10 data points and 45 possible link-

ages, there are 3.5 trillion possible explanations of what is going on. It should be obvious that there are serious limitations to this approach in all but the most stable of contexts.

It is also the case that the output of any socio-technical complex system, such as an airline operation, beyond what has been safely ordered with standard operating procedures, is dispositional, or emergent. Looking at parts of the system to extrapolate potential outcomes is likely to be less effective than we might have first thought. It is akin to digging up and dissecting an apple tree to ascertain the taste of the coming autumn's apples—a fruitless approach.

Managing

A common management misconception is that management interventions are a binary choice between fixing the system with system-level interventions, or by individually fixing the human that created a poor outcome by not complying with the rules or making errors.

A multi-domain view allows us to see the complex system as dispositional, always ready to create new outcomes regardless of structure, freeing our managers to try many new approaches to creating interventions to support the resilience vital to contend with such systemic context variations. Risk management can now be dealt with at multiple levels and with a fractal approach (by this, I mean broken up by different conceptual areas and not just scale, e.g. safety management is not the same when looking at Edinburgh-based crews as Copenhagen-based crews).

System change is also a significant concern when viewing issues from the frontline. The foremost problem, as we see it from

a resilience engineering viewpoint, is implementing changes with the belief that the system will create an output that is stable across time and outcome. This has two consequences. The first is the obvious lack of ability to spot impending emergent issues created by our own interventions.

The second is that beyond the sight of current learning approaches, this methodology of change consumes the most significant form of operational resilience in our systems. Our workers are left to control any unintended consequences of these interventions to stabilise system outputs, which absorb this finite adaptive capacity.

In summary, the ordered domain approach incentivises the creation of context-free global solutions in context-rich fractal environments, as opposed to potentially creating many methods and tools that could be combined to create systems of action coherent with the local context.

Some Benefits of Multi-Domain Approaches

Given that we are all comfortable with the ordered system approaches, the following paragraphs relate to possible differences that support risk management within the complex parts of our systems.

Learning and Data

In the complex parts of our systems, such as the parts where humans operate, we would advocate an approach to learning grounded in the belief that context is the most important element of any data collected.

Making sense of what happens within complex domains differs greatly from ordered domains. The uncertainty created by the interacting and adapting system elements that create the output means the system is immune to accurate modelling

and prediction. The good news is that, as humans, we naturally evolved to work within this uncertainty and are well-tuned to the context-rich narrative learning approaches needed to determine what is going on.

As we move into the complex domain and possible contextualised data solutions, we must switch to abductive approaches to reasoning. Abduction, sometimes called the science of hunches, is just this. This allows us to hold multiple coherent ideas of what might be going on so this is no longer about which ideas are objectively right or wrong, but which might be contextually useful.

Therefore, the upside of learning from a contextualised approach is that we can better understand what might be going on, leading to more coherent methods of system management.

Possible Contextualised Data Learning Technique

One example of a narrative-based data learning technique we could use in an airline setting might be to use the informal network structures between airline crew. This is, not to replace current approaches, but to augment them. In the complex parts of our operation, we can now imagine adding learning structures below the level of the formal systems of SMSs. These would be capable of amplifying weaker signals through informal network interactions while being more targeted.

The problem with formal learning structures such as airline SMS is that they inherently restrict the type, and quantity, of data that flow through them. Both by design and because of the levels of trust or understanding the participants have of them.

Worker culture or social heuristics (ideas that form group patterns of behaviour) are the main driver of crew behaviour beyond the vagaries of human decision-making. This means that mapping this culture creates leading indicators of safety, where compliance to a fixed system is a lagging indicator and arguably an ineffective one at that.

To ensure the informal networks are of sufficient density, airlines could carry out any variation of social network stimulation to reengage these. Based on the fleet structure or crew base size, crews would need to be networked within an appropriate number of degrees of separation from each other. This is quickly and efficiently achieved, and the operation will become safer even without formal learning as information flows are facilitated.

When these networks are in place, it is relatively simple to tap into the data stream with an appropriate data collection approach that does not allow gaming of the question, maintains epistemic justice and is seen as non-jeopardy by the participants. The correct process here is the collection of contextualised data at scale using any suitable available commercial collection software or carefully considered in-house approaches to narrative databases. We could take a lead from one of the schools of sense-making and anthropologists who have been working with the knowledge of complexity from the start.

These collection methods can be used to highlight any desired topic or used for trending. It would also support a complexity-coherent theory of change. As context changes, though, company initiatives or otherwise, we could be proactively monitoring to catch unintended consequences,

which, as it stands, are only retrospective-ly picked up when consequence amplifies poor outcomes. This approach also allows KPIs to become vector measures of change of reality and aid system management rather than hinder it.

Managing

Now that we can have a multi-domain approach to learning and data, a significant benefit becomes the freedom to manage the system of uncertainty with a more coherent approach.

If we are to hold multiple potential truths at the same time, we can test ideas for usefulness. This can be done through safe-to-fail experimentation to avoid unintended consequences of a system that we now know to be dispositional. As we now know, the outcome of all possible interventions in any complex system cannot be truly seen until the system has run through all iterations. Still, with context rich data approaches, changes can be monitored, and poor outcomes safely dampened if needed.

“ ...our systems are significantly more fragile when airlines make changes to the operation without a complexity-safe theory of change backed by contextualised data learning. ”

The lack of the need to ascribe an objective truth also allows us to practice greater epistemic justice within worker communities and improve safety culture. The use of social network stimulation further cements this culture of sharing and discussion, both improving safety, data collection and trust as the workers see their issues being addressed without undue delay.

We can create interventions that include whole systems of action across multiple levels and areas of the operation, creating contextually appropriate responses to fractal problems at any scale.

We can also anticipate that this approach will give us the ability to directly influence a significant source of undervalued resilience. This can be achieved by supporting our frontline staff through a good understanding of the system dynamics and maintaining the balance of ordered parts to complex parts. In other words, the balance of adherence to adaption. If unbalanced in either direction, it may significantly erode the adaptive capacity of the humans who keep our context-rich systems safe and efficient in the face of the uncertainty and emergence generated by complexity.

We will finish with a concern borne out of bitter experience. We now know that when changes, such as improvements in safety or efficiency, are made to nonequilibrium steady state systems we risk unwanted consequences. From experience, we see that our systems are significantly more fragile when airlines make changes to the operation without a complexity-safe theory of change backed by contextualised data learning.

The scope of this article limits our ability to discuss this in more depth. Still, we would advise some further reading on theories of change, coherent and safe, for complex adaptive systems, such as the [Vector Theory of Change](#) from Professor Dave Snowden.

In summary, although we have only touched the surface of the potential approaches to this inherent uncertainty,

we believe that it is possible to see that a multi-domain approach could have many potential benefits and allow new approaches to safety that give us a chance to break the declining returns of current linear reductionist methods.

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Risk is Not as Simple as You Might Think

By Ivan Pupulidy

Recently there has been a lot of talk about “Zero.” The zero-accident philosophy is interesting and a noble goal; however, we need to ask is it attainable and that means we also must ask. “What happens if we fail?” The concept of zero is built on an idea that all accidents are preventable, and, in hindsight, we can build causal chains that suggest that they are. When we explore this issue through the lens of complex systems, we recognize the presence of uncertainty along with the lack of ability to fully predict what will happen. Following the logic of this argument, we can see that if a worker knew in advance that they would have an accident, then it is reasonable to assume that they would avoid that outcome by doing something different. The reality is that they don’t know what will happen.

So, what does risk mean to operators?

Risk is more than a simple model of hazard coupled with duration of exposure, or

probability times severity. Interacting with hazards is a complex human activity that is influenced by a number of key human and system features—a point missed by most post-incident investigations. Commonly when something goes wrong, our assessment of field risk management is strongly influenced by hindsight bias. Couple this bias with the emphasis of many current models of investigation which are designed to attribute cause to the disposition of those closest to the work. This means that behaviors and actions are often attributed to the disposition of the operator, which frequently leads to the judgment of action described as the “bad apple” theory. This model is challenged by complex systems research.

Any review of incidents must include situational attribution. This approach focuses attention on the influences or performance-shaping factors that exist in the work environment. There is a concerted

effort to place actions and decisions in context. From a risk perspective, we need to understand how people related to the risks in the working environment and understand the normal tendency of people to normalize the risks associated with day-to-day operations. Normalization of risk is a term developed by the author during a Learning Review in the USFS. There had been a fatality tree strike and it became clear that the team of firefighters did not normalize deviance, as had been suggested by a team member. Rather they had normalized risk and fallen into a routine that made them more vulnerable as the system delivered the unexpected.

Professor John Adams has developed a risk diagram that helps us understand these risk relationships.

Adams views the reaction to hazard exposure (risk) as a balancing behavior, where influences pull toward risk exposure or

Adapted from John Adams, Risk (1995)

away from risk exposure. This is consistent with real-world operations – when, for example, a pilot senses or perceives the risk to be increasing, they naturally build margin into the operation, thus pulling away from risk exposure. In this model, balancing behaviors are influenced by four major categories: accidents, perceived danger, sense of reward, and propensity to take risk.

Propensity to take risk is a function of the individual's inclination toward risk-taking. For example, during a recent training session, I asked participants to tell me a story about a time they took a risk, that in hindsight they would not do again. A US Forest Service Smoke Jumper² reflected for a few moments and then replied, "I am not much of a risk taker, I am thinking about open ocean kite surfing, backcountry skiing and my other favorite hobby of Canyoning." This quote demonstrates at least three things; first, this person's propensity to take risk is probably higher than most. Second, they have difficulty relating risk to the things they love to do (a form of normalization of risk). Third, they did not even consider their job, jumping from a plane to fight fire, one of their high-risk activities.

The sense of reward is related to systemic and individual/personal rewards. Rewards can be institutionalized, such as awards or medals. They can also be systemic in terms of compensation such as pay and overtime. Rewards can also be individually developed, for example a firefighter responding to a vehicle fire, who sees a sign on a car that says "Baby Onboard" will likely take more risk to potentially save the at-risk child.

The term accident refers to the perception an operator or worker has regarding the severity of an adverse outcome. This works

hand-in-hand with perceived danger, which refers to the perception the operator or worker has of the likelihood of an event occurring. Together, these two factors influence how the worker or operator perceives the overall risk in the system. It is very similar to the severity part of the probability and severity equation.

Normalization of Risk

Through a systematic review of US Forest Service accidents, the author uncovered the phenomenon of "normalization of risk"³, which occurs when risk is accepted as a normal part of operations. In most cases, risk (like drift) is gradually accepted until it seems normal⁴. Normalization of risk is a common aspect of long-term human interaction with risk, regardless of any calculation of risk. The review of USFS accidents showed that the longer a system seemed safe (no accidents) the greater the amount of risk firefighters accepted.

Any risk management program has to consider all four of the influences/perceptions above to change the way that workers interact, accept, manage and deal with risk.

Hope for change can be recognized in tactical aviation operations where the environment consistently delivers uncertainty. Pilots in tactical operations are still subject to the normalization of risk; however, when a situation is recognized as novel there is a natural increase in risk awareness and experts move toward deliberation and become more risk-averse.

Stuart and Hubert Dreyfus of UC Berkeley conducted research that helps us to understand why the recognition of anomaly or novelty is so important⁵. Their research points to the system's expectations of performance based on experience or expertise. They demonstrated that novice practi-

tioners abide by a rigid adherence to rules or plans, have little situational perception and demonstrate limited discretionary judgment. When we contrast this with expert performers, we see a very different set of qualities. The expert no longer relies on rules, guidelines, or maxims, has an intuitive grasp of situations and applies analytic approaches only in novel situations. This last line is key to understanding how and why tactical pilots tend to be more deliberative during operations and thus tend to be less apt to normalized risk. When the system delivers an anomaly, tactical pilots are influenced to make sense of conflicting information, learn in the moment, and adapt or innovate solutions.

Most organizations under-rate the importance of sensemaking in favor of demanding adherence to rules and developing rote knowledge through training. These are, of course, important qualities and they work as long as the system delivers the expected. When organizations develop the capacity to accept that complex systems deliver the unexpected our definition of resilience has to change. The capacity for sensemaking, learning and innovation becomes a cornerstone of a resilient system. This resiliency is dependent upon the people in the organization and their ability and freedom to innovate in anomalous situations. This form of resilience was demonstrated during the ditching of Cactus flight 1549 and during the Qantas flight QF32 uncontained turbine failure. In each of these cases the system controls were not enough to allow for a safe outcome. The crews had to innovate. Resilience may go well beyond constructs of decision-making and, as in the two cases just mentioned, it may be represented as testing ideas to see what fits the situation.

“Normalization of risk is a common aspect of long-term human interaction with risk, regardless of any calculation of risk.”

In summary, the more routine the operation is perceived to be, the more likely the operator will be to normalize risk. Forcing operators into routine responses can make operators more susceptible to normalization of risk and therefore, the more apt they are to accept higher levels of risk exposure. All workers operate in an environment that delivers unpredictable situations and this can be leveraged into the development of capacities in the workforce designed to improve sensemaking, learning and improvisation skills.

Conclusion

Risk is not a simple issue. There are deep underlying conditions and factors that influence how people act in the presence of risk. Some of these factors are related to the disposition of the individual, but most are related to the system of work and the environment. As pilots, workers and managers, we have to consider all these conditions if we want to manage risk. Professor James Reason wrote, “We cannot change the human condition, but we can change the conditions under which humans work”⁶. This strongly points to the need for organizations, leaders and operators to become more aware of conditions and the influences that exist in normal work environments and to begin to manage those conditions, rather than magically expecting that people will change to suit an imagined work environment⁷.

Simply admonishing people to “try harder” or, as some leadership have said, “take no unnecessary risk,” creates hollow guidance

in the face of complex situations. Rather than these simple platitudes, we must endeavor to increase the capacity of our personnel to make sense of conflicting information and situational anomalies. This was once a key aspect of Crew Resource Management – perhaps it is time for us to consider how we can help our people to understand the nature of complex adaptive systems and what different skills are needed to operate with the highest margin of safety that is practical for each given situation.

There is no zero-risk option.

Ivan Pupulidy retired as the Director of the U.S. Forest Service Human Performance, Innovation and Organizational Learning Division. Ivan developed and implemented the Learning Review, which is designed to improve how large and small organizations respond to accidents and incidents. The team led by Dr. Pupulidy is credited with facilitating the improvement of risk management skills and fostering a culture of learning in the US Forest Service.

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1 This is referred to in academic literature as Dispositional Attribution or the Fundamental Attribution Error.

2 Smokejumpers are wildland firefighters trained to parachute into fires. Their primary mission is fire suppression and with the speed, range, and capacity of their fixed-wing aircraft, smokejumpers are capable of quickly delivering as few as two or as many as 12 firefighters with equipment and supplies, directly to the fire in a single trip.

3 Pupulidy, I.A. The Transformation of Accident Investigation from Finding Cause to Sensemaking. PhD Thesis, Tilburg University, Netherlands, 2015.

4 Adams, J. (1995). Risk; Routledge: Oxen, England, 1995.

5 Dreyfus and Dreyfus in, Flyvbjerg, B (2001) Making Social Science Matter, Cambridge University Press

6 Reason, J. (2000). Human error: models and management. BMJ, 320(7237), 768–770. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.320.7237.768>

7 The recognition and mapping of performance shaping factors is a major part of the Learning Review Process which is designed to build understanding of the context of decisions and actions to answer Prof. Sidney Dekker’s question, “Why did it make sense for people to do what they did?”

From Assessing to Enabling

By Ron Gantt

A few years ago I was lucky enough to work with a construction client that was interested in trying some different things with their safety assessment process. They were required to do one by upper management, but were frustrated with the traditional approaches that were often more ‘check the box’ and typically culminated in an argument between the site personnel and the assessor as to whether a finding was a “2” or a “3” in their four-point scale of importance. They were looking for something fresh. Something that would leave the project teams feeling understood and supported, rather than judged.

In talking through what they were looking for with the client’s team, we decided to try out a process that we took to calling an “operational resilience summit.” These summits were designed based on two key realizations. First, the client realized that safety issues do not exist in a vacuum. Instead, things like hazards, risks, violations, and ‘errors’ are side effects of everyday work. Put another way, these safety issues emerge from the system of work within and surrounding the organization. Therefore, the organization wanted to focus on those things that they are doing to create successful work.

It turned out that this was not hard to identify. The organization already had ten “success factors” that it identified as important for creating a success project. These were things like: having a solid operational plan; a good relationship with their customers; adequate resources; and fostering a high-performing team within the project. So, rather than the safety assessment

looking only at how the site is managing safety, what if we shifted the question to how the organization is setting up the site for success? Then the lessons from the process wouldn’t just live at the site level, but would provide a feedback loop to the whole business unit.

For example, those who worked to create bids for their jobs or who were involved in the scheduling or design often rarely visited the sites. As a result, they never got feedback on how realistic their bids, schedules, and/or designs were. Leaders would help develop plans for jobs, but when things did not go according to plan, it was viewed as a local problem, not a system issue. As a result, success and failure were typically viewed as a result of either the people at each site performing well or poorly, and/or good or bad luck. But the organization was designed to create the conditions for success at each site, specifically by using those success factors. If those were the basis for the assessment, couldn’t we create the opportunity for learning to flow beyond the site level so that each job makes the organization, not just the individuals, smarter?

The second realization that guided the creation of the summit was the idea that every instance of work is an outcome of the system of work surrounding it. This is to say that any one time that a person does a task, that instance emerges from the system it is embedded in. Furthermore, these instances of work are variable and, to paraphrase David Woods, systems work as designed but rarely as intended. Therefore, the system we were trying to assess was (1) changing all the time, and (2) not working

the way we thought it was. Its properties were emergent.

As a result, the team decided a checklist approach wouldn’t suffice. Instead, we could gather stories about how work was happening and use those to infer how the system of work is actually working. From there, we could start to see how the success factors are actually playing out, good or bad. We could see sources of brittleness or precarious success, where people were working for cross purposes, the system was stretching close to its limits, or where a strategy that appeared to be working was actually introducing new vulnerabilities to changes. We could also discover sources of resilience, where the people had developed useful or innovative ways to achieve success in the face of project challenges.

This obviously creates challenges, because checklists are seen as easy to implement and easy to measure. Story-gathering is much messier. In going this route, the organization opted to forego the ability to compare sites in any sort of reliable way. They couldn’t say that this site’s stories are 40% better than the other site’s, for example. However, the stories resonated with them because, not only are humans attuned to storytelling instinctually, but it also gave them something tangible to do. If I tell you that one site scored 83% on the latest assessment, you are left with more questions than answers. Is that good? Is that bad? If it is good or bad, what should you do about it? There is a lot of analysis that must be done before you get to the point where you can do something about it.

But if I tell you that at one site, we heard stories about how work crews had to wait around for an extra 40 minutes each day just so the crew ahead of them could finish their work because of a bottleneck in getting the right tools, now you have some tangible areas that you can explore and make changes on that touch many areas of the organization. And because the people who do this work are helping us gather these stories, those people are engaged in helping create improvements. As a result, even though it is hard to quantify (but not impossible in all cases), it was easy to point to specific improvements that resulted from this process.

"...a checklist approach wouldn't suffice... humans are attuned to storytelling instinctually..."

Based on these realizations, the team developed a basic process to pilot. We would have a summit team composed of people from outside the project (e.g., people from other projects, people involved in the project design and scheduling, safety personnel, etc.). However, we also wanted this to be a collaborative experience, so we also invited project personnel onto the team.

The summit began by gathering stories. Most team members went out in small groups (2-3) to the project to engage directly with frontline workers and ask questions about how they felt the work and the project was going. Another small group stayed in a conference room and had listening sessions with project foremen, engineers, and leadership.

In all cases the conversations centered around gathering stories. If someone said the project was going well, we would ask for an example of where the person

thought it was going well (and similar for those who said it wasn't going well). The team then came back together and shared the stories they heard. The team then would engage in what is basically a group coding session, where they described how the success factors working (or not) in practice in the stories. The focus at this point would be on identifying lessons learned that could be shared (and how), actions for the project to implement to shore up sources of resilience or manage sources of brittleness, and associated actions for the business unit to better support this and future projects.

After a pilot project at one project, team members agreed that the project was a remarkable improvement over traditional assessments. People from the project reported that they felt supported because we weren't there just to point out what they did wrong. People from outside the project reported that they learned things that could help them in their own projects or scopes of work. Leadership was amazed at how much they learned that could help them better support projects. The organization is now iterating on the summit to see how it works on different sizes and types of projects and how it can be scaled to other business units.

There were numerous lessons we learned along the way, but the most important is that by simply shifting the focus a bit away from assessing safety and towards how we can enable the successful completion of work we can not only improve safety, but other organizational outcomes as well.

Put another way, we improve work to improve safety, rather than the other way around.

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Organizational Learning Through Systems Theory

By Shem Malmquist

In a statement that captures the concept of resilient performance, astronaut Frank Borman was quoted as saying that “a superior pilot uses his superior judgement to avoid situations which require the use of his superior skill” (FAA, 2008). In a chapter of *Advancing Resilient Performance* (Nemeth & Hollnagel, 2022), Carroll and Malmquist (2022) proposed some approaches to increasing the resilience of pilots, but is there a way to do the same thing with an organization?

There are two different aspects to creating a resilient system. The first is to design the system such that the need for extraordinary performance by individuals is not required (implementing the superior knowledge). The second is to empower the people in the organization to do what they need to do in order to ensure that the outcome stays within the margins of desired performance (superior skills). Too often organizations exhibit neither of these, not learning enough to have superior knowledge and using Taylorist approaches to management that only serve to constrain their people to scripted responses that are only effective when the script matches the situation. Unfortunately, the real world is too messy for this to work consistently, although it does provide for reliable performance within the narrow scope of the design of the scripts. Note here that computers are always limited to scripted performance and hence can never be considered resilient.

Broadly defining safety as the preven-

tion from unwanted outcomes opens a pathway to applying safety and causality models to problems such as monetary losses and impacts to the brand as well as to damage to property and loss of life. It has been shown through system theory that safety is a control problem (Leveson, 2011). Here “control” is not intended to mean micromanagement and strict scripting of behaviors. The Taylorist approach to management is only effective for those problems and scenarios we have imagined in advance, and so incorporated into the methods.

"Building in...resilience requires first recognizing when assumptions are not matching reality."

Instead, control here refers to the type of more broad control that can be seen in the work of air traffic control (ATC). Contrary to public perception, ATC only controls the aircraft to the extent it is necessary to prevent collisions with other aircraft. Similarly, a good manager will not be micromanaging their employees, but rather providing boundaries for the employee to keep them from doing something unsafe (safety in this context just means preventing an undesired outcome). Obvious examples of this might be controls (rules) for policy and procedures, such as about conflicts of interest or sexual harassment in the workplace, a violation of which would always be harmful to the organization. There are also controls to meet regulatory requirements, such as limiting what equipment can

be inoperative on an aircraft and still be legal to fly. With this type of control there can potentially be operational pressure to violate as they can negatively impact reliability. Another type of organizational control is training programs, where people are trained to perform a certain function. It is important to recognize that adequate control requires both the ability to control the behavior of the component (hardware, software, human) being controlled, as well as adequate feedback so the controller can track the behavior of what they are controlling and modify their control as required to ensure that the desired outcome is met.

System theory considers the entire socio-technical system, including hardware, software, and human behavior as affected by social, psychological, and environmental factors. Through the application of system theory, it has been demonstrated that there are only four ways that a control can be unsafe:

1. A needed control action is not taken.
2. A control action taken that should not be.
3. A control action is done too soon, too late, or in the wrong order.
4. A continuous control action is taken for too long or too short a period of time (Leveson, 2011).

When applied to the examples above. If a control to prevent conflict of interest is not implemented, or if a control is implemented too late, a serious problem

can occur. Similarly, a training program can be ineffective (or worse) if not implemented properly. Clearly, not training can be unsafe, if training is flawed, then training is unsafe (see American Airline's training that contributed to the loss of AA 583), training done too soon or too late, and also training done for too short a period of time, all could result in a hazardous scenario.

Another unsafe control action would be by management providing too much constraint on an employee. Imagine a customer service agent (CSA) at a large airline where some outside event has resulted in hundreds of canceled flights. If management provides too much control the CSA will never be able to satisfy the customer. Although this would appear to lower costs for the management in the short term, it would cause damage to the brand. Clearly, there needs to be some control over what remedies the CSA can offer, but micro-managing will likely be harmful. A better control here is adequate training. The same concept can also be applied to the hiring and monitoring of personnel, providing early identification of problems. Equally important, feedback is critical at every level. If the management can get feedback on problems, they can address them.

The key here is to identify the controls and the assumptions carefully, and then match these against actual performance. Castillo (2019) outlined an approach to use System Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA) to identify unsafe control actions and use them to identify scenarios that could lead to hazards. The method has been shown to be effective at identifying factors that are missed using traditional hazard analysis methods. These are then mitigated through the design policies, procedures and training. Actual performance metrics are captured to find additional scenarios

not previously identified. These are then mitigated, and the process started again. This approach can be used across an organization to improve operations.

This process will also identify human performance that goes above and beyond. Most of the duties carried out in aviation are repetitive in nature, so can be scripted, but there are times that require a novel response (resilient behavior) by people in the organization to enable it to respond to unexpected problems. Building in such resilience requires first recognizing when assumptions are not matching reality, which can be a consequence of inadequate hazard analysis at the outset, or changes over time that render the initial assumptions invalid. In this way the process can result in organizational learning. Feedback to the organization, both formal and informal, will therefore make processes more efficient and thereby affect the bottom line positively. Systems thinking will also help an organization to diversify its lines of thought and challenge assumptions.

Aviation is an incredibly interconnected system, and oftentimes it is equally valuable to generate questions as it is to propose answers when it comes to organizational learning.

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gation and system safety. In addition, he is a B-777 Captain flying worldwide. Captain Malmquist has published numerous technical and academic articles stemming from his work on flight safety and accident investigation. His current work involves risk analysis, accident prevention, flight operations work and development of standards for transport airplanes. His past work includes several committees of the U.S. Commercial Aviation Safety team. He also has either led or been deeply involved in several major aircraft accident investigations, performing operations, human factors, systems and aircraft performance analysis. He is an elected Fellow of the Royal Aeronautical Society, as well as full member of ISASI, the Resilience Engineering Association, AIAA, the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society, IEEE, the Flight Safety Foundation and SAE where he is an active member of the Flight Deck and Handling Quality Standards for Transport Aircraft and several other committees involving aircraft certification standards.

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On the Logical Interdependency in Infrastructures: An Institutional Perspective

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It is well known within the field of resilience engineering that interdependencies of components within infrastructure networks can greatly affect system-level resilience because of their influence on how localized failures might cascade through the system (Yu et al., 2020). Interdependency is defined as "a bidirectional relationship between two infrastructures through which the state of each infrastructure influences or is correlated to the state of the other" (Rinaldi et al., 2001).

It has also become common knowledge within the field that such interdependencies can take various forms, including physical (the state of each infrastructure depends on the material output from or the state of the other because of a physical linkage between two or more infrastructures), geographic (parts of two or more infrastructure networks are co-located or in close proximity), cyber (the state of an infrastructure depends on information generated by information infrastructure), and logical (two infrastructures affect the state of each other via human decisions) (Rinaldi et al., 2001). These four types of infrastructure interdependencies, especially the physical and geographic forms of it, have been an active area of research among researchers and practitioners.

The goal of this short article is not to simply reiterate what is already known, but rather to highlight and make the

resilience engineering community aware that, among the four types of interdependencies, the logical type is potentially the most critical one, and often under-appreciated by many.

Logical interdependency may also be the least studied and the least understood among the four types. Perhaps the physically invisible and intangible nature of such logical relationships makes it harder to detect and study them. Nevertheless, as we shall show in this communication, this gap in knowledge is a paradox to us since human decisions and rules prescribing them are omnipresent and influence almost every aspect of infrastructure operation. When rule-mediated human decisions underlie operation of two or more infrastructures that either knowingly or unknowingly require coordination (think pilots and ATC), logical interdependency is potentially present.

Few mention the importance of logical interdependency and address how a shift of demand between two infrastructures with the substitutable service (e.g., road and rail) can be conceived as an example (Petit & Lewis, 2017; Petrenj & Trucco, 2014). However, we argue that this misses the point we raised above: rules, procedures, or norms that infrastructure operators use to govern their decisions during normal and emergency modes can generate logical interlinkages. It is critical to see that

human decisions around infrastructure operation are not made in vacuum. Those decisions are structured and constrained by agency-level rules and plans that have been codified, e.g., operational manuals and emergency plans of dams and hydroelectric power stations (Garcia et al., 2022). Such rules, generally referred to as institutions by scholars who study how rules shape human interactions and thus outcomes (North, 1990; Ostrom, 1990), can fundamentally shape how two or more infrastructures can affect one another through human decisions.

An example of rule-mediated logical interdependency is how operational rules at a dam and hydroelectric power plant are often interlocked. Most multipurpose dams are operated according to a set of rules known as "rule curves" that specify how much water should be released or stored and when to achieve a balance among flood control, water supply, and power generation (Garcia et al., 2022). These rules prescribe a range of water storage levels at some temporal resolution according to seasonality, water demands, and weather forecasts.

For example, under extreme precipitation and heavy inflow of water, a dam's flood pool can exceed a certain elevation (e.g., 750 feet) and the dam's operator is required by rule to make water release at a certain rate (e.g., 4500 cubic feet per sec-

ond). When this happens, the hydroelectric power plant and its operator are required by another rule to fully open its plenum tainter valve and fully close its turbine valve (so as to not disrupt or slow down water release from the dam). How well the rules are designed reflects local realities. Whether operators of the two facilities conform to the rules can greatly affect the states of these two facilities, flood outcomes, and subsequent decisions. This particular rule-based interlinkage can be represented as a network (actors and facilities as nodes and rules connecting them as edges) as shown in Figure 1. Systematic analysis of operational rules and network analysis

linkages, there likely exists another set of rules that have been codified upstream at the agency-level to prescribe how operators should handle issues associated with co-location and input-output exchanges of two facilities. More generally, such rules like these act as a "glue" that brings together heterogeneous infrastructures and defines their protocols of interaction. Thus, logical and other types of interdependencies and risks associated with them are all significantly shaped by how operational rules and plans are designed (e.g., absence of rules, rules are present but a loophole exists, rules are present and well-designed but operators do not conform to them,

definition of logical interdependency by Rinaldi et al. (Rinaldi et al., 2001) could be updated – FROM dependencies that exist between infrastructures caused by human decisions that do not belong to the physical, geographic, and cyber types TO dependencies caused by human decisions and rules regulating them that occur either independently or in conjunction with other types (physical, geographic, and cyber) of dependencies.

For this new research agenda to advance, a systematic approach to analyzing operational rules and norms of infrastructures are needed, requiring an interdisciplinary

Figure 1: Network representation of logical interdependency between dam and hydroelectric power plant

of how various actors and infrastructure components are linked by such rules may generate insights about potential logical interdependencies in a complex infrastructure network.

One could argue that this example of dam and hydroelectric power plant is actually a case of geographic interdependency (because these two facilities are co-located) or physical dependency (water releases from the dam become inputs to the hydroelectric turbine for power generation). But we would like to bring attention to the fact that even in such geographic and physical

etc.).

We suggest that more research is needed on the systematic analysis of 1) rules and plans governing human decisions on infrastructures and 2) how nodes of infrastructure networks (various actors, built and technological components) are connected by such rule-mediated edges (rules that tie nodes above). This should be an active area of research in the field of resilience engineering because of the omnipresence of such rules and their influence on human decision-making on infrastructure outcomes. Also, the original

approach and tools that encompass the study of institutions and governance and network science (Anderies et al., 2004; Eisenberg et al., 2017; Olivier, 2019). Aviation is well suited for such inquiry, as it encompasses commercial entities (airlines), regulators (civil aviation authorities), research and design (manufacturers), and many other stakeholders. By understanding logical interdependencies, we may further enhance our knowledge of resilience engineering as it relates to human decision-making.

David J. Yu is currently an Assistant Professor at the Lyles School of Civil Engineering and the Department of Political Science, Purdue University. He is also part of Purdue's Building Sustainable Communities cluster. His research centers on using a multi-method approach as a tool to systematically study the resilience and sustainability of human-dominated complex 'model' systems (infrastructure-dependent coupled natural and human systems) that captures key elements of actual governance arrangements, engineered and natural contexts, and human behaviors observed in the field. His research involves two interactive processes: 1) based on observed phenomena, define key hypotheses and contextual factors upon which to design and conduct behavioral and modeling studies, and 2) analyze results to develop generalizable insights and inform policy and planning. David brings diverse

knowledge sets together to engage in this research: resilience thinking, human behavior, collective action and the commons, dynamical systems theory, and experimental economics.

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Resilient Organizational Learning Through Action Research

By Torgeir Kolstø Haavik, Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)

How do you build and maintain resilience in organisations operating in risky environments?

The importance of understanding what characterises everyday work and what 'makes work work', as well as being able to learn from the whole spectrum of events from success to failure, is well established in the field of Resilience Engineering.

However, although the resilience literature says much about characteristics of work at a theoretical and conceptual level – I'm thinking about the substantial vocabulary describing work-as-done, adaptations, variability, ETTO and much more, – describing and analyzing this in organisations can be a challenging research task. It is often difficult even for many practitioners, safety managers and managers themselves, in the very same organisations, to describe and merge these concepts with the existing concepts and vocabularies dominating their organisations. And even if they do so, it is still challenging to fold them into the practice of work, the practice of safety management, and the practise of leadership in a meaningful and useful manner.

"...learning is an investment, and organisational knowledge – and indeed resilience – are qualities with a limited shelf life, and are in need of continuous fostering"

On one hand, one could think of this as surprising, since resilience vocabulary

describes (at a conceptual level) what people are actually doing when they are performing their everyday work, or finding solutions in the face of challenges. On the other hand, what people do and how they think and talk about what they do are two different stories. In that regard, one can find a source to explore the distinction between work-as-done and work-as-imagined, as well as a source to the conceptual difference between tacit knowledge and explicit knowledge.

As researchers of resilient performance – and researchers of sociology of work in general – we approach organisations and the people who constitute them with more questions than answers. This is also known as an inductive approach. We want to learn how they organise their work, how they produce and carry out their procedures, how they adapt to situational circumstances, and how they learn. Further, we can draw general insights out of such studies, and we can also collaborate with the same organisations to help them improve, succeed, and sometimes merely to fail better. We can help, we can provide advice and tools, but in the end, improvement is ultimately something that must be fostered by the organisations themselves.

One way such collaboration can find application and promote advances in organisations and science is through action research. In action research, researchers and practitioners work together in search of improvement. With a resilience perspective and approach to action research, we have

powerful methods and tools for improving organisational performance and gaining new research insights at the same time.

I would like to use an example an ongoing research project I am conducting together with my colleagues, that aims to strengthen the resilience of the fire management organisation on passenger and cargo ships.

The shipping industry works hard to strengthen fire management on such ship types, and a particular area of interest is in improving work processes, procedures and design solutions. In the project, the Functional Resonance Analysis Method (FRAM) lent inspiration to a process where a ship's crew got together in workshops and described in detail the work (in terms of functions) that they carried out in a simulated fire drill that they had just completed. For every little operation (function) they had carried out, they were asked to describe the particular conditions that contributed to shaping the operation. They were also asked to use both their experience and their imagination to describe different conditions that could have coloured, boosted, hampered or even prevented the operation. This produced a perspective and an understanding of their own work practices – explicit knowledge of work-as-done – that they discussed and scrutinized among themselves.

The next day the crew were asked to bring their newly acquired perspective to their own practices in yet another simulated fire drill, after which a debrief workshop pro-

vided the opportunity to reflect critically on their work, procedures and design. From here, they were prepared to think actively about improvements in a way that they usually did not have as much time nor inspiration to do. Those improvements could be ideas for new types of fire drills focusing on identified learning needs, or improved design solutions for materials or systems that are integral to maritime fire management.

This project is an example of how insights and concepts from Resilience Engineering can be operationalised into structured means for organisational learning, in this case using the FRAM. The crew expressed that they found the process very useful, but that that it would be difficult to follow up on a regular basis; in the maritime domain, a serious constraint is finding time to undertake such exercises and the ambition to go further than just checking

off the list of required safety work. However, it has to be acknowledged that learning is an investment, and organisational knowledge – and indeed resilience – are qualities with a limited shelf life, and are in need of continuous fostering. Investing in resilience is also about prioritisation. The time and resources spent on proactive activities as the one described here will in the long run still be subordinate to the cost of accidents. It might even make work more interesting!

Torgeir Kolstø Haavik (PhD) has background in geological engineering, social geography and organizational sociology. He works as a research professor at NTNU Social Research in Trondheim, Norway.

Haavik has studied organizational and societal resilience through a number of research projects, in domains such as offshore oil & gas (integrated operations), aviation (professional competence/airline-ship), health (surgical teams and simulation), maritime (professional competence and firefighting resource management), and pandemic preparedness and response in municipalities and states. A growing research interest is addressing sustainability dimensions of societal resilience, to strengthen the political dimensions of societal resilience in research areas where politics, science and technology are deeply intertwined – for example climate change.

Developing Resilience in Commercial Aviation Pilots via Training Data-Driven Insights

By Richard J Kennedy, Andrew CK Lim and David Owens, Civil Global Training Organization, CAE

The Approach to Commercial Aviation Pilot Training

The commercial aviation industry has entered the second decade of its journey to transition from so called 'Maneuvers-Based Training' to 'Competence-Based Training and Assessment' (CBTA). Historically pilots have been evaluated on their ability to perform a given exercise to a level of mastery (e.g., rejected take off, go-around, engine failure, etc.). This contrasts with the CBTA

paradigm, where pilots are instead presented with situations in training that are highly challenging and require a mixture of technical and non-technical skills to demonstrate resilient flight operations.

The current approach to developing resilience in flight crews is thus focused upon training and evaluating 'good performance' during stressful or unexpected situations. This approach requires the pilot to demon-

strate competencies including effective leadership, situation awareness, knowledge, decision-making, problem-solving and communication which can then be applied to similar situations and exercises to that being assessed.

The principal means for training for resilience include simulation, case studies and even role-playing exercises that are designed to mimic the real-world scenarios

- Helps instructors detect parameter exceedances which would not be possible to monitor from the instructor seat.
- Supports the instructor in providing effective de-brief to pilots based on objective data.
- As the technical competencies are best evaluated through telemetry data it allows the instructor to focus more of their effort on evaluating the non-technical competencies.

1. Simulator Telemetry Data

- Provides the means to tailor training content based on objective training data.
- Facilitates insight into how a particular fleet / experience level of pilots responds to challenging situations in a training environment.
- Provides evidence for good performance, and mastery of specific competencies, as well as identifying where performance could be improved.

2. Telemetry Data Analytics

helping flight crews to develop the ability to adapt to unexpected events, maintain focus and composure under pressure and work effectively as a team. Furthermore, debriefing and reflection sessions after each training session will review what was learned and how this learning can be applied in the future.

When evaluating performance, the approach however needs to encompass both Safety I and Safety II philosophies, and thus:

- Focus upon things that go right as well as avoiding that things go wrong.
- Encompass all possible outcomes over only adverse outcomes.
- Incorporate holism and emergence over decomposition and identifiable causes.
- Consider performance adjustments and variability over bimodality.
- Treat humans as resource over humans as a hazard.
- Allow continuous anticipation over reactive response.

Data-Driven Performance Evaluation

The key question is therefore what actually constitutes good performance of commercial airline pilots and how can we measure its various elements within a flight training environment? In other words, “What A Good One Looks Like” (WAGOLL) requires unpacking and, to that end, there are two main sources of training performance data that are available:

- The performance evaluations performed by the training instructor(s).
- The data which can be extrapolated from the training device.

Performance evaluations are based upon the CBTA paradigm described previously whereas telemetry data is essentially the in-situ collection of measurements or other data at remote points and their automatic transmission to receiving equipment for monitoring.

With a focus upon the second source listed above, Figures 1 and 2 further describe the

type of telemetry data that is obtained from the Full Flight Simulator (FFS) and how this data may be analyzed to provide insights on the performance of the pilot.

CAE Rise™ is a technology based-upon Full Flight Simulator (FFS) telemetry data enabling data-driven insights into the performance of pilots for the range of challenging situations that are presented in a flight training environment. The system consists of a tablet computer application and cloud-based analytics engine that uses the telemetry data to provide instant feedback to the instructor of outcomes relevant to the application of procedures and flight path management.

Rise allows operators to benchmark their performance against wider industry whilst providing data-driven insights that can be used to tailor training programs. A graphical example of the data-driven insights from by Rise is provided in Figure 3.

Calibration of Data: Instructor Grading vs Exceedance Rates

3. One Engine ILS Approach Example

When calibrating evaluations, comparison of independent sources of data will provide confidence of the quality of the grading data. Having different sources of data available to the training manager, allows a comparison of Instructor grade sheet data with simulator telemetry data of exceedances and deviations from SOPs.

An example of the use of data is the comparison of instructor substandard maneuver grades with the telemetry exceedance and error rates. One case, highlighted in Figure 4 is for a TCAS Event. In terms of instructor evaluations, this can be seen to be graded “less than standard” at around 2% of the time. However, the telemetry data indicates an exceedance of agreed tolerances or SOP errors for around 20% of the time.

The TCAS Event example above contrasts

with “Go-around – At Minima, One engine inoperative” case. With 7.7% of Instructor Grade lower than standard compared with 7.8% of Telemetry Exceedance, it is an example of near perfect concordance between the Instructor Evaluations and telemetry data.

Summary and Conclusions

This paper has described the evolution of commercial aviation flight training towards a full Competency-Based Training and Assessment (CBTA)-based paradigm. In the CBTA paradigm, both Safety I and Safety II perspectives are equally important. In order to support assessment and evaluation, it has been shown that data plays a crucial role. As well as providing insights on performance, instructor grading and simulator telemetry data can be compared to provide confidence in the quality of the assessments.

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Four Steps Towards Implementing Resilient Learning Systems in Aviation

By Kristy Kiernan and Dave Cross, Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University

Learning from mishaps and near-mishaps is a time-honored tradition in aviation. From “there I was” stories told in military ready rooms to case studies reviewed in formal training, aviators have long recognized the value of learning from each other’s mistakes. But what mechanisms do we have in place to learn from, individually and organizationally, and highlight what we do right?

In an effort to understand resilient performance, we conducted a study and asked professional pilots to describe routine yet unexpected events, and to explain their thoughts and actions in handling these situations. Of the four cornerstones of resilience, anticipate, monitor, learn, and respond, the behavior most commonly observed was learning. This was broken down into individual informal learning from peers or experience, and organizational learning from formal training.

In the vast majority of interviews, informal learning was ad hoc, based on personal networks, and not supported by any institutional structure. Common generic answers to the question “Did you share this event with anyone afterwards” were, “It wasn’t a big deal”, “I was just doing my job”, or “Not really, I just talked about it with the first officer afterwards.” In other words, when unexpected events were safely handled through the application of formal or informal learning there was no venue for that information to be shared through existing data collection mechanisms, nor was it necessarily thought

worthy of sharing. If we want to create learning systems in aviation to foster resilient performance, we have to tackle these problems.

First, we have to socialize the ideas behind resilient performance. Just as among healthcare [practitioners](#), pilots are typically receptive to the tenets of resilience, as they recognize intuitively that their behaviors contribute positively to safety beyond just not making mistakes. However, aviation lacks a standard vocabulary for discussing resilience. Part of the success of threat and error management is the clarity and ubiquity of Reason’s Swiss cheese model. Resilience does not yet have a simple visual model with as much explanatory power. The verbal equivalent is Marit de Vos’ metaphor that we have been learning about marriage by only studying divorce, but we have yet to capitalize on that memorable description. At every opportunity, we should be talking about resilient performance, using a common vocabulary, and helping pilots value the “routine” work they do every day that builds system resilience. Pilots can only report events that they recognize as valuable, and for which they have a vocabulary.

Second, we have to collect the right data. American’s [Learning Improvement Team](#), discussed elsewhere in this newsletter, and Cathay Pacific’s [Operational Learning](#) Reviews are excellent examples of collecting the right data. In addition to observational data, [our own research](#) has shown the value of debrief-style interviews for collecting

data on resilient performance. Captain Leja Collier describes this in her piece for this newsletter as well. [Industry and academia partnerships](#) can be helpful in developing systems that are tailored for the needs of specific organizations.

Third, we need to analyze data the right way. We have long collected [Flight Operational Quality Assurance \(FOQA\)](#) data, which records dozens of flight parameters for every flight every day in commercial aviation. However, what we look for in that data is exceedances. Can we instead look for occasions that identify underlying resilient performance? We also collect thousands of voluntary safety reports every month through the [Aviation Safety Action Plan \(ASAP\)](#). These reports have traditionally been analyzed through a threat and error management model, but increasingly, NASA is working to identify [evidence of resilient performance](#) in these reports. NASA’s Brian Smith is [developing a lexicon](#) that will allow automatic filtering of submissions to identify keywords associated with resilient performance.

Fourth, we need to develop structures to support both formal and informal learning.

Formal Organizational Learning

Formal training programs can incorporate the framework, terms and hallmarks of resilient performance to socialize the concepts among pilots. Simply introducing these ideas in multiple venues – initial and recurrent training, captain upgrade training, newsletters, and safety promotion literature, will help familiarize pilots with

the concepts of resilient performance.

Informal Individual Learning

Two pathways exist to support informal learning: one is to codify it into formal learning, for instance by creating a success-based reporting structure similar to what exists for reporting errors; another path is to provide more opportunities for informal learning to occur. In a recent [Safety First article](#), Airbus highlighted the importance of debriefing, particularly as it can reinforce resilient performance. The customary “good flight, no problems” leaves much opportunity for learning on the table. Several airlines, including RyanAir, All Nippon, Delta, and soon American, provide debrief tools that use flight data to allow crews to observe their own actions immediately after the conclusion of a flight. United Airlines encourages crews to reflect on positive performance using a “what went well and why” debrief after every flight.

However, effective debriefs need structural support. One extremely helpful method would be to actually pay pilots to debrief, rather than rely on the professionalism and good will of the pilot workforce. For example, extending five minutes of pay during post-flight to provide a debrief or submit a safety report would likely provide the psychological buy-in pilots would need. Providing opportunities for pilots to engage informally on professional matters would not only support resilient performance and strengthen safety culture, but build pilot engagement and affinity, which, according to [Oliver Wyman’s 2022 Flight Operations report](#), is an area of increasing concern for flight operations management.

This is a daunting list. However, the task becomes much more manageable when we consider first the minimum elements

which are required for learning from resilience, both formally and informally. Rather than wait for a perfect solution, we can take concrete steps now to support individual and organizational learning.

Kristy Kiernan, Ph.D., is the Associate Director for the Embry-Riddle Center for Aviation and Aerospace Safety, and the Program Coordinator for the Master of Science in Aviation Safety. Her current research projects include three ASSURE grants related to safe integration of unmanned aircraft into the National Airspace, and one internally funded project related to exploring data sources and theoretical models concerning the positive human contribution to aviation safety. Prior to joining Embry-Riddle, she flew Falcon 20s on search and rescue, drug interdiction, and law enforcement missions with the United States Coast Guard. She is the lead developer for the World Economic Forum drone transformation map, and is an expert contributor to Forbes.com in the area of aerospace and defense. She holds a current Airline Transport Pilot rating and a Remote Pilot certificate.

Dave Cross has been an instructor with Embry-Riddle’s Worldwide Campus for over 20 years. He lives about an hour south of Denver, CO, which gives time for skiing and flying when not teaching. Dr. Cross teaches subjects ranging from math, research, aeronautical science, safety, and statistics,

at both undergraduate and graduate level. Previously, Dr. Cross flew as an airline pilot throughout the world. He has flown as a First Officer on the Boeing 727, 757/767, 777, and 787, and as Captain on the B-757/767, B-737 and Airbus 319/320. His research interest is in conflict management, online education assessment, and teacher-student feedback. When not stuck in the office, flying, genealogy, scuba diving, and skiing take up his other time.

Learning What Goes Well and Why at American Airlines

By First Officer Nicholas Peterson

American Airlines and the Allied Pilots Association established the AA/APA Learning and Improvement Team (LIT) in 2019 as a proof of concept. The task was to develop a method for collecting data from normal flight operations where no unwanted or undesired outcomes were encountered.

SMS Integration

Aviation safety has always studied incidents and accidents, and applied lessons learned as preventative measures to ensure those instances were not repeated. As aviation became safer, these events decreased in number and the vast majority of operations were not studied at all. But to understand how the system is working, good or bad, it must be looked at it as a whole, studying both success and failure. LIT was designed to be complementary to the other AA SMS programs to help the airline learn from operations. Support and funding for LIT exists at the highest levels within AA management as demonstrated by the growth from a team of two to the current 20 between 2019 to 2022.

There are currently four main data streams collected by LIT:

- direct flight observation
- pilot interviews
- surveys
- learning teams

To date, more than 340 AA flights have been observed by LIT “Learning Navigators.” Navigators also conduct interviews, or “Shop Talks,” with pilots discussing a

variety of topics. Shop Talks help the airline gain insight into how its pilots think and why they make the decisions they do. LIT has also placed a survey within the AA Professionalism, Leadership and Mentoring (PLM) course. This survey asks current, experienced captains several questions in an effort to transfer as much knowledge and experience as possible to new AA captains and first officers.

In December 2022, LIT debuted its first two Learning Teams in Miami and Austin. LIT Navigators facilitated individual discussions on a variety of operational challenges with more than 130 pilots and what considerations those pilots had when trying to operate within those challenges. To date, LIT has observed or had direct contact with over 1200 pilots and gathered data on how everyday work is done by these pilots. The data is shared internally during monthly AA safety meetings as well as the above-mentioned PLM course and Recurrent Human Factors (RHF), a course every pilot must attend annually as part of recurrent training.

One of the challenges facing LIT is how to present the data it collects, given that the data looks quite different from other data presented within an SMS. Significantly, because LIT highlights normal work that didn’t result in an incident or accident, that data may be perceived as less stimulating or important because nothing bad happened. Additionally, LIT data is more qualitative than quantitative making it more difficult to analyze. These issues cre-

ate challenges in demonstrating why it is important to look at all outcomes, not just the undesired ones. In reviewing normal work, it is hoped that over time the airline can begin to detect weak signals. These can be difficult to detect if they are not significant enough to result in unwanted outcomes. Despite these challenges, LIT has become a valuable program to AA because it is able to capture data that was not available in the past, simply because there was not a program designed to capture it.

The Four Potential Model

LIT has gained some fascinating insights that would not have been possible prior to its creation. For example, during flight observations, LIT captures data in four “Potentials”—the potential for the pilot to do something positive. These four potentials are **Learn, Plan, Adapt** and **Coordinate**. Each potential consists of several proficiencies that can be observed by a LIT Navigator. By observing these proficiencies, the airline can begin to understand what actions and adaptations pilots make in their dynamic and changing environment. What is remarkable is that many times pilots are unaware of these accommodations they are making as they are doing them instinctively based on years of experience. In capturing proficiencies, the airline can learn more about the human contribution to safety and what pilots are doing to keep the operation safe.

Currently, AA is experiencing a significant loss of experience in its pilot workforce due

to the FAA mandated retirement age of 65. This has caused the time for a first officer to upgrade to captain to fall from above 15 years to below three years. While there is no way to compress 15 years of experience and knowledge into three, efforts must be made to facilitate this knowledge transfer. LIT data has shown that captains are almost four times as likely to ask the first officer for input in decision-making than first officers ask captains for input. These decision-making skills are essential for a captain to possess and LIT data is being used to help the airline and its captains prepare first officers for command. To help improve the captain and first officer information exchange, LIT has added content to the PLM course to educate captains on how best to utilize their first officers and to mentor them for the future.

The focus for LIT in 2023, besides continued data collection, is to intently review the data collected thus far, discover what it contains, present findings to both AA safety and its pilots, and continue the journey

of learning what goes well, and why it goes well.

First Officer Nicholas Peterson is a member of the American Airlines Learning and Improvement Team (LIT) and the Allied Pilots Association Deputy Chair, Learning and Improvement Team. A graduate of Purdue University with a B.S. in Aviation Technology, Nick began his airline career with Chautauqua Airlines. During his twenty-six-year airline career Nick has flown J31s, Saab 340s, Embraer 145s, B757s, B767s, B777s and the A320 family for a variety of airlines including Chautauqua, America West, US Airways, All Nippon Airways and

American. Nick has been working in AAL safety since 2015 and with LIT since its inception in 2019.

Resilience and Psychological Safety: The Language of Learning

By Leja Collier

As an airline captain and aviation human factors specialist, two concepts in the last ten years have captured my professional curiosity - resilience and psychological safety. I was equally interested and skeptical of both. Were these merely buzzwords? Or was there something meaningful here?

I was introduced to resilience after a hiatus from human factors work in 2015. The pause was due to a job change. Once I had spent some time learning a different airplane and organization as a new hire pilot, I returned to safety work. I asked mentors and friends what the leading edge in human factors was. The answer was resilience.

Language is my favorite data source, so I asked some questions: "What do you mean by resilience? Please tell me more."

"Through mastery, we can improvise."

To learn more, I was told I needed to talk to Shawn Pruchnicki at the Ohio State University's Department of Aviation (now Dr. Pruchnicki – Congratulations, Shawn!). Shawn introduced me to resilience engineering and the anticipate, monitor, respond, and learn framework. He also joined me on an industry panel in 2018 called "Training for the Unexpected: A Focus on Resilience." Shawn was our first panelist and provided the foundation for the discussion. Other panelists included Terry VanHoose, a safety award winner; Lou Nemeth from CAE; and Alaska Airlines'

Brad Donaldson.

Here's a link to the panel hosted by the [Air Line Pilots Association](#).

Panelist Terry VanHoose and his first officer won the Air Line Pilots Association's Superior Airmanship Award in 2015 for their performance during a dark and stormy night. They were dodging thunderstorms and experienced a loss of instrumentation and unreliable airspeed. We had Terry participate in the panel because we often dissect events that went wrong. Here was an opportunity to learn from something that went well.

Terry provided my favorite takeaway from the panel. When asked, "How do we train for the unexpected?" Terry answered, "We get really good at the expected."

Through mastery, we can improvise.

Brad Donaldson built on the concept of mastery. He discussed Gary Klein's "Intuition at Work" and Recognition Primed Decision Making. Alaska Airlines has leveraged that work to encourage pilots to build their experience in five different ways. The first is to read and research. Policy and procedure knowledge is essential. We can also learn from others' experiences through safety publications. The second tenet of Alaska's learning model is to challenge yourself. We get good at what we repeatedly do, and that can leave us stale as learners. For example, I jokingly call myself a "Day-Trip-Diva" because I like

to fly turns up and down the west coast of the US. This schedule is great for sleeping in my bed but bad for challenging myself. The third tenet is to practice deliberately. To accomplish this, Alaska encourages their pilots to practice using different combinations of automation. It is an intentional growth strategy.

Alaska's fourth and fifth steps to building pilots' experiential "tool kits" are briefings and debriefings. Alaska Airlines has championed a threat-forward, interactive, and scalable crew briefing. It begins with threat identification by the pilot monitoring. The pilot flying then discusses the plan and considerations for the plan.

Resilience Framework for a Flight

The four-dimension resilience framework created by Erik Hollnagel can be used in the planning and execution of a flight in a cyclical process. Crew briefings and debriefings can be used as anchors to the cycle.

Anticipate

In the flight deck, we use preflight and approach briefings to anticipate threats, mitigations, and a plan of action before the highest workload segments of the flight. This is also a chance to prime ourselves for potential contingency plans should our plan not execute as anticipated (departure contingencies: rejected takeoff, single-engine departure procedure, and return to the field).

Monitor

Once the plan is being executed, we shift to monitoring. How is our plan going? Is our aircraft on the intended flight path? Is our fuel state consistent with the dispatcher's plan? How are aircraft systems functioning? Is the weather as forecasted or improving/deteriorating?

Respond

We anticipated some potential contingencies. As the flight progresses, we may need to respond with one. If we encounter an unanticipated threat, we may need to improvise. Pilots do have some guidance in response to unexpected threats. From the high-level prioritization “aviate, navigate, and communicate” to a more structured and airline-specific response, including delegation of tasks. Who will fly and talk to Air Traffic Control? Who will manage the event – from running the checklist to communicating with the company, passengers, and flight attendants? These structures make non-normals indicated by ECAM, EICAS, or Master Caution systems a fairly routine response. Often, the more mundane unanticipated threats like a runway change lend to response challenges because we are less intentional about roles and responsibilities.

Learn - Debriefings

Once we are back on a stable path or at the gate, it is an excellent opportunity to discuss how everything went. We learn from the process. Did we execute our plan? What did we do well? What could we do better?

Anticipate, monitor, respond, and learn - repeat as necessary.

Psychological Safety

Psychological safety is a newer concept to me. I learned about it last Fall from a fellow doctoral student, Kimberly Perkins. If you've heard about psychological safety, it's possibly thanks to Google. Google studied their teams and found psychological safety as the key to high-performance teams. An article in 2016 about the study created a new buzz.

nizational support. Some of the results of psychological safety are speaking up about mistakes, requesting feedback, trying new things, and job satisfaction.

Psychological safety plays a role in anticipating threats. Is everyone comfortable speaking up about their perceived threats for the flight? Or does an experienced leader silence the threat by anchoring the conversation? Alaska's initiation of the briefing by the pilot monitoring identifying threats is a way to ensure a plan or person doesn't anchor the discussion.

What about the additional risk we bring to the flight deck? Performance is not binary – either good or bad. It is more like a bell curve. As two of my favorite scientists remind me (Dr. Immanuel Barshi of NASA and Dr. Jeffrey Schroeder of the FAA), 50% of the time, pilots are operating below their average. If we recognize we are working sub-optimally but still fit for duty, is it safe to bring it up?

Psychological Safety and Monitoring

“What do you mean by psychological safety?”

Psychological safety allows team members to take interpersonal risks. Amy Edmondson introduced it as a team learning concept in 1999. Edmondson has five conditional elements to psychological safety: leader behavior, group dynamics, trust and respect, use of practice fields, and orga-

A lack of first officer assertiveness is a common finding in safety events with the captain operating as pilot flying. If we only focus on transmitting the message (speaking up), we miss 50% of the communication. Captains listening to initial alerts of speed and altitude excursions is just as important to first officer assertiveness. Supporting speaking up with “good catch” is another way to encourage monitoring.

This area of the resilience framework can use some work specifically in “how we monitor” as organizational and industry structural support. Monitoring is not just what has our focal visual attention, but sometimes that is what gets critiqued.

Responding to a threat also has elements of psychological safety. Some of the structures in place are encapsulated by Edmondson’s aspects of group dynamics and organizational support. Responses may not go well when there is a lack of clear roles and responsibilities.

Learning from all operations

Creating an environment for learning is psychological safety. Debriefing is one way to accomplish learning from all operations. Psychological safety is necessary to be open to that feedback as a team.

Conclusion

One interpretation of the sixth generation of Crew Resource Management is CRM as risk management and resilience. There may be some benefits to thinking about psychological safety as well. It is a team learning concept that can enhance flight deck resilience. As I map CRM concepts to Edmondson’s elements of psychological

safety, I see some areas we can improve upon. One is the use of practice fields. I think Alaska’s five-step plan for gaining experience is something airlines should consider.

The other thing I recently read was Airbus’s resilience model showing competence and confidence as foundational. As I later thought about the psychological element of trust and respect in the flight deck, confidence made an impression. Building trust can be difficult with an interchangeable flight deck team, often of short duration. It is made more difficult with perceived inexperience due to a lack of confidence in ourselves and our teammates. I remember my first flight as an airline pilot. It was not a psychologically safe place, but the captain was correct with some heavy-handed mentoring at the time. The one thing I needed to do was to continue to show up and get experience.

Another mentor recently reminded me that we gain trust slowly in drops and can lose it quickly in buckets. While building that trust, we can certainly be respectful of each other. Our teammates often know something we don’t, and we’ll never learn what it is if you don’t do your part in facili-

tating a psychologically safe environment.

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